

AN EFFECTIVE LEARNING MECHANISM FOR MIDWIVES
CONDUCTING DOCUMENTARY REVIEW IN ACCORDANCE WITH
PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS: AN ACTION RESEARCH STUDY

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Thesis submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements
of the University of the West of Scotland
for the award of Doctor of Philosophy

Submitted 24th of March 2022

DECLARATION

An application submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements of the University of the West of Scotland for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy

by Jean Ruthven Watson

I (Jean Watson) declare that this thesis is all my own work and that it has not been submitted for any other academic award at this or any other academic establishment.

SIGNATURE:

DATE: 24th of March 2022

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Personal details withheld.

DEDICATION

I would like to dedicate this thesis to my husband Gary who throughout this challenging journey, as in all life events has believed in me. This work is also dedicated to my sons Colin and Fraser and my Mum, Moira for their unconditional love and support during this process.

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GLOSSARY OF TERMS

CPD Continuous Professional Development

EBP Evidence Based Practice

EDS Electronic Documentation Systems

EHS Electronic Health Records

ERS Electronic Recording Systems

HEI Higher Education Institute

LSA Local Supervising Authority

NMC Nursing Midwifery Council

PAR Participatory Action Research

SoM Supervisor of Midwives

UKCC United Kingdom Central Council

ABSTRACT

Internationally the quality of health care documentation is recognised to be a concern. Few tools were found to assess documentation of diagnostic skills of nurses and even fewer assessing midwifery. No tools were discovered that have explored the way people learn in clinical practice and none which incorporated the nursing and midwifery professional standards. Therefore, the study aim was to develop an effective learning mechanism for midwives conducting documentary review in accordance with professional standards.

The Participatory Action Research study involved: Exploration (Phase One), Intervention (Phase Two) and Evaluation (Phase Three). **Phase One:** A World Café event where an Expert Working Group (n=19) created the DOC Learning Tool based on NMC Standards. Face and content validity of the Tool was achieved (100%). **Phase Two:** Mixed methods of data collection - Testing the DOC Learning Tool over four cycles, 24 clinical midwives from one Scottish Health Board participated. In total, 224 DOC Learning Tools were analysed. Quantitative data examined through descriptive statistics, revealing that over four test cycles rater agreement changed from a mean of 68.10 to 78.17. Descriptive statistics revealed a reduced range in scores and a steadily increased mean. Results showed gradual increase and one way ANOVA revealed significant difference between Cycle One and Cycle Four. Qualitative data were obtained through three focus groups (n=9) and qualitative comments from the DOC Learning Tools. Thematic analysis (Braun and Clarke, 2006) revealed two overarching themes: 'Mechanisms and Practicalities' and 'Person-Centred Engagement and Enhancement through Learning'. There was clear evidence the DOC Learning Tool was in alignment with NMC professional standards. **Phase Three:** Triangulation of findings enhanced the areas of convergence and divergence resulting in ongoing improvements to the DOC Learning Tool over the study period. Further statistical testing for final evaluation and dissemination of results will be required as post-doctoral work.

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CHAPTER 1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Overview

In the United Kingdom (UK), over 35,000 midwives are on the Nursing and Midwifery Council 's (NMC) Register (NMC, 2018). One of the core functions of the midwife is to provide contemporary evidence to demonstrate their care is in accordance with professional standards (NMC, 2018). The four professional standards are prioritising people, practice effectively, preserve safety and promote professionalism and trust. Clear and accurate documentation is crucial in providing evidence that care has taken place (Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011). Previously Dimond (2011) stated if it is not documented, then in the eyes of the law the care has not been carried out, however case law now states that documentation requires to be recorded contemporaneously for the episode of care (Griffith, 2016). There is no doubt that communication and continuity of care delivery is enhanced through accurate documentation (Vowden and Vowden, 2015), which evidences quality of care assessment (Neary, 2014). This was previously acknowledged by Paans and Paans (2013) who emphasised that documentation is crucial for patient safety. Concern regarding quality of nursing documentation is an international issue (Daskein, Moyle and Creedy, 2009; Wang et al., 2011; Neary, 2014). Globally and in the UK, guidance, standards, and reports are published to inform and support health professionals, nurses and midwives regarding the purpose, accuracy and assessment of documentation as a communication strategy (World Health Organisation, 2012; National Health Service (NHS) Litigation Authority, 2012; Royal College of Midwives (RCM) and Royal College of Obstetricians and Gynaecologists, 2016; Royal College of Nursing (RCN), 2017; Office of the Midwifery Services Director Health Services Executive, 2018; RCM, 2021a).

Few tools are available to assess documentation of diagnostic skills of nursing staff (Marini and Chaves, 2011; Müller-Staub et al., 2009). Additionally, interrater reliability tends to be poor even among experts (Monsen et al., 2011). The Quality of Nursing Diagnoses, Interventions and Outcomes (Q-DIO) tool has been widely tested internationally and reported to demonstrate validity (Müller-Staub et al., 2009). Conversely, further analysis from independent assessors suggested some issues of disparity of terminology in the use of Q-DIO and further research was required to

confirm validity (Šerková and Marečková, 2018). No tools / instruments were found to specifically assess midwifery documentation, which focuses on a more holistic approach to care and less on the diagnostic element of medicalised / ill-health care. In relation to midwifery documentation there appears to be no measurement tools or instruments available for assessment which have incorporated the professional standards for Nurses and Midwives (NMC, 2015, 2018). Additionally, there is no tool or instrument which takes cognisance of the way people learn in clinical practice or explored how such a tool could be used as part of lifelong learning (NMC, 2018).

The midwifery profession has had an interesting and dynamic journey over the past century. This has involved many changes and challenges to midwifery practice. To contextualise this study, this section will explain the development and regulation of the profession of midwifery including the role of Supervisor of Midwives (SoM) in this process.

1.2 Midwifery as a Profession

Following the Midwives Act (introduced in England circa 1902), midwifery became a registered profession. This legislation was set in statute, providing midwifery with legal governance. The legislation of the midwifery profession was adopted by Scotland circa 1915 and subsequently Northern Ireland (1918) (Leap and Hunter, 1993). Resulting from the Midwives Acts the Central Midwives Board (CMB) was formed to regulate training and the legal practice of midwives (Leap and Hunter, 1993). The main function of the CMB was to provide a set of rules and define the scope of practice for midwives, endorse training programmes and approve individual midwife's entry onto the professional register. Midwives were only allowed onto the register following a written reference of their good character (Mannion, 2008).

Midwives had little control over their profession at this time nor were represented on the CMB which was chaired by an obstetrician, until midwives were elected to the panel in 1920 (Mannion, 2008). Additionally, midwives were overseen (supervised) by middle-class women who were non-midwives (i.e., women of good standing in their community with testimonials from clergy) (Towler and Bramall, 1986). Interestingly, moral character of the midwives was more important than their clinical competency

(Mannion, 2008). In 1936, following the fourth Midwives Act the working terms of midwives in England and Wales were improved (Towler and Bramall, 1986).

Midwifery legislation evolved with the establishment of the United Kingdom Central Council (UKCC) for Nursing, Midwifery and Health Visiting in 1983. This replaced the CMB following the Midwives and Health Visitors Act (1979). Subsequently, lobbying by midwives, a Statutory Midwifery Committee within the UKCC was established to ensure midwifery issues were not overlooked (Jones and Jenkins, 2004). The NMC replaced the UKCC in 2002, following the publication of The Nursing and Midwifery Order (Her Majesty's Stationery Office, 2001).

Ultimately, the main purpose of the NMC has always been to protect and safeguard the public (NMC, 2018). This is established through maintaining a register of nurses and midwives in the UK (and nursing associates who meet the requirements for registration in England) (NMC, 2021a). Furthermore, educational requirements for nurses and midwives are governed by professional standards. These standards facilitate lifelong learning, reflection and ensure quality and competency of the registrant's practice by means of the revalidation process (Macdonald, 2017). Through governance, the NMC investigates serious concerns about any nurse, midwife, or nursing associate on the register (NMC, 2021b).

One of the main standards governing practice is The Code (NMC, 2018) and comprises four main pillars: 'Prioritising people', 'Preserve safety', 'Promote professionalism and trust' and 'Practise effectively'. 'Prioritising people' means that people should be cared for with kindness and respect. Whereas 'Preserve safety' ensures registrants work within scope of practice and recognise limitations. 'Promote professionalism and trust' relates to upholding the reputation of the profession. Finally, 'Practice effectively' means using best available evidence and it is essential any communications with patients and colleagues (including written) must be clear and accurate (NMC, 2018). In accordance with The Code (NMC, 2018), practitioners are required to revalidate every three years to maintain registration with the NMC (2021c). This demonstrates evidence of the registrant's self-reflection and continued learning to ensure safe practice throughout their professional career (Ackerman, 2017) (Table 1.1)

Table 1-1 Revalidation Process

To revalidate registrants, require to demonstrate:
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• 450 hours of practice.• 35 hours continual professional development.• 5 pieces of practice-related feedback.• 5 reflective accounts on:<ul style="list-style-type: none">○ Practical experiences.○ Practice-related feedback.○ Continuous professional development.
(NMC, 2021)

1.3 Supervision of Midwifery

The statutory role of supervision of midwives was instrumental in the development of midwifery practice through The Midwives Act (1902). However, the role was a contentious one in the early twentieth century when midwifery supervisors were middle class lay women called inspectors. Their primary function was to investigate cases of misconduct, negligence, and malpractice (Mannion, 2008). In 1937, the role was appointed to non-medical and medical supervisors to replace lay women. Non-medical supervisors were experienced midwives who answered to the medical supervisors (Mannion, 2008). However, there was little evidence of this role being supportive for the midwives even after the title was changed to supervisor as it tended to take on more of a policing ethos (Ackerman, 2017). In the 1940s non-medical supervisors shifted to community-based midwives who worked alongside their supervisees. Midwives respected these supervisors as this model formed the basis of more supportive supervision (Drury and Staples, 2000). The subsequent organisational changes and developments in the midwifery supervision model are outlined in Table 1. 2.

Table 1-2:Development of the model of supervision

The development of the model of supervision	
1974	Reorganisation of NHS led to Local Supervising Authority (LSA) being handed over from Regional Health Authorities (RHA) to District Health Authorities (DHA) / Health Boards (HB) (Ackerman, 2017).
1977	Medical supervision ended. Ultimate responsibility for Supervision of Midwives lay with DHA / HBs (Mannion, 2008). Supervisors must be midwives (Towler and Bramall, 1986), all midwives became NHS employees and role of Supervisor was transferred to Head of Midwifery (Jones and Jenkins, 2004).
1993	All new SoMs required to complete a UKCC approved programme (Ackerman, 2017).
1996	Following dissolvent of RHAs LSA consortiums were formed in four UK countries (Ackerman, 2017). Only midwives were LSA Responsible Officers representing midwives at a local and national level (Mannion, 2008).
2002	NMC embraced supervision at its inception in 2002 (Ackerman, 2017).
2004	Supervision was embedded into the Midwives Rules and Standards (NMC, 2004).

According to Mannion (2008), SoMs had three distinct roles: statutory, professional, and dealing with practice issues. The statutory role involved ensuring midwives adhered to Midwives Rules and Standards (NMC, 2004; 2012), which included investigating critical incidents and supporting midwives to learn from these adverse clinical events. Effective communication was imperative for all midwives and with stakeholders involved in related policies and procedures (Ackerman, 2017). SoMs had a statutory role to meet with midwives annually to identify areas for their learning and professional development (NMC, 2012). Additionally, the SoMs, in their professional leadership role, were accountable to the LSA (NMC, 2014). Their remit was to ensure safe and appropriate care was delivered to women and their babies through quality assurance processes and standard setting (Ackerman, 2017). SoMs monitored safe practice by gaining evidence of effective verbal and written communication (documentation) within the practice setting (Ackerman, 2017).

In 2013, concerns about statutory supervision of midwives were publicly highlighted during investigations of maternity services within Morecambe Bay NHS Foundation

Trust by the Parliamentary and Health Service Ombudsman (PHSO) (PHSO, 2014). Two pivotal recommendations changed the landscape of midwifery supervision. The need for Health Board jurisdiction over midwifery supervision and the NMC to only have direct control of midwifery regulation (Hunt, 2015). These findings were emulated by an NMC commissioned King's Fund report (Baird et al., 2015), which concluded a conflict of interest between conducting investigations and supporting midwives.

Kirkup (2015) raised further concerns following an investigation into allegations of serious incidents at Furness General Hospital (Morecambe Bay NHS Foundation Trust). Failure of LSA systems and processes for midwives were discovered and failure of individuals to investigate serious incidents or complaints. These concerns endorsed the findings of the King's Fund report (Baird et al., 2015). Subsequently, in July 2015, the Secretary of State for Health announced that supervision would be removed from statutory regulation and the NMC would have direct control over this function. These legislative changes did not end supervision, but only removed the role from statute. The culture and supportive nature of supervision should be preserved to enhance the safe effective care of women and babies (Department of Health and Social Care (DoHSC), 2016).

The four UK Chief Nursing Officers (CNOs), their professional midwifery officers, NMC, RCM and Local Supervising Authority Midwifery Officers (LSAMO) representative (DoHSC, 2016), led future policy and practice developments for supervision. In April 2017, supervision of midwives became a non-statutory function across the UK (DoHSC, 2016). The current clinical supervision models used by nurses replaced the previous supportive role of the SoM and adopted a new way of supervision for midwives (RCM, 2021b). According to Keys, Marshall, and Hollins Martin (2019), this changed approach to midwifery supervision aimed to ensure high quality safe care for women / babies and address the challenges of clinical practice through facilitation and coaching.

1.4 Purpose of Documentation

Clinical documentation is as important as direct patient care because it provides effective communication between health care practitioners and the patient (Griffith, 2016). Documentary evidence provides a chronological account of care and treatment

provided to the patient. Furthermore, documentation provides legal evidence of the health professionals' involvement in that episode of care. Documented evidence is an essential component of quality assurance purposes (Griffith, 2016).

Record keeping is a key tool of professional practice and must not be seen as an optional extra (Cornock, 2020). The main function of documentation is to provide a complete, accurate and factual account of care without the need for practitioner recall (Cornock, 2020). Contemporaneous entries enrich the credibility and reliability of the documentation and are associated with improved patient safety (NHS Resolution, 2021).

Knowledge and understanding of the legal implications of documentation must be clearly understood in the day-to-day practice of nurses, midwives, and all health care professionals (Dimond, 2011). Documentation is the cornerstone to evidencing health care practice (Jefferies et al., 2011). Documentary evidence within health care will be used to defend practice against litigation claims made against a nurse or midwife to the Regulatory Body (Nursing Midwifery Council) or used in a court of law (Dimond, 2011; Symon, 2017). Records provide a pivotal role in protecting nurses and midwives from litigation and in demonstrating that practitioners are accountable practitioners who uphold the standards of The Code (NMC, 2018).

Failure to document or document inaccurately could result in errors by practitioners or their colleagues as well as causing miscommunication with the patient and other health professionals. Poor documentation could lead to late diagnosis, inappropriate or delayed treatment and possible disciplinary action against the health care practitioner (Cornock, 2020). Communication issues alongside patient care and dishonesty were the main sources of complaints to the NMC by public members between 2014 and 2019 (NMC, 2021b). Breakdown of communication is often cited in legal cases involving adverse clinical outcomes. Incomplete or inaccurate medical records that fail to stand up to examination in a court of law form part of this miscommunication (NMC, 2021b). Of proven allegations made to the NMC in 2019 - 2020 Five thousand, seven hundred and four allegations (16%, i.e., 913) involved record keeping: patient or clinical records, drug / medication records or other record keeping issues (NHS Resolution, 2021).

Within the UK, obstetric cases represent a high proportion of litigation claims and these adverse incidents can be life-changing for all involved. According to NHS Resolution (2021), obstetric claims in 2018 / 2019 formed 10% of all claims in England, of which human impact accounted for 50% of the monetary value awarded (£2,465.5 million). In Scotland, 2018 / 2019 obstetrics and gynaecology accounted for 30.5% (£132.6 million) of claims paid (National Services Scotland, 2019). Additionally, in 2018, the DoHSC launched the Maternity Safety Strategy to improve safety within maternity care (NHS Resolution, 2021). One aspect of this strategy related to documentation as evidence of care. Therefore, it is crucial to learn from and improve documentation, which will positively impact on patient safety (Dimond, 2011).

Quality assurance in health care is paramount (Renfrew et al., 2014). The purpose of documentation in this quality assurance process is important to provide evidence that local and national standards of care are met (Starr, 2016; Renfrew and Ross-Davie, 2020). Evaluation of record keeping must be awarded the same importance as other clinical skills (Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011; Starr, 2016). However, many practitioners view record keeping as time consuming, endless and a low priority (Spurrier, 2013). Additionally, staff are resentful of the time that is taken away from direct patient care for this task (Spurrier, 2013). It is without doubt that documentation is a crucial professional requirement to provide evidence of care (Porteous, 2011; Starr, 2016; NMC, 2018; RCM, 2021) and clinicians reporting that they are 'too busy to complete this task' is not acceptable as a form of defence in a case of litigation (Cormack, 2019).

A balance must be created where practitioners can complete documentation accurately and succinctly whilst meeting NMC standards (NMC, 2018) in a way that does not impinge on direct patient care (Spurrier, 2013). Resulting in an ideology where completing documentation to a high standard would be automatic. Developing a mechanism, which assesses documentation against the NMC standards (NMC, 2018), would be beneficial to ensure quality and parity across the nursing and midwifery profession. Although it would require to be deemed useful by the practitioners (Spurrier, 2013). Development of a mechanism that could also be used as a learning tool to allow the practitioners to feed forward into their future practice of documentation would also be of benefit (Starr, 2016). However, to ensure compliance, practitioners would need to be involved in the development and implementation of the

mechanism (Starr, 2016). Over the past few decades, mechanisms have been developed to assess documentation. However, none have focussed primarily on midwifery documentation or on developing a mechanism as a learning tool.

1.5 Learning and Learning theories

Learning is a process leading to change, which results from experience and enhances performance (Ambrose et al., 2010). Brown and Roediger (2014) highlighted that learning is associated with future problem solving through gaining knowledge and skills readily retrieved from memory. Sweller et al. (2010) emphasised if learning is not retained within the memory, then indeed, nothing has been achieved. Therefore, learning has an important role in leading a change of behaviour, attitude or practice acquired from a new experience (Schunk, 2020).

Learning theories are important to the understanding of how knowledge is created and how individuals learn (Harasim, 2017). In this respect, theories need to be assessed on how useful they are to underpin clinical practice (Lefrançois, 2020). The most influential theories of learning are arguably behaviourist theories, cognitive psychology, constructivism, social constructivism, experiential learning, multiple intelligence, situated learning theory and community of practice (Lefrançois, 2020). Behaviourism focuses on the idea that behaviours are learned from interaction with the environment and learning theory proposes that behaviours innate, or inherited factors have very little influence on behaviours (Watson, 1928). Whereas, in its basic form, cognitive psychology likens the human mind to a computer, resulting in the learner being passive in receiving, storing, and recalling of knowledge from memory (Neisser, 1976). In the theory of constructivism, learners are actively involved in their learning and require interpreting information which must make sense for learning to occur (Lefrançois, 2020). Bandura's (2001) social learning theory suggests that in a social situation, learning occurs during episodes of observation and role-modelling. In the late 20th century Vygotsky (1978) adapted the constructivism and social learning theory and proposed the theory of socio-constructivism where learning occurs due to interaction of the learner in the social situation (Mooney, 2013). Carl Rogers (1977) first coined the phrase 'experiential learning' where learning occurred through participation in first or second-hand experiences in everyday life with learning achieved

though facilitation and not teaching. In this situation, calm and non-stressful environments are more conducive to learning and further enhanced with self-initiated learning (Lefrançois, 2020). Lave and Wenger (1991) further developed these concepts and theories recognising learning occurs in situations within communities of practice. Therefore, it makes sense that nurses and midwives who work in communities of practice would learn effectively in this culture (Lefrançois, 2020).

Dewey (1938) cited in Mooney (2013), first wrote about reflecting on practice in the early 1900s. However, Schön (1983) pioneered the concept of reflecting on practice, for professional and personal growth. Seminal work by Carper (1978) highlighted four patterns of knowing in nursing practice: empirical knowledge, moral knowledge, personal knowing and aesthetics. Johns (1995) later defined the aesthetic pattern as intuition. Carper (1978) highlighted that all four patterns were necessary to achieve mastery in the profession. Therefore, theoretical knowledge needs to be in partnership with practical learning. Benner (1984) supported Carper's (1978) earlier work, arguing there was more than theoretical knowledge required for practitioners to progress from novice to expert. Furthermore, Porter (2010) examined Carper's (1978) fundamental patterns of knowing in nursing, against the culture of using evidence-based practice (EBP). Porter (2010) argued that comparing empirical knowledge with EBP could be considered like comparing qualitative with quantitative evidence in research, both are useful and appropriate (Porter, 2010).

Theorists agreed that structured reflection is required to make sense of a practice-based experience (Dewey, 1938 cited in Mooney (2013); Carper, 1978; Johns, 1994). Therefore, Johns (1995) created a reflective model from Carper's (1978) ways of knowing that could be used as a reflective tool for learning and informing future practice (Johns, 1995). Utilisation of models of reflection underpin the NMC revalidation process for all registrants (NMC, 2018). Every three years each practitioner submits five reflective accounts, on practical experiences, practice-related feedback or from continuous professional development as part of the revalidation process (NMC, 2021). Therefore, it makes sense to reflect on documentation, as it is an integral part of nursing and midwifery care.

1.6 Setting the scene

As a midwife and senior midwife with over 35 years' experience, I was involved in legal cases where historical clinical documentation was examined as evidence. Involvement in these cases reinforced how crucial documentation was in providing detailed accounts of clinical care as practitioner recall of events over time becomes less accurate. This sparked a special interest in the role of documentation within health care in clinical governance and quality improvement. At this time, I was also appointed in the statutory role of SoM with the key responsibility of public protection within maternity services. One aspect of this role involved examining completed patient records by midwives annually as well as reviewing patient records post critical incidents. This statutory appointment was in addition to my role as midwifery lecturer with the local university.

In 2013, during a SoM quality assurance process, I uncovered poor standards of documentation within the regional Health Board. In my role as SoM, I highlighted this concern to the LSAMO, and we agreed that work was required on improving clinical documentation. As an experienced SoM and midwifery lecturer, I was appropriately positioned to lead on this important piece of work given my clinical background and interest in clinical teaching and documentation. This combined with knowledge gained from undertaking a Post Graduate Certificate in Teaching and Learning in Higher Education, fuelled my interest to further explore how midwives learned and improve their practice in the clinical setting.

Subsequently I led a sub-group of SoMs to monitor current clinical documentation, with the purpose of improving quality of documented care. Meetings were held with midwives who highlighted for effective learning to happen it would be necessary for them to be involved in the monitoring process and development of any measurement tools to assess the standard of their documentation. One of the outputs of the sub-group was a new user-friendly documentation tool, incorporating peer review i.e., midwives reviewing other midwives' documentation. According to Haag-Heitman and George (2011), peer review is seen as an effective way of enhancing quality. The success of this peer review model for documentation was recognised across the UK

when awarded the first ever ‘*President of the RCM SoM Award for Good Practice*’ in January 2014 (RCM, 2014).

Following this recognition, the NMC recommended that this initial work was further developed for the professional practice of midwives on a national level. During a meeting with a fellow SoM, who was also a Professor of Midwifery, we discussed how this initiative could be advanced. The next step was to explore how examining documentation could help the practitioners tap into their phronesis and learn from this process with the goal to improve their practice. Through an initial literature review it became apparent to me that whilst a few mechanisms existed none of these incorporated the NMC (UK governing body) professional standards or were specifically related to midwifery documentation. This uncovered a gap in the learning process of midwives when reviewing the quality of clinical documentation. Planning of the current study began in October 2014 with the researcher and supervisors conducting an ideas and concept analysis to establish the gold standard baseline for an effective mechanism to review the quality of midwifery documentation. Figure 1.1 (and Appendix 1) presents the preliminary identification of ideas and concepts which were deemed important in any future mechanism to review nursing and midwifery documentation.

Figure 1.1: Preliminary ideas and concepts analysis

In January 2015, the NMC published new professional standard for Nurses and Midwives i.e., The Code (NMC, 2015). These standards for professional practice were closely aligned to the ideas and concepts previously identified by the researcher, in the preliminary vision for the review mechanism. Documentation is the cornerstone in providing evidence to demonstrate that registrants are complying with these standards. Within this current study, I felt it was important for these standards to be embedded in the new mechanism to review the documentation of care. In addition, it was essential to involve midwives in this process through Participatory Action Research (PAR). According to McNiff and Whitehead (2011) action research is useful in specific situations. These situations include lack of evidence to support or disprove current ways of working. This could also include deficiencies in service provision or in identifying issues with attitudes, knowledge, or skills to carry out EBP. This was further supported by Meyer and Cooper (2015), indicating that PAR focuses on exploration, intervention and evaluation, involving participants as co- researchers in the design and execution of the study.

The **exploration** in Phase 1 was initially conducted to inform the main study. During a World Café style event, the existing mechanism for documentation review was examined and compared against The Code (NMC, 2015) then questions ranked and scored using a nominal group technique. The new DOC Learning Tool was developed to take account of accurate documentation, ongoing risk, and effective communication. Following this phase an Action Research Subgroup was formed and followed the research process through to its conclusion. The **intervention phase** involved four PAR cycles (Plan Act, Observe, Reflect) using quantitative and qualitative research approaches in the evaluation processes. Quantitative components involved testing and retesting the revised mechanism with focus groups providing the qualitative data. The researcher required time to analyse data and reflect on findings with the Action Research Subgroup. Due to the cyclical nature of action research, Meyer and Cooper (2015) highlighted there is no clear finite end to the action research study. Therefore, further statistical testing for final **evaluation** and dissemination of the results will be required as post-doctoral work (Phase three).

1.7 Organisation of Thesis

The thesis is comprised of eight chapters to take the reader through the action research journey from initial planning to completion of this study. Chapter One has set the scene in context for this study. This includes the background into midwifery as a profession and a brief history of Supervision of Midwifery. Learning theories were introduced as an important theoretical framework to underpin the thesis and contextualise professional documentary evidence in practice. Finally, this chapter sets the scene and focus for the study. A detailed critical exploration of the literature is presented in Chapter Two and identifies the gaps in the existing evidence leading to the aim and objectives of the study.

Chapter Three provides a discussion on philosophical underpinnings (epistemology, ontology theoretical perspectives, social constructionism, and social constructivism). Additionally, an overview and justification for the preferred methodology (PAR) is provided to address the overall aim of the study. The methods used within each stage of the research process are detailed in Chapter Four including rigour, ethical considerations and specific issues surrounding the role of the participants and researcher.

Chapter Five presents the full range of study findings, which includes descriptive statistics for the four cycles of testing and qualitative thematic analysis. A discussion comparing the findings with the existing body of literature is detailed in Chapter Six. A reflective account of the challenges experienced by the researcher are detailed in Chapter Seven. Finally, Chapter Eight presents the study conclusions, strengths, limitations and offers evidence-based recommendations for clinical practice, professional development, and future research. A comprehensive reference list, glossary of terms and appendices provide the reader with additional information.

CHAPTER 2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

The background and setting the context for the study was provided in Chapter One. This chapter presents the detailed review of the literature which contributed to formulating the final research aim for this present study. McNiff and Whitehead (2011) argued that completing a separate literature review is not always necessary in action research. However, the authors highlighted the necessity to demonstrate how the literature has framed the development of the research project as well as developed a deeper understanding of the topic (McNiff and Whitehead, 2011). As the nature of action research is through emerging enquiry through cycles this literature review has evolved and developed (Gray, 2018). The initial literature review was conducted in 2015, updated in 2018 and again in 2020.

2.2 Literature review strategy

The following section provides an overview of the method and rationale for the literature review, the broad literature review question, the search terms and the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Method and rationale:

There are two types of literature review: systematic reviews, and narrative (traditional) literature reviews. Systematic reviews offer a rigorous and systematic approach to answer a clearly formulated question using multiple databases to inform evidence-based practice (Cluett and Bluff, 2006; Onweugbuzie and Frels, 2016). According to Parahoo (2014) it can be defined as 'research on research'. Narrative (traditional) review offers a broad comprehensive analysis of a topic, whilst identifying themes in the literature that helps identify gaps that justifies further research being conducted (Cluett and Bluff, 2006; Parahoo, 2014; Machi and McEvoy, 2016). A narrative literature review was the preferred method adopted by the researcher. Therefore, this review analysed grey literature, quantitative and qualitative studies in a rigorous manner to address the literature review question.

Literature review question

According to Beecroft, Booth and Rees (2015), formulating a research question to focus the literature review is key to ensuring the literature to be reviewed is manageable and relevant. A modified version of the PICO (Population, Intervention, Comparison and Outcome) (Glasper and Rees, 2012) model was used to develop the following literature review questions:

- How do midwives provide documentary evidence of care?
- How do nurses / midwives learn in clinical practice?

Search terms

Databases examined included CINAHL, EBSCO, MEDLINE using the key phrases 'documentation of care' AND 'nursing' AND / OR 'midwifery'. An update of the literature review in 2020 included ways nurses and midwives learn in clinical practice including peer review and reflection. Using the terms 'learning tools in clinical practice', 'learning strategies in clinical practice' AND / OR 'midwives / midwife / midwifery', for a further literature review search. Databases included CINAHL, Education Source, Health Source, APA Psycarticles and Medline. As with the other searches, this search was expanded to include other health professionals working in clinical practice (e.g., nurses, doctors, radiographers).

Inclusion and exclusion criteria

Inclusion

- Full text articles available.
- Studies using quantitative or qualitative approaches.
- Ethical approval of studies had been obtained.
- Studies involving health professionals working in clinical practice.
- Seminal studies on documentation.

Exclusion

- Articles which were not peer reviewed.
- Articles not available in English.

The first part of the literature review produced 1637 hits. A further 30 records were found through examination of the reference lists of the articles. The researcher reviewed the titles of all the articles. There were 14 duplicated and 85 articles deemed worthy of further inspection. Further scrutiny of the 85 articles including searching the reference list of the articles led to 41 articles selected for further analysis (Figure 2.1).

Due to the paucity of evidence found on midwifery documentation the search was widened to explore documentation of nursing care. Rationale being that nursing in the UK operates under the same standards as per The Code (NMC, 2018). Within this critical literature review, the purpose, assessment, barriers, improvement, and the tools used to assess documentation are examined. Additionally, the wider implementation of electronic documentation recording systems, is also considered.

The second part of the literature search identified 190 possible research articles. Through further exploration of the abstracts, this was narrowed down to 34 articles for critical analysis to be included in the literature review (Figure 2.2).

All literature was stored in the Endnote® online referencing system. This allowed all the searches to be filed in a systematic manner (Pears and Shields, 2019) along with journal PDFs. A Prisma diagram displays the literature searches process as included in Figure 2.1 (Documentation in clinical care) and Figure 2.2 (Learning in clinical practice). Appendices 2 to 11 provides full data extraction tables of the literature based on the framework by Sui and Comersay (2018). In addition, a selection of key searches is appropriately located throughout the narrative of the literature review.

2.3 Organisation of literature review

The literature review begins with a review of the purpose and quality of documentation (Section 2.3). The barriers to effective documentation are explored in Section 2.4 and what improves documentation is explored in Section 2.5. The background of documentation tools is explored in Section 2.6. In section 2.7, the move to electronic record documentation is reviewed. Finally, in Section 2.8 the learning strategies used by health professionals in clinical practice are examined. This led to the proposal for the study. A study, which would involve midwives in the development and implementation of a user-friendly tool that not only could be used to improve their documentation but also foster a lifelong learning approach to adhering to the standards of The Code (NMC, 2018).

Figure 2.1: Literature search: Documentation in Clinical Care

Figure 2.2: Literature Search: Learning in Clinical Practice

2.4 The purpose and quality of clinical documentation

A critical review of the purpose and quality of documentation within health care is now provided. This includes examining the barriers to effective documentation (time, compliance, human and organisational factors) are also explored.

2.4.1 The purpose of documentation

To assess documentation, it is necessary to first define the purpose of documentation within nursing and midwifery. Most researchers concur that whilst clinical documentation is complex, it is required to provide a narrative of the patient's journey, including prescription, implementation, and evaluation of care (Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths, 2010; Kent and Morrow, 2014; Vowden and Vowden, 2015; Kerkin, Lennox and Patterson, 2018; Ramukumba and Amouri, 2019).

Interestingly, no studies were found which exclusively reviewed the purpose of midwifery documentation. This current situation agrees with earlier findings by Kerkin, Lennox and Patterson's (2018) literature review with evidence ranging between 1990-2016. This review also emphasised the paucity of evidence available surrounding midwifery documentation. Both Kerkin, Lennox and Patterson's (2018) review and the present review followed similar stringent methodical approaches for searching the literature which enabled comparisons to be made (Cluett and Bluff, 2006). In their review, Kerkin, Lennox and Patterson (2018) also failed to identify any specific midwifery focussed literature and had to expand their search to include other health care disciplines to identify key generic functions of clinical documentation. Kerkin, Lennox and Patterson (2018) emphasised the essential role midwifery documentation has to play in evidencing standards of clinical care. They highlighted important key factors including the role documentation provides in evidencing partnership with women, communication between health professionals, improving standards of care and clear care planning. Additionally, documentation provides data for quality assurance and research processes (Kerkin, Lennox and Patterson, 2018). Key findings emphasised that the function of reviewing clinical cases improved outcomes for women / babies, informed best practice and made midwifery care visible. Ultimately, documentation provides a narrative of the woman's journey, offers

midwives the basis for reflection as well as fulfilling legal and professional obligations. Kerkin, Lennox and Patterson (2018) highlighted the need for specific research on documentation of midwifery care to meet the needs of women and midwives. However, the most important difference between documentation of nursing care and midwifery care is that that midwifery documentation can be reviewed up to a period of 25 years, whereas nursing documentation is eight years after care completed or eight years after patient has died (Dimond, 2011; British Medical Association, 2021).

Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths (2010) conducted a robust meta-synthesis to identify the essential components of nursing documentation. Polit and Beck (2018), highlighted meta-synthesis gathers information and experiences together to produce themes but warn this approach is subject to the researcher's interpretation. The researchers provided a transparent and logical account of the processes identifying the problem, search strategy, sample, appraisal of studies, data extraction and analysis (Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths, 2010). Within a meta-synthesis, these processes lead to the trustworthiness of the review (Polit and Beck, 2016). Both literature searches supporting the meta-synthesis included evidence from 1982-2008. The first meta-synthesis of qualitative studies (CINAHL, 1982-2008) identified five themes; purpose of nursing documentation; avoidance of duplication of information from charts; how to document nursing tasks; process of documenting care, with a final key theme that input from the patient is crucial in documentary evidence. The second synthesis (MEDLINE, 1996-2008) by Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths (2010) identified seven similar key themes, but also different themes materialised. These included documentary evidence that care provided by nurses was patient centred incorporating patient education, psychological care, and ongoing support. Importantly the themes identified that documentary evidence to be contemporary, objective and presented in a logical sequence recording variance of care whilst meeting legal requirements. Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths (2010) emphasised that regular reviews of nursing documentation were essential as a quality mechanism to ensure compliance of documentation appraising clinical practice. Key conclusions highlighted that nurses should be encouraged to value documentation and further research was required in this field (Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths, 2010).

A documentation policy produced by Kent and Morrow (2014), based on the World Health Organisation (WHO) (2007) Guidelines for Medical Record and Clinical Documentation was launched in 2012. This documentation policy endorsed the findings by Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths (2010). The three key policy principles identified were documentation as a mechanism for evidencing complete and comprehensive records of care: ensuring a person-centred and collaborative approach. Finally, maintaining patient confidentiality throughout was imperative. Subsequently, the policy informed the development of a new nursing patient record and standardisation of all documentation. Over time the standardisation of documentation was incorporated into clinical practice where the arrival of electronic record systems enhanced the process (Kent and Morrow, 2014).

Whilst Vowden and Vowden's (2015) report concurred with Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths (2010) findings, they added the elements that accurate documentation improves both communication and continuity of care delivery. This finding was emulated by a small intervention study by Neary (2014) involving ten nurses which highlighted that effective documentation also provided evidence of the quality-of-care assessment (Neary, 2014). Due to the small sample size these results were not generalisable and should be viewed with caution (Parahoo, 2014). Furthermore, Kent and Morrow (2014) also emphasised that documentation should be person-centred and collaborative as well as ensuring and maintaining patient confidentiality. Paans et al. (2013) also highlighted that accurate documentation is crucial to patient safety and improves communication between professionals. Documentary evidence is a record of the care carried out, not only by the individual practitioner, but also the care provided by all health care professionals involved in providing care to the patient (Paans et al., 2013; Vowden and Vowden, 2015). Evidence confirmed that documentation should also be contemporaneous, accurate, legible, objective, dated, signed, and provide a clear visible pathway of care (Paans et al., 2013; Neary, 2014; Vowden and Vowden, 2015). Vowden and Vowden (2015) strongly argued that decades of failure to provide an accurate account of risk assessment and care planning has significantly contributed to the detrimental effect on patient care. They stressed the need for regular review of documentation and development of agreed protocols to ensure appropriate risk assessment is taking place Vowden and Vowden (2015). Table 2. 1 provides a selection of the key findings from the literature presented in this section.

Table 2-1: Evidence supporting the purpose of documentation

Reference	Study overview	Key findings
Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths (2010)	<p>Aim: to identify essential components of nursing evidenced in documentation review.</p> <p>Design: meta-study.</p> <p>Methods: 171 papers initially identified, from these 28 articles met criteria required to address the aim of the study.</p>	<p>Essential characteristics: patient centred, evidence of nurses providing patient education and psychological and support.</p> <p>Evidence of nurses being:</p> <p>Objective, logical; providing sequential, contemporary, record variances of care; meet legal requirements.</p>
Kent and Morrow (2014)	<p>Aim: to promote delivery of the three quality ambitions of safe, effective, and person-centred care through improving documentation.</p> <p>Design/methods: Quality Improvement.</p>	<p>Absence of governance in nursing and midwifery regarding documentation.</p>
Vowden and Vowden (2015)	<p>Aim: to assess quality of documentation.</p> <p>Design; method: Report.</p>	<p>Documentation should be:</p> <p>Adequate.</p> <p>Easy to follow.</p> <p>Supports care delivery.</p> <p>UK.</p> <p>Need for Universal system of documentation linked to reporting.</p>
Kerkin, Lennox and Patterson (2018)	<p>Aim: to explore the literature in relation to the purposes of midwifery documentation.</p> <p>Method: literature review.</p>	<p>No research articles were found focussing on addressing the purpose of documentation in midwifery practice.</p>
Ramukumba and Amouri (2019)	<p>Aim: To explore nurses' perspectives of the documentation audit process.</p> <p>Method: Exploratory and descriptive.</p>	<p>Three themes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • implementation of documentation, • evaluation of documentation • improve documentation measures

2.4.2 Assessing the quality of documentation

Due to the paucity of studies relating to reviewing midwifery documentation, this search expanded to include nursing documentation. Where appropriate commentary of midwifery documentation is included. Whilst two of the midwifery specific studies were peer reviewed demonstrating rigour (Basu and Seopela, 2010; Markam et al., 2018), these studies proved difficult to interpret at times due to translation into English from the native language.

Wang, Hailey, and Yu (2011) conducted a mixed method systematic review (2000 - 2010) to assess quality of nursing documentation and the related evaluation instruments. Seven databases were searched resulting in n=77 quantitative (n=32) studies and qualitative (n=45) studies from fifteen countries globally. Study settings were mainly hospital based(n=51), although primary health centres and community setting studies were included with noticeably wide-ranging sample sizes from 15 to 13,776 (Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011). Study findings were summarised into two themes which included issues with nursing documentation and the effects of study interventions on nursing documentation (Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011). The researchers found the main issue with nursing documentation was that it focussed on the physical process, with little detail provided on sociological, psychological, cultural, or spiritual aspects of care. Lack of patient involvement in any decisions made lack of detailed patient assessment and little patient education documented were also key findings. Furthermore, poor legibility with paper documentation and lengthy care plans within Electronic Health Record Systems (EHRS) were reported in other studies (Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011). The disparity between what was documented compared to independent patient assessment, interviews and direct observation of clinical practice was of concern, highlighting the discrepancy between real events and what was written. Study interventions included a range of approaches. The interventions cited were the introduction of EHRS, the development of standardising documentation approaches, the introduction of nursing documentation standards and increased education surrounding documentation. Individually, each approach improved the quality of documentation (Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011).

Through examining the literature from the past decade (2010 - 2020), concern about the quality of healthcare documentation continues to be a worldwide issue (Basu and

Seopel, 2010; Monsen et al., 2011; O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Broderick and Coffey, 2012; Asamani et al., 2014; Norouzi et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018a; Vafeai et al., 2018b). However, many studies reviewed used small samples, which limits the generalisability of the results (Cluett, 2006; Polit and Beck, 2020). Furthermore, varying degrees of information provided on the construction, testing of the various tools utilised to assess the quality of documentation affected the validity and reliability of the instruments (Grove and Ciper, 2017). Therefore, it is apparent from the literature reviews that there remains a disparity in the different ways healthcare is recorded. For example, in South Africa, an 'antenatal card' is used to record midwifery care for pregnant women. Basu and Seopela (2010) comparing antenatal cards with clinical notes conducted an evaluation of documented evidence. The researchers used a convenience sample of retrospective records from women (n=413) who birthed in one hospital, over a one-month period. Findings revealed poor documentation in a range of key midwifery factors including blood results, failure to record observations such as maternal weight, blood pressures and fundal height measurement. Important findings from this study highlighted failure to document could result in sub optimal care and emphasised the need for in-service training especially documentation for maternity care professionals. Whilst no limitations of this small study were identified, it should be noted that the study was conducted by two obstetricians and only involved one unit. Therefore, this could be seen as a limitation, reducing the generalisability (Grove, Gray and Burns, 2015). Findings from other documentation related studies have also agreed with the key findings of Basu and Seopela (2010). These include findings from a small retrospective review study (n=42) by Markam et al. (2018) to explore midwives need and intention to adopt an electronic antenatal care recording mechanism in Indonesia. Findings revealed that 73% of the case note records were incomplete with failure to record key observations, which is a major concern for patient safety (Markam et al. (2018).

Current practice of nursing documentation was examined in a retrospective review of patient case notes (n=100) in Ghana (Asamani et al. (2014). The sample was randomly selected from two hospitals with the data collected using a non-validated tool specifically developed by the researchers for the purpose. All patient case notes contained documentation errors relating to communication, safe and appropriate nursing care or professional and legal standards care. Contravening the College of

Registered Nurses of British Columbia (CRNBC) documentation standards (CRNBC, 2021). Findings from this study resulted in in-service staff training focussing on documentation, which is yet to be evaluated. The researchers recommended involving nurses and other key personnel in the development of policies / guidelines on documentation. These recommendations were also reported in earlier studies (Basu and Seopela, 2010; Monsen et al., 2011; O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Broderick and Coffey, 2012; Asamani et al., 2014) and replicated in later studies (Norouzi et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018a Vafeai et al., 2018b;).

Failure to document key observations in patient case notes is reported to be an international problem (Basu and Seopela, 2010; Monsen et al., 2011; O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Broderick and Coffey, 2012; Asamani et al., 2014; Norouzi et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018a; Vafeai et al., 2018b). The quality of documentation across a sample of n=200 case notes within ten hospitals in Australia was assessed using the Nursing and Midwifery Content Audit Tool (NMCAT) created by Johnson, Jefferies, Langdon (2010). The Australian NMCAT assessed the quality of nursing documentation over five episodes of care including patient admission and discharge (Johnson, Jefferies, Langdon, 2010). The tool was created utilising a time sampling method. This involved examining the content, in addition to the qualities of documentation reported in earlier studies by Jefferies, Johnson and Griffiths. (2010), discussed in Section 2.3.1. The researchers enhanced reliability by piloting the refined tool and demonstrated 85% inter rater agreement from 20 case notes between two raters. As no other tests to check validity were stated then the overall validity and reliability of the tool remains in question (Polit and Beck, 2018). One major limitation identified was that no clinicians were involved in the development of the tool, resulting in uncertainty of the clinical usability of the tool. In their extensive testing of the Q-DIO instrument Müller-Staub (2009) emphasised the importance of involving health care participants in the development of any tools for clinical documentation review.

In their main study, Johnson, Jefferies, and Langdon (2010) examined two hundred case notes (twenty randomly selected from each of ten hospitals). The participants in this study reported that the tool was easy to use and not time consuming as each documentation review only took six to seven minutes to complete. Results revealed that scores were consistently high for logical presentation and recording of objective

information. However, there was a tendency for patient feedback including compliance to medication was not routinely recorded and therefore problematic for accuracy and completeness of patient documentation. Other issues of concern were related to grammar, spelling and overuse of local abbreviations resulting in difficulty in reading and interpreting the case notes (Johnson, Jefferies, and Langdon, 2010). The researchers recommended the use of software packages and writing coaches to improve the presentation and readability of nursing documentation as well as continual assessment of documentation using NMCAT. It is worthy of note that mental health, paediatric and midwifery case notes were included in the sample with no mention of any discipline specific issues highlighted (Johnson, Jefferies, and Langdon, 2010). Assessing the usability of the tool across disciplines may have been useful to highlight specific discipline issues (Patton, 1990). This could be portrayed as a limitation to the study (Polit and Beck, 2020). Other recommendations included the usefulness of NMCAT tool for ward staff or their managers to conduct documentation reviews timeously after episodes of care. Thus, enabling questions to be asked about the content and providing a learning opportunity and quality review of documentation standards (Johnson, Jefferies, and Langdon, 2010).

Similar issues were reported by O'Brien and Cowman (2011) following examination of pressure ulcer care documentation in a large Republic of Ireland teaching hospital. Mixed methods approaches were utilised for data collection comprising a retrospective case note review (n=85) from two hospital wards and one focus group of thirteen nurses to discuss review findings. The review tool consisted of nine questions based on a specialised framework for pressure ulcers (European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel (EPUAP), 2002) pressure ulcer minimum data set). A strength to this tool was the content validity index score of 0.98 indicated a high level of agreement amongst the raters (Polit and Beck, 2018). Review findings revealed two key issues which included poor documentation of key pressure area with only 45% (n=38) of care planning documented. Interestingly, of the 38 case notes documenting care planning, 53% failed to have the implementation of the care plan recorded and 66% (n=25) also omitted to document any care plan outcomes. Both are significant issues which are necessary to demonstrate effective patient care through documentation (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011). As highlighted by Jolley (2020), quantitative and qualitative data are equally important when assessing quality of health care. O'Brien and Cowman (2011)

extracted four themes from the qualitative data including, poor documentation of pressure ulcers, barriers to documentation, issues with inadequate care planning and recommendations for improvement of documentation. Despite the high content validity index (0.98), several study limitations were identified including issues with the data collection tool, namely failure to collect exact timing of when the pressure ulcer occurred (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011). Furthermore, poor handwriting made the notes difficult to interpret and the Hawthorne affect was apparent (Parahoo, 2014) as some participants may have changed their documentation practice as they were aware the review was being undertaken. Another limitation noted was the small sample size (n=85) thus affecting generalisability (Grove, Gray and Burns, 2015). Key recommendations identified that clear and explicit care planning was essential to improve practice coupled with more education focussed on clinical documentation (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011). These findings were further supported in later studies (Broderick and Coffey, 2012; Asamani et al., 2014).

Several studies revealed key gaps in aspects of documentation including care planning and assessment of patient care (Basu and Seopela, 2010; O'Brien, and Cowman, 2011). In a qualitative descriptive study, n=56 case notes were examined, scored, and coded into themes (Broderick and Coffey, 2012). Broderick and Coffey (2012) also identified lack of detailed documentation on psychological and sociological care. Although some evidence identified that patients' religious beliefs were documented, there was little or no documentation about patients being involved in their care planning. Broderick and Coffey (2012) recommended that nurses needed to involve patients in meaningful discussions about their care and ensure that these discussions are clearly documented. This is supported with the underpinning principles of professional standards within The Code (NMC, 2018).

A medical student and two professors in a Coronary Care Unit in Iran (Norouzi et al., 2018) conducted one of the largest contemporary studies examining the quality of nursing documentation. Four patient records from 98 nurses were reviewed, using a non-validated data extraction tool compiled by the researchers for the purpose of the study. Results for the structure of the documentation revealed that 69% of the documents scored 'very good', 1% 'moderate' with 30% scoring 'good'. For the content component of the documentation, 40% scored 'moderate', 49% scored 'good', with

only 11% of documentation scoring 'very good'. Interestingly no evidence of poor documentation was reported in this study (Norouzi et al., 2018). Significant differences between participants were noted, with higher and more positive scores from: females compared to male counterparts ($p=0.001$); those with a master's degree ($p=0.001$) and those who had completed an education programme to improve clinical documentation ($p=0.005$). Whilst it was noted that quality of documentation significantly improved at weekends and holiday periods ($p=0.003$), the researchers did not expand on the rationale for these findings (Norouzi et al., 2018). Conversely, findings highlighted that increased age, lack of experience and overtime hours had a negative effect on the quality of documentation. Researchers concluded the need for education and training surrounding nursing documentation to improve the quality of standards. Despite this being a large study with significant findings, no limitations were identified by Norouzi et al. (2018). However, it was noted that nursing documentation was reviewed by medical staff and only from one unit with no mention of the review tool being validated. These limitations have implications for reducing the generalisability of the study findings (Cluett, 2006; Polit and Beck, 2020). Although medical staff reviewing nursing documentation could be seen as objective, it would be beneficial for reviewers from the same discipline to review the notes that is peer review so that the nurses could learn from each other from this process (Watson et al., 2014).

A further study from Iran by Vafeai et al. (2018a), also revealed issues with the quality of nursing documentation ($n=200$ nursing case notes). Of the thirty key documentary components examined, none of the case notes provided information on patients' nutrition, bodily functions, or detailed explanation of the patient's condition. In eight components, less than ten out of 200 records were complete. Ultimately most components were scored as incomplete or illegible (Vafeai et al., 2018a), which is an alarming finding.

Although consensus exists in the literature about the content and purpose of documentation, agreement of assessing the quality of individual pieces of documentation is challenging, even amongst experts. Monsen et al. (2011) confirmed these challenges in a USA retrospective cohort study. A panel of experts (three experienced nurses) reviewed nursing data from 100 public health client case notes. The inclusion criteria specified three visits were required to increase the likelihood of

documentary evidence of the client's behavioural change, mental health, substance use issues and financial income. Descriptive statistics in the form of Interclass Correlation Coefficients (ICC) were used to explore agreement between the experts (Monsen et al., 2011). ICCs are useful when comparing similarity to responses noted between groups or individuals (Grove and Ciper, 2017). The results ranged from an ICC of 0.35 - 0.63 revealing very low agreement between experts, averaging 42% agreement between two experts and only 21% agreement between three experts. Notably, when this was compared to review of external agency case notes, this agreement reduced to less than 8%, suggesting that inter rater reliability was not achieved (Grove and Ciper, 2017). Monsen et al. (2011) demonstrated the challenges of verifying the quality of any data and highlighted the need for the development of robust systems, which ensure inter rater agreement. Furthermore, the need for more patient details within the case notes were required to demonstrate reliability between raters. Monsen et al., (2011) recommended the need for a reliable mechanism to record clinical data to ensure that non ambiguous facts are clearly presented to address the discrepancy identified in the case note review.

Ascertaining the opinion of how nurses feel when their professional documentation is being scrutinised is just as important as assessing the qualities and key components required of documentation. In a large United Arab Emirates (UAE) hospital, Ramukumba and Amouri (2019) conducted a descriptive study to explore nurses' views on the examination of their professional documentation. The main qualitative data collection method included three focus groups including a total of seventeen nurses. Thematic analysis revealed three major themes; 'implementation of the process', 'evaluation of the process' and 'measures to improve documentation'. The nurses stressed the review process of documentation was vital to ensure patient safety whilst recognising the value of using a standardised tool in the process. As with numerous previous studies the researchers also advocated education and training for nurses to support them in the review process and completion of documentation (Basu and Seopela, 2010; Monsen et al., 2011; O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Broderick and Coffey, 2012; Asamani et al., 2014; Norouzi et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018a). Additionally, Ramukumba and Amouri (2019) recommended that time was required to undertake the documentation review with further dissemination of the results to improve future practice. Interestingly, nurses also acknowledged the difficulties in

reviewing electronic compared to paper-based nursing documentation. Ramukumba and Amouri (2019) proposed alignment of future Electronic Documentation Systems (EDS) and documentation review tools to ensure more efficient review of documentation.

2.5 Barriers affecting quality of documentation

Within the literature, barriers to complete accurate documentation were consistently highlighted and included the time taken to complete documentation, compliance in recording data and human and organisational factors.

2.5.1 Time taken to complete documentation

Pelletier, Duffield, and Donoghue (2005) conducted a noteworthy research study within two hospital settings in New South Wales, Australia examining nurses' documentation. The study observed 51 nurses in one hospital compared to 55 nurses in another, in relation to documentation of 16,395 nursing activities. Overall findings were similar between hospitals except for the timing of when documentation took place, which peaked in late morning or mid-afternoon. This was due to the variance in shift patterns between the two hospitals. The researchers reported that whilst health professionals spent 37 - 38% of their time in the transfer of information, only 7% was dedicated to completion of formal documentation. Interestingly, the Hawthorne effect was acknowledged by Pelletier, Duffield, and Donoghue (2005). This is recognised to be a limitation of observational studies (Tucker, Brandling and Fox, 2009). However, the positive impact on documentation was short lived as the nurses forgot they were being observed and reverted to pre-study documentary processes. A further limitation in the comparison between the hospital's documentation methods was that shift patterns, skill mix, and organisation of care varied between units and may have introduced confounding variables (Polit and Beck, 2020). Perceived time for documentation was less than nurses anticipated, whereas verbal transfer of clinical information at handovers was observed to take up a larger proportion of the nurses' time. Pelletier, Duffield, and Donoghue (2005) concluded that time taken to complete documentation was not excessive and this finding should be reassuring to staff. Arguably, this could question the quality of the written documentation due to the inequity of time spent between this and oral communication, with the possibility of key

elements of care not being documented, which is concerning. Staff justified this finding as they perceived that taking the time to document could be more valuably spent conducting patient care (Pelletier, Duffield, and Donoghue, 2005).

Despite a study indicating that documentation is not time consuming (Pelletier, Duffield, and Donoghue, 2005), lack of time to complete documentation is a common finding of many UK and international studies (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Boucher et al., 2012; Bailey, Wilson and Yoong, 2015; Mutshatshi et al., 2018; Norouzi et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018a). However, irrespective whether it is time consuming or not, clear documentary evidence of patient care is reported to be just as important as conducting clinical care (NMC, 2018).

As well as lack of time to complete documentation, Bailey, Wilson and Yoong (2015) reported that the quality of documentation was also dependent on the timing during the shift when documentation took place. The study to review midwives' documentation was conducted in a labour ward in London, UK. To assess the data, a tool was created using criteria from the Nursing and Midwifery Council Record Keeping Guidance (NMC, 2009) and the National Institute for Clinical Excellence (NICE) Guidelines for Intrapartum Care (NICE, 2007). Two medical students independently reviewed sixty-one casenotes from midwifery case notes. If there was any disparity a third assessor, a consultant obstetrician and gynaecologist, reviewed the case notes to make the final decision (Bailey, Wilson and Yoong, 2015). It was noticeable that the quality of documentation of care deteriorated by the middle to end of the shift irrespective if this was day or night shift. Results on the quality / accuracy of documentation were significant ($p=0.05$) across the shift timeframe, with scores of 92% at the beginning, 90% middle and 82% at the end of a twelve-hour shift. Interestingly, this finding was irrespective of workload, staff numbers or number of high-risk cases within the labour ward. From the case note documentation reviewed, Partogram scores were lower overall with 78% at the beginning of the shift, 51% at the middle and 56% at the end. Statistical difference noted between beginning and middle of shift was $p=0.05$, but no statistical significance between middle and the end of shift. Bailey, Wilson and Yoong, (2015), noted that Partogram accuracy was directly linked to workload and woman to midwife ratio documentation. Whilst these findings are

interesting, a major limitation would be that the researchers did not consider comparing length of shifts and would be worthy of further exploration.

2.5.2 Human and organisational factors

The key human and organisational factors highlighted from research studies as being barriers to effective documentation include staffing, recording systems, lack of governance and education surrounding documentation (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Bailey, Wilson and Yoong, 2015, Mutshatshi et al., 2018; Norouzi et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018a).

Vafeai et al. (2018b) reiterated these findings when exploring nurses' perceptions on the barriers to documentation. Qualitative data were collated through semi-structured interviews involving n=20 participants (17 nurses and 3 senior nurses). Thematic analysis revealed three main themes including, 'issues with the health information system', 'lack of governance surrounding documentation' and 'documentation competency'. Issues with the health information system affected time management to complete documentation. Lack of governance surrounding documentation and legal implications of failure to document, were a concern to all nurses irrespective of their seniority. It was interesting to note that this failure to review documentation resulted in poor documentation going unchecked and negatively impacting on the quality of documentary evidence of care provided (Vafeai et al., 2018b). This important finding was also acknowledged in other studies reviewing nursing documentation (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Mutshatshi et al., 2018; Norouzi et al., 2018). Additionally, new findings emerged that nurses attributed lack of documentation competency to staff shortage, leading to any increased number of overtime hours, staff burnout which all correlated to poor documentation (Vafeai et al., 2018b). In their study, Bailey, Wilson and Yoong (2015) attributed the deterioration of the quality of documentation to fatigue, boredom, or lack of concentration during the shift and earlier deterioration of Partogram documentation due to the prospective nature of the documentation. However, they did not take cognisance that several women were looked after by the same midwife simultaneously, making it difficult to carry out all vital maternal and fetal observations timeously. Competing demands were frequently cited in other research studies where documentation was given low priority (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Mutshatshi et al., 2018; Norouzi et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018b). Bailey, Wilson and

Yoong (2015) emphasised that documentation is a marker for care and should be given priority so that it can be carried out accurately. The study recommended more breaks for midwives during the shift, especially towards the end of the shift and suggested the introduction of electronic record keeping may improve the quality of the documentation. A limitation of this study was that medical staff rather than midwives conducted the review, although this could be seen as being more objective, it lacked learning opportunities for the midwives. Therefore, the findings should be viewed with caution (Rees, 2011; Polit and Beck, 2020).

Worldwide studies have highlighted that staffing shortages are detrimental to effective documentation (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Mutshatshi et al., 2018; Norouzi et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018b). Additionally, Norouzi et al. (2018) reported that increased age, lack of experience of nurses and number of overtime hours had a negative effect on documentation and highlighted complex documentation processes and lack of stationary were issues. O'Brien and Cowman (2011) further identified poor access to notes and computers, too many distractions and illegible writing on charts were additional problems.

Two studies explored the views of senior staff compared to staff nurses on concerns surrounding documentation (Kamil, Rachmah and Wardani, 2018; Shahverdi and Nasiri, 2018). Kamil, Rachmah and Wardani (2018) conducted a qualitative study examining issues with nursing documentation in an Indonesian urban hospital. Thirty-five nurses who had worked in the hospital for at least a year, participated in four focus groups. Focus groups with senior nurses and staff nurses identified the barriers to effective documentation. Three communal key themes were identified in completing documentation: 'lack of supervision and support' (including lack of documentation review); 'lack of confidence and competence' (due to lack of education) and 'lack of enthusiasm' (due to competing demands in clinical practice). O'Brien and Cowman (2011), Mutshatshi et al. (2018), Norouzi et al. (2018) and Vafeai et al. (2018b) identified similar findings in their studies. Kamil, Rachmah and Wardani (2018) concluded that education and support to complete documentation was essential and highlighted regular review of documentation in clinical practice was required for quality improvement. A limitation was the lack of information surrounding data analysis, which limits the trustworthiness of the findings (Polit and Beck, 2018).

Shahverdi and Nasiri (2018) conducted a descriptive correlational study of nursing documentation in an Iranian hospital and replicated the findings of Kamil, Rachmah and Wardani (2018). A random selection of n=140 nurses and using a purposive sample of all 15 head nurses completed a questionnaire to explore the quality and issues of documentation. No significant differences were noted on statistical analysis irrespective of grade of nursing staff with regards to the mean scores of personal, managerial, and organisational factors impacting on the quality of the documentation ($p>0.05$). Organisational barriers revealed the highest scoring and more negative factors included heavy workload, fear of inadequate documentation and lack of guidance on documentation (Shahverdi and Nasiri, 2018).

2.5.3 Compliance in recording data

In Australia, Boucher et al. (2012) conducted a retrospective comparative study within a Paediatric Intensive Care Unit to compare nurses' compliance in completing two discharge documentation checklists. The original checklist of all patients discharged were examined (n=85 checklists i.e., Form A) in November 2009 compared with the updated checklist (n=49 checklists i.e., Form B) in February 2010. Results revealed completion of data within both discharge checklists were of a very poor standard. Essential nursing tasks were often omitted from the documentation with 70% of nursing staff across the shift patterns failing to complete the checklists. When the updated checklist (Form B) was introduced for everyday use, compliance tended to improve, although overall the standard of completion remained poor. Compliance did not improve irrespective of age of patient, length of stay or type of illness. The researchers commented that if care was not recorded on the checklist they could not confirm if care had been provided or just not documented. Boucher et al. (2012) suggested that nurses were forgoing accurate documentation to provide care for their patients. They highlighted that documentation including checklists should always be to enhance patient care and not be too complicated or repetitive, hindering already overworked staff. The researchers questioned the appropriateness of the checklists due to the low compliance. However, they indicated that accurate documentation was key to ensuring patient safety and all documentation aids / checklists should be facilitative rather than being obstructive. Boucher et al. (2012) acknowledged study limitations, which included the variance in both checklists, making it difficult to compare

them coupled by the imbalance of sample sizes. Polit and Beck (2020) indicate that sample sizes require to be similar to compare variables. Further limitations identified were that some figures were presented as graphs but not adequately explained, questioning the credibility of the findings (Gray, 2018). Furthermore, the high number of items per checklist staff had to complete may have been a major factor with compliance and this was not addressed in the discussion by the researchers (Boucher et al., 2012).

This section has provided evidence that barriers to complete documentation are complex and often multi-faceted. Reduced time to complete documentation due to competing clinical demands was cited in many studies (Pelletier, Duffield, and Donoghue, 2005; O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Boucher et al., 2012; Bailey, Wilson and Yoong 2015; Mutshatshi et al., 2018; Norouzi et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018b). Effective documentation could be dependent on the time (within the shift) documentation was completed (Bailey, Wilson and Yoong, 2015). Poor staffing levels, lack of governance and education surrounding documentation was also identified as factors (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Kamil, Rachmah and Wardani, 2018, Mutshatshi et al., 2018; Norouzi et al., 2018; Shahverdi and Nasiri, 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018b). Scarcity of equipment was also a problem with Norouzi et al. (2018) reporting lack of basic equipment such as stationary impinged on the quality of documentation. O'Brien and Cowman (2011) identified a paucity of computers as problematic within their study. Compliance to complete documentation was an issue and Boucher et al. (2012) recommended that documentation should always be to enhance patient care and not be too complicated or repetitive to make it an encumbrance to already overworked staff,

2.6 What improves documentation?

Using an action research study, Okaisu et al. (2014) investigated documentation in a children's hospital in Uganda. This involved examining the literature, conducting a retrospective review of documentation and qualitative interviews with nurse managers. The researchers aimed to improve nursing documentation through three phases of service modifications. The initial review by Okaisu et al. (2014) revealed a suboptimal standard of record keeping. Interviews with nurse leaders suggested lack of training

surrounding documentation might have been a contributing factor of the poor standard of record keeping. Therefore, phase one involved carrying out a five-day educational and training programme to improve nursing documentation. The number of participants attending was not included. Patient case notes were examined and compared both prior to and one-month following the programme. Comparison revealed very little change evidenced in the standard of documentation. This was a disappointing finding especially as education was a key recommendation from many nursing documentation studies previously examined (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Kamil, Rachmah and Wardani, 2018, Mutshatshi et al., 2018; Norouzi et al., 2018; Shahverdi and Nasiri, 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018b). On reflection, Okaisu et al. (2014) attributed perceived cultural barriers within the organisation for this lack of change. McNiff and Whitehead (2011) supported this argument, indicating that for change to occur, the people within the organisation must subscribe to the change. This includes taking ownership of the change as part of the culture of the organisation or establishment.

Phase two involved interviews with visiting professors, nursing students and nursing staff to examine the cultural barriers in more detail (Okaisu et al., 2014). Findings led to changes in the hospital's orientation programme with the focus changing care to become more patient centred care and the implementation of new documentation practices. This included a new admission and discharge documentation template incorporating a new assessment process. Although initially there was improvement in new nurses' documentation reported this improvement was not sustained (Okaisu et al., 2014). In concurrence with the findings from a previous study by Boucher et al. (2012), Okaisu et al. (2014) also found the documentation template was too time consuming to complete and needed to be modified to improve compliance.

Phase three involved a complete overhaul of organisational culture, including changes to leadership and communication strategies, staffing levels, skill mixes and recognition of nursing achievements. In addition, testing and retesting the admission and discharge assessment form was undertaken. This led to improvement in documentation and in the organisational culture. Through this action research study, Okaisu et al. (2014) reported that providing education and training alone was not sufficient to ensure sustained practice change. For this to occur a multi-faceted

approach was required which included examining best practice, listening to staff and patients to ensure that systems changed to improve care. McNiff and Whitehead (2011) highlight a multi-faceted approach is a fundamental aspect of conducting an action research project. Some study limitations were evident on review but were not cited by Okaisu et al. (2014). Providing a more comprehensive results section would have added to the credibility of the study (Parahoo, 2014). Whilst the study by Okaisu et al. (2014) involved only one hospital, the culture of other hospitals would vary therefore difficult to assess generalisability of study. In addition, phase three involved multiple changes, making it difficult to ascertain what made the difference.

Gray (2018) highlighted that uniqueness is often an aspect of action research studies and therefore findings may only be cautiously generalised. Furthermore, due to the real-life nature of action research, although practical results are achieved, they are very often underreported in academic literature making the issue of generalisability of action research more challenging (Gray, 2018). Despite these challenges highlighted by Okaisu et al. (2014) the compilation of quantitative and qualitative approaches to data collection, the collaborative nature and the cyclical nature of action research facilitated achieving the aim of the study. The researchers reported that examining nursing documentation provided a catalyst for change within their hospital, which not only resulted in an improvement of documentation but also an improvement in organisational culture (Okaisu et al., 2014).

Vafeai et al. (2018a) also conducted an action research study to improve the nursing care documentation in an Iranian emergency department. Phase one of the research cycle involved undertaking a review of the existing nursing case note documentation and interviewing nursing staff (Vafeai et al., 2018a). Phase two involved education of nursing staff on documentation, with phase three involving continual review of documentation, a further documentation workshop and rewarding nursing staff for excellent documentation (Vafeai et al., 2018a).

Following phase one review of 200 case notes, major issues were highlighted with the quality of nursing documentation (Vafeai et al., 2018a). The main primary theme to arise from the qualitative data from interviews (n=17 nurses; n=3 senior nurses) was the need for effective and specific education and training surrounding nursing documentation. These findings concurred with the nursing documentation outcomes

previously identified by Okaisu et al. (2014). Secondary themes included 'job burnout' (due to workload and staff shortage) and 'problems identified in the health information systems' (affecting time management to complete documentation). Senior staff also indicated that there was no regular review of documentation for quality assurance purposes (Vafeai et al., 2018a).

Phase two of the action research involved nurses undertaking virtual training on documentation standards followed up by a written test three weeks later. Furthermore, a two-day workshop was provided on documentation. Review of the documentation post workshop of the documentation revealed improvement from 42% to 57% (Vafeai et al., 2018a). The final cycle in phase three involved introducing continual review of documentation by allocated members of staff within the department and a further documentation workshop. In addition, points were allocated for accurate documentation, which contributed to the nurses' annual review process. New versions of patient education forms were also created and implemented and the quality score of documentation increased to 73%, an improvement of 30% (Vafeai et al., 2018a). Similar to Okaisu et al. (2014), a multi-faceted approach was required to ensure that positive change happened (McNiff and Whitehead, 2011).

In a pre and post-test study involving Iranian student nurses, Almasi et al. (2019) investigated the impact of implementing education and training on students' documentation skills (n=28). A problem-based approach to education and training on documentation was provided with students completing two reports on a patient before and two follow up reports on the same patient after training. Following evaluation, the researchers concluded that student nurses were prioritising care over documentation, with little regard to legal implications of failure to document. This emulates the findings from Boucher et al, (2012). Almasi et al. (2019) developed a problem-based approach to teaching student nurses was effective in improving student nurse's documentation on report writing and may have implications for clinical practice. The researchers recommended that specific training about report writing should be embedded into the curriculum. Furthermore, teaching a problem-based approach could be a useful learning and teaching strategy to improve nursing documentation (Almasi et al., 2019).

Two action research studies by Okaisu et al. (2014) and Vafeai et al. (2018a) in Iran demonstrated positive change surrounding documentation. They proved that action

research is a useful methodology to use when a change is required. It is also particularly useful in healthcare settings, as health care practitioners are used to the cyclical nature of service evaluation and reflection (McNiff and Whitehead, 2011). Almasi et al. (2019) demonstrated that a problem-based approach to teaching students impacted positively on their ability to report writing and this approach could be applied to qualified nurses.

2.7 Background to Documentation Tools

In studies reviewing the quality of nursing and midwifery documentation, it is essential to examine the assessment tools used for this purpose. Numerous studies from across the globe have examined the specific documentation review tools (Müller-Staub 2009; Johnson, Jefferies, and Langdon, 2010; Broderick and Coffey, 2012; Asamani et al., 2014; Neary, 2014; Ritchie et al., 2014; Tucker and Fox, 2014; Wang et al., 2014; Crawford-Williams et al., 2015; Ay and Polat, 2016; Almasi et al., 2019).

A significant systematic review of the quality of nursing documentation from 2000 - 2010 was conducted by Wang, Hailey, and Yu (2011) who identified four tools commonly used within nursing documentation studies during that time. Tools included were Ehnfors and Smedby's Comprehensiveness in Recording Instrument (1993) the Cat-ch-Ing instrument (2000), the Q-DIO instrument (2007) and a protocol for pressure ulcers. The tools measured the three main parts of nursing documentation; the structure (easy to follow), the process (reliable enough to provide detailed patient care) and the content (explicit record of the care provided) (Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011).

Validation of the tools was variable. Only the Q-DIO instrument appeared to have survived into the next decade and the only one examined in depth within this current study. The reviewers stated that 70% of the seventy-seven studies examined provided evidence of some psychometric testing. Content validity was established in nine studies where only three studies provided evidence of face validity and evidence of construct validity provided in three further studies. Inter rater consistency through Cronbach's Alpha (above 0.70) was evidenced in ten studies and a further forty studies reported inter rater reliability with five studies ranging from fair to very good. Only two studies highlighted usability, one involving nurses and another with parents, clinicians, and volunteers (Wang, Hailey and Yu, 2011).

All the studies reviewed by Wang, Hailey, and Yu (2011) used local standards to evaluate local practice. The reviewers concluded that it might not be practical to seek a universal instrument due to the complex and diverse nature of healthcare provision. However, the reviewers emphasised that accuracy, appropriateness, and comprehensiveness of documentation is fundamental to evidence care provided. Furthermore, review systems need to be embedded in practice to identify underlying factors which negatively or positively impact on the effectiveness and quality of nursing documentation. Wang, Hailey, and Yu (2011) recommended the need to evaluate the quality of any instrument from the following perspectives: conceptual (consensus required of documentation standards); theoretical (instrument is appropriate for discipline it is testing); technical (ensuring instruments are valid and reliable) and applicable (to the discipline being examined). The review concluded with the need for further research, a more consistent application of documentation standards and terminology and continual monitoring of documentation to ensure it mirrors clinical practice is crucial to improve the quality of care. Further education and organisation support surrounding documentation of the nursing process was advocated (Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011).

Within the literature, the researcher found a variety of review tools utilised to examine the quality of nursing and midwifery documentation which are described in the following Sections 2.6.1- 2.6.4.

2.7.1 Review tools to assess specific clinical criteria

Within the research literature, some tools examined specific clinical criteria such as:

- Documentation review of the handover of care (Record Evidence Enquire Discuss (REED) tool) (Tucker and Fox, 2014).
- Documentation evaluation of partner abuse (Ritchie, 2014).
- Documentation review of health education on alcohol consumption in pregnancy (Crawford-Williams et al., 2015).

In the UK, Tucker and Fox (2014) conducted a pilot evaluation on the REED model of handover, which was introduced to improve communication, more specifically documentation between nurses. The REED model involved communicating handovers completely through written documentation rather than traditional oral reports. To

assess whether this had been successful, the research team undertook a comparative review of 43 patients' case notes: 23 case notes using the REED method of handover and 20 from another ward not using this method. Four researchers reviewed the notes using a tool based on the NMC record keeping guidance (NMC, 2009) and the hospital's documentation policy. Five broad questions were asked of each patient case note pertaining to patient assessment, care planning and discharge process. Results revealed that both wards achieved a high level of documented patient assessment with the ward using the REED method of handover attaining a higher standard of documentation of care. Tucker and Fox (2014) suggested further testing was required to prove that documentation improved by this written handover method. A key finding from staff reading the handovers demonstrated that overall record keeping improved. This method ensured that everyone who read the documentation was fully informed which improved accountability, as nurses and midwives processed and acted on written documentation (NMC, 2018). Recommendations included the need for nurses and midwives to be educated in effective record keeping and have regular record keeping reviews to ensure that improvements were maintained (Tucker and Fox, 2014). These recommendations were validated in later studies (Wang et al., 2014; Kamil, Rachmah and Wardani, 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018a) with improvements in documentation not being attributed to the Hawthorne effect (Grove, Gray and Burns, 2015).

A later small exploratory study was conducted in New Zealand by Ritchie et al. (2014) to develop a tool to evaluate documentation of partner abuse. A five-step quality improvement approach was utilised to develop the tool:

- i. Literature review.
- ii. Gain expert opinion to select criteria.
- iii. Piloting of the tool.
- iv. Achieving interrater reliability.
- v. Using the tool in clinical practice.

Following the preparatory stages of the literature review and gaining expert opinion on the criteria, the pilot test involved two researchers assessing the same anonymised nine patient records using the draft tool. The tool was further modified and retested using a fresh set of anonymised records, which was subsequently repeated for a third

time to test reliability. According to Ritchie et al. (2014) Kappa Coefficient interpretation of the results indicated that good inter-rater reliability achieved although this index information was not provided. Transparency of results is required to confirm reliability of the study (Gray, 2018). Ritchie et al. (2014) suggested that without standardisation of documentation, high inter rater reliability is difficult to achieve due to the complexity of clinical situations. However, the researchers highlighted this should not be a barrier to developing and utilising structured tools to review nursing documentation (Ritchie et al., 2014). Limitation of the tool included the small sample of participants and limited testing of the tool at the piloting stage with only two raters reviewing the anonymised patient records. Furthermore, lack of key information about the testing of the tool affects the validity and reliability of the tool and therefore the quality of the overall study (Wang et al., 2014; Polit and Beck, 2018).

An Australian study was conducted by Crawford-Williams et al. (2015) to review health education documentation on alcohol consumption in pregnancy. The researchers utilised a modified version of the 'DISCERN' tool created by Charnock et al. (1999), a validated tool used to assess health promotional material. This tool was used to examine 14 aspects of health promotion publications used by midwives in routine antenatal discussions. The sections of the tool included assessing reliability, quality, and the overall rating of each publication. Findings revealed that 28% of the health promotion publications were of poor quality with none of the publications deemed high quality (n=32). Thematic analysis of the publications revealed that key health promotion messages were not clear, and the tone used in the publications negative. Crawford-Williams et al. (2015) recommended that all health promotion publications should be clear, simple, and accurate. Limitations included literature search was limited to English; exclusion of electronic publications such as applications and no evidence of inter rater reliability provided. The researchers stipulated that they slightly modified four questions within the tool however, no evidence of validation of the updated tool was provided (Crawford-Williams et al., 2015). Again, this lack of transparency of detail affects the reliability of the study (Gray, 2018).

2.7.2 Discipline Specific Tools

Many documentation review tools have assessed the quality of nursing and midwifery documentation in general terms. These include Q-DIO tool created by Müller-Staub

(2009) (discussed later in Section 2.6.4) and NMCAT (Johnson, Jefferies, and Langdon, 2010). However, the following review tools for nursing documentation were designed as discipline specific: Emergency Nurse Practitioners (ENP) by Neary (2014) and the Quality of Australian Nursing Documentation in Aged Care (QANDAC) by Wang et al. (2014).

Neary (2014) undertook a small research study to assess any link between the quality of written documentation and education amongst ENPs. The researcher used a pre - and post-test collection of the data, from attendance in a course including documentation, using a modified interrupted time series design. A group of experienced ENPs developed a tool based on national and local policies to review documentation incorporating a biomedical model. The researcher validated the tool through piloting using ten participants (ENPs), randomly selected from emergency units from a single Trust in England. The tool contained eight sections, six of which focused on the detailed examination of the patient, one on demographics and one section where the researcher made a judgement on the overall assessment of the patient (Neary, 2014). A comparison was made between the participants overall assessment to determine if the researcher agreed with participants conclusion, i.e., the Bolitho test (Segen, 2012). Red, Amber, Green (RAG) categories of assessment were awarded. Neary (2014) concluded that less than 46% scored within the red category (low quality), 46% - 79% within amber (average quality) and the score for the green category (high quality) was 79% for the quality of the ENP documentation. Post course, an improvement was noted in the ENP documentation in only some details relating to the physical assessments whilst others either remained the same or declined. Interestingly, in the mandatory demographic sections, seven participants scored green pre-course and only five post-course, however, the overall assessment had improved, with a 100% match with researcher and participants after attending the course (Neary, 2014). Neary (2014) acknowledged that this was a small-scale study and therefore expanding the study would be required to provide more meaningful data. The researcher did however highlight that the managers needed to heed the findings of the study with more emphasis on documentation required within clinical areas and should feature strongly within future education and training programmes.

Wang et al. (2014) provided the most comprehensive account of construction of an instrument to review nursing documentation. They undertook a study to develop a tool to evaluate paper based and electronic resident records within aged care home settings in Australia, the Quality of Australian Nursing Documentation in Aged Care (QANDAC) instrument. According to the researchers, this was the first instrument of its kind. The four phases of the instrument's development were: (1) Defining quality of documentation. (2) Extraction of these quality indicators. (3) Developing means of collecting the data and then (4) Testing the instrument.

As the nursing process was used in the care homes this formed the basis of the tool with scoring of the quality of the documentation using a Likert scale. Using this scale was appropriate, as attitudes to statements were required (Kale, 2015). Wang et al. (2014) provided detailed information on the process to validate the review tool. Appropriate validation of the instrument is necessary to enhance the reliability of research (Polit and Beck, 2018). Wang et al. (2014) achieved face validity through focus groups, telephone, and face-to-face discussions with senior experts in nursing. Content validity was confirmed through the consensus of five panel members. Through this process, the number of questions on the instrument were reduced from 55 to 34 (Wang et al., 2014).

Pilot testing of the instrument was conducted to achieve inter rater reliability (Polit and Beck, 2020). Three raters independently scored a convenience sample of 20 patient records. Interestingly, despite Fleiss's kappa being an objective measurement for assessment of the agreement between raters (Grove and Ciper, 2017) this was deemed unsuitable to use by Wang et al. (2014). Instead, they agreed that a percentage above 80% was appropriate to indicate reliability. Ten questions achieved 100% agreement, 17 questions achieved over 90% agreement between raters, and the remaining seven questions achieved between 81 - 89%. Wang et al. (2014) suggested a degree of subjectivity always exists in reviewing records. Certainly, inter rater agreement can be challenging when assessing subjective matter (Polit and Beck, 2020). Limitations cited by the researchers included acknowledging the small sample which meant that construct validity and internal consistency could not be achieved (Polit and Beck, 2020). Recommendations included further research studies were required in a wider range of settings and with a larger sample size. Although the

QANDAC tool targeted aged care documentation, Wang et al. (2014) highlighted the QANDAC tool could be used for the purpose of quality improvement of documentation for other nursing disciplines.

In the largest contemporary study examining the quality of nursing documentation by Norouzi et al. (2018), the compiled a data extraction tool to examine the quality of four documentation records from 98 nurses. Limited details of the construction and validity of the tool were provided. The researchers did not specify which documentation standards were included in the formulation of the tool. A group of experts agreed face validity which was the only aspect of validation included. Reliability was achieved with the documentation tool scoring 0.9 on Cronbach's coefficient (Polit and Beck, 2020).

2.7.3 Tools incorporating professional standards

Many documentation tools examined, incorporated professional standards (Müller-Staub, 2009; Neary, 2014; Tucker, and Fox, 2014; Wang et al., 2014; Asamani et al., 2014). However, the tool created by Broderick and Coffey (2012) was based on the Person-Centred Nursing Framework (McCormack and McCance, 2006). This framework focuses on nurses working with patients through engagement, 'shared decision making, working with patients' beliefs, having a sympathetic presence', and providing holistic physical care. Other researchers developed their own documentation assessment tools using their own criteria from their independent literature review (Johnson, Jefferies, and Langdon, 2010; Ritchie et al., 2014; Ay and Polat, 2016; Almasi et al., 2019). No tools were found that contained the NMC professional standards for nurses and midwives (NMC, 2015; 2018).

2.7.4 Quality of Nursing Diagnoses, Interventions and Outcomes (Q-DIO) instrument

The most widely tested instrument found was the Q-Dio instrument developed by Müller-Staub (2009) to measure the quality of documentation relating to the nursing process. The Nursing Interventions Classification and Nursing Outcomes (NANDA) classification formed the basis of its development. Key components of the tool assessed nursing diagnosis, nursing interventions and patient sensitive outcomes. Twenty-nine items were identified with scoring involving a Likert score of three or five points. Eight expert nurses confirmed consensus modelling using questionnaires and

focus groups content and face validity. The experts captured the most important aspects of documentation of clinical care to be measured (reaching 100% consensus). A pilot study conducted with two raters scored 60 nursing documentation records. Internal consistency produced a Cronbach's alpha of 0.83 for nursing diagnosis, 0.90 for nursing interventions and 0.99 for patient sensitive outcomes. Grove and Ciper (2017) highlighted that it is beneficial to give an overall Cronbach alpha score to assess internal consistency. Inter rater and inter rater reliability achieved with a kappa of 0.95. Müller-Staub (2009) concluded that the Q-Dio was a valid instrument and recommended further quantitative research to expand the testing of the tool in different settings. Thereafter the tool was tested in Switzerland, Brazil, Nigeria, Portugal, and the USA (Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011; Lynch, 2012; Lynch et al., 2015; Šerková and Marečková, 2018). In 2012, the Q-Dio was adapted into Brazilian Portuguese with some modifications including language as well as cultural changes. The Likert scale was adapted to use only three points (present, partial, absent) and was pilot tested by Lynch et al. (2012) using a sample of 40 nursing case notes (20 electronic with NANDA-I terminology and 20 paper based without terminology). Results were consistent with Müller-Staub's (2009) findings, suggesting a high level of reliability of the tool. In 2015, this version of Q-Dio was further tested when it was used to assess 180 records from two centres in Brazil (n=120) and one centre in the USA (n=60). Results revealed stability and internal consistency of the instrument, therefore good reliability was achieved (Lynch et al., 2015). The researchers proposed that the instrument could be used to assess the nursing process whether it be paper or electronic records (Müller-Staub, 2009).

Šerková and Marečková, (2018) independently assessed the Q-DIO and identified issues of disparity with terminology within the tool. Subsequently highlighting that assessment terms should be agreed if different raters were used. They also suggest that further testing of the Q-Dio would be required with more focused qualitative research to include the views of staff and raters on the tool.

As demonstrated, there is a wide range of nursing documentation tools. However, no tool was found to specifically examine midwifery documentation. Although some tools were based around guidelines and professional standards none incorporated

professional standards (NMC, 2015; NMC, 2018), the regulator for nursing and midwifery in the UK.

2.8 Paper versus electronic records

An important innovation in the history of clinical documentation was the introduction of electronic recording of health care data. Student nurses, student midwives, nurses, and midwives' experiences of using Electronic Healthcare Recording Systems (EHRS) are now reviewed and discussed in the next section.

Two influential UK studies examined student nurse and student midwives' experiences of using EHRS (Brooke-Read et al., 2012; Baillie et al., 2013). Brooke-Read et al. (2012) conducted a mixed methods study to investigate midwifery students' experience of using (EHRS). Twenty-eight student midwives completed a questionnaire and six student midwives (four pre-registration and two post-registration) participated in a focus group to obtain subjective experiences of EHRS. Of the n=28 student midwife respondents to the questionnaire, 24 had previous experience of working with electronic records. However, the EHRS were not used for clinical documentation purposes, which was a key limitation to the study. Access and input were limited and mainly confined to entering admission or discharge demographic details and accessing laboratory results.

Conversely, a later mixed methods study by Baillie et al. (2013) highlighted that students could not access blood results electronically. Findings from the survey responses n=215 (61%) and three separate focus groups for mental health (n=6), adult (n= 5) and midwifery (n=6) revealed variable student exposure to using electronic records in clinical practice and students' frustration of not being able to access some records systems. Reported benefits of EHRs included improved quality of the recordkeeping as it was always legible and made transfer of information easier especially referral processes (Baillie et al., 2013).

Both above UK studies featured professional accountability, with students raising concerns that mentors found it was difficult to review and endorse student documentation entries due to layout and ability of retrieving information from the EHRS (Brooke-Read et al., 2012; Baillie et al., 2013). Interestingly, students reported that

staff perceived using EHRS was linked less to individual accountability, as handwritten documentation was easier to link to an individual compared to electronic entries (Brooke-Read et al., 2012; Baillie et al., 2013). Students were particularly concerned with security surrounding access to EHRS with the potential for other people logging in and altering or deleting previous documented entries (Brooke-Read et al., 2012; Baillie et al., 2013).

Midwifery students perceived that using EHRS were in direct contrast to promoting the normality of childbirth and deemed it more medicalised by adding more electronic devices to the birthing environment (Brooke-Read et al., 2012). Students also reported that women were unable to access electronic case notes, and this could impact negatively on excluding them being involved in their own care. Worryingly, midwifery students highlighted that women were left unattended whilst students were inputting patient care into the computer leading to issues with keeping contemporaneous notes if the computer was located out of the room (Brooke-Read et al., 2012). Conversely, the midwifery students in Baillie et al. (2013) study did not raise concerns about women being unable to access their electronic notes or issues with leaving women unattended to complete electronic clinical documentation.

Students from both studies (Brooke-Read et al., 2012; Baillie et al., 2013) recommended that specific education, training, and guidance were required for students and clinical mentors on completing EHRS. The researchers emphasised that clinicians and nurse / midwife academics work together to ensure staff and students are adequately prepared for electronic or paper-based record-keeping (Brooke-Read et al., 2012; Baillie et al., 2013) with Brooke-Read et al. (2012) indicating that women should always be involved in related training and education. Limitations of both studies included convenience sampling and specifically the small sample sizes in Brooke-Read et al. (2012) study. Recommendations from Brooke-Read et al. (2012) and Baillie et al. (2013) studies indicated that further research was required into the use of EHRS and including students' views as well as those of trained staff.

Numerous studies have focussed on the experiences of qualified nurses and midwives using EHRS (Wang, Yu, and Hailey, 2013; Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015; Wang, Yu and Hailey, 2015; Ay and Polat, 2016; Markam et al., 2018; McCarthy et al., 2018; Ibrahim et al., 2019).

Wang, Yu, and Hailey (2013), researchers and clinicians, conducted a retrospective study to compare paper based (n=2299) versus electronic systems (n=6997) of nursing case note documentation in nine Australian care homes for the elderly. The structure, process and content of the nursing assessment documentation was evaluated by seven measures; quantity of documentation; completeness, timeously; comprehensiveness; specific care related documentation and if the forms were dated and signed. Results revealed a variety of different practices across the nine care homes (Wang, Yu, and Hailey, 2013). Electronic versions of the assessment forms were more detailed and entries more frequent than the paper versions. No difference was found in any other aspect of documentation between the two systems. Wang, Yu, and Hailey (2013) concluded that using Electronic Documentation Systems (EDS) could improve the quality of documentation in the aspects of quantity, comprehensiveness and signing and dating of assessment forms but more research was required surrounding quality of care using electronic systems. One limitation to the study was that the two samples were of different sizes which made it more difficult to compare results (Grove and Cipher, 2017). As the setting was in care homes within Australia the generalisability of the study to other disciplines and populations is questionable (Parahoo, 2014).

Two years later the quality of nursing documentation within EDSs were examined by Wang, Yu, and Hailey (2015) in a further study, using a convenience, retrospective sample of 111 paper-based and 194 electronic care plans obtained from seven care homes in 2011. The quality of documentation measured using an abbreviated version of the QANDAC instrument (Wang et al., 2014). Wang et al. (2014) acknowledged that electronic notes provided more detailed information about evaluation of care (48.30 vs. 47.34 out of 60, $p < 0.01$). Wang, Yu, and Hailey (2015) concluded that this might be due to prompts within the electronic systems. However, the electronic system had an overall lower score for quality. Fewer problem or diagnosis statements and contributing factors recorded in the electronic care plans compared to the handwritten plans ($p < 0.01$). Both electronic and handwritten care plans scored poorly regarding recording patient outcomes. Wang, Yu, and Hailey (2014) established that the introduction of EDS does not necessarily improve the quality of case note documentation. They also recommended more qualitative studies to be carried out to

capture the nurses' views on standardising terminology and documentation recording systems.

Strudwick and Eyasu (2015) conducted a literature review to examine Electronic Health Records (EHR) used by mental health nurses. The review included seven studies that were international across Europe and the USA. The reviewers reported that researchers used different instruments to measure these experiences across all studies. Quantitative and qualitative approaches were utilised to collect the data. Overall, results from the review revealed that mental health nurses reported positive experiences in using EHR, including improved access to patient information. In addition, multiple professionals were able to access information at the same time highlighting that this improved the quality of care for the patient especially in complex cases. Further benefits reported by the participants included standardisation of care planning through computerised algorithms with EHRs being easier to read. One study from the review reported that administrators, men, and newly qualified staff were more acceptable to using EHR (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015).

Challenges with EHR were also highlighted, participants indicated that the standardised design of EHR meant that care planning was limited (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015). In one study, EHRs focused on physical aspects of care rather than mental health issues with a further two studies commenting on the extent of duplication of information. Several studies highlighted the concern raised by nurses around patient confidentiality within EHR systems especially with multiple people able to access patient records. Paper case notes were reported to be easily trackable with patient information more readily kept confidential and secure. The EHR system was reported to be non-user friendly in one study whilst other studies also purported difficulty with accessing computers and lack of physical space for computers an issue (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015).

Strudwick and Eyasu (2015) produced several recommendations from their literature review. Clear communication and training of health care staff was required before, during and after implementation of EHRs. In particular, they highlighted that support systems should be immediately available to staff for trouble shooting including 'super users'. Producing an algorithm for staff would be useful to reveal how the introduction of EHR would influence their workload and development and selection of EHRs must

include disciplines using the system. Local adaptations to care planning should be included in the EHR package. Furthermore, it is essential that training is provided to health care staff to inform them of the importance of keeping information private and confidential whilst using EHR (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015).

In another systematic literature review, McCarthy et al. (2018) reviewed the effects and impacts of introducing EDS on improving quality of nursing care and patient safety in hospital settings. The review consisted of only six international studies including three from America and one each from Switzerland, Taiwan, and Canada. The studies all included pre and post intervention data, with most of the outcomes relating to the structure, content, and practice of case note documentation. All studies reported that introduction of EDS reduced documentation errors and saved time to complete thus allowing more time for patient care. Interestingly, some studies also reported a reduction on infection rates due to improved documentation of care. McCarthy et al. (2018) concluded that careful implementing of EDS could be a good investment in terms of time management therefore freeing up nursing staff to provide more clinical care.

Ay and Polat (2016) conducted a study in Istanbul to investigate nurse's opinions and beliefs in using Electronic Recording Systems (ERS). Data collected using a 28-item tool created by the researchers named USERSNurse. The survey revealed use of ERS in relation to decreased paperwork, nurses' perceived improvement in service quality, improved access to Information, standardisation of procedures (Cronbach's alpha internal consistency of 0.95), faster access to information and facilitating research (Cronbach's alpha internal consistency of 0.93) and less time for recording information (Cronbach's alpha internal consistency of 0.94). Statistical evidence was provided to support the findings which improved overall reliability (Grove and CIPHER, 2017). Ay and Polat (2016) suggested wider testing of nurses' beliefs and opinions using USERSNurse.

In Indonesia, documentation needs for the integrated antenatal care (ANC) programme suggested there was a need for electronic systems to be adopted. To address the gaps in existing paper case note documentation practices, Markam et al. (2018) conducted a study to understand documentation challenges, quantify midwives' documentation completeness in primary health care, develop a tool, and assess

intention to use the tool. The researchers analysed existing ANC records and conducted in-depth interviews with stakeholders (n=7) to understand needs for an electronic system in support of ANC. From analysis of the qualitative data, Markam et al. (2018) highlighted the stakeholders reported the paper systems to be repetitive, time consuming, easy to make mistakes and cumbersome to produce reports from for data collection and referral processes. These findings replicated previous research carried out on paper-based documentation (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015). Stakeholders also identified key requirements that should be included in the electronic-Ante-Natal Care (e-iANC) tool, these included demographics, history, physical examination and recordings, ongoing assessment, follow up and parent education.

Following development of the e-iANC 100 midwives across five regions were trained on its use. Post attendance all midwives completed the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) questionnaire (Venkatesh, Thong and Xu, 2016) to examine their willingness to utilise the new e-iANC (Markam et al., 2018). Results revealed the major factors influencing midwives to use the electronic system were practical ones, such as adequate internet access, effective training on a system and user friendly (Markam et al., 2018). These findings were supported by Juwita et al. (2019) who conducted a small study within a hospital in Indonesia to compare paper based versus electronic recordings of partographs used to document intrapartum care. Fifteen paper-based case note records were compared against fifteen electronic versions. The researchers concluded that electronic documentation was quicker to input data, easier to complete and more secure than paper versions. Contrary to Strudwick and Eyasu (2015), Markam et al. (2018) found that education level, computer literacy or age did not influence the willingness to adopt the system. The midwives accepted and understood the importance of adopting an electronic system (Markam et al., 2018). Future plans included accessibility of electronic systems to mobile devices which service users could access (Markam et al., 2018). The use of mobile devices to access EHRs would address the concerns raised by the students within the study by Brooke-Read et al. (2012).

In a similar cross-sectional quantitative study in Canada, Ibrahim et al. (2019) examined factors influencing nurses' intention in using electronic documentation systems (EDS). The online survey was completed by nurses (n=217) in care home

settings in Ontario, Of the respondents, 94% were female, 59% were educated to degree level and the average age was 47 years. Results revealed 86% of nurses used EDS in their practice setting, 77% using EDS daily with 62% reported feeling comfortable using EDS. Individual characteristics (age, education) did not influence the use of EDS (Ibrahim et al., 2019) which supports findings of earlier studies (Markam et al., 2018). However, contrary to Markam et al. (2019), Ibrahim et al. (2019) found previous technology experience had a moderate influence on nurses' intention to use EDS. As identified in earlier studies (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015; Ay and Polat, 2016; Markam et al., 2018), Ibrahim et al. (2019), the researchers identified nurses had a positive attitude to EDS and felt that it would benefit their everyday practice by saving time, even improving patient care. Interestingly, the nurses from this study thought that using EDS would improve confidentiality (Ibrahim et al., 2019). Confidentiality within EDS had been raised as a concern in earlier studies (Brooke-Read et al., 2012; Baillie et al., 2013). Ibrahim et al. (2019) recommended that EDS developers work with clinicians to get an understanding of the role before designing new systems. They recommended extensive piloting by nurses was required, with education and leadership during implementation. Furthermore, they identified the need for qualitative studies to capture nurses' views required (Ibrahim et al., 2019).

Within the section, studies examining the introduction to electronic documentation systems (EDS) compared to paper record keeping were examined. Studies conducted prior to the implementation of EDS found nurses and midwives had a positive attitude towards the introduction of EDS. Nurses and midwives reported that it would benefit their everyday practice, improve the quality of documentation they produced and reduce time taken for documentation allowing them more time for direct patient care. (Markam et al., 2018; McCarthy et al., 2018; Ibrahim et al., 2019). Key stakeholders found the paper systems repetitive, time consuming, easy to make mistakes and cumbersome (Markam et al., 2018). In the study conducted by Ibrahim et al. (2019), nurses reported that EDS would improve confidentiality. In direct contrast to this finding, student midwives who were currently using EDS were concerned with the security of the systems (Brooke-Read et al., 2012; Baillie et al., 2013). Education and training are required regarding keeping information private and confidential whilst using EHR (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015).

Documentation was easier to read in EDS, more comprehensive and improved the compliance of completion of fundamental details (Wang, Yu and Hailey, 2013); Ay and Polat, 2016; Juwita et al., 2019). EDS improved multi-professional access to patient Information, improved care planning and therefore improved care (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015). Conversely, Wang, Yu, and Hailey (2014) reported that EDS did not necessarily improve the quality of documentation due to set algorithms and text. In addition, midwifery students felt that the lack of patient access was a concern using EHRs as this was in direct contrast to promoting normality in childbirth (Brooke-Read et al., 2012). However, accessibility to mobile devices which service users could access would alleviate this problem (Markam et al., 2018).

Concern regarding lack of resources (such as computers) was cited (Wang, Yu and Hailey, 2014; Markam et al., 2018); Juwita et al., 2019) in addition to the lack of adequate education and training highlighted by some nurses and midwives (Wang, Yu and Hailey, 2014; Markam et al., 2018; Juwita et al., 2019). Development of EHRs must include disciplines using the system. Local adaptations to care planning should be included in any development of EDS (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015). Wang, Yu and Hailey (2014) also highlighted that support systems should be immediately available to staff for trouble shooting including 'super users'. Wang, Yu, and Hailey (2014) also recommended more qualitative studies to be carried out to capture the nurses' views on using EDS and standardising terminology within the systems. Table 2.2 provides a summary of the research on paper versus electronic records.

Table 2-2: Paper versus electronic records

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
Brooke-Read et al. (2012) UK	Investigate midwifery students experiences of EHRs	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism /interpretivism. Mixed methods Students and midwives	Questionnaire (28 completed) Focus group (n=6 total; 4 students, 2 midwives)	SPSSv19 for questionnaire data Qualitative data review	Questionnaire: indicated types of EHRs students had accessed and used. Qualitative data revealed: Benefits of EHRs - standardised Practical issues of EHRs used in birthing environment as this more medicalised than 'normality in childbirth Women left unattended when completing EHRs.	EHRs introduced e-devices into birth environment - direct contrast to promoting normality in childbirth. Information security issues raised	Limitation: EHRs not used for purpose of recording clinical care. Further research required
Baillie et al. (2013) UK	Investigate experiences of student nurses/ midwives' when learning to use EHRs i.e., improved quality of recordkeeping	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism and interpretivism approaches). Mixed methods (n=232)	Questionnaire survey (n=215; 61% response rate) Focus groups x 3 (n= 6,5,6)	Survey data - SPSS v19. Qualitative – transcribed and thematic analysis	Two themes: Training and preparation for using EHRs 2) Access to EHRs and involvement. Students reported inconsistent exposure, education/training, and access with EHR.	Clear EHR training guidelines required for students and mentors Information security issues raised.	Further research required

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
					Mentors concerned about students accessing EHR and endorsing their entries		
Wang, Yu and Hailey (2013) Australia	Describe nursing assessment documentation practices in aged care organisations and evaluate quality of electronic versus paper-based documentation	Quantitative (positivism) Retrospective audit - nursing documents Samples -2299 paper-based and 6997 electronic, from nine care homes	Seven criteria measured and compared quality attributes of: structure and format of nursing documentation In paper and electronic forms	SPSS (1.8 version) used to quantify the format and structure of nursing assessment documentation	electronic documentation could improve quality of documentation i.e., quantity, comprehensiveness, and sign /date assessment forms. Varying related practices identified.	Immediate availability of support systems to trouble-shoot including ‘super users’ EHR more comprehensive notes in all setting.	Further research required using E-Systems
Wang, Yu and Hailey (2015) Australia	Examine quality of paper-based versus e-nursing care plan care homes for elderly	Quantitative (positivism) Documentation audit study 1 PHD student, 1 research fellow, 1 senior lecturer	Review of 111 paper-based care plans and 194 e-care plans, conveniently selected	Statistical analysis. Quantity determined using QANDAC	Poor documentation in nursing care plans especially regarding patient outcomes.	Content in both paper and electronic comparable Concern - lack of resources (such as computers).	Quality of Further qualitative review is needed on nurse care plan

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
Ibrahim et al. (2019) Canada	Examine factors influencing nurses' intention of using EDS in home care practice	Quantitative (positivism). Cross-sectional design cross-sectional study quantitative study Nurses (n=217)	Online survey	Descriptive statistics and hierarchical linear regression	Effort expectancy and nurses' individual characteristics -do not have a direct influence on nurses' intention to use electronic documentation systems in home care practice.	Careful leadership required with introduction of EHRs. Previous technology experience had moderate influence on intention to use EDS.	
Markam et al. (2018) Indonesia	Explore midwives need and intention to adopt an E-Antenatal Care records 42 maternity records examined for accuracy	Mixed methods Interviews and questionnaire Senior midwives (n=7) Midwives (n=100)	In-depth interviews with senior midwives to assess needs for EHR Trained 100 midwives in e-i ANC then questionnaire	Statistical analyses by SPSS software	Inaccuracies found in documents Age, education level, and computer did not affect intention to use system.	Need for e-tool for ANC recording Lack of adequate education and training raised Concern - lack of resources (such as computers.)	
Ay and Polat (2016) Turkey	Investigate nurse's opinions and beliefs in using electronic recording systems (ERS Evaluate validity/ reliability)	Quantitative (positivism) 1 Midwife 1 Lecturer 601 nurses	USERNurse Questionnaire survey 28-item tool created by the researchers named USERNurse	Analyses conducted using SPSS 21.0 software	ERS – less time consuming Good for research Decreased paperwork Improved service quality Improved access to information.	USERNurse was a reliable tool	Proposed studies of USERNurse evaluation groups with different socio-demographics.

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
	of Usability Scale of the Electronic Records System in terms of Nursing Functions (USERSNurse)				Majority of respondents – were female, over 50% educated to degree level and averaged 47 years. Results revealed: 86% of nurses used ERS in their practice setting; 77% used daily and 62% felt very comfortable using ERS Individual characteristics (age, education) did not influence the use of ERS.		characteristics for implementation and investigation of validity and reliability.
Strudwick and Eyasu (2015) International studies - Europe, US and Canada	Conduct literature review to examine EHRs use by nurses in mental health clinical settings	Literature review 7 studies	Review	Critique	Mental health nurses reported positive experiences in using EHRs including improved access to patient information Facilitated multiple professionals accessing information and highlighted this improved quality of care for the patient especially in complex cases Challenges with EHR highlighted, participants	support systems should be immediately available to staff for trouble shooting including “super users” Specialist services such as mental health and midwifery need specific EHRs and need to be involved	Mental health setting is a unique environment Clear communication, education and training of healthcare staff was required before, during and after.

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
					indicated the standardised design of EHR meant that care planning was limited Confidentiality concerns raised Paper notes more trackable	in developing EHR systems Benefits reported included standardisation of care planning through computerised algorithms EHRs were easier to read One study reported that administrators, men and newly qualified staff were more acceptable to EHRs Varied responses on user friendly.	implementation of EHRs
Juwita et al. (2019) Indonesia	Develop a web-based partograph midwifery documentation database research system	Quantitative (positivism) Quasi-experimental comparative study	15 casenotes – traditional documentation 15 web-based documentation	Univariate statistics	Ease, speed, security, and relevance of data	Web based documentation more efficient than conventional documentation.	Small scale study

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
	Compare paper based versus e-recordings of partographs in intrapartum care					Concern raised - lack of resources (such as computers) Lack of adequate education and training highlighted.	
McCarthy et al. (2018)	Review evidence on effects/impact of electronic nursing documentation Focus on interventions to promote/improve quality care and/or patient safety in acute hospital settings	Institute of Technology Systematic review approach 6 international studies (Canada, USA, Taiwan, and Switzerland)	CINAHL MEDLINE EMBASE	Six studies: pre/post intervention studies reporting positive impacts on at least one or more outcomes and documentation of content	electronic nursing documentation saves time and reduces documentation errors. Evidence to suggest it also reduces falls and infections.		
Markam et al. (2018) Indonesia	Understand documentation challenges, quantify midwives'	Phase 1- qualitative Phase 2- education intervention	In-depth interviews with stakeholders n=7		Major influencing factors to use e-documentation: Practical factors e.g., adequate internet access.	Key functions to be included in electronic ANC (e-iANC) tool, i.e., demographics,	Recordings, ongoing assessment, follow-up and

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
	documentation completeness in primary healthcare, Develop a tool to assess intention to use the tool		100 midwives across five regions trained on the use		and effective training on a user-friendly system. Stakeholders found paper systems repetitive, time consuming, easy to make mistakes and cumbersome to produce reports for data collection and referral processes.	history, physical examination. Findings informed development of web-based Electronic Integrated ANC (e-iANC) system using the System Development Life Cycle method.	parent education

2.9 Learning strategies in practice

Due to the lack of midwifery specific literature available on learning strategies used in clinical practice, this search was expanded to include nurses / student nurses who also adhere to the same NMC Code (NMC, 2018). The main learning strategies adopted by nurses and midwives in clinical practice were found to be inter-professional learning, peer observation, reflection, situation and problem-based learning, self-directed learning.

2.9.1 *Inter-professional learning*

Worldwide, a range of disciplines including nursing and midwifery (Zeeni et al., 2016; Barton et al., 2018; Coleman, 2018; Stephens and Ormandy, 2018) use Inter-professional Learning (IPL). Zeeni et al. (2016) in Lebanon, explored undergraduate student attitudes towards IPL, conducting a longitudinal study using a series of questionnaires. In general, prior to undertaking learning all students felt ready to embrace IPL. However, there were notable gender and profession disparities where females displayed stronger professional identities. Nutrition and pharmacological students reported higher levels of teamwork and collaboration than other professions. Interestingly, lower scores of patient-centredness were identified in nursing students compared to other professions. Zeeni et al. (2016) concluded that this finding might be due to nurses being more reluctant than other professions to include patients in their decisions. After IPL all students highly evaluated this learning strategy, with a noticeable reduction in disparity between gender and professions.

In New Zealand, Coleman (2018) evaluated a multi-professional education programme including undergraduate students from medicine, pharmacy, nursing, and midwifery. Post programme, students self-reported improved teamwork and confidence surrounding management of patients' conditions. These findings were supported in a UK study conducted by Stephens and Ormandy (2018). In this study the researchers explored the impact of a six-week IPL programme with undergraduate students from five professions (nursing, radiography, physiotherapy, social work, and podiatry) (n=37). The programme-initiated cycles of care and explored self-assessment, team building, reflection and explored their

attitudes values and behaviours. Of the 37 students, 30 highlighted positive changes to values and attitudes and behaviours in clinical practice towards inter-professional working (Stephens and Ormandy, 2018).

IPL is effective for postgraduate and undergraduate students as demonstrated by Barton et al. (2018). In the USA, researchers carried out an IPL workshop using cadavers involving postgraduate students (n=81) from exercise, nursing, medicine, occupational health, physical therapy. Barton et al., (2018) reported that inter-professional collaboration was an effective way of learning, promoting a sense of community amongst disciplines. Participants highly valued inter-professional peer observation during the workshop, although IPL did not always take place face to face (Barton et al., 2018). Practice education facilitators identified similar findings when evaluating an IPL e-learning package they developed for undergraduate students' (n=100). Feedback from undergraduate students was mostly positive, highlighting the vital role IPL has on collaborative working, fostering teamwork and improving communication (O' Hara et al., 2018).

In summary, IPL is an effective learning strategy across a wide variety of disciplines, including in nursing and midwifery (Zeeni et al., 2016; Barton et al., 2018; Coleman, 2018; Stephens and Ormandy, 2018). It is equally beneficial at both postgraduate and undergraduate levels (Barton et al., 2018) with online resources found to be useful IPL tools (O'Hara et al., 2018). However, Davies, Fletcher, and Reeves (2016) in their literature review revealed a paucity of studies in the available literature surrounding IPL in maternity care and recommended multiple professions be involved in future studies within maternity care settings.

2.9.2 Peer observation

Peer observation was deemed to be a common method of learning in clinical practice and in Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). In Australia, Currey et al. (2015a) surveyed critical care nurses participating in a nursing speciality module where team-based learning had been introduced mid-course. In contrast to the findings by Barton et al. (2018), students did not report any increased satisfaction with peer observation / evaluation. However, they did report increased engagement and satisfaction with team-based learning compared with standard lectures. In HEIs within the UK, Davis, and Richardson (2017) introduced a peer

facilitation scheme to enable learners to be active participants in the learning process. Twelve second year student nurse volunteers were trained to be clinical skills facilitators to over 300 first year nursing students. Findings from the evaluation (n=190) positively indicated that peer facilitators were approachable, provided practical advice, instilled confidence and were professional and inspiring. Davis and Richardson (2017) concluded that peer facilitation could also be used to develop students teaching skills and recommended this approach should be adopted to encourage interdisciplinary learning. An earlier UK ethnographic study (n=15), Roberts (2008) also highlighted that student nurses learn from each other in clinical practice, forge friendships and pass on survival skills to enable them to learn how to be a nurse.

In an experimental study involving nursing students, Fertelli (2017) examined the effects of patient assessment of the nursing process through the Peer Assessment Method on critical thinking and peer support in a clinical setting. Students (n=68) were randomly allocated to either the experimental (Peer Assessment Method) or the control group (traditional method of assessing the nursing process). In the experimental group (n=34), each student was paired with a peer of their choice who then conducted their evaluation. Following assessment of a patient, the student shared findings of their patient assessment with their peer who evaluated the student in their performance. Each student carried out four care plans and provided feedback on four of their peer's care plans. Clear statistical evidence revealed that the Peer Assessment Method was more effective in developing critical thinking in patient assessments. Furthermore, peer assessment improved the peer support scores between the two student groups (Fertell, 2017). Similar findings were reported in a small phenomenological study by Wuryanto et al. (2017) who explored the introduction of a peer-learning model to student nurses in an intensive care unit in Indonesia. Eight nursing students and four clinical supervisors participated with two students paired with each supervisor. Students presented a collaborative case study to their supervisor on a weekly basis. Thematic analysis of qualitative data from focus groups revealed six themes including, improved supervision process, improved student clinical decision making, encouraging self-directed learning, encouraged collaborative learning, improved students understanding of terminology and improved documentation through use of the peer learning model.

Worldwide, students use peer learning in clinical practice. All undergraduate students highlighted the benefits of peer observation (Davis and Richardson, 2017; Roberts, 2008; Fertelli, 2017; Wuryanto et al., 2017), whilst postgraduate students highly evaluated peer observation (Barton et al., 2018). However, another study of postgraduate students found no benefit to peer observation or peer evaluation but appreciated that the team approach to learning facilitated the learning process (Currey et al., 2015). All studies involved small sample sizes so results cannot be generalised into the wider population (Polit and Beck, 2018). However, peer observation / evaluation should be considered as a possible learning strategy in clinical practice for nurses and midwives.

2.9.3 Reflection

According to Edwards (2017) reflective models tend to utilise a two-dimensional approach focussing on reflection of the action rather than reflection in action involving the full reflective cycle. Edwards (2017) provided an argument for supporting reflection to move from this two-dimensional approach to a four-dimensional process incorporating reflection before action and reflection beyond action in addition to reflection in action and reflection on action. Schön (1983) raised the status of nursing through reflection, moving professional nursing practice to a deep intellectual process. Schön (1983) indicated that practical wisdom and intelligence should be seen of equal value to theoretical knowledge. Therefore, Edwards (2017) argued that reflection before action is necessary, highlighting previous knowledge and experience help students develop strategies thus enriching their learning experience. According to Edwards (2017) reflection beyond action allows students to reflect deeply through telling their stories from clinical practice. This allows self-exploration encourages self-directed learning and fosters a lifelong learning attitude (Edwards (2017)).

As introduced in Chapter One (Section 1.5), theorists agreed that structured reflection is required to make sense of a practice-based experience (Dewey, 1938 cited in Mooney 2013; Carper, 1978; Johns, 1994). Johns (1995) used Carper's ways of knowing in his model of reflection and concluded that the most important knowledge gained, is through reflection as it will inform future practice (Johns, 1995). The NMC use reflection in their revalidation process (NMC, 2018). As part

of the revalidation process, every three years each practitioner submits five reflective accounts, on practical experiences, practice-related feedback or from continuous professional development (NMC, 2021). Therefore, it makes sense to learn and reflect on documentation, as it is an integral part of nursing (and midwifery) care (Boud, 2010).

In the UK, Adamson, and Dewar (2015) asked student nurses to explore compassionate care through reflection on listening to Podcasts of patient stories. Thirty-three of 37 students enrolled on a compassionate care module listened to the Podcasts of the patient stories, whilst only 16 contributed to the on-line discussions. However, according to Gray (2018) a 50 - 60% response rate would be considered as an acceptable response. Findings revealed that reflective learning through use of patient stories can help students explore their own values as well as influence how they will deliver compassionate person-centred care in the future (Adamson and Dewar, 2015).

Similar to the study by Adamson and Dewar (2015), Naicker and van Rensburg (2018) explored educators using reflective practice with student nurses. Findings from the 52% response rate (n=121) revealed that 98% of educators reported using reflective practice with students and identified that this learning and teaching mechanism was effective in developing problem-solving skills. However, only 46% of educators reported that reflective practice was included in their own training with only 37% of them using reflective practice in their professional role. According to Naicker and van Rensburg (2018) educators need to be fully trained in reflective practices and be encouraged to use reflection themselves to ensure students receive an authentic learning experience.

Reflection is also utilised by other students in a variety of settings including within classroom and laboratory settings. Similarly, findings of Naicker and van Rensburg (2018) and Fitriani et al., (2020) also reported that reflection is an effective approach to develop problem solving skills in biology students.

Reflection also appears to transcend the journey from student to midwife as identified by Embo et al. (2015) who conducted a small-scale cross-sectional retrospective longitudinal correlation cohort study in Belgium. Included in the retrospective sample were n=95 midwives who had graduated in the previous two

years. The longitudinal arm of the study involved n=169 student midwives (69 from first year, 50 second years and 50 third years). Overall, statistical analysis showed a moderate correlation between ability to reflect and on clinical performance ($p<0.01$). Cross-sectional analysis showed a high correlation between clinical performance and reflection in year 2 and year 3 students. Early reflective ability scores also correlated with later clinical performance scores. Embo et al. (2014) concluded that the ability to reflect links to clinical performance and is an important component of professional competence. Furthermore, the importance of written reflections as an assessment / learning tool to improve clinical practice is highlighted. However, reflection is not the only method of assessing clinical competency. The small scale of the study was a limitation. Brace, Kemp and Snelgar (2012) indicate that at least 100 subjects should be included for cohort studies.

In Nigeria, Enuke and Evawoma-Enuke (2015) discussed the challenges where students did not have a mentor / supervisor to discuss reflective practice and reflection was not embedded into the curriculum. They concluded that reflection could serve as a benchmark to measure and observe other professionals in clinical practice. This includes improving problem solving and decision-making skills and would be beneficial to be included as a learning and teaching strategy in curriculum delivery.

As a learning strategy, reflection is clearly a useful approach for students and qualified staff to adopt in their everyday practice (Embo et al., 2014; Adamson and Dewar, 2015; Enuke and Evawoma-Enuke, 2015; Naicker and van Rensburg, 2018) and as an essential component of a lifelong learning strategy for educationalists, students, and clinicians (Naicker and van Rensburg, 2018). Enuke and Evawoma-Enuke (2015) state that reflection should be used as a benchmark to observe professional practice. Furthermore, Embo et al. (2014) reported that the quality of written reflections can be demonstrated as an indicator for future clinical competence (Embo et al., 2014).

2.9.4 Situational / Problem Based Learning

Using a problem-based approach to learning is one strategy used to put learning into context. MacVane et al. (2015) introduced Problem Based Learning (PBL) into a pre-registration midwifery programme (UK) to embed the six C's model of clinical care (i.e., Commitment, Courage, Care, Compassion, Competence, Communication). They concluded that using PBL helped students acquire the necessary skills to be an effective, empathetic practitioner and to develop communication, facilitation, and leadership skills in preparation for clinical practice. PBL also encouraged a caring and compassionate attitude within students through listening to women's stories and utilising a holistic approach to solve problems whilst keeping the woman at the centre of care (MacVane et al., 2015).

Another learning approach for students should involve encouraging the learning of theory and practice within the clinical setting. Within the UK, Tweedie, Yerrell and Crozier (2019) evaluated a collaborative coaching and learning model into midwifery clinical placements. The researchers found that coaching increased student participation in their learning as it was student led and focussed on learning outcomes and problem solving. It also empowered students through peer support and encouraged them to appreciate other roles within the clinical areas. Similar findings were reiterated in an Australian survey by Van de Mortel et al. (2020) examining the effectiveness of clinical education facilitators in clinical practice. One hundred and thirty-four students responded to the survey (low response rate of 13.5%) and rated the facilitators as being highly effective in their role in supporting students. However, issues about blurring of roles and responsibilities were identified (Van de Mortel et al., 2020).

Examining learning of qualified nurses, Pool et al. (2015) conducted a study to explore Continuous Professional Development (CPD) strategies amongst younger, middle aged and older nurses (n=21) in the Netherlands. Nurses across all age groups highlighted that keeping up to date with developments pertinent to their clinical area was a catalyst for their learning. Additionally, it was interesting to note that performing new roles triggered the individual's willingness to learn. Learning and development needs tended to vary across the age continuum, with

younger nurses interested in gaining experience and career progression. Middle-aged nurses were reported to be more interested in work-life balance and variety of work. Whereas older nurses were most interested in learning on a smaller scale especially related to their work environment (Pool et al.,2015).

Similar findings were reported by Moafimadani et al. (2020), who conducted a qualitative study in Iran to identify variables about how nurses learn in clinical practice. Fifteen nurses were recruited using a purposive sampling technique. The main themes identified from the qualitative data were related to individual and organisational factors. Factors that influenced individual learning were nurses having a genuine interest in their ward and clinical environment. In addition, the individual nurse took responsibility for their own learning in response to their patient's clinical picture and subscribed to lifelong learning. Other factors that influenced learning was the culture of learning within the organisation. Issues, which affected learning from an organisational point of view, were workload and lack of staff (Moafimadani et al., 2020).

Tuyisenge et al. (2018) also explored organisational factors for situational and problem-based learning. The researchers examined the challenges that health care professionals faced in implementing skills and practices they had learned in a CPD programme on Advanced Life Support in Obstetrics® (ALSO) in a Rwanda hospital. Thirteen staff were interviewed, and further data collated on recorded turnover of departmental staff. Findings revealed there were a small number of trainees per hospital and there was no training within the health centres limiting the opportunities for health care professionals to share situational learning. In addition, sharing knowledge among colleagues was limited due to staff rotation, lack of refresher training and a high staff turnover (Tuyisenge et al., 2018).

Ali et al. (2015) reported Pakistani community midwives (n=42) increased their knowledge following attendance at a workshop on key knowledge and skills. Assessment was carried out through Objective Structured Clinical Assessments (OSCEs), revealing an increase in knowledge and skills to 70 - 80% from 50%. OSCEs are effective tools for assessing clinical competence in safe simulated environments (Black, 2018) although the clinicians enjoyed participating in the workshop and deemed them to be beneficial, they stated that they would have

preferred on the job training rather than workshops away from their clinical settings (Ali et al., 2015). Similarly, Al-Nuami, Ali and Ali (2019) identified an educational workshop on breastfeeding produced similar improvement in knowledge and practice of 42 Jordanian nurses and midwives compared to a control group who used traditional learning methods.

In Iran, Loeloe et al. (2020) investigated the effects of On-the-Job Training (OJT) versus workshop training methods on the report-writing skills of midwives working in a large teaching hospital. This quasi-experimental study involved midwives (n=70), with 35 assigned to OJT and 35 to a workshop. No significant difference in terms of pre-intervention performance score ($p=0.539$) were reported. However, the scores of performances in the OJT group were significantly higher (than those in the workshop group) during the training programme and one-month post-intervention ($p<0.05$). Although a small-scale study, the researchers concluded that midwives learning improved with OJT compared to workshop-based learning regarding report writing (Loeloe et al., 2020). These findings support similar outcomes reported in an earlier study by Ali et al. (2015).

In summary problem-based scenarios in the classroom can be useful to prepare learners to become effective clinical practitioners (MacVane et al., 2015). Later studies revealed that facilitating PBL into the clinical settings facilitated by Coaches/Facilitators makes this learning more authentic (Tweedie, Yerrell and Crozier, 2019; Van de Mortel et al., 2020). Qualified staff prefer learning that is pertinent to their clinical area of expertise and 'learning on the job' does require a positive culture of learning within the organisation (Pool, et al., 2015; Moafimadani et al., 2019; Al-Nuami, Ali and Ali, 2019; Loeloe et al., 2020). Self-directed Learning

In Saudi Arabia, Aljohani and Fadila (2018) study examined nursing students' readiness for self-directed learning (SDL) and their learning styles. Two-hundred and thirteen nursing students studying two programmes (regular and bridging) participated in the study with a response rate of 76%. Results confirmed that irrespective of learning style students expected to undergo a large portion of self-directed learning.

Cadorin, Cheng and Palese (2016) conducted a study to test Italian student nurses' readiness / ability to undertake self-directed learning. With 438 students enrolled in the study, resulting in a response rate of 90% with 48% attending their first year having an average age of 33 years and were predominately female. Data were collected using two validated tools thus enhancing the validity of the study (Polit and Beck, 2020). The tools gathered information on learning needs, learning motivation, resources, goals, plans and activities, evaluation, and communication skills. The students scored on average 83 out of 100 for one tool and 161 out of 400 for the other tool. Results confirmed that students were prepared to undertake self-directed learning. Detailed statistical analysis confirmed the reliability of the findings (Cluett, 2006; Grove, Burns and Gray, 2013). Cadorin, Cheng and Palese (2016) concluded that knowing a student's score was useful to provide individualised support for them and having information on collective students' scores facilitated the develop of appropriate strategies to improve their learning opportunities and meet their needs. This self-directed approach could be a useful lifelong learning strategy for qualified nurses / midwives working in challenging clinical environments. Furthermore, using tools to assess readiness to this method of learning could help with CPD (Cadorin, Cheng and Palese, 2016).

2.9.5 E-learning

In a large teaching hospital in Eire, Jesudason (2019) used action research to design and evaluate an on-line tutorial on how to use an electronic database for policies and procedures. Findings revealed that respect and openness were key components of learning and a need to involve learners / users in the development of electronic resources essential for service improvement to happen.

In a qualitative study, Robb, Wells and Goodyear-Smith (2012) explored whether incorporation of an online values-based tool enhanced the experience of n=613 postgraduate students on an epidemiology course in a large university in New Zealand. Qualitative data analysis obtained through focus groups revealed that using the online learning, was valued by students, as it enabled them to explore new concepts related to health care, the ability to explore a variety of different viewpoints and the opportunity to discover what it means to apply evidence to

everyday clinical practice. Power and Cole (2017) discussed the use of e-learning to teach clinical simulation as students / practitioners can review resources multiple times. Therefore, making this a meaningful learning and reflective experience for students and practitioners. Table 2.3 shows key literature surrounding learning strategies used in professional practice.

Table 2-3: Learning Strategies for Professional Practice

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
Davies, Fletcher, and Reeves (2016)	Explore interprofessional learning (IPL) in maternity care	Literature review	Database searching- MEDLINE, CINAHL	Review	Paucity of studies relating to IPL	IPL needs further investigation due to the wide range of professionals/ disciplines in maternity care.	Further related IPL research required
Zeeni et al. (2016)	Explore undergraduate students to IPL	Longitudinal IPL pre-post study Students (n=68) – nursing, pharmacology, and nutrition	Questionnaire: Pre and post IPL Attitudinal scale	Descriptive statistics	Pre- IPL: all students keen for IPL. Disparities in attitudes noted across both gender and professions. Females with more professional identity. Post IPL: All students highly evaluated IPL. Higher scores for teamwork by pharmacology/nutrition students. Nurses had lower scores for patient centredness.	Student nurses may be reluctant to include patients in their decisions.	IPL for maternity care professionals

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
Coleman (2018) NZ	Evaluate multi-professional education in UG students	Longitudinal study involving pre and post evaluation Students - medical, pharmacy, nursing and midwifery - medicine	Self-reported questionnaire	Descriptive statistics for evaluation	All students - improved teamwork and confidence surrounding management of patients' conditions.	IPL recommended as a learning strategy with health professionals.	
Stephens and Ormandy (2018) UK	Explored impact of six week IPL programme (team building and reflection) with UG students	Action research involving cycles of care using IPL UGs (n=37) - radiography, physiotherapy, podiatry, social work and nursing	Self-assessment, of attitudes values and behaviours of IPL	Descriptive statistics. practice	Majority of students revealed positive changes in attitude and behaviours in clinical.	IPL is a learning strategy to promote IP working.	

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
Barton et al. (2018) USA	Explore the value of IPL in promoting inter-professional collaboration	Intervention study involving IPL workshop UG students (81) - nursing, medical, occupational health, exercise and physical therapy	Survey questionnaire	Descriptive statistics	Promoted a sense of community across all UG professions / disciplines.	IPL. collaboration is an effective learning strategy.	Peer observation was highly valued
O'Hara et al. (2018)	Evaluate IPL e-learning programme to improve knowledge of interprofessional education in UG healthcare students	Evaluation study IPL programme developed using a logic model approach UGs (n=100)	Programme feedback	Evaluation of feedback	Overall recognised to be a positive idea to showcase and their pathway to provide a more complete picture of the patients' healthcare journey One negative feedback was that the programme duration was too long.	IPL improves communication and foster teamwork.	IPL has a vital role in collaborative working.

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
Currey et al. (2015) Australia	Evaluate nursing speciality module (team-based learning)	Evaluation study Student nurses (n=32)	Module feedback	Descriptive statistics	No increased satisfaction reported with peer observation / evaluation.	Increased engagement and satisfactions with team-based learning compared with traditional lectures.	Acquiring advanced critical thinking, teamwork empowered nurses to provide safe patient care.
Davis and Richardson (2017) UK	Evaluate a peer facilitation scheme	Evaluation of implementation of peer facilitation scheme to promote active learners Trained 2 nd year facilitators (n=12) 1st year student nurses (n=300)	Programme evaluation questionnaire (n=190 completed)	Descriptive	Peer facilitators were professional, inspiring, approachable, and instilled confidence.	Peer facilitation useful to develop teaching skills.	Encourage interdisciplinary teaching.
Roberts (2008)	Explore how students learn	Ethnographic study	Observational evaluation	Descriptive feedback	Learning clearly does take place in clinical practice	Developing social skills and forging	Survival skills are passed on

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
UK	from each other in clinical practice	student nurses (n=15)			Students learn how to become nurses.	friendships is important.	
Fertelli (2017) Turkey	Examine the effects of students' assessment of nursing process through Peer Assessment Method (PAM) in clinical setting Nursing students (n=68)	Experimental design Random allocation to 2 groups: Control (n=34) – Traditional Experimental (n=34) - student paired with their choice of peer	Verbal evaluation with peer (transferred to written evaluation)	Statistical evaluation	Statistically, PAM was more effective in developing peer support and critical thinking.	Effective learning strategy for clinical practice.	
Wuryanto et al. (2017) Indonesia	Explore peer learning model to student nurses in intensive care	Qualitative using a Phenomenological approach Student nurses (n=8) and	Focus group	Thematic analysis using Atlas software	Supervision process, improves student clinical decision making, fostered self-directed learning, encouraged collaborative learning, students	Peer learning can promote improvement in documentation.	

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
		clinical supervisors (n=4)			understanding of terminology.		
Adamson and Dewar (2015) UK	Explore what compassionate care means within practice using reflection on listening to patient stories	Action research Student nurses (n=37)	Online discussion forum (only 16 students engaged)	Descriptive	Patient stores promoted reflective learning. This facilitated students to explore their own values as well as influence compassionate care using a person-centred approach.		
Edwards (2017)	Provide an argument to support the model for reflection in or on practice	Academic evidence-based argument			Move to a four-dimensional process adding reflection-before-action and reflection-beyond-action to reflection-in-action and reflection-on-action.	Edwards (2017) reflection -beyond -action allows students to reflect deeply through telling their stories from clinical practice.	Through reflecting differently, nurses can process their reflection before-action, in-action, on action, and beyond-action.

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
Enuku and Evawoma- Enuku (2015) Nigeria	Discursive report on student learning	Discursive (in situations with no reflective practice in curriculum and in the absence in practice of mentors / supervisors			Reflection improves problem solving and decision-making skills.		Reflection can serve as a benchmark to measure and observe other professional practice.
van Rensburg (2018) South Africa	Explore role of lecturers in encouraging reflection in student nurse	Evaluative study	Questionnaire survey 121 educators (52% return rate)	Descriptive	Supported previous reported benefits of reflection. 37% personally used reflective practice. 98% used reflective practice with students. 46% reported reflection in their original training.	Reflective practice is recommended for all practitioners.	

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
Fitriani, Zubaida, Susilo et al (2020)	Evaluate the use of using a Reflection mechanism with problem-based learning scenarios	Evaluation. Biology students (n+??)	Programme evaluation feedback	Descriptive	Problem solving skills can be developed using problem- based scenarios and a reflective mechanism.	Reflection mechanism is an effective learning tool.	
Mackay, Riley and Dewing (2019) Canada, USA, Australia, UK, and Sweden.	Determine effective learning strategies for clinical supervisors	Literature review 22 peer reviewed international articles	Search databases + expert opinion from 36 clinical supervisors agreed findings	Themes Knowledge and attitude of clinical supervisor; Variation in delivery methods is crucial in sustaining learning; Face- to-face networking of clinical supervisors	Ongoing professional development of the clinical supervisors.	Active engagement fosters a community of learning approach.	

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
MacVane et al. (2015) UK	Evaluate Problem Based Learning (PBL) in Pre- registration Midwifery	Evaluation study	Module evaluation feedback	Descriptive	PBL develops communication, facilitation and leadership skills and encourages a compassionate attitude through listening to women's stories and promotes a person-centred approach to care planning.	PBL facilitates students acquire necessary skills an effective, empathetic practitioner.	
Pool et al. (2015) Netherlands	Explore CPD strategies with nurses	Evaluative study Sample of nurses: younger, middle aged and older nurses (n=21)	Evaluation feedback		Responses varied across age groups. Younger nurses interested in gaining experience and career progression, middle-aged nurses interested in work- life balance. The older nurses interested in consistency where learning was done on a smaller scale.	CPD clearly keeps nurses up to date with developments pertinent to their clinical area.	CPD is a catalyst for learning
Moafimadani et al. (2019) Iran	Identify variables on how nurses	Qualitative study	Semi structured interviews	Thematic analysis using "latent content"	Main themes: Individual factors influencing individual	Factors of learning management for achieving these	Organisations need to recognise

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
	learn in clinical practice	Purposive sample- n=15) including 8 executives and 7 nurses		analysis approach involving four steps (coding, classification, finding themes or themes, data integration)	learning and subscribed to lifelong learning. Culture of learning within organisation impacted on learning. Also, workload and staff shortages impacted on learning.	goals seems necessary.	effective factors to promote learning of nurses
Van de Mortel et al. (2020) Australia	Examine effectiveness of clinical education facilitators in clinical practice	Evaluation study Students: (n=134)	Questionnaire survey	Low response rate of 13.5%	Nurses rated facilitators highly effective (4.43/5 +/- 0.75).	Blurring of roles and responsibilities was highlighted.	
Cadorin, Cheng and Palese (2016) Italy	Measure concurrent validity between the Self-Rating Scale of Self-Directed Learning (SRSSDLIta and Self-Directed	Comparative Survey design Sample - nurses (n=428)	Questionnaire survey using validated tools for Learning needs, learning motivation, resources, goals, plans and activities and	Pearson correlation coefficient CI 95 % bias-corrected and accelerated bootstrap (BCa) calculations	Confirmation of concurrent validity of the SRSSDLIta with the SDLI. The SRSSDLIta instrument is useful in identifying Self-Directed Learning abilities.		Strategies required to support individual/collective learning needs for lifelong learning.

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
	Learning Instruments (SDLI) in UG nursing students		evaluation and communication skills				
Aljohani and Fadila (2019) Saudi Arabia	Determine the nursing students' readiness for self-directed learning (SDL) and their learning styles	Criss-sectional descriptive analytical research design Two programmes (regular and bridging) Sample- Nursing students (n=213)	Survey - demographics, SDL readiness (SDLR), and student-recorded responses to an online visual, aural / auditory, read / write, and kinaesthetic (VARK)	Statistical analysis using SPSS (V20) to identify descriptive and bi-variate outcomes	Response rate = 76 Desire for learning subscales statistically significant for gender ($t= 1.985, p= 0.048$), academic level ($F= 2.969, P= 0.033$), and mode ($t= 3.610, p= 0.001$). Overall SDLR scale scores were significant for residence ($t= 4.938, p= 0.001$) and learning style ($F= 5.197, p= 0.002$).	The dominant learning style for student nurses was kinaesthetic Findings revealed a correlation between readiness to undertake SDL and participants' learning styles.	
Al-Nuami, Ali and Ali (2019) Jordan	Evaluate educational workshop on breastfeeding versus	Comparative study	Evaluation feedback	Descriptive statistics	Carrying out a workshop on key knowledge, skills and practice increased. Objective Structured Clinical Assessments (OSCEs). OSCEs was an e effective tool for		

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
	traditional methods	Intervention - Breastfeeding workshop. Control- Traditional Nurses and midwives – (n=42)			assessing clinical competence.		
Jesudason (2019) Eire	Evaluate an on- line tutorial on how to use an electronic database for police and procedures	Action research	AR cycles		Respect and openness were key components of learning.	e learners/users need to be involved in development of electronic resources for service.	
Loeloe et al. (2020) Iran	Investigated effects of 'on the-job' training (OJT) versus workshop training methods on	Quasi- experimental study Sample – Midwives (n=70); 35	Statistical using SS{S (V20)		No significant different was found in pre-intervention performance score ($p=0.539$). Significant score - performance in the OJT group were significantly higher than workshop group	Midwives learn better with' on 'the job training' compared with workshop-based	Small scale study

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
	report-writing skills	assigned to OJT and 35 to workshop			during the training program and one-month post-intervention ($p < 0.05$)	learning regarding report writing	
Robb, Wells and Goodyear-Smith (2012) New Zealand	Explore if on-line 'values based' tool enhanced post graduate experience	Mixed methods using a qualitative approach Students on an epidemiology course – (n=613)	Students responded to case scenario, using analytical frameworks for assessing decision making	Focus groups evaluated the process Taped and transcribed	Three themes: Using Values exchange based tools allowed students to explore new ideas. Taking on board other student views diversified the students' views. the experience enabled to apply evidence in everyday practice.	Students highly valued this approach and enabled them to gain different perspectives into its application to clinical practice.	
Scerri, Innes and Scerri (2017) International	Examine dementia training programmes	Systematic literature review N=14 peer reviewed studies			No randomised controlled trials identified. Difficulties reported with longer longitudinal studies difficult due to staff turnover.	High quality studies required to evaluate staff change in behaviour/practices and patient outcomes.	

Publication Country of origin	Research Focus	Methodology Study design Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions	Comments
		UK (9); Australia (3) and USA (2)					
Tuyisenge et al. (2018) Rwanda	Explore organisational factors causing challenges CPD) on Advanced Life Support in Obstetrics® (ALSO) ace in transferring knowledge into practice	Qualitative study Sample – nurses (n.=13)	Interviews Staff turnover collated	Transcripts and analysis of qualitative data	small number of trainees per hospital. Limited opportunities for shared learning and knowledge due to continual staff rotation, high turnover of staff, lack of in-service training.		

2.10 Summary of literature

This chapter summarises the literature from three key perspectives of nursing and midwifery documentation, documentary assessment tools to determine quality of nursing and midwifery documentation and the learning strategies used to prepare for clinical practice.

It is evident that the concerns about the standard of clinical documentation is indeed a worldwide issue. Documentation exists to; provide evidence of care, legal purposes and to allow quality of standards of care to be measured. The process of ensuring clinical documentation is of a high standard is complex with many barriers to the effectiveness and efficiency of the documentary process. identified. Education, training and regular auditing and monitoring were offered as solutions to improving the standard of documentation to provide evidence of care provided.

An overview of the many tools and instruments to assess the quality of nursing and midwifery documentation was provided however none were found specifically relating to midwifery documentation which focuses on a more holistic approach and less on the diagnostic element of medicalised / ill health care. Also, the content of tools requires to be discipline specific for the practitioner. Although many of the tools incorporated, guidelines and professional standards none were found incorporated the UK professional standards for Nurses and Midwives (NMC, 2015; 2018). Furthermore, tools require to be user friendly to ensure compliance therefore it makes sense for the practitioners to be involved in the development, testing and evaluation. This would incorporate training and learning requirements and potential uses for the documentation review tool.

Learning strategies utilised in clinical practice were examined. Inter-professional learning (IPL) works well across a wide variety of disciplines including in nursing and midwifery. Online sources viewed as useful IPL tools as it allowed learners to revisit material as often as they wish. Peer review and peer observation was evaluated well by some practitioners however poorly evaluated by others. Reflection viewed as a valuable learning strategy for students as well as qualified

staff to use however should be practiced by teachers and learners alike to foster a culture of lifelong learning.

This present study was planned to address the main gaps identified from the literature review relating to the assessment of the quality of clinical documentation. Everyday professional practice is underpinned by documentary evidence which should accurately reflect the care provided. Whilst the study focuses on midwifery documentation, it is anticipated that the processes will be readily transferrable to other health related documentation.

2.11 Overall aim

The overall aim of the study is to develop an effective learning mechanism for midwives conducting documentary review in accordance with professional standards.

CHAPTER 3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter will present the ontology, epistemology and theoretical perspectives explored and relate this to social constructivism and social constructionism underpinning the present study. In relation to research practice, methodology and methods are two distinct terms relating to key elements (Robson and McCartan 2016). Methodology refers to the approaches underpinning the systematic enquiry developed within a theoretical and philosophical framework with associated epistemological assumptions (Holloway and Wheeler, 2010; Gray, 2018). Research methodology examines the logic and underpinning rationale for adopting the methods used and is the strategy used to conduct research (Wilson, 2013; Robson and McCartan, 2016). The term 'method' relates to the systematic and detailed approach towards those techniques and approaches used to conduct each stage in the research process from access and recruitment to data collection and analyses (Robson and McCartan, 2016; Polit and Beck, 2020).

The outcome of the literature review has confirmed the existing gaps relating to the area of interest, contributed to determining the study aim, and informed the focus of investigation. An overview of the epistemology, ontology and theoretical stance is presented which informed the methodological stance for the proposed study i.e., qualitative, quantitative or a mixed methods approach. The philosophy of social constructionism and social constructivism are explored.

The range of key research approaches is presented along with the benefits highlighting key differences in each approach. The selection for the preferred research approach is detailed and explored further. Action research, the preferred approach, was selected as being the most relevant methodology to appropriately address the research aim and objectives of the study.

3.2 Ontology, epistemology, and theoretical perspectives

To conduct research in any meaningful manner it is necessary to explain ontology epistemology, and theoretical stances from the researcher's perspective (Polit and Beck, 2020). Broadly speaking ontology refers to whether reality (being) is seen as objective, separate from human interaction leading to the positivist theoretical prospective or whether it is viewed as a multifactorial concept making it more open to interpretation, therefore subjective (Gray, 2018). There is recognition of the changing and emerging world or becoming ontological where chaos and formlessness exist (Chia, 2002).

Once this view of reality has been explored then the epistemological stance can emerge. Epistemology provides a framework where knowledge can be critically examined and provides a philosophical argument for endorsing legitimacy of knowledge which underpins the methodology and ultimately the methods used (Gray, 2018). Crotty (2015, p.3) supports this framework, stating that epistemology is concerned with "*the theory of knowledge embedded in the theoretical perspective and thereby the methodology*". Of importance is how this knowledge is discovered, objectively or so-called 'hard' evidence or 'soft' subjective evidence. Furthermore, from a socio-cultural perspective the role individuals play in gaining this knowledge requires to be examined (Gray, 2018).

Broadly speaking there are three epistemological research positions i.e., objectivism, constructivism, and subjectivism (Parahoo,2014; Polit and Beck, 2020). Objectivism is about discovering the objective truth and sits with the positive theoretical prospective, where scientific enquiry is prevalent (Parahoo, 2014). Conversely, constructivism is concerned with how humans interact with the world, where truth is discovered (Polit and Beck, 2020). The theoretical perspective linked with constructivism is interpretivism (Gray, 2018). Although both interpretivism and objectivism hold opposing epistemological stances, they are rooted in being ontology (Parahoo, 2014). Subjectivism is where subjects construct meaning from dreams, religious beliefs and fits with the becoming ontology (Gray, 2018).

Through examining the literature, it became clear that both positive and interpretive theoretical perspectives would be required to meet the aim and objectives of the study. Interpretive to collaboratively develop the learning tool and positive aspects to testing and validation (Parahoo, 2014; Polit and Beck, 2020) The process in constructing and testing the learning tool would need to involve midwives as the learning tool would be used by them in their everyday practice (Macfarlane and Bucknall, 2015)

3.3 Social constructionism / social constructivism

Constructive theory has two branches, social constructionism, and social constructivism (Burr, 2015). Both perspectives subscribe to the postmodern concept that reality and knowledge are subjective. Constructivists believe that knowledge and reality are created through discussion or conversation (Burr, 2015). Furthermore, constructivists emphasis is on what is occurring within the individual brain (or mind) during social interaction (Figure 3.1 displays the midwife and social constructivism in pictorial form) whereas social constructionists concentrate on what's happening between people during the social interaction. This is succinctly described by Guterman (2006).

“Although both constructivism and social constructionism endorse a subjectivist view of knowledge, the former emphasises individuals’ biological and cognitive processes, whereas the latter places knowledge in the domain of social interchange” (p.13).

Figure 3.1:Represents the midwife and social constructivism

Social constructionism is looking at the interaction between humans and their surroundings (Crotty, 2015). According to Crotty (2015) there must be human engagement to make any sense of surroundings. Burr (2015) further develops this concept acknowledging the constructionist point of view, is both objective and subjective because of this human interaction. Therefore, making sense of the meaning requires construction in a social manner (without exception), hence the term social constructionism. This theory emerges through the process of interpreting and reinterpreting (Burr, 2015). According to Mead (cited in Crotty, 2015) every human has the potential for social constructionism. Fish (1990, cited in Crotty,2015) states objects made by social and conventional means are created physically, but only become socially constructed when they interact with humans through physical contact or inter-connection. Furthermore, the culture is pivotal in social constructionism as Geertz (1973, cited in Crotty, 2015) explains that humans would not function without culture, which is the cornerstone of human behaviour. Crotty (2015) highlights that because something is socially constructed it does not make it less real. Our interpretations of reality are just

that, our interpretations from where we are culturally and historically placed, at that given time (Crotty, 2015).

The development of the learning tool to review the quality of midwifery documentation would require collaboration from midwives (a cultural and professional group) i.e., socially constructed (Burr, 2015). However, the theory of social constructivism is also necessary as the learning tool needs to be tested and retested involving individual interpretation (Crotty, 2015). Furthermore, as this is a very interactive tool for use in everyday professional practice (working in accordance with the NMC standards (NMC, 2015; 2018), phronesis (practical wisdom) would be a prerequisite of the participants in ongoing development and testing. *“Practical wisdom (Phronesis) is a state of grasping the truth, involving reason, concerned with action, about what is good or bad for a human being”* (Aristotle, 1999. P.89). Figure 3.2 shows the relationship between the midwife, social constructivism, social constructionism, The NMC Code (NMC, 2015; 2018) and the DOC Learning Tool.

Figure 3.2:Midwife, Code, social constructionism

3.4 Research methodologies

Methodology is described as the bridge between the theoretical framework and the reality of data collection and analysis (Rees, 2011; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). The research methodology selected for a research study needs to be carefully considered to ensure the methodology is appropriate to address the aim, purpose, and context of the research (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Gray, 2018). The deliberations by the researchers in this process cannot be underestimated due to the wide range of approaches and styles of research methodology available (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). The section provides an overview of the main research methodologies and research paradigms. Each research enquiry approach is founded on a group of theoretical perspectives and paradigms (Holloway and Wheeler, 2010). A paradigm is a set of thoughts and beliefs with different research approaches rooted within their philosophical backgrounds and assumptions (Parahoo, 2014; Polit and Beck, 2020). Quantitative and qualitative research approaches are the most common influential paradigms (Gray, 2018; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018) whereas latter a mixed method design combines both paradigms in a pragmatic approach (Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

3.4.1 Quantitative research

Regarding the philosophical approach, the positivism paradigm underpins quantitative methodologies where the fundamental assumption is the existence of the real world (Robson, 2016; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Polit and Beck, 2020). The quantitative paradigm associated with positivist methodologies include cross-sectional studies, quasi-experimental and randomised controlled trials (Grove, Burns and Gray, 2013). These quantitative methodologies aim to locate relationships within the data and ideally the cause-and-effect relationship (determinism), by reviewing populations rather than focusing on individuals (Grove, Burns and Gray, 2013; Parahoo, 2014; Polit and Beck, 2020). The essential features involve the processes to be systematic, objective with control and manipulation of conditions of interest to the researchers (Parahoo, 2014; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). The approaches use numerical data in the process of explaining, predicting, or testing statistical hypothesis to determine the result,

relationship, or expected outcome from the research question (Grove and Ciper, 2019). Reducing a complex theme to measurable and recordable units to test strength and persistence of relationships between variables and outcomes is a deductive approach to research (Jolley, 2020). Quantitative data collection usually involves measurements using pre-determined questionnaires, observation schedules or other measurement formats (Grove and Ciper, 2019). Measures need to be validated to ensure they are reliable and not open to numerous interpretations (Polit and Beck, 2020). Validity is the extent to which a data collection tool is fit for the purpose intended (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Data analysis involves the use of statistical tests to determine the results where findings may also be generalisable to different populations (Polit and Beck, 2020).

The role of the quantitative researcher is more objective in nature (Parahoo, 2014; Polit and Beck, 2020). Due to the nature of the present study, quantitative research approaches alone were not viable options to fully address the aim of the study (Section 2.10).

3.4.2 Qualitative Research

Approaches to qualitative research are often described as a humanistic and holistic philosophy investigating real world inductive experiences (Robson, 2016). Researchers acknowledge that the social world can only be understood from the individual's perspective especially if they are part of the ongoing action under investigation (Robson, 2016; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Polit and Beck, 2020). This is in direct contrast to the objectivity of positivist paradigm (Robson, 2016). Qualitative methodologies tend to be an interpretivist and inductive approach to the research enquiry (Parahoo, 2014), with more of a focus on the understanding of situations rather than determining associations and relationships (Robson, 2016; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; In addition to identifying key issues, qualitative research can also provide the researcher with rich subjective data on individual experiences with information on how relationships affect participants, how individuals adapt and identify what works and what does not work in life situations and practice (Polit and Beck, 2020). Qualitative approaches can provide meaningful insight into the reasons, barriers and challenges experienced. Therefore, qualitative research approaches will be appropriate to facilitate

understanding of experiences, perceptions, and processes from the perspective of a variety of health and social areas of interest (Topping, 2015)

Qualitative research is often conducted to address a problem which needs clarification and further exploration. This approach places value and more importance on interpretation and viewpoints, examining contexts, environments, and a deep understanding of ideas (Polit and Beck, 2020). Researchers strive to provide a holistic understanding of issues, processes, and life experiences (Robson, 2016). The methods used usually involve gathering subjective narrative data, analysis, and interpretation which aims to understand the experiences and attitudes of individuals and groups in society (Robson, 2016). Qualitative data collection methods aim to address the 'what', 'how' or 'why' of a phenomenon rather than determining the frequency, number, and cost (Parahoo, 2014; Gray, 2018). The researcher makes use of mostly open-ended interview questions designed in a semi-structured technique often in a convenient natural setting for the participants (Gray, 2018). The qualitative study can be described as an array of interpretive approaches which aims at describing, decoding, translating, and making the full meaning of the occurrence in the social world (Parahoo, 2014). Numerous variants of naturalistic qualitative approaches are available, each with the own characteristics and approaches (Polit and Beck, 2020) The main qualitative approaches used in health include ethnography, grounded theory, narratives and storytelling, and case studies (Robson, 2016; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Three key approaches were considered for this present study including phenomenology, appreciative inquiry, and action research (Parahoo, 2014). Phenomenology, an umbrella term incorporating a philosophical movement and a series of research approaches was introduced by Husserl over 100 years ago (Galvin and Holloway, 2015). This new approach of studying philosophy aimed to capture human perceptions and describe their lived experience (Galvin and Holloway, 2015). The 'lived experience' refers to experience as lived through people's actions, relations, and situations of human beings (Robson, 2016; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018;). Husserl purported to use bracketing to keep the researcher's own values and beliefs in abeyance (Polit and Beck, 2020). The theorist Heidegger expanded the phenomenological method to focus more on consciousness, existentialism, and interpretive hermeneutic dimensions

without the use of bracketing (Galvin and Holloway, 2015). For qualitative methods, subjective data is normally gained through open or semi-structured interviews (Grove, Gray and Burns, 2015). Transcripts are analysed using various methods to interpret the qualitative phenomena in a meaningful way (Grove, Gray and Burns, 2015).

Another approach is appreciative inquiry for organisational change. Appreciative inquiry focuses on achieving positive change through focusing on strengths rather than on weaknesses (Parahoo, 2014). It involves five stages including: Dawn, Discovery, Dream, Design, Delivery and Barriers to Culture Change (Cram, 2010). The essence of appreciative inquiry methodology is a search for what is best in the organisation. The broad focus involves a systematic exploration of what gives 'life and energy' to an efficient organisation (Clarke, Reed and Keyes, 2015). Appreciative inquiry involves asking the right questions with the aim to improve the system's capacity and reach its potential (Cram, 2010). Neither phenomenology nor appreciative inquiry were appropriate research methodologies to meet the aim of the study. Table 3.1 summarises the key differences between quantitative and qualitative research methodologies.

Table 3-1: Quantitative and Qualitative methodologies: main differences.

	Quantitative	Qualitative
Nature of the research objective/question	Quantifiable, frequencies, magnitude.	Quality or meaning of experiences.
Reasoning process	Deductive Objective Analysis of numerical data (statistical/ testing a hypothesis).	Inductive Subjective Analysis of subjective data (seeking themes or patterns in the data from which may tentatively develop into theory).
Philosophical paradigm	Positivism	Interpretivism or Constructivism
Sample size	Large	Smaller
Strengths	Delineates variables Provides generalisable results to other populations.	Facilitates in-depth comprehension and understanding of processes and motives. Provides contextual information about real situations
Weaknesses	May not identify unanticipated findings. May be difficult to implement as results too broad.	Findings not generalisable May be limited in scope Time consuming to collect and analyse data.

3.4.3 Mixed Methods

More recently in health and social care research, mixed methods approaches have become more popular in the attempt to incorporate the best of both qualitative and quantitative paradigms (Grinnel and Unrau, 2010; Creswell and Creswell, 2018). Indeed, Grinnel and Unrau (2010) suggest that mixed methods design is ideal for exploring complex topics. It can also provide some triangulation of results by undertaking a quantitative-qualitative loop. This is done by undertaking a complementary qualitative study using a small sample from the quantitative study. The findings may strengthen or attenuate the original quantitative study (Creswell

and Creswell, 2018). Mixed method makes use of the strength of both quantitative and qualitative research (Creswell and Creswell, 2018).

A component of mixed methods is triangulation which combines at least two or more theoretical perspectives, methodological approaches, data sources, investigators, or data analysis methods (Creswell and Creswell, 2018; Gray,2018). This approach converges information from different sources which can confirm validity, reliability, and generalisability. The intention of triangulation is to increase the researcher's ability and confidence to interpret the findings and gain a more comprehensive understanding of what the findings have revealed. This can provide the study with confirmation and completeness, adding depth and breadth and richness to the data. Triangulation using multiple methods can promote more insights about the study findings and negate and counterbalance any deficiency in using a single strategy approach (Denzin and Lincoln, 2017; Gray,2018).

3.5 Action research

Action research is defined by its title, whereby action occurs with research methods guiding the action (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Parahoo, 2014). Through action research there is an epistemological necessity for collaboration in the interpretation of data (McNiff, 2017). Action research lies on the continuum between positivism and interpretivism however more towards interpretivism as the chosen subjects (midwives) are participatory i.e., participants in the research (Polit and Beck, 2020).

Action research is an approach that focuses on both action (solving concrete problems in real situations) and research (trying to further the goals of science) simultaneously (Robson, 2016; McNiff, 2017;). Improvement and involvement are central to action research (Robson, 2016; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Watson, 2018). The approach focuses on the real world and directly seeks to improve practice. Action research aims to give something back. Research subjects work in partnership with the researcher (Gray, 2018). The approach merges education, practice, and research (Meyer and Cooper, 2015; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018;).

Action research is often chosen as the preferred methodological design for studies when analysis of existing practice is required and elements of change are identified (Robson, 2016; McNiff, 2017). It involves a practical approach to professional enquiry. This reflective practice is also a constant variable in nursing and midwifery professional practice, with practitioners being familiar with the processes involved (LoBiondo-Wood and Haber, 2018). Action research acknowledges the true planning, action, monitoring, reflection cycle and as such, does not always start with planning (Robson, 2016; Gray, 2018). This is also called 'reconnaissance' (Gray, 2018). Schön (1983) calls this 'knowing in action'. According to Kemmis, McTaggart and Nixon (2014) all that is required for action research to take place is a general idea that something might be improved.

Action research combines the methodological approach of social science with the action required to respond to the social problems of the day (McNiff, 2017). The approach is a useful research technique in nursing and midwifery as it has been

widely used to effect change in a variety of settings (LoBiondo-Wood and Haber, 2017). Meyer and Cooper, (2015, p.303) highlighted that action research is a research approach that involves *“interpreting and explaining social situations while implementing a change intervention”*. This concept supports the underpinning theoretic aspects of social constructivism and social constructionism.

The role of the researcher in action research is to break down the problem, act as facilitator and help the participants understand the problem or events (Gray, 2018). The task of the action researcher is to bring together people with different views and perceptions so they can collectively formulate an agreed plan of action (Meyer and Cooper, 2015; Cohen, Manion and Morrison,2018; Gray, 2018;).

The concept of action research originated from the 1940's founded by the US Commissioner of the 50 Indian Affairs, Johns Collier (Bate, 2000). However, the term action research was first used by Kurt Lewin in 1946 (Lewin,1946). Whilst action research became less popular in the 1980s, there has been a revival in the use of this research approach since the 1990s especially within large organisations such as health care and education (Meyer and Cooper, 2015). This is due mainly to the emergence of improvement methodology and practice development where involvement of people is central to these processes (McNiff and Whitehead, 2010). Reason, Bradbury, and Sage (2008) highlight that health care workers are attracted to action research due to its developmental nature, practical foundation, knowledge in action as well as its democratic framework.

Action research is a practical research approach intended to benefit the participants in some way (McNiff and Whitehead, 2010). It is participatory and collaborative, not only involving the participants directly in the research process but also in the development of the evolving stages in the process (Gray, 2018). The researcher and participants working in true partnership to obtain the outcome of the research (McNiff and Whitehead, 2010). The problem solving and cyclical nature of action research makes it emotionally challenging and very time consuming for the researcher as well as participants (Meyer and Cooper, 2015). However, due to its participatory nature as well as the purpose, to make a difference to the participants in some way this makes the research more tangible

to the participants. Ultimately the participants shape and mould the research as the study develops in a democratic way.

3.6 Models of action research

Since the inception of action research, numerous theories and authors surrounding this research design have emerged. Hart and Bond (1996) offer a range of authors interpretation of action research. Lewin (1946) was associated with 'Experimental, Empirical, Diagnostic and Participative' models. Kingsley (1985) focussed more on the 'Management Model, Autonomy Model and Underclass Model' whilst the action research models of Holter and Schwartz-Barcott (1993) were 'Technical-Collaborative, Mutual Collaborative and Enhancement'. Hart and Bond (1996) highlighted that the type of action research may vary across each cycle of the study. Watson (2018) supports this theory indicating that these types of models are too rigid, and it is more important to focus on the characteristics of action research rather than the prescriptive types.

3.7 Characteristics of action research

According to Watson (2018) the main principles of action research involve participation and collaboration to bring about change and improvement usually focusing on practical and context specific-related issues. The process is cyclical in nature involving the generation of theory underpinned with evidence of reflection and reflexivity (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018).

Action research has a political and developmental role. Critical examination of organisational power is necessary to ensure a balanced view of issues is presented. Due to the element of change, action research can be seen as political, and the potential to be transformational (Cluett and Bluff, 2006; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Watson (2018) highlights there is agreement amongst theorists, that empowerment of others is pivotal to action research. It is also necessary for change to take place whether this change is at an individual or organisational level (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Watson, 2018). Elden and Chisholm (1993) argued that change should be self-generating and self-maintained. However, Lewin (1946) indicated that raising self-esteem with participants should remain a key research goal.

Throughout the action research cycles, participants are co-researchers and research is carried out in collaboration with them and not to them (Gray, 2018). Rolfe (1996) describes this collaboration as a 'defining characteristic' within action research. In agreement, Elden, and Chisholm (1993) and Waterman et al. (2001) describe this collaboration as being an essential component. More recently 'McNiff (2013) simply states that action research is 'always collaborative'. Importantly, participation is fundamental to ensure democratic decisions are made throughout the course of the study (Watson, 2018) where the level of collaboration can also vary (Gavens et al., 2018).

In relation to the principle of 'change', Bate (2000) highlights key questions about the need to be asked what requires to be changed in the organisation at the beginning of the research. This is an important step to ensure a balanced view is achieved without focussing on the negative (Bate (2000)). Elden and Chisholm (1993) insist that evidence of change that occurs is also a key element of action research. Where change is recognised as a process and not an event (Robson, 2016). However, others argue that change is not always attainable (Whyte, 1991) and does not always represent a successful study (McNiff, 2017). More importantly is the desire for improvement (or change) to take place (Watson, 2018). Watson (2018) also highlights nurses are used to working within rules and regulations and these can help focus, provide motivation or reference to their action research. Action research appeals to participants who work in practical and context specific settings such as education and health (Cohen, Manion and Morrison; 2018 Gray, 2018). Action research in the workplace i.e., context specific means that changes can occur although it makes the generalisability of the research low (Watson, 2018).

3.8 Research Cycles

Lewin (1946) first highlighted the planning, acting, observing, and reflecting cycle Figure 3.3 Hart and Bond (1996) used this cycle (cycles) to link research, action, and evaluation. Gray (2018) highlighted that the stages in the process are overlapping. Heron (1996) suggested that as the research moves through the cycles a refinement of data takes place, progressing the research. Heron (1996)

also highlighted that moving through the cycles adds to the validity of the research.

Figure 3.3: Action research cycle of activity

Action research should generate theory and this key element differentiates action research from audit (Watson, 2018). McNiff and Whitehead (2011) emphasised that the action researcher is a theorist as well as a practitioner, “*a knowledge creator in your own right*” (p.77). They also stated that the knowledge gained from the research may be difficult to generalise. Although Greenwood (1994) argued there may be a chance of replicating the results under the same circumstances.

The roots of action research are embedded within Lewin’s (1946) work. Therefore, by nature action research is a reflective process which requires constant self-analysis and self-appraisal (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Reflection and reflexivity are central to action research with reflection taking place at every stage in the cycles (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018). Furthermore, it is important that all researchers acknowledge they influence their research to a certain degree which is good practice (Cluett and Bluff, 2006; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018;).

3.9 Types / models of action research

McNiff and Whitehead (2011) stated that broadly speaking there are two main ‘families’ of action research. The first, was formed by Johns Elliot (Whitehead and McNiff, 2011), which is usually referred to as interpretive action research and is the most popular type of action research. This type involves a researcher

reporting (interpreting) on what other practitioners are doing (Whitehead and McNiff, 2011). The second type of action research founded by Jack Whitehead, involves practitioners reporting on their own actions. This type is called “*self-study action research, first-person action research, living theory action research or just plain action research*” (p.11). McNiff and Whitehead (2011) highlighted the two main types subdivide and different types have emerged. Participatory action research, insider action research, outsider action research, feminist participatory action research are all terms used. Some of these types cross over into narrative inquiry, appreciative inquiry, or complexity theory, which makes it difficult to define.

3.10 Rationale for choosing action research

Action research is the preferred methodology to use in a study when there is a requirement for analysis of existing practice and elements of change are identified. It involves a practical approach to professional enquiry (McNiff, 2013). Action research acknowledges the true planning, action, monitoring, reflection cycle and as such, does not always start with planning. Also called ‘reconnaissance’ (McTaggart, 1997). Schön (1983) calls this ‘knowing in action’. According to Kemmis, McTaggart and Nixon (2014) all that is required for action research to take place is a general idea that something might be improved. Reflective practice is also a constant variable in the Nursing Midwifery Council (NMC) professional practice with practitioners being familiar with the processes involved (NMC, 2018).

Action research combines the methodological approach of social science with the action required to respond to the social problems of the day. Action research is a useful research design in midwifery as it has been widely used to effect change in a variety of settings (Reason and Bradbury and Sage, 2008). Although there are different types of action research, all types involve the researcher as facilitator and evaluator of change (Gerrish and Lathlean, 2015). The role of the researcher is to break down the problem, act as facilitator and help the participants understand the problem or events. The task of the action researcher is to bring together people with different views and perceptions so that they can collectively

formulate an agreed plan of action (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Gray, 2018; Meyer and Cooper, 2015;).

The two main types of action research were examined, and it became clear that the research required for this present study would be more interpretive action research rather than self-study or first-person action research. Participants involved were practising midwives within the organisation. Insider action research was also discounted as this required the researcher to be part of the organisation being examined (Gray, 2018). Although the researcher had previously worked with participants and at the onset of study they were not working clinically or using the clinical documentation, which would be a prerequisite for an insider action researcher.

The principles of Participatory Action Research (PAR) as a branch of the interpretive action research 'family' (Gray, 2018), was the preferred research methodology for the present study. This design was appropriate to address the aim of the study (Section 2.10) to generate data from the participants' 'on the job' related experiences as development of the learning tool. The scope of PAR includes identifying goals, freedom, democracy, empowerment while examine a problem or concern (Gray, 2018). Then through progressive cycles of research, learning and action gleam new knowledge (Grant, Nelson, and Mitchell, cited in Reason and Bradbury and Sage 2008). According to Reason and Bradbury (2008) the relationship between the researcher and the participants is important during PAR.

"We stop working with people as subjects Instead, we build relationship as co-researchers" (Reason and Bradbury, 2008 p.9).

McTaggart (1997) highlighted that PAR is more than just taking part, it means involving the participants in decision making throughout the study. Importantly there is also shared control between the participants and the researcher.

Co-researching means that the participants are engaged with the process (Gray, 2018) It is also political, giving participants a say in decisions made about them and claims to generate knowledge about them. Interpretation of events / facts by

the participants themselves rather than through an outsider's eye (Gerrish and Lathlean, 2015). Furthermore, it is confidence building for the participants to see change / developments take shape (Reason and Bradbury, 2008).

An approach was required which involved participation and collaboration in the development and testing of a mechanism to review the quality of midwifery documentation. Therefore, participatory action research (PAR) involving mixed methods was the preferred research design confirmed to be appropriate to address the nature and purpose of the study.

CHAPTER 4 METHODS

4.1 Introduction

This chapter provides an overview of the participatory action research (PAR) study. Given the nature of the action research design, this chapter details on the methods adopted to address the aim and objectives. The ethical principles considered in the planning of the study design and processes adopted to protect these key principles will be explored. The role of the researcher and study participants will be discussed. The action research study adopts both quantitative and qualitative research paradigms which are detailed throughout this chapter.

4.2 Aim, objectives and research questions

The overall aim of the study is to develop an effective learning mechanism for midwives conducting documentary review in accordance with professional standards.

Study objectives:

- a. Identify key issues required to evidence quality of documented care in accordance with NMC professional standards.
- b. Develop an appropriate educational and developmental mechanism to assess quality of documented midwifery care.
- c. Implement the educational and developmental mechanism to assess quality of documented midwifery care.
- d. Test the educational and developmental mechanism to assess quality of documented midwifery care.
- e. Evaluate the educational and developmental mechanism to assess quality of documented midwifery care.

Research Questions:

- a. What are the key issues required to evidence the quality of documented care in accordance with NMC professional standards?
- b. What is an effective learning tool for midwives to examine and evaluate the quality and robustness of documented care?

Participatory Action Research (PAR) offered a reasonable solution to producing an effective learning tool for midwives, which could be used for teaching and learning as well as for ongoing monitoring purposes. In addition, an opportunity to gather the thoughts and experiences of clinical midwives as there was a lack of studies surrounding clinicians' views of using documentation tools.

4.3 Study design

Action research is useful in situations where no evidence exists to support or refute current practice, poor knowledge skills and attitudes to carry out evidence-based practice or gaps identified in service provision (McNiff and Whitehead, 2011; Watson, 2018). Participatory action research (PAR) focuses on exploration, intervention and evaluation involving participants as co-researchers in the design and execution of the study (Meyer and Cooper, 2015; Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2018; Watson, 2018).

Meyer and Cooper (2015) highlighted there is no clear end to the action research study. Figure 4.1 presents the research plan to conduct the PAR study and summarises each of the phases. Due to the cyclical nature of the PAR, there was ongoing analysis of the emerging findings and reflections on the subjective evaluation. As this PAR involved participant involvement, the researcher required time to feedback preliminary findings to participants following each study phase to date. This process informed development of the methods and through improvement and refinement of the study facilitated achievement of the research aim and objectives. Triangulation of findings enhanced the areas of convergence and divergent resulting in ongoing improvements to the DOC Learning Tool over the study period.

This methods chapter focuses on the methods and discussion around the initial Exploration phase (phase one) and the planned Intervention phase (phase two). Subsequent amendments to the methods due to the emerging outcomes of each PAR cyclical review process in the intervention phase are presented in Chapter Five with the results

Figure 4.1: Research plan for study

4.4 Ethical considerations

Research involves human beings and must be conducted under strict ethical and moral guidelines to protect the participants (LoBiondo-Wood, 2018; Beauchamp and Childress, 2019). Following the atrocities and the subsequent trials of the researchers of experiments during World War Two, The Nuremberg Code (1947) evolved (Polit and Beck, 2020). This code protects the rights of the participants, ensuring that their involvement in the study is voluntary, and informed consent is obtained (Polit and Beck, 2020). These principles were further developed by the World Medical Assembly and in 1962 with the production of the Declaration of Helsinki (Gelling, 2015a). This highlighted that conducting research involving people must be undertaken within the boundaries of specific ethical and moral principles to protect the confidentiality and privacy of those involved (Gelling, 2015a). The Declaration of Helsinki was updated in 2000 and stated that the four principles that ethical research must include were autonomy (respecting the rights of the individual), beneficence (doing good), non-maleficence (not doing harm), and justice (fairness and equity) (Gelling, 2015a). Adhering to these principles ensures that the researcher places participants at the heart of society and above the interests of the study itself (Gelling, 2015a). Ultimately, the health, privacy and dignity of the participant must always be protected (NMC, 2018; Beauchamp and Childress, 2019; Parahoo, 2014).

This study was designed and conducted using these key ethical principles (Polit and Beck, 2020; LoBiondo-Wood, 2018). According to Gray (2018) as action research is embedded in the social structure of the organisation, failure to defer to the policies and procedures within the organisation would negatively affect any effort to instigate change. Badger (2000) highlighted that due to its collaborative approach, action research demonstrates minimal ethical issues. Conversely, Lathlean (cited in Badger, 2000) argued that due to the complex nature of action research and often involving qualitative and quantitative approaches, this causes participants to become confused and jaded due to the protracted nature of the process. Gray (2018) highlighted that action research as any other research requires to adhere to the key ethical principles. Strategies to protect the key ethical principles were upheld throughout the duration of the study and will be detailed in relevant sections.

UWS ethics approval (Appendix 12), NHS Letter of access (Appendix 13), and NHS research and development approval (Appendix 14) were granted by the end of 2016. As a result of statutory Supervision of Midwives being withdrawn from UK legislation, the researcher (an appointed SoM until this date) was required to obtain a research passport from the NHS Health Board (Appendix 15 complete this study).

4.5 Phases and cycles of PAR

A range of quantitative and qualitative data collection methods were used over the phases and cycles in the PAR study. Table 4.1 summarises the range of data collection methods, actions and participants involved. Each phase of the study will be presented in more detail in the relevant section.

Table 4-1: Phases and cycles in the PAR study

Phases of PAR	Actions	Participants/ Documents
Phase 1 Exploration		
<p>Aim: Inform the development of assessment tool to review the quality of midwifery documentation (in line with NMC professional standards).</p>	<p>One full day to include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - World Café - Nominal Group Technique 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Expert Working Group (n=19) - Lead Midwife for Education - Practice Development Director - NHS Executive Director of Nursing - Consultant Midwife - Maternity Service Manager - LSA Midwifery Officer - Supervisor of midwives (n=13) - Lead Supervisor (observer/ supporter)
Finalise the development of first draft of assessment tool to review midwifery documentation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Developed DOC Learning Tool for Phase 2. - Agreed 'Content' validity and 'construct' validity of DOC Learning Tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EWG - Researcher
Gain approval for the study.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Gained UWS Ethics committee and NHS Research and Development 	Researcher
Phase 2 Intervention		
Preparation for Cycle 1		
<p>Overall aim of Cycle 1: Plan pilot of the DOC Learning Tool</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Prepare sample of anonymised case notes 	<p>Risk Management midwife Action Research Subgroup Researcher/statistician</p>
	<p>Initial statistical plan:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Principal component analysis and factor analysis calculated for sample size. - Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin - sampling adequacy test 	<p>Statistician Criteria (three): Red (n=100); amber (n=100); and green (n=100) Practising midwives (n=100)</p>

Phases of PAR	Actions	Participants/ Documents
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Cronbach's alpha index - Internal consistency - Kappa and Kendall coefficient - inter-rater agreement 	Sample of n=300 case notes (i.e., 100 red, 100 amber and 100 green)
	<p>Revised statistical plan: Mainly descriptive statistics. One inferential statistical test i.e., One-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)</p>	Statistician/researcher 15 midwives to review 4 x case note samples. Include second amber criteria (i.e. four criteria).
<p>(PAR Cycles 1-4) Pilot, test, review and amend the DOC Learning Tool</p>	Quantitative and Qualitative research approaches	Statistician/researcher Participants (15 midwives per cycle) Action Research Sub-group (representation from EWG)
<p>(PAR Cycles 2-4) Aim: Pilot the draft DOC Learning Tool with follow up review, reflection, and amendments (as required through on-going evaluation).</p>	<p>Spirals of activity i.e., involve, plan, act, observe and re-plan.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Agreed clinical patient records - Participant briefing sessions for recruitment - Descriptive statistics - testing DOC Learning Tool Focus groups using Braun and Clarke (2006) - Thematic Analysis Framework. 	Participants/ sample case notes scoring DOC Learning Tool: Cycle 1 (n=15):60 sample case notes Cycle 2 (n=14):56 sample case notes Cycle 3 (n=12):48 sample case notes Cycle 4 (n=15):60 sample case notes Total sample case notes reviewed (n= 224) Participants (n=9)
<p>Triangulation of multiple methods</p>	EWG Action Research Subgroup Focus Groups Testing	

4.6 PHASE ONE (EXPLORATION)

An overview of the phases of the research project was provided in section 4.3. The exploration phase of the project is now presented in more detail. Through action research there is an epistemological necessity for collaboration in the interpretation of data. It involves exploration, intervention, and evaluation phases. Change is more difficult to happen when it is from the top down so that it is important that interventions are tailor made with the involvement of the practitioners. Receiving clinicians' views is an important component of action research. However, Polit and Beck (2020) state that although action research can be seen as more qualitative than quantitative both approaches are appropriate. Gray (2018) supports this highlighting that both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection may be utilised in action research.

The first phase (exploration phase) of the action research process involved establishing an expert working group and development of a mechanism for reviewing documentation that was fit for purpose. A group of experts agreed to review the existing documentation review learning tool (Appendix 16). Representatives invited to join the Expert Working Group (EWG) are detailed in Table 4.1. The EWG were invited to attend a full day workshop to examine and develop the learning tool currently used to review the quality of documented evidence of care provided by midwives (Appendix 17).

The full day workshop was conducted using a World Café (World Café Foundation, 2015) approach which was facilitated by the researcher. The workshop was video recorded. The EWG were asked to examine the existing mechanism against each of the four main statements in The NMC Code (NMC, 2015).

- a) Prioritising People
- b) Practise Effectively
- c) Preserve Safety
- d) Promote Professionalism and trust

World Café (World Café Foundation, 2015) events are informal events, which allow the participants to explore issues in a relaxed environment. The World Café is an interesting process using social interaction or technology to engage individuals and groups in meaningful conversation (Coghlan and Brydon-Miller, 2014). The approach uses a well-controlled format to establish conversations and engages stakeholders in meaningful dialogue to identify and shape directions for future action. The facilitator encourages discussion between participants and ensures everyone's opinion is heard. In this study, participants were moved between tables each with a different focus for discussion led by a facilitator and this approach meant that each aspect of the existing mechanism was examined, then mapped against the new Code (NMC, 2015). During the session, individual representatives of the EWG were encouraged to write down any further comments, questions, or highlighted issues on individual 'Post-Its' under the four main statements of the NMC Code (NMC, 2015). These comments, questions or highlighted issues were collated and reviewed (see Appendices 18 and 19).

The next step was to revise the list by formulating an updated list of comments, questions, or highlighted issues. The EWG then ranked the revised list utilising a nominal group technique (McMurray, 1994, Foth et al., 2016; Harvey and Holmes, 2012). The nominal group process is a structured approach to gain group consensus on the relative importance of problems, issues or potential solutions following group brainstorming and including all group members. It is an approach used by healthcare professionals and nursing educators to glean 'the profession's collective knowledge' (Foth et al., 2016). This approach needs to be well structured and tightly controlled to add robustness in the process to gain professional consensus and generating priority information (McMurray, 1994; Harvey and Homes, 2012;). This can be an effective method to gain consensus involving clinical experts on creating a priority list of factors for the subsequent Participatory Action Research Group (Harvey and Holmes, 2012).

Team members begin the process by writing down their ideas, then selecting which idea each of the participants feel is best. This process was repeated until consensus of the main criteria was established. The participants agreed 100% content validity of the new mechanism on the day (100%) (Polit and Beck, 2020). A modified nominal group technique was then used where each member

examined the 'Post-its' silently and added any further comments/ideas. As per nominal group protocol (McMurray, 1994; Foth et al., 2016; Polit and Beck, 2020), a round robin discussion was conducted involving all EWG representatives. In turn, each representative was asked to highlight a main point which was then further discussed by the EWG.

The five main discussion points were:

- 1) Rationale – giving evidence, for using or not using guidelines.
- 2) Professionals- promoting trust, role modelling for students, multi-professional working.
- 3) Person centredness- evidence of individual care, evidence of care planning.
- 4) Safe standard of care, safe evidence-based practice, how this is evidenced.
- 5) Communication – Situation, Background, Assessment, Recommendation (SBAR), Data Exchange (DATEX), standardisation of escalating care - clear process, identify constraints.

Following this discussion, a list of statements was produced containing 38 Post-it notes numbered, 1-38 with the facilitator then reading out each item in turn. The EWG were then individually asked to vote their top 10 statements on the paper provided. The scores on the list of statements were then tallied up and a new list formulated. Statements receiving less than four votes were removed from the list. The facilitator then asked the EWG to review the 'discarded' list and review the new list, ensuring that all pertinent topics had been covered. Subsequently, the facilitator invited the EWG to re-vote on their top ten statements. One Post-it was reinstated to the new list following the review, making a total of 26 statements. This process continued until 16 key statements remained (each receiving three votes or more from the EWG members). Table 4.2 presents these key statements in descending order in relation to votes described as a 'thermometer' with the 'hottest' topic at the top, with the greatest number of votes (8) and the 'coolest' topic at the bottom with the lowest number of votes (3).

Table 4-2:Nominal group voting

Number	Question/Comments (Top 16)	Score
1.	Has a timely and appropriate referral been made following assessment and documented within relevant paperwork?	8 votes
2.	Evidence of discussion around risks / benefits of care been undertaken relevant to woman's uniqueness.	7 votes
3.	Evidence of escalating concern.	7 votes
4.	Is there evidence to reflect rationale for decision around further reviews / subsequent plan of care?	7 votes
5.	Evidence that woman involved in planning of pregnancy journey demonstrated through use of woman's own words.	6 votes
6.	Changes to birth plan clearly recorded with rationale and demonstration of woman's understanding through recording of her own words.	6 votes
7.	Individualised care recorded showing evidence of informed consent and demonstration of woman's understanding.	6 votes
8.	Documented evidence that individual needs of the woman is clear in her plan of care.	6 votes
9.	How do we measure the documentation of multidisciplinary communication and appropriate escalation?	6 votes
10.	Excellent care as opposed to excellent account.	6 votes
11.	Identify inadequate time, resources staff.	6 votes
12.	Integrity-evidence of situation that is causing delay- truths.	5 votes
13.	All records appropriately completed within the different mediums i.e., case notes / online etc.	5 votes
14.	Was evidence-based care utilised in line with local policies / guidelines?	5 votes
15.	Clear recording of discussions with women of changes to planned care. Woman's understanding demonstrated by use of her own words.	4 votes
16.	Does the documentation indicate difficulties in communication relating to options for and delivery of care?	3 votes

Underpinning all discussions on the day was the importance of developing a mechanism to review the quality of midwifery documentation that would be meaningful and 'user friendly' for the midwives. It was deemed necessary to encourage the midwives to reflect on and learn from their clinical documentation through the process of reflection, situated learning and peer support. Furthermore, it was essential that this new mechanism encompassed all the NMC (2015) professional standards required of nurses and midwives in their everyday practice.

The statements from the Nominal Group Technique informed the development of the new mechanism to review midwifery documentation. This mechanism would demonstrate the NMC (2015) standards: i.e., **D**ocumented care accurately; provided **O**ngoing risk assessed (patient safety) and **C**ommunicated care effectively with all disciplines. Based on these key standards, the new mechanism was subsequently named the DOC Learning Tool (**Figure 4.2**).

Figure 4.2: Formation of DOC Learning Tool

4.7 The DOC Learning Tool

The DOC Learning Tool was developed following the detailed and intricate process described in Phase One. The development and design of the review mechanism needed to be effective and efficient and take account of the following key priorities:

- Key outcomes, based on NMC standards (NMC, 2015), recommended by the EWG (Phase one) for inclusion in the review Tool.
- Adhere to the key purpose of the review Tool i.e., **D**ocumented care is accurately; provided **O**ngoing risk assessed (patient safety) is evident and **C**ommunicated care effectively with all disciplines is demonstrated.
- Practical recommendation to keep the review tool concise and user friendly for practitioners.
- Ensure the review Tool is meaningful and supportive (not punitive) to continually develop nurses and midwives in their everyday professional practice.

Figure 4.3 and Figure 4.4 presents the developed DOC Learning Tool. Testing and further development of the DOC Learning Tool was central to the Intervention phase of the PAR design.

The DOC Learning Tool displayed the NMC professional standards in The Code (NMC, 2015) on the left-hand side of the tool. The criteria to assess the quality of case note documentation was agreed by the EWG in Phase One.

<p>The DOC Tool is a peer review tool to critically examine all forms of record keeping to assess if the practitioner has:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Documented care accurately Ongoing risk assessed (patient safety) Communicated patient care effectively with all disciplines <p>Instructions: Please tick only one box for each Documentation Criteria Documentation Number (please circle the set of notes you reviewed): SWHMR 1 / SWHMR 2 / SWHMR 3 / SWHMR 4</p>					
The NMC Standards	Documentation Criteria	N/A	YES	Missing on 1 occasion	NO or missing on ≥ 2 occasions
PRIORITISING PEOPLE	Evidence that the woman is involved in her care planning				
	Changes to plan of care clearly documented including rationale and action plan				
	Evidence of consent noted throughout all documentation				
PRACTICE EFFECTIVELY	Evidence of appropriate risk assessment				
	Evidence of referral and appropriate involvement of the multidisciplinary team				
	All records completed appropriately (**see record checklist)				
	Only NHS Board approved abbreviations used				
	CHI numbers on drug Kardex's: all records including electronic versions				
	Timely (as per NMC guidelines) and appropriate referral made and documented				
PRESERVE SAFETY	Evidence of rationale for decision around further reviews and plan of care				
	Factual account only, no personal opinions				
PROMOTES PROFESSIONALISM AND TRUST					
Total Score (for use of researcher only)					

Figure 4.3:DOC Learning Tool for Cycle 1 (Quantitative data)

DOC Score <i>(what the red, amber, green means)</i>	
All Green	Very well done. Keep up the good work. All professional standards on record keeping met (NMC, 2015)
Yellow x 1	Some areas for improvement required to your documentation.
Red x 1 or Yellow x 2	Some major areas of concern, please contact your Supervisor of Midwives (SOM) to discuss your documentation. A copy of this DOC tool will be forwarded to your named SOM.

Comments on using the DOC tool (please leave any comments you wish about using the tool)

Figure 4.4:DOC Learning Tool for Cycle 1 (Scoring and Qualitative data)

4.8 Validity and reliability of the DOC Learning Tool

Ensuring validity and reliability of a measurement tool is crucial to any experiment (Polit and Beck, 2020). However, tools can be reliable without being valid to the subject under experiment, so care needs to ensure that the tool is both reliable and valid related to the aim (Polit and Beck, 2020).

Rattray and Jones (2007) highlight that validation of the measurement tool is important to ensure it is measuring what it is supposed to do. They highlight several different methods of validity that are appropriate to this study, face validity, content validity and construct validity. Content validity and construct validity of the DOC Learning Tool was agreed by the EWG in Phase One. The new tool was constructed following a rudimentary approach to factor analysis confirming construct validity (Polit and Beck, 2020). Different criteria on the DOC Learning Tool linked together under the four pillars of the NMC Code (NMC, 2015). The EWG confirmed face validity of the DOC Learning Tool. Although subjective, face validity is confirmation that the DOC Learning Tool is relevant to the practitioner that will be using it and is clear and precise (Rattray and Jones, 2007). However, in keeping with Action Research, multiple cycles of refinement / development of the tool, would be required through the testing and retesting process. Testing and retesting is crucial when the tool is being used to measure changes to practice (Rattray and Jones, 2007). Inter rater reliability would be estimated calculating the percentage of agreement between the raters. Triangulation of multiple methods is detailed in Section 4.21. Validity, reliability, testing, and retesting is further discussed in Chapter 5. The next section will detail the testing and retesting involved during the Intervention phase of this study.

4.9 Phase Two (Intervention)

The second phase of the action research (intervention phase) involved testing the DOC Learning Tool. This phase is described as spirals of activity, where periods of planning, acting, observing, and re-planning happen (Gray, 2018). Initial detailed planning was necessary prior to the spirals of activity were commenced to test the DOC Learning Tool.

Testing involved the participants reviewing and scoring anonymised documentation samples and commenting on experiences and viewpoints of using the DOC Learning Tool. Quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection were used. Following ethical and research and development approval from the targeted Health Board, data collection for Cycle One commenced in 2017. Preparation, selection and anonymisation of the case note samples was a key preparatory phase prior to proceeding with the intervention. Thereafter, the quantitative arm of the study involved testing and retesting the DOC Learning Tool (four cycles in total). The qualitative arm involved collating subjective experiences and viewpoints from the participants following testing of the DOC Learning Tool.

4.10 Recruitment strategy

According to Gray (2018), negotiating access can be straightforward in action research, especially if the researcher is affiliated with the organisation. However, Coghlan and Brannick (2009) warned that conducting research in one's own organisation is political and may be interpreted by some as manipulative. Gray (2018) states that it is important for the researcher to be open and honest about what they are trying to achieve and inform the participants about the participatory nature of the study explaining they will be co-researchers and not subjects. In addition, the researcher needs to ensure participants are aware that the study process will not be a single episode but will be protracted and involve cycles of change (Parahoo, 2014). Although action research is seen as inclusive and democratic (Gray, 2018), Parahoo (2014) argues that there is potential for conflict and power struggles between the researcher and the participants as well as amongst participants themselves.

Permission to access to approach the midwives from the targeted health board midwives was granted from the Head of Midwifery. As the researcher was employed as a SoM (until April 2017) in the targeted Health Board, cognisance of the political influence the researcher could have on the participants was acknowledged. Therefore, the researcher did not directly approach participants and an email was sent out centrally from the targeted health board inviting individual midwives to take part in this study.

4.11 The participants

Purposive sampling was used to identify potential participants for the intervention phase of the study. Purposive sampling is useful when the researcher chooses the target population and sometimes the participants to elicit the necessary information (Parahoo, 2014). To meet the aim of the study (Section 2.10) , the target population required to be qualified midwives working in clinical practice. The targeted Health Board was chosen due to the affiliation the researcher had with that Health Board (discussed in Section 4.12). The sample of participants was a cross section of all midwives working in this clinical location, from a population of 404 midwives, irrespective of years qualified or if hospital or community based. It was important to the researcher and for the ethos of action research (McNiff, 2017) that participants volunteered for the study. Ongoing recruitment was required over the study to maintain the sample size due to retirement / staff changes.

To protect the ethical principles of beneficence and non-maleficence, participants need to be fully informed of the benefits and risks of taking part in the study to prevent them from harm, discomfort, or exploitation (Polit and Beck, 2020). In action research it is easier for the participants to recognise the benefit of the study as they are co-producers (McNiff and Whitehead, 2011).

Each midwife was sent a recruitment pack which contained participant information sheets (with contact details), consent form and a copy of the draft DOC Learning Tool (Appendices 20-22). Midwives were given opportunity to ask questions either by email (to the researcher) or at the information sessions. It was explained to the midwives that the purpose of the research was to promote good

practice by developing a more effective and reliable mechanism to review the quality of documentation of care provided by midwives. McNiff (2017) highlighted that due to the complex nature of action research it is important that potential participants are clear what they consented to. The midwives were given two weeks to decide to participate in the study. Rees (2011) states that it is important to give participants time to respond. Participants emailed / telephoned to book sessions to take part in the study. One follow-up email reminder was sent out and the target sample was achieved.

Written participant consent (Appendix 20) was obtained after the information session. This time allowed potential participants to ask further questions and decide if they wanted to take part (Rees, 2011). In addition, this session provided the researcher the opportunity to discuss the study in more depth and confirm that participation was voluntary. No obvious risks to the potential participants were identified by the researcher and no participant raised any concerns with the researcher or the Director of Studies / Lead Supervisor throughout the duration of the study. The quantitative and qualitative aspects of the study were not anticipated to raise any concerns. Polit and Beck (2020) indicate that all researchers undergoing qualitative research should be vigilant for any issues that may arise and be prepared for them.

Once midwives consented to participate, they received a personal copy of the consent form (Appendix 20) and the researcher retained another copy. Participants were informed that they have the right to withdraw at any time without any prejudice. However, they were also informed if they decided to take part in the focus groups then their contribution would not be able to be removed (Parahoo, 2014).

At the onset of the study, it was planned for 15 participants to be involved in the intervention phase of the study. Overall, 24 midwives participated across the four cycles of the study of which nine participants were involved in the focus groups. Parahoo (2014) states that the degree of real participation in action research varies according to the aims of individual projects. Participation ranges from token, minimal, to full. Midwifery experience ranged from one year to thirty-five

years and all participants were familiar with completing clinical case note documentation in everyday practice.

To ensure an ethical approach was taken to the research, keeping participants informed of the progress of the study was imperative (Gray, 2018). To maintain this communication throughout the study, the researcher met regularly with the Action Research Sub-Group. This subgroup comprised five midwives drawn from the participants recruited to the study. The Action Research Sub-Group met regularly to discuss the progress of the study and maintain communication links between the researcher and participants (McNiff and Whitehead, 2011).

Furthermore, Meyer and Cooper (2015) highlighted that within action research it is not only ethical approval that is important but also necessary to agree a code of ethical practice with the participants involved. McNiff (2017) concurs, advocating that the participants are not just subjects within action research but co-researchers and co-producers. Therefore, participants were kept informed and engaged in the study progress including access to research findings as these emerged.

Protection of anonymity and confidentiality throughout the research process are key ethical principles that need to be considered (Parahoo, 2014). Confidentiality and maintaining the identity of participants are paramount. Polit and Beck (2020) emphasised that participant anonymity is addressed so that their identity cannot be linked to any responses.

The researcher allocated code numbers to identify participants in testing the learning tool to ensure anonymity and confidentiality was maintained. Only the researcher knew of the link between the code numbers and the identity of participants. This information was stored on a password - protected computer. In qualitative data collection methods, pseudonyms / numbers were used to protect the identity of the participants (Gray, 2018). Anonymity of participants was not possible due to the participatory nature of action research data collection methods. However, during the focus groups consensus was agreed between the participants about respecting individual views and confidentiality of the discussions.

4.12 The researcher

In this section the role of the researcher within this action research project is explored. As explained already the researcher was a Supervisor of Midwives within the targeted NHS Board until April 2017. They had also been a clinical midwife / senior midwife within the targeted Health Board for twenty years before leaving to become a lecturer practitioner at a local Further Education Institution (FEI) (which became a Higher Education Institution (HEI) from 2007) in 2006, and then full-time lecturer since 2007. Positionality is considered first.

4.12.1 Positionality

Coghlan and Brydon-Miller (2014) highlights that it is necessary for the researcher to consider their position with the community, organisation, or participants at each stage of the action research study. The researcher taught on pre-registration and post-registration midwifery programmes since starting in 2006. Therefore, they knew a large proportion of the midwives who worked in the Health Board, through working with them as clinical colleagues or from teaching them on the midwifery programmes.

The three main positions the researcher can adopt are described as insider action research, participatory action research and outsider (action science) action research (Gray, 2018). Insider action research is to examine one's own practice or one's own organisation (Gray, 2018). Although, the researcher cannot deny that their experiences and professional practice may have had an influence on the participants (mentioned in Section 4.12.4), the researcher would require to be a clinical midwife within the organisation being examined (Gray, 2018). Although the researcher had worked with the participants in the past and at the time of the onset of study was still a Supervisor of Midwives (SoM) within the organisation. Furthermore, they were not working as a clinical midwife providing direct patient care and therefore were not using the clinical documentation on a daily basis, which would be required for the aim of this study. However, the researcher is a midwife, has a detailed knowledge of the topic under study, and therefore could be classed as an insider researcher.

PAR involves the researcher and participants being involved in a partnership (Parahoo, 2014). Partnership with individuals who share a common interest. It can involve collaborative partnerships with outsider (in this case the researcher) and insiders (the clinical midwives). Collaborative work between the researcher (outsider) who invited the midwives to develop a new learning tool to examine documentation. Data collected from the participants' experiences of using the learning tool, which fitted well with the principles of PAR. Furthermore, mutual interest between researcher and midwives existed to develop a tool (Gray, 2018).

Traditional social science research is closely related to outsider (third person) action research. Where outsiders examine the effects of action research projects alongside critically examine action research methodology (Gray, 2018). Although outsider research is not the focus of this study, some cognisance is taken of the critical examination of how different approaches to learning affect midwives and impacts on their clinical practice and therefore features of outsider action research are apparent. This is explored within the discussion section of this thesis (Chapter 6). The sharing of control between researcher and participants was fundamental to this study and therefore a key difference between choosing the position of PAR and action science (Gray, 2018).

4.12.2 Researcher bias

Arguments for and against the researcher undertaking research in a familiar setting are widely reported in the literature (Whitehead and Niff, 2011; Gray, 2014; Parahoo, 2014; Meyer and Cooper, 2015; Polit and Beck, 2020). Main issues highlighted are concerns regarding objectivity and bias with the researcher not being able to keep their distance from the project (Gray, 2014; Polit and Beck, 2020). Although these are genuine concerns, they are no different from many qualitative studies (Smith, Mackay, and McCulloch, 2013). Furthermore, to conduct research in a familiar setting with knowledge of the organisation, same culture and background is an advantage due to the participatory nature of action research as it helps gain the trust of the participants (Whitehead and Niff, 2011; Meyer and Cooper, 2015). To reduce the element of bias, one researcher supervisor attended each of the focus groups.

4.12.3 Reliability and validity

To validate and improve reliability of the results, the researcher needs to involve other people in reviewing the results (McNiff and Whitehead, 2011). Sometimes within action research, the researchers and participants have equal control of the results. However, for this project, and most action research projects, there is a lead researcher who has this control (Gray, 2018). With this control means that it is the responsibility of the lead researcher to glean feedback from the participants to confirm the authenticity of the findings (Gray, 2018). For the quantitative phase of the research, the results were viewed by the researcher's supervisors and a statistician. Transcripts and audio recordings were shared with one member of each focus group to confirm accuracy of transcripts. Smith, Mackay, and McCulloch (2013) confirm that it is important to present the participants with data before analysis to minimise undue influence. In this study, the raw data was presented to one participant from each focus group. Then the researcher met with the participant to confirm findings ensuring member checking (Jolley, 2020). Participants were given the opportunity to view the data after each cycle.

Reason, Bradbury, and Sage (2008) argues that instead of policing research, validity involves examining the practical, political and the moral issues. Quality of action research involves not about getting it right but ensuring that questions about choices made are addressed. What choices were made and why and being transparent about these choices during the write up of the thesis (Reason, Bradbury, and Sage, 2006).

4.12.4 Researcher influence

It is important that the researcher provides evidence that they did not influence to coerce participants into taken part in their study (Parahoo, 2014). As already mentioned, (Section 4.12.1), the researcher was a Supervisor of Midwives, employed as a Supervisor within NHS Board and also taught many of the midwives employed and was known to participants. Initial recruitment to take part in the second phase of the action research study was by email, which ensured that the midwives were free to decline or take part in the study to avoid any influence to take part in the study. If during the study any conflict arose; the

researcher would have declared this to the academic supervisor. No conflicts were raised for the duration of the study.

The researcher engaged with the participants throughout the action research study therefore difficult to confirm that they did not influence the participants. Gray (2018) highlights that this is a problem in action research. However, Reason, Bradbury, and Sage (2008, p.4) state that this is not necessary in action research as it is defined as a “*a participatory process*”. In fact, many authors see relationship building between researcher and participants as being beneficial (Hart and Bond, 1996; Waterman et al., 2010; McNiff and Whitehead, 2011).

To minimise risk of influencing results participants completed learning tools on their own, placing them in a sealed envelope for the attention of the researcher. Furthermore, the focus groups were conducted by the researcher, with lead supervisor or supervisor present to ensure that no influence was exerted on the participants.

4.12.5 Reflection and reflexivity

Reflexivity is an instrumental part of action research (McNiff, 2017). According to Meyer and Cooper (2015), it is an important process to enhance the rigour of studies and to provide a detailed map the personal journey that the action researcher undergoes throughout the research process. The researcher documented their own actions, values and perceptions using a personal diary (Appendix 23). A reflective section is also included after every cycle (Section 5.5.4, Section 5.6.4, Section 5.7.4, and Section 5.8.4

4.13 The case note samples

The Risk Management midwife identified the selected samples from real patient case notes. These casenote samples came from cases that the Risk Manager had been reviewing during clinical incident reviews. These patient case notes were then sent to administrative staff to anonymise the sample of case notes before emailing them to the researcher. This anonymisation was a crucial step necessary to protect data protection. The Action Research Sub-Group agreed on the selection of the sample of case notes and met to confirm how each set of

case notes would be coded into categories. Four case note samples were agreed and included 'green' (all information was correct); 'red' (at least one major documentation error on the case note sample from the red category of the DOC Learning Tool); 'Amber 1' (one documentation error on the case note sample from the amber category of the DOC Learning Tool). Following discussion with Statistician it was also agreed to include one further amber category, 'Amber 2' (two documentation errors on the case note sample from the amber category of the DOC Learning Tool). A sample of the categorised / anonymised case notes are found in Appendix 21.

4.14 Scoring using the DOC Learning Tool

Midwife participants reviewed and scored the four anonymised case notes (Appendix 24 using the DOC Learning Tool (one for each case note sample) (Figure 4.3 and 4.4). Participants scored criteria as being Red, Amber or Green depending on their review findings. Not Applicable (NA) box was scored for some criteria. Midwives were already familiar with a similar RAG format used within the Modified Early Obstetric Warning Scoring system. Each participant was asked to read through the four case note samples and then score each case note sample against an individual DOC Learning Tool. Reviewing the documentation criteria and placing a tick in either the not applicable, green, red, or amber boxes.

- Green, if the midwife assessed that the criteria had been fully addressed throughout the case note sample.
- Amber, if the midwife assessed that the criteria had not been addressed on one occasion.
- Red, if the midwife assessed that the criteria had not been addressed on two or more occasions or altogether.

At the end of the documentary review process each midwife participant had scored four different case note samples and would have completed four DOC Learning Tools (one from each case note sample).

The researcher collated the completed DOC Learning Tools from the midwife participants for statistical testing and analysis. To ensure anonymity, no names were identified on any documentation. Only the researcher, research supervisors and statistician had access to the data to preserve confidentiality. Furthermore, no participants were identified from the returned DOC Learning Tools. The researcher allocated a participation number for statistical purposes only. All paper copies of the DOC Learning Tools were retained in a locked drawer within the researcher's workplace for the study duration with plans to be destroyed on submission of the study.

4.15 Quantitative data

Planning the quantitative data collection and analysis for the Intervention phase with the statisticians was a timely and detailed process. This resulted in an initial statistical plan which over time evolved into the final plan for the PAR cycles. Given the nature of action research, it is important to provide information on this changing statistical direction for the testing of the DOC Learning Tool. Chapter 5 provides information on the findings of the study with more detail in the evolving and changing process for the testing of the DOC Learning Tool.

4.16 Initial statistical plan

- The sample size for principal component analysis and factor analysis had been calculated by number of observations multiplied by number of items or variables (e.g., 10-15 participants for each item on the DOC Learning Tool (Field, 2013). However, many statistical manuals indicate a sample size of 300 as adequate for principal component analysis and factor analysis (Rouquette and Falissard, 2011; Tabachnick and Fidell, 2012). The initial study sample size of 300 case note documents was identified i.e., with three criteria: Red (n=100); Amber (n=100); Green (n=100) categories.
- A sampling adequacy test (Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin) was planned to check that the data collected was sufficient to undertake meaningful principal component analysis. If the test result fell below the required, critical level of 0.05, then a decision would be made about collecting more data or refining the data analysis plan.

- To test the reliability and validity of the DOC Learning Tool. Stability, internal consistency, and inter-rater agreement on the score of the tool was required. Internal consistency planned to be assessed using Cronbach's alpha index and inter-rater agreement by Kappa and Kendall coefficient (Grove, Burns and Gray, 2013).

The Expert Working Group (EWG) had already rated scored and agreed the content validity of the DOC Learning Tool.

4.17 Revised statistical plan:

Following discussions with different statisticians the original statistical plan was changed to pilot the case note samples and DOC Learning Tool before undergoing full testing with 300 samples required for principal component analysis and factor analysis.

- Participants (15 midwives per cycle) with each to review 4 x case note samples i.e., each cycle to test the DOC Learning Tool over 60 sample case notes.
- DOC Learning Tool to include second amber criteria (i.e., increased to four criteria).

Inferential statistic test using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). This was to compare the results across the four cycles, as this is the preferred test to use when comparing more than two groups (Grove and Ciper,2017). All other testing used descriptive analysis presented as follows.

- The numerical data were presented in the form of mean, standard deviation, median and interquartile range (Grove, Burns and Gray, 2013).
- The visual presentation included histogram or boxplot to show the distribution and variations including outliers. The categorical data are presented in the form of frequency and percentages as well as histograms for visual data presentation. Figure 4.5 represents the four PAR cycles in pictorial form.

Figure 4.5: Pictorial representation of the four cycles of PAR

4.18 Qualitative Data

Qualitative data were collated from the open text box comments in the DOC Learning Tool and from focus group interviews with midwife participants.

4.19 Focus Group interviews

The action research process involves collaboration and discussion with the participants to help the researcher move forward with the aim and objectives of the study (Gray, 2018). One key advantage of a focus group is the opportunity offered to participants to share their viewpoints and experiences, discuss and debate issues in depth with others (Gray, 2018). Focus groups are different from group interviews as the idea is to generate discussions between participants and promote self-disclosure (Goodman and Evans, 2015) During focus groups, participants can achieve 'light-bulb' moments when listening to the experiences of others and the ideas generated through discussions (Lindof and Taylor, 2002 cited in Gray, 2018).

Three focus group discussions were conducted following PAR cycles two, three and four to capture the participants experiences and viewpoints of using the DOC Learning Tool (Appendix 22). All participants involved in the testing process of each PAR cycle were invited to participate in the related focus groups as part of the initial invitation to the study (Appendix 21). According to many authors the ideal numbers of participants would be between four and twelve to generate discussion (Parahoo, 2014; Gray, 2018; Polit and Beck, 2020). However, Goodman and Evans (2015) highlighted it is not the number of participants, but the quality of the discussion related to the study aim, which is the most important. Gray (2018) emphasised that if participants are comfortable with the researcher and with each other, then the size of the focus group becomes less important. Also, if the group is too large then participants may feel reluctant to discuss any sensitive issues (Gray, 2018). Homogenous groups (such as midwife participants in this study) are generally preferable to ensure free discussion amongst participants and enable comparison between focus groups (Goodman and Evans, 2015). However, Kitzinger and Barbour (1999) warned that groups where participants are very familiar with each other may resort to their normal

hierarchies, meaning some participants might be reluctant to participate. Therefore, the group dynamic and equitable flow of discussion required careful moderation (Gray, 2018).

A semi-structured interview schedule (Appendix 25) was planned to generate discussion amongst the participants (Grove, Gray and Burns, 2013). This approach facilitated participants to share their experiences, perceptions, and viewpoints about using the DOC Learning Tool. Whilst the facilitator still had some structure to maintain focus on the purpose of the discussion group, prompt questions were introduced to further explore responses and viewpoints. The researcher obtained informed consent from each participant prior to attending the focus group. Permission was also obtained at the focus group for the session to be audio recorded and to use any anonymised direct quotes to support findings.

The venue for the focus groups were conducted within the Health Board premises at the convenience and preference of the participants where refreshments were provided by the researcher. Conducting the research in the participants' workplace meant they did not have to travel and were familiar with the setting. Grove, Gray and Burns (2015) highlighted that focus groups should take place in a non-threatening, private, and relaxed environment. The focus groups were planned to last no longer than 45 minutes.

4.19.1 Advantages and limitations

Advantages of focus groups include the formal opportunity for participants to provide feedback on any changes (Gerrish and Lathlean, 2015). This is an important factor during action research projects (McNiff and Whitehead, 2011), especially in this present study where comments were being asked about the DOC Learning Tool and any suggestions for improvement. Furthermore, participants may feel less pressured in a focus group setting rather than in a one-to-one interview situation (Gray, 2018). A major advantage of focus groups is that they can be digitally audio recorded and transcribed to enable the researcher time to process the information (Gray, 2018).

Researcher control is another issue during focus groups (Polit and Beck, 2020). An effective focus group is dependent on the researcher's direction of questioning

moving from general to more specific (Polit and Beck, 2020). Goodman and Evans (2015) warned that facilitation of focus groups is difficult. A balance needs to occur between encouraging contributions to discussion without biasing responses. In addition, the facilitator requires to have the ability to refocus the group where required if discussions are dominated by one participant or go off topic (Goodman and Evans, 2015). An observer / note taker was present for all three focus groups and took field notes (Appendix 26). The observer / note taker was able to confirm that the researcher (moderator) did not unduly influence the participants during the discussion.

Although focus groups compliment action research due to the collaborative approach, limitations should be acknowledged. 'Group think' is highlighted as a potential issue in focus groups, with participants conforming to stronger members in the group (Bluff, 2006; Gray, 2018; Polit and Beck, 2020). Gray (2018) also stated that group members can be suspicious of participants that are more knowledgeable. Another limitation of focus groups is transcription of any recordings made may be challenging due to identifying who was talking and at what point in the discussion (Goodman and Evans, 2015). Gray (2018) stated that a combination of field notes by the researcher and the observer / note taker can negate some of the issues that occur during transcription

4.20 Qualitative data analysis

Data collated on the participant viewpoints, experiences and suggestions on the DOC Learning Tool were transcribed from the digital audio recordings (Appendix 27). Additionally, digital audio recordings and transcripts from the focus group were anonymised and stored in a locked drawer within the researcher's workplace. To ensure confidentiality only the researcher, supervisors and transcriber had access to the digital audio recordings and transcripts.

The transcriptions were analysed using the thematic framework by Braun and Clarke (2006). This framework involves the following six steps which provides a consistent, systematic, and robust approach to data analysis.

- Step 1: Become familiar with the data.
- Step 2: Generate initial codes.
- Step 3: Search for themes.
- Step 4: Review themes.
- Step 5: Define themes.
- Step 6: Write-up.

The open ended qualitative written comments recorded by the midwife participants on the DOC Learning Tool were also collated and included as part of this analysis process. The data were analysed to search for recurring patterns emerging from the data (Appendix 28). Once meanings are formulated and interpreted then collated themes and subthemes are identified. Further detail in this

4.21 Triangulation

Triangulation in research combines at least two or more methodological approaches, theoretical perspectives, investigators, data sources, or data analysis methods (Braun and Clarke, 2013). This approach converges information from different sources which can confirm validity, reliability, and generalisability. The intention of triangulation is to increase the researcher's ability and confidence to interpret the findings and gain a more comprehensive understanding of what the findings have revealed. Triangulation using multiple methods can promote more insights about the study findings and negate and counterbalance any deficiency in using a single strategy approach (Braun and Clarke, 2013). Triangulation in this action research was included to seek completeness (McNiff,2017) in the evaluation of the DOC Learning Tool. This related to both the development and usefulness DOC Learning Tool being 'fit for purpose', trustworthy and credible for use in every day professional practice (McNiff,2017). Through the ongoing evaluation in the development of the DOC Learning Tool, the researcher involved each aspect of the PAR research stages in this triangulation process (Figure 4.6).

Figure 4.6: Triangulation: DOC Learning Tool Development and Evaluation

4.22 Data management

All data were protected in line with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (2018) and Data Protection Act (1998) and managed in accordance with the NHS Board Policy for data management (including data collection, storage, retrieval, and disposal). All information about the study was stored on a password protected computer and a password protected encrypted USB. For the study, permission was sought from NHS Board for the Risk Manager (an experienced SoM) to obtain and photocopy four sets of existing case notes. The Risk Manager fully anonymised the case notes prior to the researcher receiving them to protect the identity of any health care providers and any women involved in the care.

4.23 Summary

This chapter provided an overview of the research methods used in this PAR study and set the scene for the phases and cycles involved in the PAR cycles. The ethical considerations and discussed within the context of the methods and participants involved in the study. Initial planned methods including data

collection for the first and second phases of the PAR processes are provided. Given the cyclical nature of PAR, there was ongoing review and action taken to amend and improve the study methods. Action research does not have a definitive end point. Therefore, preliminary discussions were ongoing in late 2019 as to the appropriate time in the PAR to cease data collection and any further statistical testing of the DOC Learning Tool at that time. This decision was confirmed with the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in early 2020. This had a major impact on the routine approaches to everyday clinical practice which in turn negatively impacted on the involvement and collaboration of the NHS workforce. This delay will now be addressed by completing a post-doctoral study to include further testing, full evaluation, final validation of the DOC Learning Tool and further dissemination of findings. The next chapter provides a detailed account of the quantitative and qualitative findings from the four cycles of Phase Two of the PAR study.

CHAPTER 5 RESULTS

5.1 Introduction

The second phase of the action research (Intervention phase) is described as spirals of activity, where periods of planning, acting, observing, and re-planning happen (Gray, 2018). In this phase, the DOC Learning Tool was tested by the participants. This process involved the participants reviewing the sample of case note documents and then scoring the quality using the DOC Learning Tool. Qualitative comments specifically on using the DOC Learning Tool were gathered from focus group interviews and analysed into collective themes. In keeping with action research, multiple Participatory Action Research (PAR) Cycles of refinement / development of the DOC Learning Tool were with the researcher and the Action Research Subgroup with retesting of the DOC Learning Tool carried out following relevant PAR cycles.

This chapter details the research methods used in the PAR Cycles of the intervention phase (Figure 4.5). This includes details of the planning, acting, observing, and re-planning involved following each PAR cycle. Detailed information is provided in relation to the participants and interventions, data collection and data analysis methods adopted for the quantitative and qualitative research approaches. The findings are presented as individual PAR Cycles including a summary of the developmental amendments made based on the findings of each completed PAR cycle and the planned actions carried forward into the next PAR cycle. An overall summary of quantitative and qualitative data is provided

5.2 Data analysis methods

Presentation of the quantitative aspect of the action research study was by descriptive statistics. This was guided and confirmed by the Statistician. Thematic analysis of qualitative data from the focus groups and open-ended comments from the DOC Learning Tool was conducted by the researcher using the Thematic Framework by Braun and Clarke (2006). The quantitative and qualitative processes are described in the following sections.

5.3 Statistical approaches

Descriptive statistics were used to analyse and interpret the testing of the DOC Learning Tool with the sample case note documents across the four PAR cycles.

5.3.1 Descriptive statistics

Grove, Burns and Gray (2013) stated that the most common descriptive statistics used in nursing and health care are categorical data for example mean, standard, and median (Parahoo, 2014). Inter Quartile Range (IQR) are also commonly utilised for numerical data in nursing and health care. Parahoo (2014) warned that modes can be unstable, as they tended to vary across data sets. Gelling (2015a) concurs, stating that when the central values of data are required, the mean and median are more valuable. Although the mean is useful, careful consideration is required due to outlier information, which can skew results (Polit and Beck, 2020). These descriptive statistics have been applied within this study. Noticeably, where outlier information is present (as in Cycle One), then the median score is provided as it was more useful and offered the middle value irrespective of skewed results (Grove, Burns and Gray, 2013).

5.4 Qualitative data

Focus groups were used to collect data for the qualitative component from the study participants. In total, three focus groups (Appendix 27) were conducted with each focus group held following Cycle Two, Three and Four PAR documentary review and scoring of the case note documentation using the DOC Learning Tool. The focus groups were conducted using a semi-structured interview schedule (Appendix 25) to guide the discussions. This was to support meaningful evaluation of the feasibility and usability of the DOC Learning Tool as a mechanism to review the quality of midwifery documentation accurately and consistently. Through the cyclical process, the focus groups highlighted areas for further refinement of the DOC Learning Tool structure and content that was then tested in future cycles.

According to Gerrish and Lathlean (2015), there is no agreed way of analysing qualitative research data. However, the process must be transparent, systematic,

and rigorous (Polit and Beck, 2020). Holloway and Wheeler (2016) highlighted that when analysing focus group interviews the purpose of the analysis must be considered, whether it is 'group think' or individual contribution being considered (Holloway and Wheeler, 2017). The research focus guided the analysis and informed how the data were organised. Whilst individual participant responses were important in this study, collective themes were more useful in relation to the aim of the research (McNiff, 2017). Certainly, the aim of focus groups is to capture the collective views and experiences from all group participants (Gray, 2018). The researcher ensured all participants had opportunity to influence the discussions and add their viewpoints and perceptions about using the DOC Learning Tool to review case note documentation. This ensured rich and detailed data (Appendix 27) were gathered at each focus group and every relevant angle was exhaustively explored.

Gray (2018) identified that analysis of data begins immediately after the focus group has ended. Therefore, after each focus group the audio digital recordings were transcribed verbatim. Furthermore, the observer / notetaker transcribed the focus group field notes for the researcher. Goodman and Evans (2015) highlighted that debriefing with observer / notetaker following the focus group is good practice to compare field notes and discuss the proceedings. The observer should also provide valuable information such as non-verbal cues and group dynamics to inform the interpretation of the data and enhance reflexivity (Bluff, 2006; Gray, 2018). Therefore, for this present study, the researcher met with the observer / notetaker immediately after each focus group to discuss any pertinent points.

Lincoln and Guba (1985) highlighted member checking was crucial to demonstrate credibility and trustworthiness of the research. Gerrish and Lathlean (2015) stated that whilst it was not always practical to ask participants to check the validity of the transcripts following focus groups, it was useful to ask them to endorse the themes created. However, participant involvement including reviewing the data are reported to be an important aspect of the action research process (McNiff and Whitehead, 2011). Therefore, to enhance confirmation of focus group discussions the researcher sent the transcripts to one participant of each of the focus group to confirm accuracy. Following the first focus group, after

reviewing the data and discussion with the observe / notetaker, further clarity was sought from one participant regarding a point they had raised during the session. Polit and Beck (2020) corroborated that member checking can be conducted face to face, through written individual communication or in small groups. Polit and Beck (2020) cautioned that member checking was not always straight forward as participants may be reluctant to take part or be unwilling to disagree with the researcher. Interestingly, Morse et al. (1999) highlighted that it was beyond the participants remit to interpretate the analysis of the researcher. However, given the nature of action research and the triangulation methods used in this study it was important to involve the participants for confirmation and completeness of the qualitative data.

Certainly, many authors agreed that involving participants in the analysis of the data is controversial and against the principle of qualitative enquiry (Parahoo, 2014; Gray, 2018; Polit and Beck, 2020). However, due to the participatory nature of action research (Gray, 2018) the researcher felt that the participants should be able to comment on the accuracy of the transcripts of the focus groups they attended. Irrespective of how the data are analysed it should be immersed in the participants' contribution (Parahoo, 2014). Themes were also shared with the Action Research Subgroup for endorsement. For quality enhancement of the thematic analysis, the supervisory team also peer-reviewed the data and coding of the themes (Appendix 29). This process of investigator triangulation assured the trustworthiness of the coding and analysis of the data (Polit and Beck, 2020). Parahoo (2014) stated that although thematic analysis is regularly used, researchers rarely acknowledge a model or framework used in the analysis process. To enhance auditability and credibility of the findings the researcher produced a detailed account of how the analysis occurred (Polit and Beck, 2020). It is essential that qualitative data analysis is conducted in a meticulous and rigorous way to produce useful and significant results. Braun and Clarke's (2006) approach to thematic analysis was cited by several authors as a structured framework to highlight the steps in the analysis process (Parahoo, 2014; Nowell, Norris and White, 2017; Gray, 2018; Polit and Beck, 2020). Therefore, this thematic analysis framework approach was chosen to undertake the action research data analysis. The process of thematic analysis is detailed in Section 5.7.

Phase two involved the intervention and ongoing evaluation of testing the DOC Learning Tool to review the quality of midwifery case note documentation. The four PAR cycles (plan, act, observe (findings), reflect and re-plan) are now systematically presented.

5.5 Cycle One

5.5.1 Plan

Initially for Cycle One the plan was to sample 300 case note documents to produce measured agreement between raters. This was decided during a supervisory meeting with the researcher, Lead Supervisor and Statistician. This would include 100 midwives each reviewing three sets of case note documents (i.e., 100 sets identified in the Red categories, 100 identified in the Amber categories and 100 identified in the Green categories = total 300 case note documentation). This sample of case note documents was identified from a population of 404 midwives who worked in the targeted Health Board. The initial statistical plan was to conduct inferential statistical tests (Section 4.16).

The approach to data analysis changed following discussions with a new statistician in 2017 (previous statistician had retired). During this meeting, the statistician recommended that this process should be taken slower and multiple refinements of the DOC Learning Tool needed to be completed before wider testing was considered. This guidance fitted in with the cyclical nature of the action research process. Following each cycle, detailed review of the DOC Learning Tool took place with the Action Research Subgroup. The statistician also advised the introduction of a fourth category of scoring (i.e., two amber scores) to allow more scope for scoring by the reviewer. Therefore, it was agreed for the Intervention phase that fifteen participants would now review four sets of anonymised case note documents using the DOC Learning Tool (Appendix 22) (one from each RAG category of scoring). This would potentially result in a sample of 60 completed DOC Learning Tools documents per cycle, which would then be analysed using descriptive statistics.

5.5.2 Act

Fifteen potential participants attended the study briefing sessions resulting in all agreeing to participate in the study. Participants took 45-60 minutes to review the four samples of case note documents and score them using the DOC Learning Tool. Furthermore, participants were invited to provide some written comments about using the DOC Learning Tool in the open-ended text box (Appendix 28). Through Anonymisation of the DOC Learning Tool only the researcher knew the details of each participant and the set of DOC Learning Tools completed.

5.5.3 Observe (quantitative summary)

The fifteen participants scored the four case note documents using the DOC Learning Tool. There was wide variation between the results reported (Appendix 31). Appendix 32 shows key to the scoring) Table 5.1 displays the results in ascending order. Range of scores for inter rater agreement of sample of case note documents reviewed using the DOC Learning Tool by the Action Research Subgroup was 40.97% to 89.55%. Multi Modals (n=2) for 59.09%, 63.64%, 68.18% and 72.73% were present. The mean score was 68.10% and the median 68.18%. Standard deviation being 11.836. One participant scored below 50%, three between 50% and 60%, four between 60% and 70%, five scoring between 70% and 80% and two scoring between 80% and 90%. The highest score was 89.55% with 100% agreement not attained. Figure 5.1 shows a histogram of frequency of distribution of results from PAR Cycle One, demonstrating that the 40.97% was an outlier score. The remainder of the scores sit within a normal curve distribution.

Table 5-1:Results for PAR Cycle One presented in ascending order

Participants														
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Score (%)														
40.97	56.82	59.09	59.09	63.64	63.64	68.18	68.18	70.45	72.73	72.73	75	77.27	84.09	89.55

Figure 5.1:Histogram of frequency distribution of results from PAR Cycle One

Participants did not report any issues in using the DOC Learning Tool. However, as the Health Board had moved to electronic case note documentation, some participants suggested it would be appropriate to now use electronic case note samples to reflect these changes.

5.5.4 Reflect and Action Plan

Initially the researcher had hoped to test 300 case notes (n=100 midwives reviewing 3 case note samples) with three RAG (Red, Amber, Green) criteria. The plan was to pilot the DOC Learning Tool with the discrete purpose of reviewing the process, including sample of written case notes and relevance and completeness of content in relation to the NMC Code (NMC, 2015; 2018). The first piloting process (PAR Cycle One) was to confirm appropriate case note samples and subsequent cycles would test and refine the content of the DOC Learning Tool. If this pilot had not been conducted, then the researcher would not have been aware of any discrepancies with the written case note samples.

However, the pilot sample changed, and it was agreed that 60 case note samples (n=15 midwives reviewing four case notes) was sufficient rather than the initially proposed 300 (n=100 midwives reviewing three case notes). Each midwife would now review case note documentation using the RAG criteria and the DOC Learning Tool.

As there was a significant variation between raters, following discussion with the Lead Supervisor, Action Research Sub-Group and the statistician it was agreed more robust 'cases' for the case note samples were required prior to re-testing with participants. Furthermore, the targeted Health Board had changed to an electronic record system therefore having electronic case note samples reflecting this would be more authentic. In addition, to ascertain if the raters were detecting the same errors as the Action Research Subgroup, they (the raters) were asked to circle errors on printed copies of the anonymised electronic case note documents. An outline of PAR Cycle One and the summary of action points that led to PAR Cycle Two is detailed in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.2: Outline of PAR Cycle One and summary

5.6 Cycle Two

This was the second PAR cycle incorporating the actions arising from Cycle One. This section presents the quantitative and qualitative data following testing of the DOC Learning Tool. This cycle reviewed the new electronic case note samples and functionality of the DOC Learning Tool.

5.6.1 Plan

Planning of PAR Cycle Two had been delayed due to the demise of Supervision of Midwifery from UK Legislation. This meant the researcher was no longer a SoM within the targeted Health Board and had to apply for a Research Passport to continue with the study. This involved a lengthy process with the Research Passport being issued in December 2017 (Appendix 15).

Due to the new electronic record systems within the targeted Health Board the Risk Management Midwife was required to select new samples of electronic case notes. Subsequently these case note samples were anonymised by administrative staff prior to emailing PDF copies to the researcher. The Action Research Subgroup met to agree the selection of the new case note samples (Appendix 33). Recruitment process continued as before.

5.6.2 Act

Data collection for PAR Cycle Two took place between July and August 2018. Fifteen participants agreed to complete the DOC Learning Tools, only fourteen participants returned the completed forms. An email invitation was sent out to all participants who had previously completed a DOC Learning Tool and they agreed to take part in a focus group. It was hoped that six to eight participants would be able to attend.

5.6.3 Observe quantitative and qualitative summaries

The fourteen participants scored the four case note documents using the DOC Learning Tool. Variation between results was still noted (Appendix 34). Table 5.2 displays the results in ascending order. The range was between 59.09% to 88.64% agreement with DOC samples scored by Action Research Subgroup. Mode = 72.73% (n=3), Mean 75.02% and the median score 72.73%. Standard deviation being 8.763. One participant scoring between 50% and 60%, two between 60% and 70%, seven between 70% and 80% and four scoring between 80% and 90%. The highest score in this cycle was 88.64% with 100% agreement still to be attained. Figure 5.3 shows a histogram of the frequency distribution of results from PAR Cycle Two, again, normal distribution curve. No outlier scores were noted.

Table 5-2:Results for PAR Cycle Two presented in ascending order

Participants													
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14
Score (%)													
59.09	63.64	68.18	70.45	70.45	72.73	72.73	72.73	77.27	79.55	84.09	84.09	86.64	88.64

Figure 5.3:Histogram of frequency distribution of results from PAR Cycle Two

Comments on the day indicated that participants found it difficult to navigate through the printed version of the electronic case note samples and would have preferred reviewing case note documents electronically. Also noted by the researchers was a small number of false recorded errors such as missing files / charts (despite participants being informed to assume all charts were included).

For the qualitative data collection process, the first focus group was conducted in March 2019 in a seminar room within the targeted Health Board. In attendance three participants (n=3), field note taker (observer) and the researcher. All participants had completed the DOC Learning Tool previously and consented to take part in a focus group at that time. Participants were offered hospitality on arrival. The researcher used a semi-structured interview schedule with prompt questions (as required) to facilitate group discussion with participants (Appendix 25). The focus group discussions were digitally audio recorded with participant permission. Appendix 27 contains an excerpt of transcripts of the recorded session.

Initial reflections from the participant responses of the focus group indicated that the main themes appeared to be the issue of consent. In the live electronic case notes, practitioners were 'not allowed' to progress through the case notes until they had ticked that box, whereas it was possible to progress through the case-note samples if consent had not been ticked. Participants provided positive comments about using the Red, Amber, and Green (RAG) system when reviewing the case note documents. They felt it was a manageable review tool, concise, easy to use and in line with the NMC Code by focusing on prioritising people, practising effectively, safety and promoting professionalism and trust (NMC, 2015; 2018).

Participants highlighted that the DOC Learning Tool would be useful to enhance their learning and understanding surrounding case note documentation. They recommended that the DOC Learning Tool could be used as peer review, self - review or by managers as part of the annual professional development review. It was also suggested the DOC Learning Tool could have a useful role for midwives in the NMC (2021) three-year revalidation process. This would require individual midwives to invite peers to review their case note documentation and then use this as evidence for revalidation. Participants liked the NMC headings and

categories (NMC, 2018). Although the participants indicated that they liked the use of a RAG system, there was focussed discussion on issues with the 'amber' criteria. This area would need to be explored in subsequent focus groups. Furthermore, more open questions in the interview schedule would have helped participants explore the key areas of the DOC Learning Tool.

One participant indicated that another tool was also being used to review case note documentation, so this issue would need to be followed up by the researcher. Using 'live case notes', as suggested would not be feasible, as the researcher did not have access to the electronic case note documentation system.

Section 5.10 provides detailed thematic analysis of qualitative feedback from Focus Groups.

5.6.4 Reflect and Action Plan

Initially disappointed that only three of the five consenting participants attended the focus group. Participants appeared relaxed and made a worthwhile and meaningful contribution by providing detailed and rich information on their viewpoints, perceptions, and recommendations. The focus group discussions flowed well with the participants allowing each other time to respond.

Preliminary data analysis of the second round of testing and the first focus group took place. A further meeting with the Action Research Subgroup allowed a review of the preliminary results. Although there were some aesthetic issues with the case note samples, these appeared to be satisfactory. They agreed that further testing following refinement of the DOC Learning Tool would be required. The statistician supported this decision. An outline of PAR Cycle Two and the summary of action points that led to Par Cycle Three is detailed in Figure 5.4

Figure 5.4:Outline of PAR Cycle Two and summary

5.7 Cycle Three

5.7.1 Plan

Following with the Action Research Subgroup meeting to review PAR Cycle Two, the researcher met with the participant who had highlighted another documentation review tool was used within the targeted health board. This was clarified as the participant had meant they had previously reviewed case note documentation as a SOM. It was confirmed that no other documentation review tool was available within the target Health Board. As already stipulated, another round of testing was required. In addition, the next focus group would include more specific questions surrounding the RAG system (Appendix 35) and also explore the DOC Learning Tool and the role it will play with the revalidation process.

Minor amendments were made to the DOC Learning Tool to exclude existing criteria i.e., correct CHI number was blocked out and all additional records section removed. Minor word changes to case note documentation samples were made to improve the understanding and interpretation of the criteria (Appendix 33). Recruitment processes were as with previous cycles. Furthermore, an updated DOC Learning Tool (Appendix 36) was sent out via email to original participants. The invitation for staff to participate in the study was extended to include all midwives working in the hospital within the targeted Health Board. This would maintain a PAR sample for Cycle Three of at least fifteen participants as the participants had changed due to retirement / staff changes.

5.7.2 Act

Data collection for PAR Cycle Three took place in March 2019. Although fifteen participants agreed to complete the DOC Learning Tools, only twelve participants returned the completed forms. This time, each participant received a printed copy of the four electronic case note samples. Participants were now asked to circle on the case note samples where they thought there was a documentation error. This illustrated where the errors occurred in addition to participants completing the DOC Learning Tools.

As before, all participants who had previously completed the DOC Learning Tools were invited via email to take part in the follow up focus group. It was hoped that 6-8 participants would attend.

5.7.3 Observe (*quantitative and qualitative summaries*)

The twelve participants scored the four case note documents using the DOC Learning Tool. There was still variation between results (Appendix 37. Table 5.3 displays the range between 52.78% to 97.22% agreement with DOC samples scored by the Action Research Subgroup. Mode = 75% (n=3), Mean 75.93%. Median score was 76.39%. Standard deviation being 13.829. Two participants scored between 50% and 60%, one between 60% and 70% and four scoring between 70% and 80%, three between 80% and 90% and two between 90% and 100%. Whilst 100% scores were not attained the findings were increasing with the highest score noted as 97.22%. Figure 5.5 shows a histogram of the frequency distribution of results from PAR Cycle Three. Again, a normal distribution curve was present.

Table 5-3: Results for PAR Cycle Three presented in ascending order

Participants											
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Score (%)											
52.78	52.78	63.89	75	75	75	77.78	80.56	83.33	86.11	91.67	97.22

Figure 5.5: Histogram of frequency distribution of results from PAR Cycle Three

Comments from participants on the day indicated they found the DOC Learning Tool user-friendly when reviewing the case note samples. One participant indicated that a section should be included to note if observations were completed.

The second focus group took part in September 2019, in a private room within the targeted Health Board. In attendance were three participants (n=3), observer / field note taker and the researcher. All participants had already completed the DOC Learning Tool previously and consented to take part in a focus group at that time. Hospitality was offered to the participants on arrival. The focus group was conducted using the revised interview schedule with questions to further probe and explore issues raised through discussion (Appendix 35). The session was digitally audio recorded and lasted 34 minutes.

Initial reflections from the participant responses from the second focus group indicated there was a need for the DOC Learning Tool to move to assessing electronic records. Participants perceived it was easy to navigate through the sample case notes and cross-reference using the DOC Learning Tool. They acknowledged the challenges in using electronic case note documentation compared to paper case notes, including limited space to further document episodes of care. Participants highlighted that it was difficult to assess if appropriate abbreviations were being utilised when using live case notes as an approved abbreviation sheet was not included within the electronic system.

Participants confirmed that the DOC Learning Tool criteria were closely aligned with the requirements of the NMC Code i.e., prioritise people, practise effectively, preserve safety and promote professionalism and trust (NMC, 2015; 2018). Inserting a section on the involvement of women was highlighted as being a useful addition when reviewing case note documentation. However, participants reported that it may be difficult to provide evidence to demonstrate involvement of women. Discussion ensued about challenges and subjectivity of reviewing case note documentation. This included the ambiguity of the DOC Learning Tool 'amber criteria'. Initial thoughts from participants indicated that case note documentation was either right or wrong. Therefore, the 'Amber criteria' was not appropriate as it should be scored Green (right) or Red (wrong). Through further

discussion, participants recognised that the DOC Learning Tool could be used to promote and encourage good practice, rather than being a punitive tool. Consensus was agreed that the 'Amber criteria' should be retained to demonstrate developmental opportunities for practitioners to guide them towards achieving 'Green criteria every time' with their documentation. In general, participants expressed the view that if staff just saw the red criteria, this would be disheartening, and not be conducive to their learning.

Participants indicated that the DOC Learning Tool would be useful for their own learning including self-review and reflection of their own case note documentation. Also, this was useful as a checklist on the electronic documentation system to act as a prompt to ensure staff complete documentation accurately. Participants felt the DOC Learning Tool could be used as part of the Personal Development Annual Review process, where practitioners provide evidence of peer review of their case note documentation. Participants also highlighted that the DOC Learning Tool would be useful as part of remedial action to improve practice following adverse clinical incident reviews.

There were only minor changes to the wording on the Tool suggested. Participants were not concerned about the subjective nature of the scoring of the DOC Learning Tool. They expressed that peer or manager feedback of the DOC Learning Tool would involve discussion with the individual rather than used in isolation. Therefore, the scoring could be explored during this one-to-one professional meeting.

See Section 5.10 of this chapter for complete thematic analysis of qualitative feedback from Focus Groups.

5.7.4 Reflect and Action Plan

Preliminary data analysis of the third round of testing and a further meeting with the Action Research Subgroup took place to review preliminary results. Overall, the DOC Learning Tool and case note samples were deemed to be more robust. Changes identified for the DOC Learning Tool included adding a statement regarding clinical observations (Appendix 38). An outline of PAR Cycle Three and the summary of action points that led to Par Cycle Four is detailed in Figure 5.6

Figure 5.6: Outline of PAR Cycle Three and summary

5.8 Cycle Four

5.8.1 Plan

The Action Research Subgroup met to discuss findings from data collection of PAR Cycle Three and plan for PAR Cycle Four. It was agreed to expand the testing of the DOC Learning Tool to include community midwives within the targeted Health Board as previously only hospital midwives had been included. Minor amendments were made to the DOC Learning Tool to include a section on observations. Recruitment strategy was as before, with the invitation extended to midwives working in two of the community areas within the targeted Health Board.

5.8.2 Act

Data collection for Cycle Four took place in September 2019. Fifteen participants took part. Again, all participants previously completing the DOC Learning Tool were invited by email to take part in the next focus group. It was hoped that 6-8 participants would be able to take part.

5.8.3 Observe (quantitative and qualitative summaries)

The fifteen participants scored the four case notes using the DOC Learning Tool. Still variation between results (Appendix 39). Table 5.4 displays the results for

Cycle Four in ascending order. Range 67.5% to 97.5% agreement with DOC samples scored by Action Research Subgroup. Mode = 70% (n=3), Mean 78.17% and the median 77.5%. Standard deviation being 8.317. One participant scored between 60% and 69%, eight scoring between 70% and 79%, four between 80% and 89% and two between 90% and 100%. The highest score reported was 97.5% which was approaching near 100% agreement. Figure 5.7 shows a histogram of the frequency distribution of results from PAR Cycle Four. As before, comments from participants on the day indicated that they found the DOC Learning Tool easy to use.

Table 5-4: Results for PAR Cycle Four presented in ascending order

Participants														
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15
Score (%)														
67.5	70	70	70	72.5	75	75	77.5	77.5	80	82.5	82.5	85	90	97.5

Figure 5.7: Histogram of frequency distribution of results from PAR Cycle Four

5.8.4 Reflect and Action Plan

Preliminary data analysis of the fourth round of testing and a further meeting with the Action Research Subgroup took place to review preliminary results. Overall, the DOC Learning Tool and case note samples were deemed to be robust. No further changes identified for the DOC Learning Tool. Following discussions with supervisors, statisticians, and the subsequent onset of Covid-19 pandemic it was decided to write up findings and postpone full statistical testing to post-doctoral studies.

For the qualitative data collection process the third focus group took part in September 2019, in a quiet designated meeting room within the targeted Health Board. In attendance were three participants (n=3), observer / field note taker and the researcher. All participants had already completed the DOC Learning Tool previously and consented to take part in a follow up focus group. Hospitality was offered to the participants on arrival. The focus group was conducted using the same interview schedule (Appendix 35). with questions to further probe and explore issues raised through discussion. The session was digitally audio recorded and lasted 28 minutes.

Initial reflections from the participants indicated that they perceived the DOC Learning Tool would be useful to assess clinical documentation. Participants reported that the electronic documentation system was less detailed than the previous handwritten case notes. The participants referred to the electronic documentation system as being a series of 'tick boxes'. They felt that by using the DOC Learning Tool alongside the electronic case notes would highlight any problems or gaps in their documentation. Participants also highlighted that peer review of their case note documentation using the DOC Learning Tool would be useful in providing feedback in a constructive manner. It was also suggested that the DOC Learning Tool would be a useful teaching tool on the required standards of documentation for new staff and students. Furthermore, it could be used for risk management purposes when reviewing critical incidents to identify gaps in clinical staffs' knowledge and highlight any training requirements. Suggestions from participants also included that the DOC Learning Tool could be used as a reflective process during one-to-one meetings with their line manager.

Participants were happy with the RAG system and had no issues with the amber category as they described it as a 'softer option', indicating that it was important to keep positive when giving constructive feedback if the case note documentation was of a poorer standard. Therefore, having just the right and wrong option (Red and Green) would not facilitate this important feedback mechanism. Section 5.10 details the thematic analysis of the focus groups.

5.9 Overall summary of quantitative analysis

The DOC Learning Tool was tested over four cycles conducted over an 18-month period. The participants (ranged from n=12 to n=15) examined the four case note documents during each cycle. This produced a sample size ranging from 48 to 60 case notes which were then scored and compared with the Action Research Subgroup scores.

Cycle One revealed that the case note samples produced were not robust and would need to be amended before further testing of the DOC learning Tool could take place. This decision was compounded by the targeted Health Board moving to an electronic documentation system. New case note samples had to be produced using the electronic format that the targeted Health Board were using. This produce a more authentic and contemporary representation of the case note documentation for the midwife participants.

The three subsequent cycles involved refinement of the DOC Learning Tool. Only minor changes to wording of the Tool was required. This included removal of the additional records section which was superfluous and confused the participants. In addition, a clinical observation section was also added to the DOC Learning Tool.

Tables 5.5 and 5.6 provide an overview of the one-way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) multiple comparison across the four cycles of testing and the descriptive statistics produced. This revealed a reduced range of scores over the four PAR cycles and a steadily increased mean (score from 68.10 to 78.17). Distributions of all cycles in one graph enable the reader to compare the four distributions including variations and central tendencies (Figure 5.8).

Figure 5.8: Distributions of all cycles

Table 5-5 :One-Way ANOVA Multiple Comparisons

Dependent Variable: Scores

	(I) Cycle	(J) Cycle	Mean Difference	Std. Error	P-value	95% Confidence Interval	
			(I-J)			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
Fisher's Least Significant Differences (LSD)	1	2	-6.92	4.00	.090	-14.96	1.11
		3	-7.83	4.17	.066	-16.20	.54
		4	-10.07*	3.93	.013*	-17.96	-2.18
	2	1	6.92	4.00	.090	-1.11	14.96
		3	-.91	4.24	.831	-9.41	7.60
		4	-3.15	4.00	.435	-11.18	4.88
	3	1	7.83	4.17	.066	-.54	16.20
		2	.91	4.24	.831	-7.60	9.41
		4	-2.24	4.17	.594	-10.61	6.13
	4	1	10.07*	3.93	.013*	2.18	17.97
		2	3.15	4.00	.435	-4.88	11.18
		3	2.2	4.17	.594	-6.13	10.61

* The mean difference is significant at the 0.05 level.

Table 5-6:Descriptive Statistics

	n	Range	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Error	Std. Deviation
Cycle.1	15	48.58	40.97	89.55	68.10	3.06	11.84
Cycle.2	14	29.55	59.09	88.64	75.02	2.34	8.76
Cycle.3	12	44.44	52.78	97.22	75.93	3.99	13.83
Cycle.4	15	30.00	67.50	97.50	78.17	2.15	8.32

5.9.1 Summary from quantitative phase

Due to the restrictions imposed by Covid 19 pandemic in addition to the duration of the PhD, further testing of the DOC Learning Tool needed to be ceased. Post-doctoral work will include further testing to finalise the statistical validation of this DOC Learning Tool. Plans will involve including 75 participants within targeted Health Board, each reviewing the four case notes. Furthermore, the plan is to pilot the DOC Learning Tool using live electronic case notes samples.

5.10 Thematic Analysis

Gaining viewpoints and perceptions of midwives when using the DOC Learning Tool to review the quality of case note documentation was a key part in the research process and development. It was important to plan the data analysis to ensure the process was conducted in a detailed, consistent, and thorough manner to establish credibility (Nowell, Norris and White, 2017). Therefore, the framework by Braun and Clarke (2006) provided a robust and systematic process for the thematic analysis of the qualitative data from the focus group transcripts. Although the stages used in the analysis of the data appeared to be a sequential series of steps, these tend to be iterative in nature with movement back and forth between each stage. This repetition in the analysis process involves building up on the previous stage (Braun and Clarke, 2006). Details of the process involved in each of the six steps in the framework are provided.

5.10.1 Step 1: Become familiar with the data

The first step in the process required the researcher to become familiar with the data. This involved listening and re-listening to the digital audio recordings. It was essential to review the field notes, perform initial reflections and actively engage in reading over the transcriptions. Grove, Gray and Burns (2015) termed this initial step as 'dwelling in the data'. An experienced transcriber word processed the transcripts from the digital recordings. However, the researcher reviewed these transcripts whilst continuing to listen to the digital recordings multiple times and inserted any missing words, tone, or hesitations to ensure the transcripts were an accurate record of the data collected. Cluett and Bluff (2006) advised

that clear details of who transcribed the data is important to ensure transparency of the process.

5.10.2 Step 2: Generate initial codes

The next step involved organising the data in a systematic manner into 'chunks of meaningful information' (Braun and Clarke, 2006). The transcripts of each focus group were examined on an individual basis. Each section of relevant information was highlighted through colour coding key chunks of data (Appendix 29) within the transcribed word documents. The process initially involved highlighting relevant information then returning to the highlighted data and colour coding sections that linked together to form the codes. Open coding was utilised to allow the data to be refined throughout the process. As the purpose of the focus groups was to address the research aim, theoretical thematic analysis was used rather than inductive analysis (Maguire and Delahunt, 2017). Each focus group transcript was first coded then examined and refined before moving to review the next transcript.

Although many computer packages undertake coding, Polit and Beck (2020) acknowledge that this should not replace the involvement of the researcher within the analysis process. Furthermore, hand analysis encourages the researcher to make decisions about codes and emerging themes allowing focus on the data rather than the software package (Parahoo, 2014). In this present data analysis, the researcher preferred to be fully involved in conducting the coding process. Whilst this was labour intensive, it was a worthwhile process as it allowed the researcher to become familiar with the data collected and become immersed in the analysis.

5.10.3 Step 3: Search for themes

A good quality thematic analysis process makes sense and interpretes the qualitative data from the transcripts. The process needs to go beyond summarising and organising the data collected (Braun and Clarke, 2013). The purpose of thematic analysis is to identify themes across all the data. Braun and Clarke (2006) explained there are no set rules about what constitutes a theme. In general terms, a theme is defined by its importance and often defined as being

patterns found within the data, which says something significant or interesting about the research aim (Braun and Clarke, 2006). If the study compromised a very small data set (e.g., one short focus-group), overlap between coding and preliminary themes may occur. Subthemes emerging from the data are often discrete but still interact and relate to the main theme.

Initially the codes allocated across all the data transcribed were examined and re-examined. Once this coding process was finalised then the codes were grouped together (highlighted text) into three very broad draft themes: Challenges using DOC Learning Tool; Positive uses of the DOC Learning Tool and Future use of tools. However, these draft themes changed following Steps 4 and 5.

5.10.4 Step 4: Review themes

During the process, each individual code was handwritten on coloured 'Post its' (that matched highlighted text) and placed under the three preliminary themes. The 'Post-its' also contained details of the data origin in relation to the exact focus group and participant (number only). The researcher and supervisors discussed and debated the themes and explored the codes in more detail. The process of reviewing the themes and data continued until consensus agreement was reached. Appendix 30 illustrates this process in pictorial form.

5.10.5 Step 5: Define themes

The detailed data analysis process resulted in confirming the two final main themes. These were ***Mechanisms and Practicalities*** and ***Person Centred Engagement and Enhancement***. Sections 5.12 and 5.13 provides more detail and discussion on both the main themes and subthemes produced.

5.10.6 Step 6: Write-up

In writing up the findings, the researcher must demonstrate credibility, dependability, and transferability (Polit and Beck, 2020). In this current process, steps detailing the transcription of the data are provided. Clear description is provided relating to how the themes were developed and formed. Potential for

transferability to other settings or other professional groups can be extrapolated from the detailed reporting of the findings (Section 5.14).

5.11 Themes and sub themes

Two main overarching themes emerged from the detailed analysis of combined data from the focus groups and comments from the DOC Learning Tool. These were ***Mechanisms and Practicalities*** (Section 5.12 and ***Person Centred Engagement and Enhancement*** (Section 5.13. Figure 5.9 presents the two main themes and six subthemes. A selection of direct quotes from participants is provided to evidence the findings underpinning the main themes and related subthemes.

Figure 5.9: Themes and sub themes

5.12 Theme One: Mechanisms and Practicalities

Mechanisms and Practicalities of the DOC Learning Tool was a robust and overarching main theme. This was not surprising given the purpose of the focus groups was to ascertain the perceptions and viewpoints of midwives' experiences when using the DOC Learning Tool to review case note documents. Within this theme four discrete sub themes emerged. Two relating to the structure and content of the Tool; ***Application*** and ***Grading criteria***. A third strong sub theme emerged described as ***Relevance of current documentation system*** related to issues with the current electronic case note documentation system whilst a fourth sub theme on ***Future proofing*** focussed on how the DOC Learning Tool could be adapted for future use. However, Figure 5.10 presents the sub themes and related components. The sub themes with key discussion points and related sub themes components will now be presented.

Figure 5.10:Theme 1 subthemes

5.12.1 Subtheme; Application

One key aspect of gathering qualitative information from participants was to ascertain their subjective experiences of using the DOC Learning Tool to review case note documents. In this respect, several key discussion points highlighted provided valuable and useful information on the application DOC Learning Tool. This included the alignment to the NMC professional standards of practice for nurses and midwives (NMC, 2015; 2018), issues highlighted around formatting and content, views on subjectivity and the challenges experienced.

Participants positively confirmed the DOC Learning Tool was appropriately aligned to the current NMC Code (NMC, 2018). There was clear evidence reported by participants that the key professional NMC categories were embedded in the DOC Learning Tool. These categories included prioritising people through person-centred care, evidence of practising effectively, preserving safety and promoting trust and professionalism.

“I do like that it’s [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] in line with the [NMC] Code and I like a RAG [Red, Amber, Green] as well”. (F1, P1, L 92)

“The criteria fits in very well with the [NMC] Standards. I would definitely say that”. (F2, P4, L156)

It is heartening to report that none of the participants identified any negative formatting aspects of the DOC Learning Tool to assess the quality of case note documentation. In fact, participants commented that the DOC Learning Tool was perceived to be very useful especially since the implementation of the electronic record system.

“I don’t have any problems following the tool. I don’t think there is anything I would change”. (F3, P8, L99)

“I think it [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] can only be a positive thing to implement”. (F3, P7, L 96)

“I don’t see any negatives”. (F3, P7, L90)

"I think it's [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] something that's really needed especially now that we have electronic records". (F2, P4, L9).

The consensus across all participants was that the DOC Learning Tool was user friendly, fit for purpose, straightforward, and well structured, easy to use. It had the added benefit of having all the information captured on one page.

"It's [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] concise". (F1, P2, L26)

"...on one page", A4 so it's a manageable thing". (F1, P3, L74)

"Quite self-explanatory". (F3, P8, L88)

"It's [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] as good as it can be to give us standard set questions and parameters". (F1, P3 L28.

"So I really liked the headings and the categories...Just through the [NMC] code...you know assessing someone's documentation it's against that. So I really like the fact that it's [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] broken down so I think that's really good". (F1, P3, L62)

All participants reported these factors were important if the DOC Learning Tool was to be effectively implemented in everyday practice when reviewing clinical documentation. A few participants specifically focussed on two documentation criteria within the DOC Learning Tool. 'Evidence that the woman is involved in her care planning' and 'Evidence of consent noted throughout all documentation'. They reported these questions within the Tool really challenged them to reflect on the documentation of care they provided in clinical practice. This prompted them to question their own documentation as to 'Had they really provided documented evidence [i.e., in their own case note documentation] that the woman had been involved in their care?' Furthermore, the issue of consent was displayed as a tick box in the electronic notes that the midwives used. Participants highlighted they needed to 'tick the box' to progress onto the next section of the notes Therefore explicit description of informed consent was not detailed in the notes. Participants identified these as concerns for everyday practice in

documenting evidence and they would take these issues back to their clinical setting.

“One of the strengths about the Tool ... [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] is...evidence that the woman is involved in the care planning...I probably don't document very much ...because again it's a tick box”. (F2.P5, L113)

“I think that the tool... [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] does help you kind of think about actual consent and what you are documenting”. (F3, P9, L82)

Throughout the four cycles of testing the DOC Learning Tool there was variation in the interpretation of results by raters. All participants revealed that overall, they were not concerned about this degree of subjectivity when using the DOC Learning Tool.

“I don't think you can take that [Subjectivity] out no matter how good the tool is. Individuals have got their own viewpoint”. (F1, P3, L275)

I don't think you are ever going to get to the stage where you have got a tool that everybody interprets the same way. (F2, P4, L484)

“You are thinking standard of documentation can be really good overall however there is a possibility one omission...that brings it right down...that makes sense”. (F1, P2, L144)

One interesting point was raised that the DOC Learning Tool would never be used in isolation and would involve discussion between the midwife whose documentation was under review and the reviewer. This opportunity for discussion would encourage reflection and lead to improved clinical documentation and practice.

“It allows discussion about why we scored differently...leads to improved practice... promotes learning”. (F2, P4, L498)

There was an initial challenge with using the DOC Learning Tool raised in the first discussion group with participants highlighting the difficulty experienced with the 'print out' of the new electronic records. The formatting in the 'print out' version of the electronic notes was skewed when compared to the old system of paper case-note samples. Interestingly this was not commented on in either of the other focus groups. It was anticipated that this was due to participants becoming more familiar with using the printed version of the electronic notes.

"We have changed the systems completely in the middle of the process which is very difficult to then adapt". (F1, P3 L38)

"I suppose when we used it [i.e., DOC Learning Too] before ...with handheld notes the flow was better". (F1, P2, L27)

"But when we were testing it [i.e., DOC Learning Too] with printouts from electronic notes it looked like that (there was) no consent". (F1, P1, L14)

5.12.2 Subtheme; Grading Criteria

The key discussion points within the *Grading Criteria* sub-theme related to the Red, Amber, Green (RAG) System and use of the 'Amber criteria'. Midwives were familiar with using the RAG system when assessing women postoperatively or when they were critically ill. Whilst the concept of assessing documentation using a similar system was not alien to them, the RAG system did generate discussion and debate. Overall, participants supported using the RAG system as they found it useful and user-friendly.

"I like a RAG system". (F1, P2, and L67)

"I totally understand that there's variety of standards that go from high to medium to acceptable to sub-standard to unacceptable". (F1, P2 L127).

Challenges surrounding the subjectivity of the Amber Criteria were highlighted especially in the earlier PAR Cycles. The researcher reflected on the challenges which were discussed with the Action Research Subgroup. It was agreed that the

researcher should pursue this and further explored subjective viewpoints surrounding the Amber criteria in future discussions.

“I think the amber bit in the middle is sometimes difficult to make your decision... I think the amber bit is a wee bit of a challenge. I think you know the black and white...the red is below standard but I also understand you need the bit in the middle. There is variation it's not black and white”. (F1, P3, L127)

One midwife expressed her concern about the purpose of the Amber category. This issue generated discussion and debate.

“If you've got all your green ones ticked or if there is more over onto the kind of a red. I am not sure of the purpose of the amber. What is that actually telling us? The green is telling us that it is done the way that it should. And the red is telling us that it's not done the way that it should. Is the amber telling us that part of the notes are okay? And we need to keep it in for that purpose” (F2, P6, L285).

Other participants reported that the 'Amber criteria' was useful especially as there was an explanation as to what the purpose of the 'amber criteria' attached to the DOC Learning Tool.

“I can see where the red, amber, green is coming from”. (F2.P4, L173)

“You have ...a wee explanation...what's relevant to the green, amber, and red so no problem with that”. (F3, P7, and L108).

Moreover, all other participants felt that the 'Amber criteria' should remain part of the DOC Learning Tool. They reported that it was a more constructive way of providing feedback and encouraged reflection and learning.

“I think to take it out [amber] you are just getting, yeah these are good or these are really bad and again. I don't think that's good for peoples' self-esteem”. (F2, P4, L296)

“Midwives going away with a bit of a feel-good factor. I am doing okay but there is room for improvement...I agree...the amber should stay”. (F2, P5, L308)

“I suppose it’s [i.e., Amber criteria] a gentler way”. (F2, P5, L299)

“There could be a bit room for improvement then”. (F2, P4, L292)

“If you have Amber...there is a lot of good practice and a lot of good documentation but there are a couple of wee things that you are not sure of”. (F2, P6, L303)

Overall, there was consensus agreement that participants were confident with the RAG grading criteria and confident that the ‘Amber criteria’ should remain as part of the DOC Learning Tool.

5.12.3 Subtheme: Relevance of Current Documentation System

This sub theme ‘**Relevance of Current Documentation System**’ emerged from the consistent discussion points arising around the advantages of conducting the documentation review process. These discussions revealed how the case note documentation review by participants uncovered key issues about the current electronic documentation system in relation to highlighting limitations, potential areas for improvement, and raising awareness of pertinent issues.

There was consensus agreement with participants that the new electronic documentation system was not conducive in encouraging midwives to provide a detailed documentary account of patient care. In this respect, participants felt the testing of the DOC Learning Tool with case note documents was a beneficial process in highlighting the reliance of the use of ticking boxers in the electronic documentation system. The format of the system consisted of an increase in the amount of ‘ticking boxes’ for midwives to move through the documentation for many sections. This ‘tick box’ approach was negatively viewed by participants as this did not provide opportunity for midwives to detail evidence of the care they had provided for the women and babies.

“Ticking boxes is not enough and I think that [i.e., DOC Learning Too] highlighted that for us”. (F3, P7, L284)

“A lot of tick boxes...when we got through [named electronic documentation system]. And a lot of the time things aren't being documented in your additional notes. I think if we use them [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] it should tighten that up and make documentation better”. (F3, P7, L10)

“Documentation has gone from being from fairly, a fairly good standard and when we hand wrote everything to being not very well I don't think it's very good because it's all it's all tick boxes ..., I would consider, you know using [the DOC Learning Tool] myself”. (F2, P5, L15)

It was alarming to note that participants highlighted how as practitioners they were becoming dependent on the tick boxes within the electronic documentation system. Participants explained that if the boxes had been ticked then it was assumed that they had documented that section correctly. Following reflection on their findings, participants raised this as a concern indicating that this reliance could lead to the potential of omissions of documentation of key clinical events.

“We rely on tick boxes”. (F2, P5, L547)

“People now rely on [named electronic documentation system] because it's telling you you've done it”. (F2, P5, L549)

“A majority of tick boxes so things that that we would normally elaborate on possibly isn't getting elaborated on so things are getting or potentially getting missed”. (F3, P8, L30)

“[Named electronic documentation system] ...it's only asking you to tick a box. It's not asking you for an explanation”. (F1, P1, L246)

“Well the tick box on [named electronic documentation system] is even for your e.g. postnatal check...there's not really any expansion...other than the comment box at the bottom...I don't get a true picture of what that the lady is all about yes/no”.(F2, P5,L46).

Participants also openly shared and discussed their own experience of using the electronic documentation system. On reflection of reviewing other midwives' documentation, participants focussed on the lack of documentation reported in the 'free text box'. Indeed, one participant admitted that they were unaware that there was even a free text box available for them to add in comments.

"I think they forget to use the free text box". (F2, P4, L69)

"Before somebody would have written...the actual advice that had been given or the plan of action. It probably does go on but it's not actually written in the notes". (F2, P5, L63)

"Nobody tends to write anything...there's no free text. There's no clinical notes added". (F2, P6, L85)

Many participants also reported how concerned they were with the number of unapproved abbreviations midwives were using within their documentation, especially newly qualified midwives. Within the targeted Health Board only an approved list of recognised abbreviations should be used in documenting care.

"There's a lot more missing on the [named electronic documentation system] notes. And then even the abbreviations...if you are starting to think is this a recognised abbreviation...a lot of the new midwives will use abbreviations that somebody else has used it is all right to use". (F2, P6, L35)

One issue emerging related to 'consent' of the patient within the electronic documentation system which was now only a tick box. Concern was expressed that this was insufficient to evidence informed consent by the women receiving care.

"But is the woman being involved in her care? Although you are assuming that she is involved because she is coming to the appointments, and we are asking consent but is she fully making a choice or is it kind of us doing it for her...The consent at the first part is vague...what is she consenting to?". (F3, P8, L76)

The key issue around legal Implications related to midwifery documentation was raised within this subtheme. The testing of the DOC Learning Tool to review midwifery case note documents served the important purpose of highlighting situations revealing a lack of documented evidence of care or actions. This is a serious limitation for midwifery practice which could have major consequences for individual's practice if their provision of midwifery care came under scrutiny during adverse outcomes under legal review in the future. Importantly, participants also openly recognised that the use of 'tick boxes' in the electronic system would not provide midwives with sufficient evidence to support the care they provided. Further documented evidence of accurate and contemporaneous care would be required. It is emphasised that in prima facie situations, if it is not written down then in the eyes of the law then it did not occur (Andrews and St Aubyn, 2015). Furthermore, as midwifery cases could be archived for at least 25 years following the birth of a child then midwives would be unable to remember exactly what had been done and therefore unable to defend their actions or inactions unless they had clearly documented it

"Five years down the line if somebody says what do mean by yes or what do you mean by no...if there was yes there was an issue but if you haven't put anything in, and you have nothing to back yourself up with the [named electronic documentation system] notes". (F2, P6, L53)

"We need something...people use... [Named electronic documentation system] and its tick this, tick that...people feel alright if they have ticked a box. But in a court of law, you know five years down the line what does a box mean?". (F2, P6, L531)

"You would certainly think more. If it's not written down there it hasn't taken place". (F2, P6, L563)

5.12.4 Subtheme: Future Proofing

Within the subtheme **Future Proofing**, aspects of the future developments of the DOC Learning Tool were discussed. This included using the Tool with and within the current Electronic Documentation System (as an aide memoire). In addition,

there was discussion and debate around using the DOC Learning Tool to review an individual midwife's documentation and / or an episode of care.

The participants discussed potential developments of the DOC Learning Tool, including using it with live electronic records.

"Do it [i.e., use DOC Learning Too] with live electronic records...with a laptop". (F1, P3, L35)

"If you were using the tool as it's designed to, we would use it [i.e., DOC Learning Too] on live records". (F1, P3, L48)

"Maybe further down the line...and part of everyday practice then at that point it [i.e., using the DOC Learning Too] could be part of the electronic record". (F1,P3, L258)

Although one participant highlighted that it would take time to get used to using the DOC Learning Tool directly from the online case notes.

"I think the printout was good...I think it might take a bit longer if you were doing it from an electronic record...just until you get used to where you need to go to find the evidence we are scoring". (F2,P4,L102)

One participant felt that DOC learning tool would be useful if it was embedded into the electronic documentation system.

"If this [DOC Learning Tool] was here on an electronic form people would be more aware". (F2, P6, L179)

Discussion between participants also focussed on how the DOC Learning Tool could be used in the future, either by overviewing a full episode of care or reviewing an individual midwife's documentation.

"Would we be using tool to assess full episodes of care or are we using it to assess an individual's standard of documentation?". (F1, P3, L114)

“Evidence of the woman being involved in a care planning and so actual fact, you are reviewing the whole, the case notes as a whole to see then if that has actually happened throughout. That there has been lots of conversation and lots of discussion. And obviously it’s [i.e., DOC Learning Too] designed to, do then evidence of consent and things like that throughout”. (F1, P2, L77)

“You would need to read the whole set of case notes and then use the tool”. (F1, P2, L82)

“With the changes from 2016 to now from going from (SWHMR) to [named electronic documentation system], yes it would be reading the whole case note... And then completing it [i.e., DOC Learning Too]”. (F1, P1, L93)

“So you would maybe use it [i.e., DOC Learning Too] for one aspect of care, like labour care and then postnatal care”. (F1, P2, L104)

In general, there was consensus that the DOC Learning Tool had a worthwhile role to play in both current and future review of documentation. This could include the integration of the DOC Learning Tool in everyday practice to review the quality of documentary evidence of care provided. This evidence could focus on individual midwives or individual care episodes to meet the NMC standards of professional practice.

5.13 Theme Two: Person Centred Engagement and Enhancement (through learning)

Person Centred Engagement and Enhancement was an overarching main theme to emerge from the qualitative data. There was a clear and consistent consensus that this theme was underpinned with learning and professional developmental opportunities for nurses and midwives. Participants recognised the potential learning opportunities colleagues could experience in their everyday professional practice. This could neither be using the DOC Learning Tool to

review their own case note documentation or through constructive feedback if their case note documentation was peer reviewed.

Further exploration of midwives' views of the DOC Learning Tool revealed two subthemes *internal perspectives* and *external perspectives*. It was evidenced from midwives that learning and development opportunities could be experienced for the individual or within the organisation. These two distinct perspectives for learning opportunities were regarded as being mutually beneficial to the quality of care. Figure 5.11 presents the two subthemes with related components.

Figure 5.11: Theme 2-Two subthemes

5.13.1 Subtheme: Internal Perspectives

Key points from the discussions underpinning *Internal Perspective* focused on how using the DOC Learning Tool for documentation review would be of benefit to individual midwives in maintaining and developing in their professional practice. The highlighted areas related to revalidation, reflection, and self-review, providing feedback and individual learning. Whilst these are discrete components within this subtheme, the components are also interconnected and aligned to the process of learning through everyday practice and continuous professional development.

The NMC Triennial revalidation process is mandatory to remain on the NMC register for all nursing and midwifery practitioners, educationalists, and managers (NMC, 2015, updated 2018). As the DOC Learning Tool is used to review the quality of documentation then this Tool has a potential role to play in underpinning

the professional aspects of everyday practice. There was consensus across participants that the DOC Learning Tool could provide evidence of reflecting and reviewing their practice:

“We could use the Tool and keep in like a portfolio thing so if we got audited (and) it’s [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] there for revalidation”. (F3, P8, L211)

“As part of the revalidation process...individual’s self-review...they went and said L would you peer [i.e., review], so it’s coming from individuals rather than us putting it on them”. (F1, P3, L222)

In recent decades, the NMC has emphasised the key role that both reflection and self-review has as part of continuous professional development to support professional learning. This is in addition to the integral role reflection and self-review have on the revalidation process. There was general agreement across participants that through the process of documentation review, the DOC Learning Tool had a key role to play in enabling midwives to become reflective practitioners. This in turn would promote increased self-awareness, self-identity and personal and professional growth resulting in improved practice surrounding documentation.

So I think the questions themselves [i.e. in the DOC Learning Tool] ...would certainly prompt staff to ask questions [of their own documentation] ...abbreviations...management plan clearly documented. (F2, P4, and L192)

“Then there’s the possibility of a bit of reflection within it [i.e., DOC Learning Tool]”. (F1, P2, L229)

“It’s [DOC Learning Tool] a way of improving [their] practice”. (F2, P4, L249)

“So, it [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] would prompt questions of staff’s own documentation without someone else having to come and say I’ve audited these notes”. (F2, P4, L198)

“Use as a reflective tool [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] for your own personal use”. (F3, P8, L160)

Participants highlighted that documentary review should not just be confined to the mandatory review by managers. They strongly agreed that individuals should be given the opportunity to review their own documentation using the DOC Learning Tool. Furthermore, regular self-review of documentation using the DOC Learning Tool would enable individual midwives to pick up errors from their own documentation. Participants recommended that it would be useful for the DOC Learning Tool to be incorporated into the electronic documentation system to allow review of documentation on a case-by-case basis.

“If you highlighted x amount of notes a month [i.e., to be reviewed by DOC Learning Tool], then you could think well I won’t do that again because I have learned from that”. (F2, P6, L246)

It [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] could be a standard form on [named electronic documentation system] ...for yourself...have I done that...or for [the] peer as well. (F2, P6, L21)

There was consensus across all participants of the value in using the DOC Learning Tool to provide positive and constructive feedback. Participants also agreed that reviewing documentation of other practitioners, meant that they learned from the review experience too.

“If you are going through somebody’s notes and you notice the documentation is excellent then that’s a good thing to take to somebody. People are quick to hear negative feedback but...positive feedback is just as important”. (F3, P7, L218)

“Highlighting the things they did well ... so they can use that for revalidation”. (F3, P7, L203)

Participants emphasised that it was essential to follow up negative reviews especially in situations where the reviewed documentation raised concern. They highlighted those midwives would require support and specific instruction to provide this feedback.

“No matter whether its amber or red even one flag up I think we would still need to speak to the midwife...this is what we found. This is what needs addressed. If you need any assistance with your documentation, you know where I am, or your team leader will review in a months’ time”. (F3, P8, L40)

“We want instructions on the back ...so actually a kind of step by step”. (F1, P3, L190)

“It’s probably a wee bit about being supported in doing that-Instruction [i.e., providing feedback]”. (F1, P2, L198)

Participants clearly recognised and acknowledged the value the DOC Learning Tool in providing a range of learning opportunities for midwives. This was evidenced in the strong discussion points threading through the sub-themes. Participants recommended that the DOC Learning Tool would be a valuable learning resource in a variety of situations, examples included teaching student midwives, newly qualified midwives and as part of a documentation workshop. Training to use the DOC Learning Tool efficiently would also be required.

“A learning tool, something we could learn from”. (F1, P2, L219)

“For teaching, new students...these are the things you need to think about documentation...using it as a tool not just for the students but for us as well”. (F3, P9, L149)

“The students coming through have no experience of using handwritten notes or the paper notes so they are aware of what the NMC are looking for ...as a wee step by step guide”. (F3, P3, L190)

“There will be an element of training on it for people...but do they feel comfortable doing it. Is there an escalation plan?”. (F1, P2, L213)

“Documentation study days...get a set of case notes that’s maybe got a few errors...as a team...go through it ...as learning”. (F3, P8, L182)

“Should be a LearnPro module for this ...using a fake set of notes and you are just given the basic information...to document...then review the case notes”. (F3, P8, L412)

5.13.2 Subtheme: External Perspectives

The **External Perspective** subtheme encapsulates the key discussion points from the midwives’ use of the DOC Learning Tool to review documentation. These focussed on three areas (Figure 5.11.) including how learning could occur through **peer review**, **manager review** or through the systematic **risk management** process.

The NMC promotes the role of peer review in supporting nurses and midwives in their continuous professional development in the revalidation process (NMC, 2021). All participants agreed that the DOC Learning Tool had a supportive learning role when used during peer review of documentation or as a team review approach. Participants agreed that peer review would be useful for midwives reviewing documentation of other midwifery colleagues who work in similar clinical areas.

“I think it’s [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] perfect for peer review. That’s because that you have got your parameters and you know that it’s a specific area of care”. (F1, P3, L165)

“If you were looking a peer review it would be talking for example...somebody in postnatal looking at their colleagues notes in postnatal. I think that would be more beneficial”. (F1, P2, L16)

“In [named electronic documentation system] there isn’t a tool...that we could do peer review...I think it would be a good thing for us to use [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] as a team”. (F3, P7, L245)

You could use it [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] to instil more confidence in your colleagues that their documentation is good examples. (F3, P7, and L229)

Using it [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] amongst your peers...because from the [sample case-note] examples ...the documentation isn't grand and it was picked up using [the] Tool. (F3, P7, L15)

Whilst peer review of documentation was previously conducted in everyday practice, participants suggested that it would be of value to resurrect this practice through the implementation of the DOC Learning Tool. Participants recognised that introducing this practice would need to extend to include the peer review midwives facilitating the discussions with the midwife whose documentation is under review.

"We have lost the whole peer review and if we did it [i.e. DOC Learning Tool] once a month. 3-4 sets of notes if making same errors take the time to go through the notes without making them feel ...chastised". (F3, P7, L325)

"Go through Tool with them [peers] to make sure that both your understanding of how to use it [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] were both the same". (F2, P4, L445)

Participants agreed if negative findings from peer review of documentation was found then they (the midwife reviewers) would be duty bound to escalate and raise concerns through risk / line management. Furthermore, it was suggested the DOC Learning Tool could be used as a supportive component in the management appraisal process for midwives.

"The individual midwife has got that responsibility to highlight that not only to the midwife but also through the line management structure if it [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] was really bad". (F1, P2, L183)

Or the DOC Learning Tool could be used as part of the appraisal process (1: 1) "You could use it [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] as an appraisal". (F3, P7, L226)

"I think this also could be used for like your one to one with your team leader. We do a one to one. It would be a good thing maybe

to get a couple of your, bring up a couple of your records then use this [i.e., DOC Learning Tool] to go through just so as you are looking closely using that at your own documentation so as then you could constantly improve". (F3, P8, L120)

Participants also recommended that risk managers could use the DOC Learning Tool to review case notes when adverse incidents had occurred. This would need to be a supportive and facilitative process to not only provide learning points for the individual staff but also highlight key learning issues for the organisation. In addition, participants recommended the DOC Learning Tool had a key supportive role in reviewing documentation to avoid a blame culture. There was agreement that further training and support would be required to fully embed the DOC Learning Tool in everyday practice.

"It's not trying to pin the blame on someone. It's kind of looking at systemic, sort of system failures and I think documentation is really crucial in that so you are looking at ... the documentation when things go wrong you know instead of sort of feedback to the wider maternity services, em would be important for everybody". (F3, P9, L253)

"Used when there is an issue...risk management has been involved...analysing and scrutinising the notes". (F3, P8, L120)

"If they are reviewing documentation, they could use the Tool [i.e. DOC Learning Tool]. Feedback to the whole maternity staff". (F3, P8, L238)

"Identify areas that maybe...require a wee bit of additional training or support with, so it might identify gaps that are consistently showing up across the board therefore identify learning needs for staff". (F3, P7, L242)

5.14 Chapter Summary

Triangulation of emerging data findings was ongoing as the Participatory Action Research study progressed through the cycles. There was consensus of the study findings through evaluation of the DOC Learning Tool.

In summary, a detailed account of the first two phases of the PAR study was presented along with the results from four cycles of testing of the DOC Learning Tool. This included providing a detailed thematic analysis from the focus groups and comments from the DOC Learning Tool.

Over the PAR cycles, minor amendments and adaptations were made based on the qualitative data provided from the participants. These amendments provided a more robust sample of case note documents from Cycle Two onwards, including moving to electronic case note samples, refinement of the DOC Learning Tool and further exploration of issues raised during the focus groups.

Over the four cycles, descriptive statistics revealed a reduced range in the variation of scores and a steadily increased mean score. Results showed gradual increase while Cycle Four becomes significantly different from Cycle One.

Thematic analysis revealed two overarching themes relating to the DOC Learning Tool, including ***Mechanisms and Practicalities and Person Centred Engagement and Enhancement through Learning***. There was clear evidence the DOC Learning Tool was in alignment with the NMC professional standards.

There were no negative comments about the DOC Learning Tool, which was reported to be user friendly, concise, and appropriate to review the quality of documented evidence of patient care. Issues were raised about improvements required in the electronic documentation system to keep documentation meaningful to accurately represent the care provided. Overall, findings are summarised in Figure. 5.12

Figure 5.12: Summary of findings

CHAPTER 6 DISCUSSION

6.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the key findings contributing to the existing body of literature relating to review of the quality of midwifery documentation. The study was designed to incorporate best research practice to support the nature and purpose of the study relating to clinical practice. In this respect, this study has successfully addressed the aim to develop an effective mechanism to review midwifery documentation in accordance with NMC Standards for practice. Findings are discussed within the context of previous research findings.

The impetus for the study was to address a key gap in existing evidence in the lack of any form of assessment to review nursing and midwifery documentation. This was in relation to the emphasis focusing more on the provision of holistic care in professional practice and less on the diagnostic element of medicalised care and ill health. Recording and documenting health care is an essential tool of professional practice and not just an optional extra (Cornock, 2019). The main function is for clinical benefit to provide a complete, accurate and factual account of care without the need for practitioner recall (Cornock, 2019). Contemporaneous entries enhance the credibility and reliability of documentation and contribute to improve patient safety (NHS Resolution, 2021). It is fundamental for nurses and midwives to realise that recording care is important from a legal perspective and adheres to professional standards (Dimond, 2011; Symon, 2017).

The quest to address the evidence gap involved planning this study using a participatory action research design to optimise best research practice. Previous studies exploring documentation used both qualitative and quantitative approaches (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011; Brooke-Read et al., 2012; Baillie et al., 2013; Okaisu et al., 2014; Crawford-Williams et al., 2015; Markam et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018a; Vafeai et al., 2018b). Researchers highlighted further related quantitative studies needs to include the views and experiences of the practitioners (Pelletier, Duffield, and Donoghue, 2005; Monsen et al., 2011; Boucher et al., 2012; Wang, Yu, and Hailey, 2013;

Neary, 2014; Ritchie et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2014; Šerková and Marečková, 2018). Furthermore, researchers highlighted that involving clinicians to glean their views in development of documentation review tools improves compliance (Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths, 2010; Boucher et al., 2012; Okaisu et al., 2014). Therefore, adopting this approach was necessary when developing a user-friendly and fit for purpose mechanism for use in clinical practice.

Key findings are now discussed under two main sections. The first one discussed is mechanisms and practicalities in the creation, implementation, and evaluation of the DOC Learning Tool. The second, focuses on professional development and lifelong learning opportunities from individual and organisational perspectives.

6.2 Mechanisms and practicalities of developing and using the DOC Learning Tool

This study created and developed the first effective mechanism to review midwifery documentation incorporating professional standards for nurses and Midwives (NMC, 2015; 2018). In addition, it took cognisance of the way individuals learn in clinical practice and integrated lifelong learning opportunities in everyday practice activities (NMC, 2018).

6.2.1 Development of the DOC Learning Tool

The DOC Learning Tool was successfully created and revised through action research cycles using a mixed method approach. Action research explores the social constructionism element of involving participants in the design process, which facilitates the integration of change (Burr, 2015; Polit and Beck, 2020). Other previous studies have emphasised the usefulness of participant involvement in successfully developing practice-based tools resulting in positive change and improved quality of documentation (Okaisu et al., 2014; Vafeai et al., 2018). The researchers also highlighted that documentation training alone was not enough to ensure the quality. Okaisu et al. (2014) and Vafeai et al. (2018) argued that to sustain any change in practice required a multi-faceted approach including best practice and involving staff and patients in the development of systems to improve care. However, researchers found that by examining clinical

documentation provided a catalyst for change within their hospital (Okaisu et al., 2014). Additionally, Vafeai et al. (2018) reported that involving staff in development and implementation of patient education forms significantly improved quality score of documentation.

Subsequently, midwives in this study were involved in the development and testing of the DOC Learning Tool by examining the quality of the case note sample documentation. Through this involvement, midwives confirmed that the DOC Learning Tool would be a valuable resource to improve clinical documentation.

Jones and Rattray, (2015) highlighted that validation of the instrument for face, content and construct validity is important to ensure the instrument is measuring exactly what it is supposed to do. Early in the study, midwives confirmed one hundred percent content validity and construct validity of the DOC Learning Tool. As detailed by Polit and Beck (2020) the new tool was constructed using a rudimentary approach to factor analysis confirming construct validity. This was achieved through linking sections of the Tool under the four pillars of The NMC Code (NMC, 2015). Although subjective in nature, all midwives confirmed face validity meaning the DOC Learning Tool was relevant to the practitioners using it (Jones and Rattray, 2015). Over the course of the study refinements were made to ensure the anonymised case note samples were robust and contemporary in accordance with the new implemented documentation systems. This ensured that the DOC Learning Tool was deemed fit for purpose in assessing real world clinical documentation.

In this study four cycles of testing took place, producing overall sample of 224 case note samples. To ensure construct validity and internal consistency of the DOC Learning Tool further statistical testing using a larger sample size would be required. Midwives approved of the DOC Learning Tool format including the structure limited to one page. They reported it was easy to use and appropriate for documentation reviews especially on the new electronic record system. Similar to findings in other studies, gaining inter rater agreement was a challenge (Larson et al., 2005; Monsen et al., 2011; Wang et al., 2014). Monsen et al. (2011) previously highlighted that inter rater reliability is poor even among experts.

Furthermore, Wang et al. (2014) stated that subjectivity is inevitable when reviewing documentation, especially when assessing subjective matter (Polit and Beck, 2020).

This was the case with the present study although over the course of the study, there was improvement noted in the mean score of rater agreement with a reduced range of scores. A statistical significance was noted between the mean of Cycle One and Cycle Four. These results demonstrated that the DOC Learning Tool was developing into a useful instrument to assess documentation. Adapting the Tool to refine the criteria and training the midwives in its use were important aspects of this study to ensure the reliability of the DOC Learning Tool. This is supported by Monsen et al. (2011) who recommended that reducing the items to be assessed, dropping unreliable criteria and ensure that the raters are appropriately trained in using the Tool was crucial.

Initially midwives reported challenges in using the DOC Learning Tool with the new electronic records and recommended alignment of electronic documentation systems and documentation tools is necessary for the reviews to be more efficient. Findings contribute to similar studies highlighting challenges in scoring electronic records (Markam et al., 2018; McCarthy et al., 2018; Ramukumba and Amouri, 2019) .

There is evidence that identified concerns surrounding subjectivity of using documentation tools (Wang et al., 2014). The midwives in this study revealed that they were not concerned about the subjectivity of the DOC Learning Tool. They attributed this to the fact that it would not be used in isolation. Even if there were discrepancies with scoring, meaningful discussion and reflection would naturally occur between the reviewee and reviewer. Therefore, subjectivity was not deemed to be an issue.

Midwives were already familiar with using the Red, Amber, Green (RAG) grading system within the Modified Early Obstetric Warning System (MEOWS) (Royal College of Physicians, 2012). They were unanimous in their agreement in supporting this grading method to be user friendly. This supports similar findings of using RAG grading in reviewing nursing documentation by Neary (2014). Following some debate around the ambiguity of the 'Amber' criteria, midwives

concluded this criterion should be retained as it served the purpose of providing constructive feedback to the midwife and a learning mechanism. This supported a 'softer' way of providing feedback rather than just right or wrong actions. The follow up feedback conversation would encourage reflection and learning. Midwives recommended more detailed explanation of the RAAG classifications on the DOC Learning Tool was included.

6.2.2 Application of the DOC Learning Tool

Midwives highlighted the value and important role the documentation review had in ensuring patient safety. Previous studies also stated they valued using a standardised tool to assess documentation (Basu and Seopela, 2010; Monsen et al., 2011; O'Brien and Cowman, 2011). This included advocated training surrounding conducting the review process and documentation itself (Broderick and Coffey, 2012; Asamani et al., 2014; Norouzi et al., 2018; Vafeai et al., 2018a). The midwives in this study also indicated the benefits of reviewing their documentation against the DOC Learning Tool especially since the advent of the electronic documentation system. Midwives in this study highlighted that lack of documentation could have major implications if their care came under scrutiny during legal cases in the future. They discussed that documentation provided evidence of care delivered. Additionally, it may be used to defend practice against litigation claims against them to the Regulatory Body (Nursing Midwifery Council) or in a court of law. They acknowledged that records provide an important role in protecting them from litigation. Furthermore, as midwifery cases could be filed up to 25 years following the birth of a child, midwives would be unable to recall all care events. Therefore, they would be unable to defend their actions or inactions unless they had clear and accurate documentation. Similar to findings by Vafeai et al. (2018a), midwives in this study also raised concern about the legal implications of failing to document the care that they provided. Interestingly these concerns were irrespective of their seniority in the organisation.

The midwives alluded to the fact that good documentation demonstrated that they are accountable practitioners who uphold the standards of The Code (NMC, 2015; 2018) Therefore the midwives felt that it was important that the DOC Learning Tool linked to the NMC Code (NMC, 2015; 2018) to provide them with

evidence that they had provided care. Also, to recognise that midwives were adhering to the rules of their profession and meeting the expected standards. They agreed that The Code (NMC, 2015; 2018) provided them with a benchmark of expected care, and documentation was a fundamental tool demonstrating achievement of that professional requirement. Furthermore, in concurrence with findings from earlier studies (Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths, 2010; Kent and Morrow, 2014), the midwives indicated that practitioners should value documentation and it should be person-centred and collaborative. In agreement with Wang, Hailey and Yu (2011) the midwives also found the main issue with health care documentation was that the focus was on the physical process, lacked detail about patient assessment and did not contain enough information on sociological, psychological, cultural or spiritual aspects of care. Furthermore, there was a lack of patient involvement in any decisions made and little patient education documented. Moving to electronic documentation is a necessity however having written documentation where rich qualitative data on healthcare was collated must not be diminished or overlooked. These are key areas necessary for the holistic overview of patient care which must be maintained in contemporary documentation.

Key findings related to midwives reporting the DOC learning Tool made them question their own clinical documentation against their professional standards (NMC 2015; 2018). Important issues such as documentation of evidence around consent and the woman's involvement in planning of her care was not transparent. This was particularly evident in the current electronic documentation system where no qualitative information was provided on either the woman's involvement in obtaining consent or care planning. This led the midwives to question if or where this important information was evidenced in the electronic documentation system. These current findings build on those of previous similar studies (Wang, Yu, and Hailey, 2014). Kent and Morrow (2014) also highlighted that documentation needs to be person-centred and collaborative demonstrating key omissions in the midwife's documentation. Numerous researchers have reported that the questions within a documentation review tool led the reviewers to also question if they were providing evidence of the quality-of-care assessment (Paans et al., 2013; Neary, 2014; Vowden and Vowden, 2015). As with previous studies, midwives realised the negative impact of poor documentation on

professional communication, patient safety and implications in legal and professional contexts (Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths, 2010; Paans et al., 2013; Vowden and Vowden, 2015)

6.2.3 Relevance of current documentation system

Midwives were concerned that since the advent of the EDS less reviews of their documentation had been undertaken. In their recent study Vafeai et al, (2018a) also reported this lack of governance surrounding nursing documentation was concerning. Midwives were also anxious and expressed that failure to review documentation meant that poor documentation went unchecked. These anxieties were related to the EDS similar to other study findings (O'Brien and Cowman, 2011; Mutshatshi et al., 2018; Norouzi et al., 2018). Conversely, Vafeai et al. (2018a) also reported anxieties in their studies, but midwives attributed this to the lack of documentation competency due to staff shortages and increased workload.

In agreement with previous studies (Markam et al., 2018; Ibrahim et al., 2019) midwives had a positive attitude towards the introduction of the EDS. They also reported that EDS benefited their day-to-day practice and reduced time taken for documentation allowing them more time for direct patient care. Whereas the paper systems were deemed to be repetitive, time consuming, easy to make mistakes and cumbersome. Documentation was easier to read in EDS, more comprehensive and improved the compliance of completion of fundamental details (Wang, Yu, and Hailey, 2013; Ay and Polat, 2016; Juwita et al., 2019). They agreed that EDS improved multi-professional access to patient information and improved care planning (Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015). These findings require further exploration as they were not evidenced in the current study.

In concurrence with Wang, Yu, and Hailey (2014), midwives reported that using the DOC Learning Tool did not improve the quality of documentation due to set algorithms, tick boxes and restricted text. Also, the midwives agreed that using electronic health records did not promote normality which was also a finding from Brooke-Read et al. (2012). As found by Wang, Yu, and Hailey (2014) the midwives commented that the new EDS was not conducive to encouraging midwives to provide a detailed account of patient care. The format of the system

consisted of a fair amount of tick boxes with little opportunity for qualitative information. Alarming, some of the midwives discussed how they had become dependent on the tick boxes within the electronic documentation system. The midwives explained that if the boxes had been ticked then they perceived that documentation in that section had been completed correctly. Through using the DOC Learning Tool, the midwives identified concerns that this reliance could lead to the potential documentation omissions of key clinical events. This was compounded by lack of detail that could be inserted into the 'free text box'. With some midwives admitting that they were unaware that a 'free text box' even existed. These findings were not apparent from the evidence reviewed. In addition, midwives expressed concern with the number of unapproved abbreviations used, especially newly qualified midwives within their documentation. This is a finding that had been corroborated by Johnston, Jefferies and Langdon (2010) in their study. Issues with lack of documentation, unapproved abbreviations and lack of knowledge surrounding the EDS led the midwives to discuss the need for discipline specific training on this system. This finding is also highlighted in previous studies (Wang, Yu, and Hailey, 2014; Strudwick and Eyasu, 2015; Markam et al., 2018; Juwita et al., 2019).

As stated by Strudwick and Eyasu (2015) the midwives highlighted that the development of EDS should incorporate detailed care planning and involve practitioners in its development. Wang, Yu, and Hailey (2014) also confirmed practitioner involvement and further indicated that ongoing support should be provided to staff in the form of super-users. This would be an interesting initiative to take forward in further research.

In this present study midwives discussed using the DOC Learning Tool with live electronic records and reported that training was required to support practitioners in documentary review. This agrees with Ramukumba and Amouri (2019) who highlighted in their study that time and training would be required to support practitioners in using a documentation assessment tool for online case notes. Ramukumba and Amouri (2019) recommended that EDS and documentation review tools should be aligned to ensure that time taken to review documentation is reduced. In addition, Jesudason (2019) study indicated that respect and openness were key components of learning and a need to involve learners / users

in the development of electronic resources was essential for service improvement to happen. This was not evident from this study and would be worthy of further exploration. Robb, Wells and Goodyear-Smith (2012) revealed that using online learning platforms embedded in clinical platforms were valued by practitioners. Furthermore, these platforms enabled the student / practitioner to review the resource multiple times (Power and Cole, 2017). The midwives from this study acknowledged that embedding the DOC Learning Tool at the end of each episode of care (antepartum, intrapartum, or postpartum) would encourage each individual practitioner to examine their documentation. Resulting in improved standard of documentation whilst maintaining contemporaneous records.

6.3 Person centred engagement and enhancement through learning

Through self-reflection the midwives confirmed that learning had occurred through the documentary review process. This finding emulates the concepts of phronesis within midwifery and takes cognisance of practical wisdom which is the philosophy of action research (Aristotle, 1999). Therefore, as well as quantitative measures for accuracy, it was also important to collate subjective responses to glean the wisdom from the practical actions of the midwives using the DOC Learning Tool. Multiple previous studies have also identified this in clinical practice where practitioners are consistently learning through reflection in-action and reflection on-action in their role (Jefferies, Johnson, and Griffiths, 2010; Wang, Hailey, and Yu, 2011; Boucher et al., 2012; Baillie et al., 2013; Ritchie et al., 2014; Rachmah and Wardani, 2018).

Most of the discussion from the midwives were based on how the DOC Learning Tool could be utilised through person centred engagement. Learning occurred by the midwives whilst using the Tool or having someone else review their documentation in clinical practice. Studies have revealed that facilitating this problem-based approach to learning into the clinical settings makes learning more authentic (Tweedie, Yerrell and Crozier, 2019; Van de Mortel et al., 2020). Midwives stated they preferred learning that was pertinent to their clinical area of expertise and preferred to 'learn on the job'. This finding was also identified in similar studies (Pool, et al., 2015; Al-Nuami, Ali and Ali, 2019; Moafimadani et al.,

2019; Loeloe et al., 2020). However, for learning to occur a positive culture of learning was required within the organisation (Pool, et al., 2015; Al-Nuami, Ali and Ali, 2019; Moafimadani et al., 2019; Loeloe et al., 2020). This was not a finding revealed in this present study.

The midwives discussed how the DOC Learning Tool could be used individually or within the organisation. Therefore, internal, and external perspectives are presented in the next few sections.

6.3.1 *Internal Perspectives*

Midwives discussed how the DOC Learning Tool could be used individually, through revalidation, reflection, and self-review.

The NMC revalidation process involves continuous professional development and reflection (NMC, 2018). Every three years each practitioner requires to submit five reflective accounts, on practical experiences, practice-related feedback or from continuous professional development as part of this process (NMC, 2021). Therefore, it makes sense to reflect on documentation as it is an integral part of nursing and midwifery care. Some of the midwives indicated that the DOC Learning Tool could be used as part of the NMC (2018) triennial revalidation process providing evidence of reflection and review of their practice.

Unanimously, the midwives discussed using the DOC Learning Tool for reflection on their documentation. The midwives highlighted through regular self-review of documentation using the Tool, they would pick up errors from their own documentation and learn from this. A key aspect of reflective practice (Johns, 1995). According to many theorists structured reflection is required to make sense of a practice-based experience (Dewey, 1938 cited in Mooney,2013; Carper, 1978; Johns, 1994). Johns (1995) utilised Carper's ways of knowing in his model of reflection concluding that the most important knowledge gained, is through reflection as it will inform future practice (Johns, 1995). Fundamentally, reflection offers a lifelong approach to learning (Naicker and van Rensburg, 2018).

Nurses and midwives use reflection in their day-to-day clinical practice (Boud, 2010). Therefore, it makes sense to learn and reflect on documentation, as it is

an integral part of nursing and midwifery care. In addition, Eneku and Evawoma-Eneka (2015) stated that reflection should be used as a benchmark to observe professional practice. The midwives also discussed how the DOC Learning Tool could be embedded into the current EDS to standardise practice for review of documentation on a case-by-case basis. This would become part of the culture and is an interesting finding from this study. The midwives highlighted that continual self-review of documentation and reflection would enable them to learn from this process and in turn lead to improved practice surrounding documentation. No other studies have raised these findings and more research into this would be worthy of exploration.

The midwives indicated they valued the opportunity to review their own documentation using the DOC Learning Tool rather than it just being used by managers. Self-directed learning is predominately used by educational institutions to encourage self-critical reflection and awareness (Veine et al., (2020). The midwives from this study agreed with findings by Cadorin, Cheng and Palese (2016). They indicated this would be a useful learning strategy for qualified nurses / midwives who work in challenging clinical environments that require to undertake lifelong learning. The midwives demonstrated readiness to this method of learning and recognised the contribution to their continuous professional development.

6.3.2 External perspectives

Midwives indicated the valuable lessons they had learned in the past when reviewing others documentation during peer review. It was identified that the DOC Learning Tool could be a valuable resource to use when teaching students and encourage inter-professional learning. Additionally, midwives highlighted that it would be a useful resource during the risk management process or as part of the annual review process with their line manager.

Interestingly, all midwives recommended that the DOC Learning Tool would be valuable to use during peer review of documentation or as a team. Especially for midwives reviewing colleagues' documentation who work in a similar clinical area. This was evident from a previous study where peer review of documentation became standardised practice within their practicing Health Board (Watson et al.,

2014). However, there is limited evidence on this finding. The midwives highlighted that this was good practice and suggested the DOC Learning Tool could be used to resurrect this professional approach to review the quality of documentation. Certainly, peer learning has been found to be a useful learning strategy for pre and post registration students within clinical practice (Barton et al., 2018; Davis and Richardson, 2017; Roberts, 2008; Turkey and Fertelli, 2017; Wuryanto et al., 2017). Previous work by Watson et al. (2014) also indicated that midwives valued peer review of documentation.

All midwives highlighted the value of using the DOC Learning Tool to provide positive and constructive feedback. Therefore, during peer review, midwives would discuss the results of the DOC Learning Tool with the reviewee. This replicates findings by Turkey and Fertelli (2017) regarding feedback during peer review. However, Currey et al. (2015) stressed the only direct benefit to peer feedback was collaborative learning. This collaborative learning involved in peer feedback was also raised by the midwives in this study illustrating that reviewer and reviewee both learned from the experiences. Midwives also recommended that follow up would be required if the documentation they reviewed caused some concern. This indicated that they would fulfil professional obligations (NMC, 2018). Midwives also discussed that training and support would be required for them to provide this feedback, recommending the need for an algorithm to be included in the DOC Learning Tool. This would provide specific instructions on who to contact if they had concerns about a colleague's documentation. These were interesting findings not identified in the previous body of literature reviewed.

Midwives indicated that the DOC Learning Tool would be a useful teaching tool for self and peer learning. Furthermore, this could be used with students or newly qualified staff to highlight the important aspects of documentation. They also highlighted that it could be valuable for other disciplines to adopt the DOC Learning Tool, including medical staff. Thereby fostering a culture of inter-professional learning (IPL). Online tools have been found to enhance IPL (O'Hara et al., 2018) and across the world, IPL is used by a wide variety of disciplines including nursing and midwifery (Zeeni et al., 2016; Barton et al., 2018; Coleman, 2018; Stephens and Ormandy, 2018). However, more studies surrounding the value of IPL in maternity settings is required.

In concurrence with Johnson, Jefferies, and Langdon (2010) the midwives from this study recommended that a tool to assess documentation would be valuable for managers as part of the annual review process. Furthermore, the midwives indicated that managers should take more interest in clinical documentation. This was a finding highlighted by Neary (2014) in a nursing study exploring documentation. Concern was raised by the midwives that the poor quality of documentation could affect the women's quality and standard of care resulting in an adverse incident. Midwives indicated that risk managers could use the DOC Learning Tool to review case notes where adverse incidents had occurred. Not only to provide learning points for the individual staff but also to highlight key learning issues for the organisation. In addition, this would also indicate if, and when, further education and training was required.

6.4 Chapter summary

Key findings from this participatory action research were discussed and compared with evidence from previous study findings. The DOC Learning Tool was confirmed through evaluation to be an effective mechanism to review midwifery documentation in accordance with NMC professional standards. Midwives were positive about the usefulness of the mechanism in everyday practice and confirmed it was user friendly and fit for purpose to review midwifery documentation. It was also positively recommended to facilitate lifelong learning; opportunities for individuals through revalidation, reflection, and self-review or within the organisation through peer review, as a teaching tool whilst encouraging interprofessional learning. Midwives also recognised the DOC Learning Tool had a potential role to play during the risk management process or as part of the annual review process. Overall, the DOC Learning Tool was confirmed to have positive benefits for professional, practical, and lifelong learning practice. This study has also identified some interesting new findings not previously identified in the literature, demonstrating original knowledge and contribution to the existing body of literature in this field.

Chapter Seven presents the challenges, reflection, and reflexivity of the study.

CHAPTER 7 CHALLENGES, REFLECTION AND REFLEXIVITY

7.1 Introduction

The challenges experienced across the lifespan of this study and how these were ameliorated are presented in this chapter. Ongoing active reflection throughout the research process is inherent in action research as previously evidenced. McNiff and Whitehead (2011) warn against reflection with no action and indeed Schön (1995) refers to reflexivity as reflection on and in practice. The essential roles of active reflection and reflexivity were intricately associated with the challenges highlighted in this chapter.

Reflexivity is also a key component in action research (Meyer and Cooper, 2015) and deemed to be best practice (Walker et al., 2013). The reflexive process offers transparency about the personal values and positionality of the researcher and how this may influence data collection and analysis (Walker et al., 2013) and demonstrates sound ethical practice (McNiff and Whitehead, 2010b). Whilst evidence of reflexivity is often missing from published papers, reflexivity is useful in qualitative and quantitative research as self-awareness and analysis enhances the quality of research studies (Polit and Beck, 2020; Walker et al 2013). As the researcher, I engaged actively, critically, and reflexively to acknowledge how my values influenced the research process. The process of reflexivity provided an open and honest reflection of the action and on my actions to present how this research could inform practice. Reflective summaries at the end of each testing cycle are provided in Chapter Five. Appendix 23 provides an extract of my reflective journal.

7.2 Challenges

The organisational, academic challenges as well as those of being a doctoral student are discussed next.

7.2.1 Organisational

Action research itself involves collaboration and participation (Gray, 2018) therefore it was important to reflect on the impact these factors had on the study. According to Meyer and Cooper (2015) action research involves a need for change however clinical staff need to willingly embrace the change to allow change to occur. McNiff and Whitehead (2011) highlighted that management 'buy-in' can be an issue in action research. Therefore, involving clinical staff throughout the process encourages this to happen. From the outset, this was not an issue as nursing and midwifery management were involved in the early World Café event leading to immediate support and endorsement of the study. Staff retirement and changes to job roles are constant in the clinical environment therefore the changing dynamics occurring in participant representation was inevitable during this seven-year study. By the end of the study, changes were evidenced in the reduction (from five to two members) in the representatives in the Action Research Sub-Group and in the replacement of the midwife population involved in testing of the DOC Learning Tools over the four cycles. Open and frank peer debriefing took place amongst the Action Research Subgroup after each focus group. According to Jolley (2020), this process is useful in ensuring the reflective process is open and transparent.

One ongoing challenge was securing engagement of midwives as participants in the study due to competing demands on clinical staff. Whilst midwives were willing to participate, clinical demands often took priority over participating in the study. Midwives were often called away to other clinical activities during testing the DOC Learning Tool and focus group appointments were often cancelled at short notice. Due to being an organisational insider (as previous senior midwife and employed as SoM), I was supportive of these situations as I knew midwives were keen to support this research and were familiar enough with me to feel comfortable with this non engagement. Nevertheless, it did incur further delay with the study and involved rescheduling appointments and deadlines. On reflection, this may not have happened so regularly if I was not professionally known to the midwives or managers.

Further organisational delay and challenges were evident when I was no longer an employee of the targeted Health Board (following the demise of statutory Supervision of Midwives). As a result, I had to apply and obtain an NHS research passport to continue with the study. This process proved challenging due to lengthy delays with administration at both NHS and HEI level which contributed to delays in testing of the DOC Learning Tool.

As previously reported, the first cycle of testing the DOC Learning Tool revealed flaws in the case note samples leading to further delays in testing until this issue was resolved. In addition, the targeted Health Board moved to using electronic record keeping in late 2017 resulting in further delay for the study to include this transition from paper to electronic records. Incorporating this amendment into the study was essential for the process to remain contemporary, relevant, and meaningful for the midwives reviewing the documentation. Therefore, preparing a full set of new sample case note documentation was required before proceeding with any further testing of the DOC Learning Tool. My role as researcher supported these delays to retain authenticity with the sample of case notes and to ensure meaningful testing in everyday practice and credibility of the study.

7.2.2 Academic

Throughout the life of this thesis, challenges were created due to balancing my roles as a part time doctoral student, full time midwifery lecturer, Pre-registration Midwifery Programme Leader, and deputy Lead Midwife for Education within the HEI. These roles were very demanding and challenging and over the seven years of the study I was required to pause my research (sometimes for months) to deal with the immediate demands of my academic role. This was especially evident during the Covid-19 pandemic which had a dramatic and immediate impact on the midwifery programme which required a profound and unprecedented move to a complete online theoretical delivery over a short time span and a series of contingency plans for clinical skills and practice placement continuation. This required major reorganisation of the programme and lengthy discussions with students, clinical areas, government and HEIs. During this time, I was acutely aware that my academic role was mandatory whereas my role as PhD. student was seen very much my own project and viewed by many as an optional hobby.

However, my line manager and supervisors were persistent in successfully gaining agreement for me to have protected study time to complete this study of which I am very grateful. Latterly, other competing demands such as the mandatory NMC re-approval of Midwifery programmes and UWS Institutional Led Review seriously impacted in further delay and disruption to the planned completion of the doctoral thesis.

7.2.3 Doctoral student

The main challenges I have encountered as a PhD student have been related to time constraints and changes to my supervisory team and specialist input. Hart and Bond (1996) cite time to complete action research as the major challenge for researchers, especially when undertaken as part of an academic award. Gray (2018) endorses this major challenge, warning that the research must not be manipulated to achieve academic goals due to time constraints. Certainly, time has been challenging during this research project. Resulting in delays during the testing phase. In addition, the decision to stop the testing of the DOC Learning Tool generated much discussion and debate with the supervision team. It was agreed to stop testing the DOC Learning Tool at the validation stage based on the action research evaluations to date. This was time sensitive to allow me time to analyse the data and write up the findings to comply with the academic deadline. Therefore, it was essential to focus on writing up the final doctoral thesis. The statistical validation of the DOC Learning Tool would be continued as a post-doctoral study.

One major challenge I faced were the multiple changes to my PhD supervision team which pervaded the study. The supervision team has included five different statisticians, three different second supervisors and three different internal assessors. The changes to the statistical input have been particularly challenging as each new statistician has had very different ideas about the study which has caused me persistent angst and confusion. Fortunately, there was a consensus plan agreed which enabled me to confidently progress the study. My Lead Supervisor has remained consistent which was appreciated. Alongside my critical friend, who became my second supervisor, has both provided me with invaluable support and encouragement throughout the study.

7.3 Reflections on self

As a clinician and educator, I have always learned and improved through reflection on clinical practice. Conducting reflections at the end of each cycle were useful not only to reflect on the testing itself but also myself as a researcher throughout this process. My aspiration to produce a fully statistically validated, user-friendly DOC Learning Tool ready for circulating to the world at the onset of the study was at best naïve and demonstrated my inexperience as a researcher and on the Action Research process. The process of conducting this action research study has honed my planning, organisational and research-related skills which has taken me on a valuable and worthwhile learning journey. The journey has been frustrating, as I do not like to give up on achieving final goals especially as I will need to continue the research as post doctorate studies to achieve full statistical validation of the DOC Learning Tool. However, there is no doubt that key self-learning occurred on so many personal and professional levels throughout the life of this study.

Personally, and professionally, I am a bit of a conundrum I enjoy structure and order, keeping things organised and easy to follow hence the development of the DOC Learning Tool to try to improve clinical documentation. Elements of analysis from a positivist approach were required to test and ultimately validate the DOC Learning Tool. However, I also embrace the subjectivism of involvement and participation which is fundamental to my psyche. Therefore, choosing action research, by its nature collaborative, to conduct this study was key. It was important to me to ensure that the midwives views and opinions were sought throughout the DOC Tool's development. There is no doubt that the meaningful information gathered from the focus groups provided valuable insight and added to the depth of the study, providing evidence of the reflective learning of the midwives that occurred during these sessions.

The strong interpersonal relationships that I had forged as a clinical midwife and SoM were important for the sustainability of the study. These relationships were apparent in the enthusiasm and engagement of the midwives.

Throughout this thesis I valued the importance of patience and stamina in the research process. In addition, this PhD study has fostered a lifelong approach to my learning and research. I have also embraced listening to the midwives during the focus groups who openly reflected and shared their own experiences and on the documentation practices identified. The midwives questioned assumptions they had made and those of others and offered explanations why they occurred. Furthermore, I enjoyed witnessing the 'light-bulb' moments that the midwives encountered, which will enable them to improve their own future documentary practice. Gaining viewpoints shared from these perspectives has confirmed that reflection as a valuable process in highlighting the important role lifelong learning has in learning together.

According to several action researchers it is important to reflect on the personal impact of conducting the research study and write this into the thesis (Cooper, Meyer and Holman, 2013; Meyer and Cooper, 2015; McNiff and Whitehead, 2011). Undertaken a PhD part-time whilst working in a full-time demanding job is a long and painful journey which at times can feel quite lonely and isolating interspersed with self-doubt. Throughout the life of this research, I have had the unquestioning support of my family and a few close friends as well as my supervisors. Furthermore, my dogged determination and stubbornness to never give up has sustained me to keep going. Without the support and my stubbornness to complete I would not have made this journey.

7.4 Chapter Summary

The process of active reflection highlighted several key issues which proved to be challenging throughout the life of this study. The main challenges were multifactorial and related to organisational issues, academic and doctoral student factors. Although these factors influenced the path and pace of the study, the challenges experienced also revealed that action research like change in an organisation is continuous and dynamic. The reflective process included the value of capturing the insights from experiences of midwives participating which added to the depth of the study. They provided evidence of the reflective learning of the midwives that occurred during these sessions. The process of reflexivity provided an open and honest reflection of the action and on my actions to inform

practice. Self-learning was evident on personal and professional levels throughout the life of this study. The final chapter will now summarise the study conclusions, implications, and recommendations.

CHAPTER 8 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

8.1 Introduction

This chapter presents the conclusion of this PAR study to develop an effective learning mechanism for midwives conducting documentary review in accordance with NMC professional standards. The strengths and limitations of the study are highlighted and explained. Implications of the findings for professional practice are presented and evidence-based recommendations are detailed to endorse specific actions regarding clinical practice, CPD and future research. This section will contextualise the philosophical, theoretical, and professional concepts within the action research study.

Evidencing care through case note documentation is fundamental for the everyday practice of health care professionals. The crucial role documentation must play in evidencing a high standard of quality assurance in patient care is widely published in the literature. Nevertheless, the standard in the quality of nursing and midwifery documentation remains a worldwide concern. Despite numerous attempts by researchers to develop an effective document review tool for the purpose of assessing the standard of nursing and midwifery documentation, this issue remains a gap in the literature. Therefore, the study aimed to address this gap by designing the research using best research practices, incorporating key professional standards, and integrating lifelong learning opportunities. The underpinning ethos of this approach was to design and construct a documentation review mechanism which was both practical and meaningful for nurses and midwives in their everyday practice.

Action research has no definitive end as the researcher always comes back to the change (McNiff, 2017), This process cannot continue indefinitely with a deadline for data collection required (Gray, 2018). This deadline enabled the researcher to have time allocated for analysis and share findings with participants to allow them time to agree their views were represented (Gray, 2018). Adopting this approach, the deadline was planned to coincide with sufficient evaluation to confidently support the DOC Learning Tool as an effective learning mechanism for midwives conducting documentary review in accordance with NMC standards for professional practice.

8.2 Conclusions

On several levels, this study has made a significant contribution to the current body of literature relating to the quality of documented care in nursing and midwifery practice. Overall, the aim of the study to develop an effective learning mechanism for documentary review was successfully achieved. This is the first ever mechanism co-created and developed involving midwives. It is also the first review mechanism to incorporate the NMC professional standards (NMC, 2015; 2018) and integrate learning theories promoting lifelong learning (NMC, 2018).

8.3 Effective Learning Mechanism

8.3.1 Creation and development of the DOC Learning Tool

Evidence from the literature confirmed that review of the quality of nursing and midwifery documentation is an essential component of professional practice. This study addressed a gap to successfully create and develop a review tool for documentation to take account of the holistic approach to care provided by midwives. A group of expert midwives were involved in the creation and development of the initial mechanism named the DOC Learning Tool (See Figure 8.1).

Figure 8.1: Summary of DOC Learning Tool to review midwifery documentation

8.3.2 Collaboration and ownership of the DOC Learning Tool

Successful collaboration with midwives was achieved in the development, implementation, evaluation of the DOC Learning Tool. This is evidenced from the outset of the study and promoted ownership of the DOC Learning Tool within the midwifery profession. The range of collaboration was evident across the designated groups, each with a specific role and function in the development of the DOC Learning Tool within the PAR process. Figure 8.2 summarises the professional groups involved.

Figure 8.2: Collaboration in development of the DOC Learning Tool

8.3.3 Implementation and evaluation of the DOC Learning Tool

The DOC Learning Tool was successfully implemented to review the ongoing development to review midwifery documentation over four discrete cycles of testing. This was in line with the nature of PAR. Through the detailed development process, face validity and content validity of the DOC Learning Tool was confirmed. Implementation, testing and evaluation by midwives confirmed the DOC Learning was reliable and 'fit for purpose' to review the quality of midwifery documentation. Benefits related to the ease of using the DOC Learning Tool in practice and the range of professional and lifelong learning opportunities provided to enhance midwifery practice and promote good practice in the midwifery profession and lifelong learning.

The evaluation process was strengthened with convergence of findings through the triangulation process. This was achieved through findings from research paradigms and across midwife groups (see Figure 8.3).

Figure 8.3: Triangulation of evaluation processes

8.4 Philosophical, theoretical, and professional concepts

Figure 8.4 presents a visual representation of the DOC Learning Tool in the context of the philosophical concepts, theoretical and professional basis underpinning the development process. Social constructionism required collaboration with practising midwives and experts in the specialist area. As the NMC Standards for professional practice provide a key measure of quality of health care, these were incorporated in the DOC Learning Tool which was supported by appropriate learning theories to facilitate lifelong learning in practitioners. Involvement and interaction of midwives in the implementation and evaluation process ensured the development progressed in a meaningful way to become contemporary, authentic, and fit for the purpose in everyday practice. Individual interpretation involved social constructivism to produce an authentic and contemporary DOC Learning Tool (Figure 8.4).

Figure 8.4: Integration of philosophical, theoretical, and professional concepts

8.5 Strengths and limitations

Researchers undergo a steep learning curve during the lifespan of a study and this study was no different. Despite the challenges faced, the researcher strived to adhere to the principles of action research throughout the study. The researcher embraced the strengths in study design and methodology which complemented the study process and acknowledged the limitations impacting on the study.

8.5.1 Strengths

Strengths in the study were evidenced through the research design, characteristics of the participants, methods adopted for data collection and analysis and the involvement of experts to guide the study. The origin of the study designed emerged through clinical need which was endorsed with the gap identified from the literature review. The study was planned to be ethically sound, and protection of the ethical principles remained high priority throughout.

Using action research was conducive to the involvement of practitioners in a study to address an issue for everyday practice. Therefore, involving practitioners in the research process ensured the study remained contemporary and relevant to clinical midwifery practice. The characteristics of the research design facilitated detailed planning and re-planning of the research process as the study progressed through the phases involved in contributing to the development and evaluation of an effective mechanism to review the quality of midwifery documentation. The Expert Working Group involved a wide range and number of relevant experts who were involved in developing the DOC Learning Tool and the subsequent confirmation of face and construct validity. This initial contribution of the EWG and ongoing guidance from the Action Research Sub-Group added credibility to the study.

Undoubtedly, one key strength was the underpinning principle of developing the effective mechanism to be user-friendly and meaningful for midwives in their everyday practice (Figure 8.2). The DOC Learning Tool was based on the NMC standards for professional practice and incorporated the ethos of supporting midwives with continuing professional development through appropriate learning theories. The detailed preparation and planning for both the DOC Learning Tool using the familiar

Red, Amber Green (RAG) scoring system with the selected sample of case note documents previously prepared and updated by the Clinical Risk Midwife and Action Research Subgroup ensured relevance for midwives and credibility for the study.

Midwives were recruited to the study from a busy Health Board within Scotland, involving urban and rural population. Midwives involved a typical skill mix from the general midwifery population, enhancing the credibility and generalisability of the study. Midwifery documentation is inherent in everyday clinical practice and midwives were already familiar with the purpose for reviewing case note documentation.

The research study used both quantitative and qualitative approaches to gather data which allowed a more transparent and complete picture of creation, development, and evaluation of the DOC Learning Tool. Using four cycles of action research enhanced validity, and reliability of the study as this included a large sample size of case note documents to test the DOC Learning Tool followed by a process of review, reflection, and refinement of the DOC Learning Tool, involving the Research Action subgroup. Choosing to interview the midwives about their experiences of documentation and their views of the DOC Learning Tool in focus groups, was a key strength of this study. The discussions between midwives, promoted self-disclosure and listening to the experiences of others this generated ideas and experiences. During discussions a few meaningful 'light-bulb' moments were achieved. Midwives revealed they had sudden recognition of knowledge, insight or revelation relating to the purpose, characteristics, or benefits of the DOC Learning Tool. Importantly, they acknowledged the value of reviewing the quality of the case note documentation in their everyday professional practice.

Only one researcher was involved in the full research study which enhanced the inter-rater reliability. The researcher remained consistent across the cyclical nature of the study in compiling reflective accounts with rationale for 'action' and 'in action' which can be rewarding for both the researcher and the organisation (Zuber-Sherritt, 2018). In addition, the researcher consistently applied reflexive practice which is emphasised to be essential in action research (Kindon, Pain, and Kesby, 2007).

The meaningful insights about the DOC learning Tool evaluation obtained through the focus group were informative and rich in detail despite the small sample size of

midwives in the qualitative phase. Thematic analysis was conducted using a systematic thematic analysis framework with findings and interpretation confirmed by the researcher's supervisors. Verification of findings from the focus groups were confirmed by the midwives to ensure accuracy and trustworthiness. Furthermore, reflections of research process were kept in a reflective diary by the researcher and discussed with the supervisors to ensure credibility and trustworthiness of the research.

8.5.2 Limitations

The study was compromised with organisational and statutory changes which were out with the control of the researcher. These included the decision of the Health Board in the early stages of the study to move from paper-based case note documents to electronic case note documents. This move to electronic case notes was in line with worldwide recommendations to decrease prescribing errors (World Health Organisation, 2012) and monitor patient outcomes for quality assurance purposes (Rocheftort, Buckeridge, and Abrahamowicz, 2015). In April 2017, the role of Supervision of Midwives in UK was removed as a statutory function. This statute change generated a significant delay as the researcher (no longer an employee of the Health Board) now needed a research passport to progress the study.

Whilst it is recognised that action research is time consuming (Gray, 2017), further delays in progressing the study were experienced. Over the duration of the study, ongoing recruitment of midwives was required to maintain the sample size due to staff mobility and retirement. Maintaining the sample number to progress the study was time consuming and caused frustration to the researcher as it added another layer of activity which detracted from progressing the study. The number of experts in the Action Research Subgroup also reduced over the study duration. The number of statisticians involved across the duration of the study did generate delays which was a limitation and source of frustration and confusion for the researcher.

The characteristics of action research involve being 'complementary and iterative' and as such adaptation and change occurs throughout the process (Reason and Bradbury, 2008). The cyclical nature involved in testing and refining the DOC Learning Tool generated significant delays in progress of the study. Although the DOC Learning Tool

was validated as being 'fit for purpose' through evaluation processes, the ultimate statistical validation stage was not possible within the time constraints of the study.

8.6 Implications and Recommendations

Clinical documentation has a crucial role to provide fundamental evidence of safe and effective care. The purpose of this action research study was to develop an effective mechanism to review the quality of midwifery documentation. Subsequent findings have highlighted the following important and useful implications for clinical practice and professional development. In addition, findings have informed the evidence-based recommendations presented which endorse specific actions for clinical practice, professional development, and future research.

8.6.1 Implications for clinical practice

- Regular review of midwifery documentation using the DOC Learning Tool would ensure documentation is of a high standard for quality assurance purposes.
- Embedding the DOC Learning Tool at the end of each episode of care in the Electronic Health Records (i.e., antepartum, intrapartum, or postpartum) will encourage individual practitioners to examine their documentation and improve the standard of the documentary evidence of the care they have provided.
- The DOC Learning Tool review criteria RAG (Red, Amber, Green) is beneficial and detailed explanation of the criteria is required in related guidance.
- DOC Learning Tool for documentation review will benefit other practitioners, especially nurses who adhere to the same professional standards (NMC, 2018).
- Practitioners need to be encouraged to prioritise contemporary accurate documentation as they would any other aspect of clinical care.
- Women's views and informed decisions on their clinical care need to be evidenced in documentation.

- Alignment of Electronic Health Records and documentation review tools is essential to improve efficiency and reduce the completion time.

8.6.2 Implications for professional development

- Regular self-review of documentation should be encouraged to promote reflective practice and life-long learning.
- Instill in clinicians that documentation is fundamental evidence in the provision of safe effective care.
- Embedding regular peer review of documentation in clinical practice will promote CPD opportunities.
- Involving students' midwives in the peer review process will facilitate them to learn the importance of accurate documentation.
- Including regular multidisciplinary CPD sessions on documentation in clinical practice using case studies will facilitate learning.
- Clinical documentation should be a key component in the curriculum for midwifery pre-registration programmes to midwifery.
- Training is required on keeping information private and confidential whilst using Electronic Health Records

8.6.1 Recommendations

Clinical practice:

- In collaboration with clinicians, develop evidence-based national and international guidance on completing clinical documentation.

Professional development:

- Integrate peer review of clinical midwifery documentation as one of the reflections essential for the NMC triennial revalidation.

8.6.3 Future research

- Conduct full statistical validation of the DOC Learning Tool for review of the quality of midwifery documentation.

- Conduct well planned and robust collaborative studies on the review of documentation in a wider range of clinical settings to inform evidence-based practice for the quality of clinical care.

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[sessmgr02&vid=3&format=EB&rid=2](http://web.a.ebscohost.com/ehost/ebookviewer/ebook/bmxlYmtfXzIzMTcxMI9fQU41?sid=5100b8eb-40b0-4daf-84ed-8ec698c88601@sdv-sessmgr02&vid=3&format=EB&rid=2) (Accessed: 17th of February 2021).

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1: Ideas and concepts

Appendix 2: Paper versus electronic records data extraction table (Table adapted from Siu and Comerasamy (2013))

Author(s) and Date	Author(s) Details	Philosophical Basis	Research Aim/Question	Methodology	Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions
Baillie et al. (2013)	Not stipulated. However, 3 from healthcare and 1 from university	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism and Interpretivism)	Investigate experiences of student nurses/ midwives' when learning to use EHRs i.e., improved quality of recordkeeping	Not stated	Survey n=215 3 Focus groups n= 6,5,6	Questionnaires And focus groups	Questionnaire data was analysed using SPSS v19. The focus group - thematic analysis	Students reported inconsistent exposure, education / training and access with EHR.	UK Clear training guidelines required for students and their mentors regarding EHR.
Wang, Yu and Hailey (2013)	1 PHD student 1 Research Fellow 1 Senior Lecturer	Quantitative (Positivism)	Describe nursing assessment documentation practices in aged care organisations and evaluate quality of electronic versus paper-based documentation	Retrospective nursing documentation audit study	Study samples were 2299 paper-based and 6997 electronic, from three aged care organisations	format, structure, and process of nursing documentation assessment (7 criteria)	Data analysis by SPSS (1.8 version)	Documentation varied.	Australia EHR more comprehensive notes in all settings.
Wang, Yu and Hailey (2015)	1 PHD student 1 Research Fellow 1 Senior Lecturer	Quantitative (Positivism)	The quality of paper-based versus electronic nursing care plan in Australian aged care homes	A documentation audit study	One hundred and eleven paper-based and 194 electronic nursing care plans, conveniently selected, were reviewed	The quantity of documentation in a care plan was determined using the QANDAC	Statistical analysis	Both types of nursing care plan were weak in documenting measurable and concrete resident outcomes.	Australia No difference between electronic records and paper-based records More qualitative research with nurses and care planning required.
Ibrahim et al. (2019)	4 PHDs	Quantitative (Positivism)	To examine factors that influence nurses' intention of	A cross-sectional design	Nurses (n=217)	An online survey using	Data were analysed using: hierarchical	Effort expectancy and nurses' individual	Canada Careful leadership required with introduction of

			using EDS in home care practice				linear regression and descriptive statistics	characteristics were not found to have a direct and/or moderating influence on nurses' intention to use EDS in home care practice.	electronic record keeping.
Markam et al. (2018)	3 PHD 1 Professor	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism and Interpretivism)	Exploring midwives need and intention to adopt an Electronic Antenatal Care recording mechanism	Not stated	42 maternity records 7 key stakeholders 100 midwives	The maternity records were Trained 100 midwives in electronic antenatal care documentation	Statistical analyses by SPSS	Inaccuracies of documentation age, education level and computer did not affect intention to use system.	Indonesia Need for electronic tool for ANC recording.
Ay and Polat (2016)	1 Midwife 1 Lecturer	Quantitative (Positivism)	To evaluate the validity and reliability of the Usability Scale of the Electronic Records System (ERS) in terms of Nursing Functions (USERSNurse)	Not stipulated	601 nurses completed the USERSNurse	USERSNurse Questionnaire	Analysis by SPSS 21.0	ERS – less time consuming. Good for research. Decreased paperwork. Improved service quality.	Turkey USERSNurse was found to be a reliable tool. Future studies proposed.
Strudwick and Eyasu (2015)	1 University Lecturer 1 Clinical Mental Health	Qualitative (Interpretivism)	review the literature on electronic health record (EHR) use by nurses in mental health clinical settings	Literature review	7 studies	Ovid/MEDLINE , PubMed, and the Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature databases were searched	Two researchers independently searched databases	EHR benefits included improved access to patient records including multiple access to patients notes at the same time.	Canada Specialist services such as mental health and midwifery need specific EHR and should be involved in developing EHR systems.

Juwita et al. (2019)	Not clear	Quantitative (Positivism)	To develop a web-based partograph midwifery documentation database research system.	Quasi-experimental comparative study	15 case notes – traditional documentation 15 web-based documentation		Univariate statistics	Ease, speed, security, and relevance of data.	Indonesia Web based documentation more efficient than conventional documentation.
McCarthy et al. (2018)	School of Nursing Institute of Technology	Quantitative (Positivism)	To review the evidence on the effects/impact of electronic nursing documentation interventions on promoting or improving quality care and/or patient safety in acute hospital settings	Systematic review	6 articles	CINAHL MEDLINE EMBASE	pre/post intervention studies reporting positively on at least one or more outcomes. and documentation of content.	EDS in acute hospital settings: saves time, reduces documentation errors and reduces infections and falls in an acute setting.	1 Canada, 3 USA, 1 Taiwan, 1 Switzerland
Brooke-Read et al. (2012)	2 Practice Educator 1 Reader in Healthcare 1 Senior Lecturer	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism and Interpretivism)	To investigate midwifery students experience of electronic health Records (EHR)	Not Stated	28 completed questionnaire n=64 preregistration student midwives and 2 post registration) for focus group	Questionnaire and focus group	SPSSv19 for questionnaire	Identified EHRs students used in clinical practice. Qualitative results: Benefits Accountability Disparity between using electronic documentation records and normality.	UK

Appendix 3: Documentation tools data extraction table (Table adapted from Siu and Comerasamy (2013))

Author(s) and Date	Author(s) Details	Philosophical Basis	Research Aim/Question	Methodology	Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions
Šerková and Mereckova (2018)	Research Student and Researcher from Czech Republic	Quantitative (Positivism)	To summarise relevant information on the creation and validation of the Quality of Nursing Diagnoses, Interventions and Outcomes (Q-DIO) assessment instrument	-	Three sources	Literature review	Statistical analysis by author of Q-DIO	content and face validation agreed by authors (100% consensus of experts and 88.25% agreement).	Czech Republic Q-DIO valid assessment tool by authors however Nursing terms should be agreed.
Crawford-Williams et al. (2015)	PHD student, researcher, senior lecturer 2 professors	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism and Interpretivism)	To review health education documentation (on alcohol consumption in pregnancy)	Not stated	32 documents	? 2 researchers (not stipulated) reviewed the documents using a modified DISCERN tool	By DISCERN tool and thematic analysis	Majority of documents scored low to moderate quality. Key theme – no safe level of alcohol consumption during pregnancy. Multiple subthemes including alcohol causes harm to fetus.	Australia DISCERN tool used to assess health promotion material. Need for better quality of documentation No comment on raters.
Ritchie et al. (2014)	1 Unclear? rep 2 Healthcare Workers 1 Lecturer	Quantitative (Positivism)	To develop an audit tool to evaluate documentation of partner abuse	Exploratory Study	2 raters reviewed 9 anonymised case records	5-step process informed by a quality improvement approach	By SPSS 11.5	good inter-rater reliability was achieved.	New Zealand Only nine records x 2 reviewed at interrater step 4 – only 2 raters.

						was used to develop the tool then the tool was tested for interrater reliability			
Tucker, and Fox (2014)	2 Senior Nurse 1 Researcher	Quantitative (Positivism)	To evaluate the REED (record, evidence, enquire and discuss) model of handover	Pilot comparison study – ward using REED handover model and one using traditional model	43 patients notes (23 from one ward using REED and 20 from another ward not using REED were reviewed	4 researchers Reviewed records and scored using 5 questions based on NMC guidance and also Trust guidelines	Not clear-but percentages provided	Ward using written handover scored higher than ward using verbal handover.	England One trust Small size.
Neary (2014)	Senior Lecturer	Quantitative (Positivism)	A study of whether staff who have completed an emergency nurse practitioner course provides more detail in their patient assessments	Modified interrupted time series design i.e., before and after attending course	10 participants who had attended course	Single site One researcher scored documentation pre and post course and rated them using a specially developed audit tool	Not clear however graphs provided of results	Post-course standards of documentation maintained /improved in some areas, but declined in others.	England Results inconclusive.
Wang et al. (2014)	1 PHD student 1 Research Fellow 1 Senior Lecturer 1 not stated	Quantitative (Positivism)	To develop a Quality of Australian Nursing Documentation in Aged Care (QANDAC) instrument to measure the quality of paper-based and electronic	The instrument was based on the nursing process model. Development involved five phases	Pilot study x 2 20 electronic records and 20 paper records assessed by 3 raters	Identify what constitutes quality of nursing documentation . Develop an instrument to assess the quality of documentation then test the instrument	Validity and interrater reliability	The instrument consisted of three sections: history taking and initial assessment, the care planning process and data conformity. Validity and inter-rater	Australia The QANDAC instrument may be useful to assess the quality of documentation in aged care settings.

			resident records					reliability confirmed.	
Johnson, Jefferies and Langdon (2010)	2 PhD Research Assistant	Quantitative (Positivism)	The Nursing and Midwifery Content Audit Tool (NMCAT) was developed to monitor the quality of nursing documentation	Mixed method design	A healthcare record audit was conducted on 200 records from 10 hospitals	Audits collected by author	Inter-rater reliability (85%) between two raters	The NMCAT – instrument was a logical presentation. From audit: nurses failed to document interventions including medications, provide contemporaneous entries. Readability of entries dubious at times. Use of unapproved abbreviations was problematic.	Australia Recommended: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Language support software • Writing coaches.

Appendix 4: Qualities and quality of documentation data extraction table (Table adapted from Siu and Comerasamy (2013))

Author(s) and Date	Author(s) Details	Philosophical Basis	Research Aim/Question	Methodology	Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions
Monsen et al. (2010)	7 Authors, 6 have clinical expertise All 7 have Master's or PHDs	Quantitative (Positivism)	To test a panel of experts approach at verifying public health nursing data	Retrospective cohort design	Convenience sample of 100 PHN files + 3 experts	PHN files were assessed and scored by experts. An agency then generated results	Statistical tests	Agreement averaged 42.0 (2 experts), 21.3 (3 experts), and only 7.8 (3 experts and agency). Intra-class correlation coefficients ranged from 0.35-0.63.	U.S.A. Interrater reliable not reliable even among the experts. ? More detail required to accurately score files Need for reliable documentation of clinical data.
Vowden and Vowden (2015)	Lecturer and Professor	Report	Quality of documentation	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Documentation has to be: Adequate Easy to follow Supports care delivery.	U.K. Need for Universal system of documentation linked to reporting.
Wang, Hailey and Yu (2011)	1 PHD Student 1 Research Fellow 1 Senior Lecturer	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism and Interpretivism)	To review the quality of nursing documentation and the instruments used to evaluate it	A mixed-method systematic review	Searches were made of seven electronic databases.	Data extracted through databases.	Systematic review	Errors in the quality of documentation affects nursing practice and patient outcomes.	Australia Comprehensive list of audit tools between 2000-2010.
Basu and Seopela (2010)	1 Researcher 1 Obstetrician	Quantitative (Positivism)	The aim was to evaluate the health professional's performance on	Retrospective record review	Antenatal clinic cards and obstetric files of 413 women	All components of antenatal cards were evaluated	Data were analysed using EPI info software. Numbers and percentages	Poor documentation of key areas.	South Africa May result in sub-standard antenatal care. In-service training necessary.

			documenting antenatal cards				were presented		
O'Brien and Cowman (2011)	1 MSc RGB 1 Professor	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism and Interpretivism)	To explore the nature and quality of documented care planning for pressure ulcers in a large teaching hospital in the Republic of Ireland	A mixed method design	85 Nursing records examined 13 nurses in focus groups	Retrospective evaluation of nursing records and focus group	Analysed using SPSS V15 Focus group - thematic analysis.	It was identified that Only 45% (n=38) of charts had some evidence of documented care planning, and of those 53% (n=20) had no evidence of implementation of the care plan and 66% (n=25) had no evidence of outcome evaluation.	Ireland Standardisation of documentation of pressure ulcer care required.
Okaisu et al. (2014)	3 Work in Children's Hospital 1 Practice Development	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism and Interpretivism)	The project aimed to improve nurses' documentation of their patient assessments at the CURE Children's Hospital of Uganda in order to enhance the quality of nursing practise	Action research	Number not stipulated-all nurses employed at the hospital	From charts Literature review interviews	Training workshop - no change. Modification of orientation programme and development of a documentation template - slight change at first then none. System changes to professionalism	The initial cycle revealed that staff training alone did not improve documentation It required improved staffing levels, service redesign and continuing Education programmes with leadership support.	Uganda Multiple approaches to achieve positive change: Evidence-based practise. Changes to systems and processes Changes to leadership style.
Norouzi et al. (2018)	1 Medical Student 3 Professors	Quantitative (Positivism)	Examine the quality of nursing		Convenience sample of 98 nurses	Four documents of the last document of	Descriptive statistics, independent t-test,	The results showed that in the structure domain, 69.1%	Iran some structure and content standards

			documentation in CCU			each nurse were evaluated using the researcher-made checklist based on documentation standards	ANOVA test and Pearson Correlation coefficient were used in SPSS 20 software	of documents had very good qualities. 49% of the documents in the content domain had also good qualities. In general, 28.4% had moderate, more than half (59.4%) good and only 12.2% had very good quality.	required to improve documentation.
Almasi et al. (2019)	6 Authors from Nursing / Medical background	Quantitative (Positivism)	The present study was performed to determine the effect of problem, intervention, evaluation (PIE) training on the quality of nursing students' documentation	Semi-experimental single-group study with a pre-test-post -test design	28 students randomly selected	The data collection tools included a demographic questionnaire, PIE documentation form and documentation quality checklist	A total of 112 reports were analysed using descriptive statistics and paired <i>t</i> test in SPSS	Based on the re/post test results of paired <i>t</i> test, there was a significant improvement in the quality of Documentation.	Iran PIE is effective in improving the quality of nursing documentation.
Broderick and Coffey (2012)	Nurse Manager PHD	Qualitative (Interpretivism)	To explore nursing documentation in long-term care	Qualitative descriptive	56 case records	Tool using PCN framework	Thematic analysis	Many records incomplete. Little or no evidence to suggest that patients were involved in decisions regarding their care.	Ireland Documentation that is person centred can contribute to a more meaningful relationship between cared and carer Education key.

Jefferies, Johnson and Griffiths (2010)	3 PHD	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism and Interpretivism)	To examine the the essentials of quality nursing documentation	Metastudy	28 articles from 171 papers	Through CINAHL and Medline	Themes	Nursing documentation should be: patient-centred Reflect clinical judgement of the nurse, logical and sequential, timeously, record variances in care, meet full legal requirements.	Australia
Vafaei et al. (2018)	1 PHD student. 3 Nursing Lecturers	Quantitative and Qualitative (Positivism and Interpretivism)	The aim of the study was to improve the nursing care documentation in an emergency department, in Iran	Action research study	200 case records 13 participants	1 st phase involved an educational workshop and improvements to the hospital technology systems . 2 nd phase involved recruitment of human resources, ongoing training, a good documentation reward system and an audit of patient education leaflets.	Percentages. Thematic analysis	nursing documentation improved 73.2%, which was a 32% improvement.	Iran improving nursing documentation are: employee participation, managerial accountability, nurses' compliance to nursing standards. Strong leadership Continuous monitoring.

Appendix 5: Barriers affecting compliance data extraction table (Table adapted from Siu and Comerasamy (2013))

Author(s) and Date	Author(s) Details	Philosophical Basis	Research Aim/Question	Methodology	Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions
Vafeai et al. (2018b)	1 PHD Student 3 Assistant Professors Department of Medical-Surgical Nursing	Qualitative (Interpretivism)	To identify barriers to improving the nursing documentation services using the experience of nurses in the emergency department of one of the Iranian hospitals	Not stated	20 nurses of variable grades	semi-structured interviews	Coding. Thematic analysis	The main themes were: documentation competency. Job burnout due to workload. Perceived control Issues with the health information system which impacted on time management to complete documentation . Legal issues.	Iran Preparatory work for action research by same authors.
Kamil, Rachmah and Wardani (2018)	3 Nursing, Leadership and Management Department	Qualitative (Interpretivism)	Identify issues with nursing documentation	Not stated	35 head nurses and staff	Focus groups x 2	Thematic analysis	Lack of supervision regarding nursing documentation . Issues with accuracy of documentation . Lack of confidence motivation in completing documentation .	Indonesia Lack of education major factor in completing documentation.

Boucher et al. (2012)	7, 6 MSc, 1 BSc all relevant field	Quantitative (Positivism)	To compare nursing compliance with, and completion of, two versions of a nursing care management form	Retrospective audit	Convenience sample of 134 medical records	5 researchers collected data between 3-month period	By SPSS-descriptive and correlation analyses were conducted	Compliance levels improved following the introduction of form B, although overall poor with 70% of nursing shifts recorded no information on the checklist document. Compliance levels were not related to age of nurse, length of stay or severity of patients illness.	Australia Compliance completing both forms was low
Asnirajanti, Hamid and Hariyati (2019)	Nursing Background x3	Quantitative (Positivism)	To identify nursing activities in the delivery of nursing care based on the documentation completed	Retrospective study	240 records examined	Using observation forms	Univariate statistics	Documentation of ongoing nursing care was poor.	Indonesia Every nursing activity and action plan requires documentation. Monitoring of standards of documentation required.

Pelletier, Duffield and Donoghue (2005)	3 clinical experts 2 PHD 1 MSc	Quantitative (Positivism)	Examine timing of documentation in two settings in NSW	Not stated	106 nurses in 2 care settings	Observation and data collection by two collectors	By statistical tests	16,395 observations of nursing activities recorded 37-38% of Nursing Day involves the transfer of information.	Australia Time required to document essential. Efficiently and effectively so as not to impact care.
Bailey, Wilson and Yoong (2015)	2 Medical Students and a Consultant Obstetrician and Gynaecologist	Quantitative (Positivism)	To explore what factors, affect midwives documentation	This was a prospective observational study.	Intrapartum notes/ partograms of 61 women	The quality of midwifery documentation at the beginning, middle and end of a 12-hr shift was assessed	Validated criteria NMC (2009) Plus, scoring based on intrapartum guidelines (NICE, 2007) (Documentation deteriorated middle to end of 12-hr shift, unaffected by workload or day/night shift Partogram documentation poorer in middle of shift (also not affected by shift pattern) however was influenced by women: midwife ratio. a	U.K. Documentation better at beginning of shifts. Tiredness a contributory factor. Recommended scheduled breaks especially middle to end of shift.

Asamani et al. (2014)	3 Senior Nurses 1 Lecturer	Quantitative (Positivism)	To examine current practices of nursing care documentation in Ghana	Multiple sampling strategies? Retrospective	100 patient care records in two hospitals	Via a tool designed by researchers using NMC guidelines and textbooks? and college of Registered Nurses of British Columbia	Data analysis was carried out using (SPSS v.16)	46% of care given to patients was not recorded. Progress notes, after admission were not completed 63% of the time and 57% of all documentation was not signed.	Ghana nursing care documentation practices in Ghana poor. Development of local documentation guidelines, training of nurses completed. Further research.
Shahverdi and Nasiri (2018)	MSc Student and Associate Professor	Quantitative (Positivism)	This study compared nurses' and head nurses' perspectives on the factors behind the quality of nursing documentation	Descriptive-correlational study	Random selection of 140 nurses and purposive sample of all 15 head nurses	Questionnaire	Statistical analysis	Head nurses / nurses scored similarly in personal, managerial, and organisational factors affecting the quality of nursing documentation ($p > 0.05$). Organisational factors being the biggest issue.	Iran

Kerkin, Lennox and Patterson (2018)	3 School of Midwifery	Quantitative (Positivism)	The aim of this article is to explore the literature in relation to the purposes of midwifery documentation.	Not applicable	56 articles included in discussion. 7 articles midwifery focussed	Through databases CINAHL and Pubmed	Electronic search by the three authors then hand searching of reference list where midwifery mentioned	No specific research articles found on the quality of midwifery documentation .	New Zealand midwifery documentation complex and multi-factorial.
Ramukumba and Amouri (2019)	Department of Health Studies	Qualitative (Interpretivism)	The aim of this study was to explore nurses' perspectives of the documentation audit process	Exploratory and descriptive	17 nurses	Semi-structure interviews conducted in focus groups	Thematic analysis	Three themes surrounding: Review of documentation evaluation of review and measures to improve the quality of nurses' documentation .	United Arab Emirates
Kent and Morrow (2014)	2 Practice Development Practitioners	Not applicable	To promote delivery of the three quality ambitions of safe, effective and person-centred care through improving documentation	Quality Improvement	One NHS Board	PDSA	Not stipulated	Policy produced in 2012.	Scotland Absence of governance in nursing and now midwifery regarding documentation.

Mutshatshi et al. (2018)	Department of Nursing Science	Qualitative (Interpretivism)	To explore and describe the challenges experienced by nurses with regard to record-keeping	Explorative and descriptive research design	Purposive n=13	Semi-structured interviews	Tesch's descriptive analysis	Nurses found record keeping challenging. Lack of time, volume of work and lack of resources.	South Africa
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Appendix 6: Inter-professional learning data extraction table (Table adapted from Siu and Comerasamy (2013))

Author(s) and Date	Author(s) Details	Philosophical Basis	Research Aim/Question	Methodology	Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions
Davies, Fletcher and Reeves (2016)	Researchers	Qualitative (Interpretivism) and Quantitative (Positivism)	Inter-professional education in maternity services: Is there evidence to support policy?	Review of IPL	8 articles focussed on maternity	Systematic review of MEDLINE, CINAHL, British Education Index and Applied Social Sciences Index and abstracts databases	Not stipulated although Prisma diagram included	Only eight articles focussing on IPE for maternity services were found.	UK Recommend more studies.
Stephens and Ormandy (2018)	School of Nursing, Midwifery and Social Work	Qualitative (Interpretivism)	To evaluate the impact of the IPL programme on the student's attitudes and values and to identify behaviour changes in clinical practice towards interprofessional working	Action Research)	Students from radiography, physiotherapy, social work and podiatry (n=63)	Data collected in semi-structured focus groups (n=37)	The students experiences of the IPL were examined	Imitating 'circles of care,' explored team building, encouraged reflection and self-assessment, may lead to changes in values, attitudes, and behaviours.	UK
Zeeni et al. (2016)	University Lecturers	Qualitative (Interpretivism) and Quantitative (Positivism)	Student perceptions towards interprofessional education	Quantitative survey	A longitudinal survey design	Questionnaires	ANOVA	Students ready to undertake IPL (Professional identity stronger in women compared to men) (Higher teamwork and collaboration in pharmacy and	Lebanon

								nutrition students. Lower patient centredness in nursing students. After participation in the IPE these differences decreased.	
Barton et al. (2018)	University Lecturers	Quantitative (Positivism)	Cadaver laboratory	Case sample	81 students from exercise, nursing, medical, occupational health, physical therapy Undergraduate and postgraduate	Anonymous course assessment survey Likert Scale	Not stipulated	Interprofessional collaboration effective way of learning. Peer observation useful. Improve relationships by creating a sense of community among peers.	USA
O'Hara et al. (2018)	4 Practice Education Facilitators	Evaluation	To develop an eLearning package for IPE	Logic model	Multiprofessional team developed module. 100 completed modules	Survey	Not stipulated	No formal evaluation. Mostly positive Feedback. Negative: length of module.	logic model provided a clear visual pathway in the creation of educational programmes. Interprofessional education (IPE) plays a key team working role. Failure to provide IPL/ Multidiscipline opportunities / among health professionals /

										students could lead to ineffective communication and patient care amongst disciplines in clinical practice.
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Appendix 7: Peer observation data extraction table (Table adapted from Siu and Comerasamy (2013))

Author(s) and Date	Author(s) Details	Philosophical Basis	Research Aim/Question	Methodology	Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions
Currey et al. (2015)	All work in university teaching healthcare	Qualitative (Interpretivism)	to investigate critical care nursing students' perceptions and experiences of TBL after it was introduced into the second half of their postgraduate specialty course	Not stipulated	32 students	Questionnaire	Not stipulated	no significant increase in satisfaction with peer evaluation. Higher student engagement in TBL classes.	Australia Team-based Learning Peer review.
Davis and Richardson (2017)	Student Nurse and Associate Professor	Qualitative (Interpretivism)	Introduction of peer facilitation scheme	Evaluation	Twelve 2 nd year student nurses to be peer facilitators for first – year clinical skills sessions. 300 BSc and 30 PGDIP nursing students	Questionnaire From Student Nurses Peer Facilitators and Lecturers	Not stipulated	Students stated the peers were approachable, provided practical advice, installed confidence. Lecturers noted good interaction between facilitators and lecturers. Also peer facilitators professional, inspiring, and insightful. Peer facilitators enjoyed the experience.	U.K. Peer facilitation enables students to be active learners, engages them in lifelong learning, develop their teaching skills especially if this is intradisciplinary.
Fertelli (2017)	Assistant Professor	Quantitative (Positivism)	The effects of students' assessment of nursing process through the Peer Assessment Method on critical thinking and peer	Experimental study	68 nursing students	The sociodemographic questionnaire, California Critical Thinking Disposition	Through statistical analysis	California Critical Thinking Disposition Inventory and Peer Support Scale scores of the experimental group improved.	Turkey peer assessment method was more effective in the development of critical.

			support in a clinical setting			Inventory and Peer Support Scale.		between first and second readings.	thinking and peer support of the nursing students.
Roberts (2008)	Nurse Lecturer	Qualitative	To explore whether nursing students learn from each other and, if so, how, when and where this learning takes place	Interpretive ethnographic	15 pre-registration students	Through observation	Thematic analysis	Fostered learning, survival skills and friendships in clinical practice as well as developing clinical skills.	U.K. Students used peers as a source to glean survival skills and learn how to be a nurse.
Wuryanto et al. (2007)	University Lecturers	Qualitative	To explore the experience of nursing students and clinical instructors, following the application of the OPT-peer learning model	Phenomenology	8 nursing students and 4 clinical instructors	Focus groups	Thematic analysis using Atlas software	Peer learning; improves clinical skills. Encourages self-directed learning. Reinforces North American Nursing Diagnosis Association (NANDA), Nursing Intervention Classification (NIC), and Nursing Outcome Classification (NOC); and helps with report writing.	Indonesia

Appendix 8: Reflection data extraction table (Table adapted from Siu and Comerasamy (2013))

Author(s) and Date	Author(s) Details	Philosophical Basis	Research Aim/Question	Methodology	Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions
Adamson and Dewar (2015)	School of Health Lecturer, Researcher	Qualitative	Project that sought to capture what compassionate care means within practice and utilise this learning within education	Action research study	37 student nurses – preregistration and post registration	Through online discussions. Only 16 students contributed to online discussion, although 33 students listened to the podcast of patient stories	Through narrative stories	Reflective learning and care giving story telling increases awareness of others' expectations and values and reinforces person centred care.	U.K.
Edwards (2017)	University Lecturer	Commentary	To move reflection from a 2-dimensional process to a 4-dimensional process	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Reflection in action, reflection on action and reflection before action and reflection beyond action.	U.K. Reflection can help foster a lifelong learning approach focusing on a holistic, practical approach to care
Embo et al. (2014)	Head of Midwifery 3 Professors	Quantitative	To investigate the relationship between reflection ability and clinical performance	Cross-sectional Retrospective, Longitudinal correlation cohort study	Cross-sectional data; Year 1 n= 69, Year 2=50, Year 3 n=50 Retrospective 95 students who had graduated in the previous 2 years	1 st , 2 nd and 3 rd year student midwives	Through statistical analysis	Moderate observed correlation between reflection ability and clinical performance scores. When adopting a cross-sectional perspective, all correlation.	Belgium Reflection important component in midwifery competence. Moderate but significant relationship between 'reflection ability' and

								values were significant ($p < 0.01$) and above 0.4, with the exception of the third-year correlations. indicated a high association between reflection ability and clinical performance (40.6).	'Clinical performance' scores in clinical practice
Enuku and Evawoma-Enuku (2015)	2 Lecturers	Discussion paper	To highlight the importance of reflective practice in Nigeria. To explore the concept of reflection and reflective practice in nursing. To examine the obstacles to reflective practice in nursing in Nigeria.	N/A	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Reflection improves practice - what could be done better. Alternative solutions. Encourages deep learning. Enhances problem solving skills -analysing problems to find solution. professional practices. Helps improve confidence.	Nigeria Challenges - no Mentor / Supervisor to discuss reflective practice. In Nigeria Reflection not in the curriculum. Reflection from experience powerful. Reflection not in the curriculum.
Naicker and van Rensburg (2018)	University Lecturers	Quantitative	Explore the role of educators in facilitating reflection for students	Explorative descriptive study	9 nursing institutions 121 nursing educators through a multi-staged probability sampling method	Structured questionnaire closed: demographics, Likert scale to explore reflective practice open and closed -	Statistical analysis	Only 46% said they studied reflective practice in their educator training. Only 37% used reflective practice themselves.	South Africa

						describe facilitation of reflection. 231 given out, 121 completed questionnaires: 52% return rate		Peer 98% used reflective practice with students.	

Appendix 9: Situational / Problem-based learning data extraction table (Table adapted from Siu and Comerasamy (2013))

Author(s) and Date	Author(s) Details	Philosophical Basis	Research Aim/Question	Methodology	Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions
Fitriani et al. (2020)	Post-registration Student and University Lecturers	Quantitative (Positivism)	To investigate the potential effects of problem-based learning (PBL), predict observe explain (POE), and PBLPOE on students' problem-solving skills and self-efficacy in Biology	Quasi-experiment	132 Biology students age 15-17 years	Essay test and observation sheets	Statistical tests	PBLPOE is effective in encouraging students' problem-solving skills and self-efficacy.	Indonesia PBL highly recommended .
Mackay, Riley and Dewing (2019)	One stated as a University Lecturer	Literature review	To determine effective learning and teaching strategies for clinical supervisor education and also gain expert opinion on literature review	Literature review and participatory study	22 peer reviewed articles 36 Clinical Supervisors	US (11), Australia (7), Canada (2), UK (1) and Sweden (1)	Thematic analysis	4 themes: Education and the influence on attitudes, knowledge and skills of clinical supervisors. Varying the modes of education Clinical Supervisors' beliefs about face-to-face networking. CPD for Clinical Supervisors required.	Australia
MacVane et al. (2015)	Associate Lecturer and 3 Lecturers	Discussion paper	Embedding 6 Cs using PBL Commitment, Courage, Care,	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	PBL facilitates positive communication and effective	U.K. PBL may be an effective way of developing

			Compassion, Competence, Communication					skills development. Through positive regard and mutual respect. Develops leadership skills. Fosters compassion and empathy through clinical story telling.	person centred compassionate care in qualified staff
Moafimadani et al. (2019)	University Lecturers	Qualitative	To identify a variety of variables, including attitudes, beliefs, and facts about nurses' organizational learning management in the field of health	Not stipulated	15 participants Purposive sampling	Semi structured interview	Thematic analysis Individual. Contextual and organisational factors	Individual. Contextual and organisational factors.	Iran
Pool et al. (2015)	2 University Lecturers 2 Researchers	Qualitative	To explore continuing professional development strategies among younger, middle-aged, and older nurses	Biographical approach	21 nurses	Semi-structured interviews	Audio recorded Transcribed Thematic analysis	Clinical work provided the catalyst for learning as was working with new equipment or procedures. Age group of nurses affected learning needs.	Netherlands CPD should be applicable to nurses' daily task. Demographics of work force should also be considered.
Russell and Coventry (2019)	Associate Professor Senior Lecturer	Qualitative	To determine the impact of the Graduate Diploma of Perioperative Nursing on student learning and career progression	A mixed methods descriptive study	n=67 for survey only 22 returned n=12 for focus group	Survey then focus group	Descriptive statistics	Learning Empowerment Opportunity (100 %) Staff development support (90 %) Online academic content (96 %).	Australia WIL (Work Integrated Learning)

								WIL (96 per cent).	
Tweedie, et al. (2019)	1 Lecturer 1 Practice Development Midwife 1 Professor of Midwifery	Evaluation	Collaborative coaching and learning in midwifery clinical placements	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Modified version of coaching model used in the CLiP pilot project in nursing embedded on an inpatient ward	Improved student participation and confidence. Student-led. Encouraged coaching Appreciation of other health care roles.	U.K. Coaching in midwifery education evaluated well
Van de Mortel et al. (2020)	12 authors with credible links to nursing and midwifery practice, education and research	Qualitative and Quantitative	To evaluate the acceptability of the Collaborative Clusters Education Model to stakeholders by examining their perceptions of the facilitators and barriers to the model in its implementation	Mixed methods	134 nursing students - response rate 13.5% Interviews: five new graduates, seven Entry to Practice facilitators, four Registered Nurses, and three Nurse Academics	Online survey with nursing students Interviews with new graduates, Entry to Practice facilitators, ward-based registered nurses, and academics	Descriptive statistics and Thematic analysis was conducted on qualitative data.	Students rated facilitators' effectiveness highly (4.43/5 ± 0.75).	Australia Low response rate (13.5%) Further research recommended .

Appendix 10: Self-directed learning data extraction table (Table adapted from Siu and Comerasamy (2013))

Author(s) and Date	Author(s) Details	Philosophical Basis	Research Aim/Question	Methodology	Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions
Cadorin, Chen and Palese (2016)	Three nursing lecturers	Quantitative (Positivism)	To test validity of self-rating scale of self-directed learning amongst Italian nursing students	Concurrent validity study	Target population n=428 undergraduate student nurses	Questionnaire	Pearson correlation: the confidence of intervals (CI 95 %) bias-corrected and accelerated bootstrap (BCa), were also calculated	The majority of participants were students attending their first year (47.9 %) and were predominately female (78.5 %). Their average age was 22.5 ± 4.1 . The SDL abilities scores as measured with the SRSSDL Ita (min 40, max 200), were, on average, 160.79 (95 % CI 159.10–162.57; median 160); while with the SDLI (min 20, max 100), they were on average 82.57 (95 % CI 81.79–83.38; median 83). The Pearson correlation between the SRSSDL Ita and SDLI instruments was 0.815 (CI BCa 95 %	Italy

								0.774-0.848), ($p = 0.000$)	
Aljohani and Fadila (2019)	Both from Community Health Nursing College	Quantitative (Positivism)	to determine the nursing students' readiness for self-directed learning (SDL) and their learning styles	A cross-sectional descriptive, analytical research design was utilized in the present study. Instruments: demographics, SDL readiness (SDLR), and student-recorded responses to an online visual, aural/auditory, read/write, and kinaesthetic (VARK) survey	Two-hundred and thirteen nursing students studying two programs (regular and bridging) responded to the study	Using an education scale for nursing education (Fishes-King, 2010)	Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS (version 20) to identify the descriptive and bivariate outcomes	The response rate was 76%. Learning style results showed that aural, read-write, visual, and kinaesthetic learning styles accounted for 19.7%, 8.5%, 6.6%, and 25.8% of participants, respectively. Desire for learning subscales were statistically significant for gender ($t = 1.985$, $P = 0.048$), academic level ($F = 2.969$, $P = 0.033$), and mode ($t = 3.610$, $P = 0.001$). The overall SDLR scale scores were significant for residence ($t = 4.938$, $P = 0.001$) and learning style ($F = 5.197$, $P = 0.002$).	Saudi Arabia Outdated VAK System

Appendix 11: Workshop data extraction table (Table adapted from Siu and Comerasamy (2013))

Author(s) and Date	Author(s) Details	Philosophical Basis	Research Aim/Question	Methodology	Sample	Data Collection	Data Analysis	Findings	Conclusions
Al-Nuami et al. (2019)	2 Professors and 1 Nurse	Quantitative	To evaluate the effectiveness of a breastfeeding educational workshop on Jordanian nurses' and midwives' knowledge, attitudes and practices towards breastfeeding	Pre-test was conducted for both groups. post-test was conducted 2 weeks after the intervention for both groups	A convenience sample of 82 nurses and midwives were Recruited: 42 intervention group and 40 in control group	Through pre-post-test questionnaire	Descriptive analysis	The results showed significantly higher mean and standard deviation in the intervention group (M=11.73; SD=2.6), compared to the control group (M=8.38; SD=2.59) after conducting the workshop ($P<0.001$).	Jordan workshop improved knowledge and practice of breastfeeding.
Ali et al. (2015)	Lecturers in Health	Quantitative	To enhance the knowledge and skills of community midwives	Pre and post-test evaluation	42 Community Midwives	Demographics, knowledge test MCQ and Skills Assessment via OSCE	Not stipulated	Pre-test participants scored less than 50%. Workshops increase knowledge to 70-80%.	Pakistan Practitioners prefer on the job training.
Caveião et al. (2017)	University Lecturers	Quantitative	Identify the tendencies and teaching-learning strategies used for leadership development in the discipline Nursing Administration in higher education institutions in Brazil	Non-experimental, type survey, descriptive and exploratory, cross-sectional	265 of the 777 Professors took part	Through data collection instrument	SPSS-descriptive and inferential statistics	The lecture was used by 241 (91%) Professors, research, by 237 (89%), and discussion or group work, by 221 (83%). Online programmes and spiral learning	Brazil

								were not widely used.	
Jesudason (2019)	Midwife Lecturer	Qualitative (Interpretivism) and Quantitative (Positivism)	The design and evaluation of the eLearning tutorial for the use of Q-Pulse	Action research	8 Midwifery Managers	Questionnaire and focus groups about use of Q Pulse and views of eLearning tutorial	Not stipulated	Cycle 1 - evaluation of Q Pulse Cycle 2 - development of eLearning resources.	Ireland Respect and openness key components of learning. Need to involve learners
Loeloe et al. (2020)	MSc Student Lecturer 2 Professors	Quantitative	To investigate the effects of on-the-job training (OJT) and workshop training methods on the report-writing performance of the midwives working in the teaching hospitals	Quasi-experimental study	70 midwives 35 OJT 35 workshops	questionnaires	Mann-Whitney U test and Friedman test using SPSS software (version 24)	No significant difference pre-intervention performance score (P=0.539). However, scores of OJT group were significantly higher than the workshop group during t training programme and one-month post-intervention ($p < 0.05$).	Iran OJT is effective in improving documentation performance of midwives intervention in improving the report-writing performance of midwives.
Power and Cole (2017)	Lecturer Senior Lecturer	Editorial	Implication of Xerte learning to teach obstetric emergencies	Discussion paper	Not applicable	Not applicable	Not applicable	Excellent feedback - eLearning. Can review multiple times.	U.K. Simulation-excellent resource - not for documentation
Robb et al. (2012)	2 Lecturers Post-graduate Chair	Qualitative (Interpretivism)	To explore whether incorporating an online values-based tool enhanced learning in a post graduate epidemiology course	Evaluation	613	Focus groups	Analysed by two independent coders	The Values - Exchange Healthcare encouraged decision-making, broadened their horizons and helped	New Zealand

								.consolidate evidence based practice.	
Scerri et al. (2017)	3 Lecturers	Qualitative (Interpretivism) and Quantitative (Positivism)	To review current evidence on dementia training programmes	Literature review	Fourteen peer-reviewed studies were identified with the majority being pre-test post-test investigations.	PubMed, Academic Search Complete, PsychInfo, CINAHL databases searched	Kirkpatrick's four level training evaluation model was used	No RCTs Methodological quality variable. Mainly short ward based interdisciplinary sessions using experiential and active learning.	Worldwide High quality research required to evaluate changes of staff behaviour/practices and patient outcomes following dementia training programmes.
Tuyisenge et al. (2018)	Researchers Clinicians	Quantitative and Qualitative	Explored the challenges that healthcare professionals who participated in a Continuing Professional Development (CPD) program on Advanced Life Support in Obstetrics® (ALSO) face in putting the learned knowledge and skills into practice in hospitals of Rwanda	Mixed methods	13	Interviews and data on turnover of staff	Not applicable	Small number of trainees in acute hospital settings only. Trainees valued shared learning experiences. Difficulties included staff shortages to allow attendance at course, lack of refresher training and high staff turn over	South Africa

Appendix 12: UWS ethical approval letter

UWS UNIVERSITY OF THE
WEST of SCOTLAND

Ref: WGM/ESB

School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery
Hamilton Campus
Caird Building
HAMILTON
ML3 0QA

22/04/2016

Jean Watson

Dear Jean,

Outcome of School of Health Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee

Thank you for your recent submission to the above Committee.

I can confirm your submission (SEC/SHNM/APRIL16/057) was reviewed by the Committee, where the outcome has been:

- **APPROVED - subject to External Body Approval(s)**
- **APPROVED - subject to required (compulsory) changes (under guidance of supervisor)**

This outcome requires you to refer to feedback, and address issues under guidance of supervisor.

Feedback from the Committee is attached for your information.

On behalf of the School Ethics Committee, I take this opportunity to wish you well with your study.

Yours sincerely,

Personal details withheld.

Dr W Gordon Mackay
Chair
School of Health Nursing & Midwifery Ethics Committee

CC Supervisor

Appendix 13: Letter of access

LETTER OF ACCESS (NON-NHS) BETWEEN NHS LANARKSHIRE AND

Researcher Name: Jean Watson

Employer / Place of Study: University of the West of Scotland

Report to: Lyn Clyde

(Principal investigator / Head of Department)

PERIOD of ACCESS

From: 06.07.17

To: 31.10.19

DECLARATIONS / SIGNATURES

1. EMPLOYER / PLACE OF STUDY REPRESENTATIVE (e.g. Line Manager / HR Department representative)

- I confirm that the necessary pre-engagement checks have been carried out, are satisfactory, and that the Researcher is suitably trained and experienced to undertake the duties associated with the research activities outlined in their Research Passport Application.
- As the Representative of the Researcher's Employer / Place of Study I confirm that we retain responsibility for ensuring that the Researcher has appropriate Occupational Health Clearance for the research activities that they will undertake within NHS Lanarkshire, including, but not limited to, appropriate immunisation. Health clearance has been undertaken in line with Scottish Government Health Clearance document - Health Clearance for Tuberculosis, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C and HIV for New Healthcare Workers with Direct Clinical Contact with Patients (2008) / or where relevant; Department of Health England Health Clearance document - Health Clearance for Tuberculosis, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C and HIV: new healthcare workers (2007). Immunisation screening has been undertaken in line with Immunisation against Infectious Disease – The Green Book (2013).
- As the Representative of the Researcher's Employer / Place of Study I agree that we will inform **NHS Lanarkshire** if we become aware of any issues that impact on their suitability or ability to carry out their agreed research activities within **NHS Lanarkshire**. This includes, but is not limited to, situations where PVG Scheme/Disclosure Scotland/CRB Disclosure vetting information suggests that the Researcher may have become unsuitable to do regulated work.
- I confirm that we retain full responsibility for ensuring compliance with all applicable clauses in the attached Letter of Access, and in particular for ensuring that your **Employee** is aware of, and agrees to comply with the terms contained therein.

Signature:

Date:

Name:

Position:

2. RESEARCHER

- I accept the offer of a Letter of Access from NHS Lanarkshire, and agree to comply with its terms.
- I agree to ensure that my Employer / Place of Study and NHS Lanarkshire are made aware of any issues that impact on my suitability to carry out my role, in particular, but not limited to, any changes to my health or criminal records check status.

Signature:

Date:

Name: Jean Watson

3. ON BEHALF OF NHS LANARKSHIRE

Signature:

Date:

Name: Raymond Hamill

Position: Senior R&D Manager

Jean Watson
Midwifery Programme Leader
University of the West of Scotland
Caird Building
Caird Park
Hamilton
ML3 0JB

R&D Department
Corporate Services Building
Monklands Hospital
Monkscourt Avenue
AIRDRIE
ML6 0JS

Date: 06.07.17
Enquiries to: Elizabeth McGonigal
R&D Facilitator

Dear Jean

Personal details withheld.

Project Number: L16097

Project title: A study to develop, implement and validate an effective mechanism to review the documentation of care provided by midwives in line with professional standards

Letter of Access (LoA) for a non-NHS researcher to carry out research

NOTE: Please complete sections 1 and 2 on Page 1 of this LoA and return it to the R&D Department at the above address. The R&D Manager will countersign and return Page 1 to you. The LoA becomes active only when you receive the countersigned Page 1, which you should attach to this letter as confirmation of your access to conduct research.

This letter confirms your right of access to conduct research through NHS Lanarkshire* for the purpose and on the terms and conditions set out below. This right of access commences on 06.07.17 and ends on 31.10.19 unless terminated earlier in accordance with the clauses below.

* Note: Independent Contractors (GPs / GDPs) are responsible for the governance arrangements related to any staff working on their premises. If you will be working with an Independent Contractor you should discuss your proposed arrangements with them directly. You are free to copy this letter to individual Practices, which may help facilitate that process; individual practices may also wish to issue their own formal letter confirming your right of access to their premises.

You have a right of access to conduct such research as confirmed in writing in the NHS Lanarkshire R&D Management Approval letter for the above named research project. Please note that you cannot start the research until the Chief Investigator for the research project has received a letter from NHS Lanarkshire giving permission to conduct the project.

While undertaking research through NHS Lanarkshire you will remain accountable to your employer / place of study **University of the West of Scotland** but you are required to follow the reasonable instructions of **Lyn Clyde** in NHS Lanarkshire or those given on her/his behalf in relation to the terms of this right of access.

You must supply the appropriate member of staff in your Human Resources Department with a copy of this Letter of Access. Your **Employer / place of study** must inform **NHS Lanarkshire** if it becomes aware of any issues that impact on your suitability or ability to carry out your agreed research activities within **NHS Lanarkshire**. This includes, but is not limited to, situations where PVG Scheme/Disclosure Scotland/CRB Disclosure vetting/criminal records check information suggests that you may have become unsuitable to do regulated work.

The information supplied about your role in research at NHS Lanarkshire has been reviewed and you do not require an honorary research contract with NHS Lanarkshire.

You are considered to be a legal visitor to NHS Lanarkshire premises. You are not entitled to any form of payment or access to other benefits or indemnity provided by NHS Lanarkshire to employees and this letter does not give rise to any other relationship between you and this NHS organisation, in particular that of an employee.

Where any third party claim is made, whether or not legal proceedings are issued, arising out of or in connection with your right of access, you are required to co-operate fully with any investigation by NHS Lanarkshire in connection with any such claim and to give all such assistance as may reasonably be required regarding the conduct of any legal proceedings.

You must act in accordance with NHS Lanarkshire policies and procedures, which are available to you upon request, and the Research Governance Framework.

You are required to co-operate with NHS Lanarkshire in discharging its duties under the Health and Safety at Work etc Act 1974 and other health and safety legislation and to take reasonable care for the health and safety of yourself and others while on NHS Lanarkshire premises. You must observe the same standards of care and propriety in dealing with patients, staff, visitors, equipment and premises as is expected of any other contract holder and you must act appropriately, responsibly and professionally at all times.

You are required to have the appropriate Occupational Health Clearance for the research activities that you will undertake within NHS Lanarkshire, including, but not limited to, appropriate immunisation; Health clearance has been undertaken in line with Scottish Government Health Clearance document - Health Clearance for Tuberculosis, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C and HIV for New Healthcare Workers with Direct Clinical Contact with Patients (2008) / or where relevant; Department of Health England Health Clearance document - Health Clearance for Tuberculosis, Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C and HIV: new healthcare workers (2007). Immunisation screening has been undertaken in line with Immunisation against Infectious Disease – The Green Book (2013).

You are required to ensure that all information regarding patients or staff remains secure and *strictly confidential* at all times. You must ensure that you understand and comply with the requirements of the NHS Confidentiality Code of Practice (<http://www.dh.gov.uk/assetRoot/04/06/92/54/04069254.pdf>) and the Data Protection Act 1998. Furthermore you should be aware that under the Act, unauthorised disclosure of information is an offence and such disclosures may lead to prosecution. You should ensure that, where you are issued with an identity or security card, a bleep number, email or library account, keys or protective clothing, these are returned upon termination of this arrangement. Please also ensure that while on the premises you wear your ID badge at all times, or are able to prove your identity if challenged. Please note that NHS Lanarkshire accepts no responsibility for damage to or loss of personal property.

We may terminate your right to attend at any time either by giving seven days' written notice to you or immediately without any notice if you are in breach of any of the terms or conditions described in this letter or if you commit any act that we reasonably consider to amount to serious misconduct or to be disruptive and/or prejudicial to the interests and/or business of this NHS organisation or if you are convicted of any criminal offence. Your substantive employer / place of study is responsible for your conduct during this research project and may in the circumstances described above instigate disciplinary action against you.

NHS Lanarkshire will not indemnify you against any liability incurred as a result of any breach of confidentiality or breach of the Data Protection Act 1998. Any breach of the Data Protection Act 1998 may result in legal action against you and/or your substantive employer.

If your current role or involvement in research changes, or any of the information provided in your Research Passport changes, you must inform your employer through their normal procedures. You must also inform your nominated manager in NHS Lanarkshire.

Yours sincerely

Personal details withheld.

Raymond Hamill
Senior Research & Development Manager

NAME	TITLE	CONTACT ADDRESS	ROLE
Dr William Mackay	Senior Lecturer	University of the West of Scotland	Sponsor Contact

Professor Jean Rankin	Professor	University of the West of Scotland	Named Contact
Lorraine Scott	HR Recruitment Manager	Law House, NHSL	Human Resources Contact
Lyn Clyde	Chief Midwife		Local Contact

Appendix 14: Research and development management approval letter

Mrs Jean R Watson
BSc Midwifery Programme Leader
University of the West of Scotland
Caird Building
Caird Park
Hamilton
ML3 0JB

R&D Department
Corporate Services Building
Monklands Hospital
Monkscourt Avenue
AIRDRIE
ML6 0JS

Date: 23.11.2016
Enquiries to: Elizabeth McGonigal,
R&D Facilitator

Personal details withheld.

Dear Jean

Project title: A study to develop, implement and validate an effective mechanism to review the documentation of care provided by midwives in line with professional standards.

R&D ID: L16097

I am writing to you as Chief Investigator of the above study to advise that R&D Management approval has been granted for the conduct of your study within NHS Lanarkshire as detailed below

NAME	TITLE	ROLE	NHSL SITE TO WHICH APPROVAL APPLIES
Jean Watson	BSc Midwifery Programme Leader	Principal Investigator	Wishaw General Hospital

For the study to be carried out you are subject to the following conditions: Conditions

- You are required to comply with Good Clinical Practice, Ethics Guidelines, Health & Safety Act 1999 and the Data Protection Act 1998.
- The research is carried out in accordance with the Scottish Executive's Research Governance Framework for Health and Community Care (copy available via the Chief Scientist Office website: <http://www.cso.scot.nhs.uk/> or the Research & Development Intranet site: <http://firstport2/staff-support/research-anddevelopment/default.aspx>)
- You must ensure that all confidential information is maintained in secure storage. You are further obligated under this agreement to report to the NHS Lanarkshire Data Protection Office and the Research &

Development Office infringements, either by accident or otherwise, which constitutes a breach of confidentiality.

- Clinical trial agreements (if applicable), or any other agreements in relation to the study, have been signed off by all relevant signatories.
- You must contact the Lead Nation Coordinating Centre if/when the project is subject to any minor or substantial amendments so that these can be appropriately assessed, and approved, where necessary.
- You notify the R&D Department if any additional researchers become involved in the project within NHS Lanarkshire
- You notify the R&D Department when you have completed your research, or if you decide to terminate it prematurely.
- You must send brief annual reports followed by a final report and summary to the R&D office in hard copy and electronic formats as well as any publications.
- If the research involves any investigators who are not employed by NHS Lanarkshire, but who will be dealing with NHS Lanarkshire patients, there may be a requirement for an SCRO check and occupational health assessment. If this is the case then please contact the R&D Department to make arrangements for this to be undertaken and an honorary contract issued.

I trust these conditions are acceptable to you.

Yours sincerely,

Personal details withheld.

Lorraine Quinn – Senior R&D Facilitator

cc.

NAME	TITLE	CONTACT ADDRESS	ROLE
Dr William Mackay	Senior Lecturer	University of the West of Scotland	Sponsor Contact
Professor Jean Rankin	Professor	University of the West of Scotland	Named Contact

Appendix 15: Research Passport

Research Passport Application Form – Version 3 01/09/2012

Please refer to the guidance notes before completing the form.

Personal details withheld. Original document: completed research passport application form.

Personal details withheld. Original document: completed research passport application form.

Personal details withheld. Original document: completed research passport application form.

Personal details withheld. Original document: completed research passport application form.

Personal details withheld. Original document: completed research passport application form.

Personal details withheld. Original document: completed research passport application form.

Personal details withheld. Original document: completed research passport application form.

Appendix 16: Documentation tool prior to new DOC learning tool

5 marks each	✓	3 marks	✓	0 mark	✓
Displays excellent account of care given		Displays generally account of care given		Displays limited account of care given	
All documentation: legible, written in black ink, alterations scored out using a single line followed by initials – always		More than half of the documentation: legible, written in black ink, alterations scored out using a single line followed by initials		Documentation illegible or not written in black ink, Or alterations not scored out using a single line followed by initials	
All entries dated timed and signed. Student midwife entries countersigned by registered practitioner if applicable				Some / no entries dated timed and signed. Student midwife entries not countersigned by registered practitioner	
Only approved abbreviations used		Few non approved abbreviations used		Multiple use of non-approved abbreviations	
Prescription charts accurately completed / no requirement for prescription chart				Prescription charts inaccurately completed	
CHI number recorded on documentation - always		CHI number recorded on documentation most of the time		CHI number recorded on documentation seldom/never	
All charts and inserts, completed and filed appropriately		Most charts and inserts completed and filed appropriately		Some / no charts and inserts, incomplete and / or filed inappropriately	
Evidence of consent noted throughout all documentation		Evidence of consent noted throughout most of the documentation		No evidence of consent noted throughout the documentation	
Total		Total		Total	
Overall total:					

Green

30- 40 - Excellent!

Very well

Keep up the good work

Watch out for minor errors

Amber

Score 18-29 - Satisfactory

Some areas for improvement required to your documentation

Overall satisfactory

Red

Score 17 or less - Unsatisfactory

Some major areas of concern.

Your Supervisor of Midwives will be informed. Please contact your SOM

for support and to discuss your documentation

Comments / Action plan:

Midwife reviewed.....

Reviewed by.....

Named Supervisor of Midwives notified **Yes / No**

Name of Supervisor of Midwives.....

Appendix 17: Information for participants; expert working group event (14.8.15)

Information for Participants

Thank you very much for accepting my invitation to attend an Expert Working Group on Friday the 14th of August.

- The venue is confirmed as room C3.16, Caird, Hamilton Campus, UWS
 - Time: 10am to approximately 4pm
 - Lunch and refreshments will be provided
 - Parking is booked
-
- 10.00-10.30hrs Tea, coffee and welcome
 - 10.30-13.00hrs Morning Session
 - 13.00-13.45hrs Lunch
 - 13.45-15.45hrs Afternoon session
 - 15.45-16.00hrs Close

The overall aim of this stage of my study is: To provide midwives with a facilitating mechanism that evidences the provision of care in their everyday practice.

Learning Outcomes

Develop, test and implement a documentation tool which provides midwives with evidence that they have:

- Documented care accurately
- Ongoing risk assessed (patient safety)
- Communicated patient care effectively with all disciplines

Morning session (10.30-13.00hrs) / Afternoon Session (13.45-15.45hrs)

The post-its and revised questions will be reviewed, and the questions revised. Voting and ranking will then take place to rate the importance of each question using a nominal group technique.

Nominal group technique

- The review of the questions silently
- Sharing of ideas in a round robin fashion
- Group interaction around ideas

- Explanatory group discussion
- Individual re-assessment and ranking and possible re ranking
- Mathematical tabulation of revised questions
- Formation of new audit tool

It is then proposed that following ethical approval this new audit tool (DOC) will be piloted in NHS Lanarkshire in 2016.

Reference

Nursing Midwifery Council (NMC) (2015) The Code: Professional standards of practice and behaviour for nurses and midwives. NMC: London

Appendix 18: Notes of expert working group event (14.8.15)

Notes of Expert Working Group Event

An expert working group facilitated by the researcher met on the 14th of August 2015 to examine the current Audit tool and develop it in accordance with the NMCs Code. Those invited included LME, Practice Development Director, Director of Nursing, Consultant Midwife, Maternity service manager, LSAMO, SOMS (all of the existing subgroup), midwives (n=13) and also the students Supervisor as observer / supporter.

The event was videotaped with verbal permission obtained from attendees at the start of the session.

In the morning the world café approach was taken and the group were asked to examine the existing tool **against each of the 4 main statements:**

- **Prioritising People (green)**
- **Practise Effectively(orange)**
- **Preserve Safety (blue)**
- **Promote Professionalism and Trust (pink)**

Further questions or points that they felt were missing could also be added.

These points were then written down on individual 'Post-its' and displayed under the 4 main statements.

In the afternoon a modified nominal group technique was used where each member examined the 'Post-its' silently and added any further comments / ideas.

A round robin discussion then took place where, in turn, each of the group was asked to highlight a main point and this was discussed further.

Main discussion points were:

- Rationale - giving evidence, for using or not using guideline.
- Professionals - promoting trust, role modelling for student, multi-professional.
- Person centredness - evidence of individual care, evidence of care planning.
- Safe standard of care, safe evidence-based practice - how do we evidence it?
- Communication - SBAR, DATEX, standardisation of escalating care - clear process, identify constraints.

Following this discussion, a list was produced containing 38 'Post-it' notes which were each numbered, 1-38. He facilitator then read out each item. The group was provided with a piece of paper and individually asked to vote their top 10 comments /questions.

This was then tallied up and a new list formulated. Comments/questions that received less than four votes was removed from the list. The facilitator then asked

the group to review the new list, review the 'discarded' list to ensure all pertinent topics had been covered and re-vote their top ten. One post-it was reinstated to the new list following the review, making a total of 26.

Following this, 16 questions / comments remained, each receiving three votes or more. They were presented in descending order in relation to votes as a thermometer with the "hottest" topic at top – most votes (8) to the "coolest" or lowest vote (3):

1. Has a timely and appropriate referral been made following assessment and documented within relevant paperwork (8 VOTES)
2. Evidence of discussion around risks/benefits of care been undertaken relevant to woman's uniqueness (7 VOTES)
3. Evidence of escalating concern? (7 VOTES)
4. Is there evidence to reflect rationale for decision around further reviews/subsequent plan of care? (7 VOTES)
5. Evidence that woman involved in planning of pregnancy journey demonstrated through use of woman's own words (6 VOTES)
6. Changes to birth plan clearly recorded with rationale and demonstration of woman's understanding through recording of her own words (6 VOTES)
7. Individualised care recorded showing evidence of informed consent and demonstration of woman's understanding (6 VOTES)
8. Documented evidence that individual needs of the woman is clear in her plan of care (6 VOTES)
9. How do we measure the documentation of multidisciplinary communication and appropriate escalation? (6 VOTES)
10. Excellent Care as opposed to excellent account (6 VOTES)
11. Identify inadequate time, resources staff (6 VOTES)
12. INTERITY evidence of situation that is causing delay- truths (5 VOTES)
13. All records appropriately completed within the different mediums i.e., case notes / online etc. (5 VOTES)
14. Was evidence-based care utilised in line with local policies / guidelines (5 VOTES)
15. Clear recording of discussions with women of changes to planned care. Woman's understanding demonstrated by use of her own words (4 VOTES)
16. Does the documentation indicate difficulties in communication relating to options for and delivery of care (3 VOTE)

Group thanked

Send out questions / comments for member check.

Appendix 19: Photographs of expert working group event (14.8.15)

Consent has been given by the photographed subjects to publish these photographs.

Appendix 20: Consent form

Consent form for the DOC tool

An action research study to pilot and test the DOC tool for reliability and validity: i.e.

The study aims to develop, implement and validate an effective mechanism to review the documentation of care provided by midwives in line with professional standards.

Name of Researcher: **Jean Watson**

		Please initial box
1.	I confirm that I have read and understand the information sheet dated 6/9/19 (version 5) for the above study and have had the opportunity to ask questions.	
2.	I understand that my participation is voluntary, and I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason without my medical care or legal rights being affected	
3.	I agree to take part in the above study and complete the DOC tools as instructed	
4	I agree to take part in a focus group to discuss using the DOC tool	

Name of Participant agreeing to participate:

Signature:

Date:

Name of Researcher:

Signature:

Date:

1 copy to participant and 1 copy for researcher.

Please return to researcher during DOC information session

Appendix 21: Participant information sheet

PARTICIPANT INFORMATION SHEET for DOC tool

You are invited to take part in an action research study to test a documentation tool for all record keeping. This new tool is called the **DOC** tool. The tool aims to check there is evidence that care is **D**ocumented accurately, there is evidence of **O**ngoing risk assessment (patient safety) and also that patient care is **C**ommunicated effectively with all disciplines. Hence called the **DOC** tool.

The study aims to develop, implement and validate an effective mechanism to review the documentation of care provided by midwives in line with professional standards.

Who is the researcher?

The researcher is currently a PhD student within the University of the West of Scotland and was a Supervisor of Midwives within NHS Lanarkshire.

Why have I been asked to take part?

This DOC tool is being developed specifically to assist midwives to review documentation to ensure they are achieving the NMC standards set out in the Code (NMC, 2018).

All we would like you to do is:

- Read this participant information leaflet
- Complete the consent form.
- Attend a DOC tool information session
- Complete four DOC tools to review four sets of anonymised printed copies of electronic notes that will be provided.
- You will also be invited to take part in a focus group to discuss using the DOC tool. The focus group will be audiotaped only for use by the researcher to extract data

Do I have to take part?

No., we would be grateful for your help, but the choice is yours.

If you choose to take part in the study, you can withdraw at any time. You can also complete the DOC tools and choose not to take part in the focus group.

Confidentiality

All DOC tools will be entirely confidential. Participants will be identified by numbers to aid the data extraction. The number will not be linked to any individual participant. The DOC tools will be analysed by the researcher from the University of the West of Scotland to fulfil PhD study requirements. Data extracted will not be identifiable to any participants only themes will be used as part of the data analysis and will be published as such.

The DOC tools and audio tapes of the focus group will be analysed by researchers from the University of the West of Scotland, data extracted, and a thesis produced. It will not be possible for anyone to link anything in the thesis to you.

The University of the West of Scotland and Health Protection Scotland are registered under the Data protection Act and has an Information Security Policy to safeguard the collection, processing and storage of confidential information.

What if you have any issues?

If you have any issues using the DOC tool or have any questions then please contact:

Researcher: Jean Watson, [REDACTED]

Research supervisor: Professor Jean Rankin, [REDACTED]

What if I want to find out more or have a complaint about the research?

If you want to find out more about this research or have a complaint about this research, please contact:

Professor Jean Rankin, University of the West of Scotland, [REDACTED]

[REDACTED]

Please keep this sheet for your information.

THANK YOU FOR YOUR HELP

Jean Watson

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 22: DOC Learning Tool for Cycle One and Cycle Two

<p>The DOC Tool is a peer review tool to critically examine all forms of record keeping to assess if the practitioner has:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Documented care accurately • Ongoing risk assessed (patient safety) • Communicated patient care effectively with all disciplines <p>Instructions: Please tick only one box for each Documentation Criteria</p> <p>Documentation Number (please circle the set of notes you reviewed): SWHMR 1 / SWHMR 2 / SWHMR 3/SWHMR 4</p>					
The NMC Standards	Documentation Criteria	N/A	YES	Missing on 1 occasion	NO or missing on ≥ 2 occasions
PRIORITISING PEOPLE	Evidence that the woman is involved in her care planning				
	Changes to plan of care clearly documented including rationale and action plan				
	Evidence of consent noted throughout all documentation				
PRACTICE EFFECTIVELY	Evidence of appropriate risk assessment				
	Evidence of referral and appropriate involvement of the multidisciplinary team				
	All records completed appropriately (**see record checklist)				
	Only NHS Board approved abbreviations used				
	CHI numbers on drug Kardex's: all records including electronic versions				
	Timely (as per NMC guidelines) and appropriate referral made and documented				
PRESERVE SAFETY	Evidence of rationale for decision around further reviews and plan of care				
	Factual account only, no personal opinions				
PROMOTES PROFESSIONALISM AND TRUST					
Total Score (for use of researcher only)					

DOC Score <i>(what the red, amber, green means)</i>	
All Green	Very well done. Keep up the good work. All professional standards on record keeping met (NMC, 2015)
Yellow x 1	Some areas for improvement required to your documentation.
Red x 1 or Yellow x 2	Some major areas of concern, please contact your Supervisor of Midwives (SOM) to discuss your documentation. A copy of this DOC tool will be forwarded to your named SOM.

Comments on using the DOC tool (please leave any comments you wish about using the tool)

Appendix 23: Reflective diary excerpt

Focus Group: Date 28th of March 2019 at 1pm

All participants who had previously completed a DOC tool were invited by email to take part in a focus group to discuss it. I had set some questions to ask about the DOC tool.

The focus group took part in the seminar room within the maternity wing of Wishaw General Hospital. In attendance three participants, field note taker (Lyz Howie) and me. All participants had already completed the DOC tool previously and consented to take part in a focus group at that time. Hospitality was offered to the participants on arrival. The focus group lasted 21 minutes and was audiotaped.

Feelings

Initially disappointed that only three participants turned up for focus group. Five had initially agreed to take part but unfortunately two had to withdraw at the last minute. I was nervous undertaking the Focus group as I have only done this once before during my MSc. My questions could have been more open at times and I could have asked participants to expand on some of the answers in more detail.

Analysis

I appreciated the participation of the three participants who are all busy practitioners. Participants appeared relaxed and contributed well throughout. The focus group flowed fairly well with participants allowing each other time to respond. Main themes appeared to be consent explicit in live electronic notes whereas not so in DOC tool samples. They liked the Red, Amber and Green (RAG) system. They felt it was a manageable tool, concise, easy to use in line with the code. Could be used as peer review, self -review or by managers. One participant highlighted it could be very useful for revalidation for individuals to ask peers to review their documentation and use this as evidence for revalidation.

Evaluation

Following the first listen to the audiotape and brief discussion with field note taker I was happy with the initial analysis however one key piece of information should have been explored in more detail. Participants like NMC headings, categories. Although the participants indicated that they all liked the RAG system one participant had indicated that they had a bit of an issue with the 'Amber' criteria which should have been explored. More questions would have helped ensure participants explored the key areas of the DOC tool. Also one of the participants indicated that they were using an audit tool to review documentation so this would need reviewing.

Issues with consent from printed out DOC case note sample evident. This element would need to be removed before further testing of DOC tool. Using live case notes would not be possible

Action Plan

- Review and adapt DOC tool for further refinement with Action Research Sub-group
- Review new NHS documentation tool
- Arrange another focus group with more specific questions surrounding the RAG system and also its use with revalidation
- Further round of testing of DOC tool

Appendix 24: Example of written case note for Cycle One

Labour

Labour and birth record: Initial assessment for **spontaneous labour** (continued)

Discussion of preferences for labour and birth

Comments and details of any revised preferences

Preterm labour 35+3.
 From 22/5/14 at 0715.
 Aware of options for pain relief.
 monitoring of baby discussed.

Signature

Date 23/5/14 01:00

Plans for initial care following discussion with the woman

would like Diamorphine. open minded regarding analgesia
 2nd dose of steroids given
 consent given for Active 3rd stage
 and Konakion 1m for baby
 Dad does not want to cut cord.
 continuous CTG monitoring.

Circle Pathway as per KCND Pathways for Maternity care Green - Midwife Led Care

Red - Maternity Team Care

Lead Care Provider for Intrapartum Care Consultant

Initial monitoring intentions for fetal heart rate:

Method CTE Reason for choice

Frequency CEFM Signature

Date 23/5/14 01:00

Please complete the "Whose Signature" page at the back of the record

20
19
18
17
16
15
14
13
12
11
10
9
8
7
6
5
4
3
2
1

1	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
2	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
3	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
4	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
5	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
6	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
7	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
8	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
9	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
10	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
11	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
12	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
13	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
14	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
15	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
16	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
17	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
18	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
19	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
20	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100

Sio of a live
girl @ 06:42
Appears
7/19/5

Syntocinon 10m

SYNTHONIN 12
PARALIN 10

Time
(use 24 hour clock)

Syntocinon

Epidural

Medications
(including all analgesia
& antacids)

Urinalysis

Urine volume

Maternal temperature (°C)

Pool temperature (°C)

Labour

Consideration should be given to pressure area care. Risks include immobility, moisture and poor nutrition.
 For further advice see www.healthcareimprovementscotland.org for SSKIN care bundle.

Date: _____ Time: _____ Details: 3st 2 Red Pathway Prim.

Please use 24 hour clock and sign each entry and insert your details in the 'Whose signature?' section on the back cover.

22/4/15 00⁴⁰ Diamorphine 10mg and Stavelil 12.5mg given M with consent.
 Care transferred from Antenatal booked from OT'S 22/5/14.
 VE at 00.20 by Dr 2-3cm Dilated
 Fully effaced
 Station 0+1
 2nd dose of Betamethasone given at 00.30.

00⁵⁵ Using entonox. vomitted 10mls. Post staff. Standing at side of bed.

01²⁰ Into bed, Contracting 3:10 moderate.

	Reassuring	Non reassuring	Abnormal
Baseline fetal heart rate	110-160 ✓ 120bpm	100-109 161-180	<100 >180
Variability bpm	5 bpm or more ✓	<5bpm for 40 mins or more but <90	<5 bpm for 90 mins or more
Accelerations	Present ✓		
Decelerations	None ✓	Early/variable decelerations Single prolonged <3 mins	Late decelerations Single prolonged deceleration >3 mins (bradycardia)
Opinion	Normal CTG all 4 features reassuring ✓	Suspicious CTG 1 non reassuring feature	Pathological CTG - 2 or more non reassuring or one or more abnormal
Syntocinon ml	Contractions 3/10	Maternal Pulse: 88	Liquor colour: N1
Plan of Care: Continue to observe	Date & Time 23/5/14 01 ¹⁰		
Sign _____	'Fresh eyes' Signature: _____		

Date	Time	Details
		35+3 Prim Red Pathway

Please use 24 hour clock and sign each entry and insert your details in the 'Whose signature?' section on the back cover.

23/5/14, 02³⁰

	Reassuring	Non-reassuring	Abnormal
Baseline fetal heart rate	110-160 110-120 ✓	100-109 161-180	<100 >180
Variability bpm	5 bpm or more ✓	<5 bpm for 40 mins or more but <90 mins	<5 bpm for 90 mins or more
Accelerations	Present ✓		
Decelerations	None	Early/variable decelerations Single ✓ prolonged <3 mins	Late Decelerations Single prolonged >3 mins (bradycardia)
Opinion	Normal CTG all 4 features reassuring	Suspicious CTG 1 non reassuring feature ✓	Pathological CTG - 2 or more non reassuring or one or more abnormal
Syntocinon	Contractions ..2...10	Maternal Pulse 96	Liquor colour:

Plan of Care: Continue to observe. Date & Time: 23/5/14 02.35AM

Signature _____ 'Fresh eyes' Signature: _____

02⁵⁰ Assisted up to the toilet, CTE stopped to allow same.

02⁵⁴ Back to bed, CTE recommenced. Fm 114 bpm. Maternal pulse 101 bpm

03¹⁵ Pushy involuntary. nil visible on in-band.

03²³ Vomitted. changed position to kneeling on bed. Fm 129 bpm

03²⁵ on in the room. For update. Maternal pulse 110 bpm. Fm 126 bpm

03⁴⁰ Position changed to sitting. continues to push involuntary, nil visible.

04⁰⁰ Vertex just visible at height of

Date	Time	Details
Please use 24 hour clock and sign each entry and insert your details in the 'Whose signature?' section on the back cover.		
23/5/14	04 ⁰⁵	decent contractions. Fm 146 mat pulse 108
	04 ¹⁰	OK in the room. Happy with cre.
		cre baseline 120-125bpm Variability > 5bpm
	04 ¹⁵	Fm 110bpm maternal pulse 106 bpm
	04 ²⁰	Fm 131bpm mat pulse 102 bpm
	04 ²⁵	Fm 123bpm mat pulse 103
	04 ³⁰	Vertex advancing slowly Fm 126 bpm maternal pulse 108 bpm
	04 ³⁵	Vertex advancing and receding Fm 100bpm maternal pulse 108 bpm
	04 ⁴⁰	Vertex advancing well.
		NMC called to attend by
	04 ⁴²	SVO of a live girl.
		Synthesizer 1014 give IM with coxart
	04 ⁵²	Placenta and membranes delivered by CCT.
		Small 2° tear noted. Skin intact.

Labour and birth summary - mother page 1

	Date	Onset	Duration	Print name	Designation	
First stage	22/5/14	23:00	5hrs.	Delivered by PIN Number of delivering midwife		
Second stage	23/5/14	04:00	1 hr			
Third stage	23/5/14	04:42	1 hr			Also present
End of third	23/5/14	04:52				Type of delivery <i>(if operative delivery, etc.)</i>
Total duration of labour			5hrs 52m	S/O		
SIRM /ARM	22/5/14	07:15				

Induction of labour No Yes

Indication _____

Augmentation of labour No Yes

Indication _____

Presence of meconium liquor 1st stage 2nd stage

Description of meconium _____

Maternal pyrexia in labour No Yes

Maternal antibiotics given No Yes

Details _____

Shoulder dystocia at birth No Yes

Maternal bloods taken No Yes

Indication yes Rh-ve

One-to-one midwifery care received throughout labour & childbirth No Yes

Comments _____

Labour & birth discussed No Yes

Preferences for labour & birth met No Yes

Comments _____

Signature: _____

Date 23/5/14

Instruments Tracking Label

energy health
 FEDERAL DELIVERY **2014**
 BL/FE
 UIN: 224842424
 *IC: 030667170480999017
 - 10.00.00000

Please complete the "Whose Signature" page at the back of the record

Labour and birth summary - mother page 2

Placenta, cord & membranes

Delivery: Controlled cord traction
 Maternal effort Manual removal
 Placenta appears Complete Incomplete
 Membranes appear Complete Incomplete
 Number of umbilical cord vessels 3
 Sent to pathology No Yes
 Indication _____

Comments _____

Perineum

Intact Grazes skin intact
 1st degree tear 2nd degree tear
 3rd degree tear 4th degree tear
 Episiotomy Labial tear

(If 3rd or 4th degree, document in 3rd stage complications pages)

Perineal suturing

Suture material Vicryl 6/0
 Anaesthesia Lidocaine 1% 2mls
 Technique Modified Flemming Technique

Rectal exam prior to suturing No Yes
 Haemostasis achieved No Yes
 Rectal exam following suturing No Yes
 Swabs correct No Yes
 Needles correct No Yes
 Tampon used No Yes
 Tampon removed No Yes
 Instruments correct No Yes

Checked by _____

and _____

Advised on perineal care No Yes

Sutured by _____

Routine Oxytocic drug administered	Dose	Route
<u>Syntocinon</u>	<u>10IU</u>	<u>IV</u>

Blood loss 200 ml

Blood transfusion/products received No Yes

Details _____

Post delivery

Maternal observations

First set on 23/5/14 at 04:55
 Temperature 36.6°C Pulse 115 BP 128/80

Pain/analgesia Comfortable

Fundus Firm Lochia Average

Second set on 23/5/14 at 06:00

Temperature 36.4°C Pulse 120 BP 127/82

Pain/analgesia Per Voltadol Bilamin sutured

Fundus Firm Lochia Average

Urinary function NR yet

Revised thrombosis risk after birth

Low Moderate High

Actions Required: _____

Mother transferred on / / at :

To _____

Reason _____

Perineal repair diagram

Please complete the "Whose Signature" page at the back of the record

Labour and birth summary - baby page 1 (if multiple birth please complete multiple birth baby page on reverse)

Mode of delivery SVD on Fri day 23/5/14 at 04:42 sex Girl

Indication _____ Presentation Cephalic Location wd 23

Livebirth Stillbirth Gestation 35+3 Birthweight 3140 g OFC 33.5 cm Length 44.4 cm
48cm

APGAR	1min	5mins	10mins
Activity (muscle tone)	1	2	
Pulse	2	2	
Grimace (reflex, irritability)	2	2	
Appearance (skin colour)	1	1	
Respiration	1	2	
Total scores	7	9	
Time to first breath	<u>at birth</u>		

Cord blood taken at time 04:43
Indication Rh -ve

Cord pH results No pH taken
Venous pH _____ Arterial pH _____
Base Excess _____ Base Excess _____

Vitamin K administered

No Yes

IM Oral

(sign for administration below)

O. Smls
as per

Skin-to-skin contact offered No Yes

Time started _____ Time ended _____

Reason discontinued _____

Comments _____

First feed offered / / time 05:30

Type of feed _____

Comments _____

Record of Vitamin K administration

Date	Drug	Dose	Route	Time (24 hr)	Prescriber (print and sign)	Given by	Time given (24 hr)
<u>23/5/14</u>	<u>KONAKION</u>	<u>0.5mg</u>	<u>IM</u>	<u>06:30</u>			<u>0625</u>

Resuscitation (tick all that apply)

Nil	
Inflation breaths	
Ventilation breaths	
Suction under direct vision	
Mask & IPPV	
Drugs-specify below	
Cardiac massage	
Endo-tracheal tube	
Description of baby at birth/resuscitation details	
Other-specify below	
Resuscitation performed by	
Sign	

Further details 35+3, SVD.

No resus. needed
- looks good size
- To stay in mum

Any anomalies identified at birth should be noted in the relevant sections of the baby/neonatal record for follow up.

Complete details of initial examination on baby record

Resuscitation performed by			Baby identification checked & correct by		
Signed	Print name	Designation/Grade	Signed	Print name	Designation

Please complete the "Whose Signature" page at the back of the record

Appendix 25: Interview schedule and prompt questions for Focus Group 1

Focus Group 1 – Interview Schedule

The sequence of questions for the focus group interviews was based on a schedule by Tod (2015).

Introduction

- The focus group took part in the participants clinical area of work.
- Ensured that participants were comfortable, and hospitality provided.
- The participants were welcomed by myself and introduced to the notetaker (they already knew me).
- The purpose of the focus group was explained to them.
- Written consent to take part in study was obtained.
- Verbal permission for digital audio recording was obtained.
- Purpose of focus group explained to group i.e., to elicit their views in the structure and content of the DOC Tool and any uses they think it may have in clinical practice.

Warm up

- A broad question was asked about how they found using the DOC Tool. A paper copy of the DOC Learning Tool was provided as a visual aid.
- Any general thoughts / observations about using the DOC Tool?

Main focus group questions (semi -structured)

- How did you feel completing the DOC Tool?
- What do you like about the DOC Tool?
- Any challenges about using the DOC Tool?
- How do you feel about peer review of documentation using the Tool?
- How else do you think the tool would be useful for?

Close of focus group

- Asked if participants had any final remarks.
- Participants were reminded of the confidentiality of the discussion within the group.
- Participants were informed that one member would be sent transcript to check for accuracy.
- Participants reminded if they have any questions then they could contact myself or my supervisor (details available on participant information sheet)
- Participants thanked and focus group ended.

APPENDIX 26: OBSERVER NOTES

Focus Group 26.9.19 AHC 16.27pm-16.55pm

Small warm room, no windows with bright light in a health centre that staff work in so familiar surroundings. Some outside noises in the corridor but not disruptive. All staff have refreshments and sitting on comfortable chairs.

Three participants where two out the three knew the researcher. All staff focussed and good eye contact with researcher. Actively listening to each other and allowing people to speak and acknowledging others contributions by head nodding and saying yeh, mmmh. Relaxed open postures leaning into the group and also using the tool as a reference throughout. Facilitator also included the quieter member of the group and encouraged them to contribute. Reinforcement of points by facilitator. Sitting in a nice circle where all can see each other.

Researcher gave information and good introduction prior to focus group. Consented again for audio recording.

Useful for peer review as xxxx a tick box and tool would highlight any problems

xxxx less rigorous with auditing and lack of feedback to know how their documentation is

Auditing swimmer notes monthly for peer review and not this now since xxxx

Not clear if women involved in care/choice or input.

Positive feedback about the tool. Didn't see any negatives. No changes required. Happy with green, amber, red.

Some question leading could have made them more open.

Uses for DOC tool: risk management. Would be good as a teaching tool for documentation with staff and students; One to one with your team leader to go through records that had been completed. Reflective tool for your own personal development.

Tick box of current notes quite evident and concern about this.

Use as a learning tool if pick up reds or ambers. Could be used in the documentation study days. What would they do with the outcome of problems...speak to other staff member? Highlight things that did do well and use for revalidation. Use it in their ePortfolio.

Highlight the positive...good to give positive feedback as negative tends to be given. Positive feedback more important. Use as an appraisal to instil confidence in colleague. Risk management could used tool and could feedback to all staff and identify gaps and training required.

Helps with complacency of documentation. Noted that the errors in the notes were quite alarming to see and help with why you need to write and giving formation rather than a tick box.

Linked it to MEOWS chart and scoring system and could have instructions on it as to where it could be referred to using levels of referral and levels of triggers to use to refer. Discrepancy as to whom would be best and at what stage so not to be too heavy handed.

Phone beeping went off...though did not appear to put group members off but facilitator aware.

Depends on how frequently observations are carried out will depend on whether you can address errors. Depends on level of severity would mean some form of referral. Might be speak to staff member then review or refer for training or attend a Learn pro module.

End of observer notes

Appendix 27: Transcript (Focus Group 1 Cycle Two)

- Focus Group 1

Researcher: Hi everybody and welcome to the DOC focus group. Thanks for coming along. I really appreciate your input. I have in front of me the DOC tool that you have all completed. So I would just really like to ask you a wee bit more about the DOC tool. So as I said you are free to say as much or as little as possible. I will ask a few wee questions along the way. And you know that it is being audio taped but just really just for my own transcription. So em we have the DOC tool in front of you and you did complete it. Can you say about how you felt about completing the DOC tool or how you felt?

Participant 1: Well, I'll start. I actually I liked the DOC tool when we had hand written notes. I thought it was excellent and I found it very easy to use. But I struggled when we have moved onto the electronic notes. Em mainly through, a lot of it about consent and stuff because if you tick a box on the electronic notes and they then assume consent because you've ticked a box to say consent. But when we were testing it again with the print outs from electronic notes it looked as if there had never been consent. But In the back of my mind was well you can't actually open that until you've ticked a box to say you've given consent. So and I know that is just one little part of it. But I found it more difficult to use with electronic notes than I had with the when we used to do the handwritten notes.

Participant 2: So I would agree with that because again I think, obviously because when we did look at it we were using a print off copy for the electronic notes and sometimes the flow is. It happens kind of chronologically on the way xxxx works when you are printing it off. But sometimes you do find you are going backwards and forwards a fair bit. I don't know if that's more to do with possibly the system as opposed to the tool but it made it kind of difficult to look at. Whereas I suppose when we used it before, when we used it with hand held notes. Em It was... It was probably the flow was better. Again it might be just purely down to the fact of that we are still although

we are used to using a system, when we actually print it off and look at it, it's a collection of notes and documentation. But we will be getting used to that

Researcher: Ok How do you feel, do you feel it would be useful, more useful as a live document when you were looking on line to do it or...

Participant 3: That's what I am thinking actually, just to do it with a live electronic record. So em with a laptop so bring it up and use the tool there instead of what we did which was produce paper copies. So that mightI think part of the problem is this originated when we had paper notes. We have changed the systems completely In the middle of this process which is very, very difficult to then adapt.

Researcher: Yeah

Participant 2: Yeah Because I think when you're looking, when you actually look at it as a live record you can go in and out the area. You know. You will probably be able to find the areas a lot quicker because you can click into a particular area as opposed to it flowing off chronological. the way it has been printed off.

Participant 3: And I guess if we were, if we are using the tool, as it's designed to do then we would use a live record. Yeah.

Researcher: So that's a kind of sort of systems and processes sort of issue about how we can take forward at this stage. But what about the actual, the tool content? Would you say, If you can imagine yourself looking at live notes and not looking at the printed off version of the electronic notes. Can you think about what sort of good,

bad ugly about that, what you would think of changing or to make it more useable, user friendly really?

Participant 3: What about what we really like. Like start with what we like about it.

Researcher: Yeah, whatever.

Participant 3: So I really like the headings and the categories. Just through the code I think that's really... because if we are, you know assessing someone's standard of documentation it's against that. So I really like the fact that it is broken down. So I think that's really good.

Participant 2: I agree. I agree with that. I like a RAG [*Red, Amber, Green*] system. I like a RAG [*Red, Amber, Green*] system

Participant 1: You do.

Participant 2: I like it for lots of things. So yes, that appealed to me too so I really liked that about it. I don't think

Participant 3: And it's you know on one page it's on one A4 [*Page size*] so it's a manageable thing.

Participant 2: And it is quite, it's concise in the fact of that, you know, that you are making a comment on e.g. Evidence of the woman being involved in a care planning and so actual fact, you are reviewing the whole, the case notes as a whole to see then if that has actually happened throughout. That there has been lots of conversation and lots of discussion. And obviously evidence of consent and things like that throughout. So that I think probably to quote something that I maybe I won't say didn't like but is that you would probably for me, I think, you had to. You would need to read the whole set of case notes and then use the tool.

Researcher: Yeah

Participant 2: As opposed to Yes there's that and tick and things like that. So I suppose it's about different people and how they would approach it.

Researcher: Okay.

Participant 1: I would just say exactly the same actually. I do like the fact that it is in line with the code. And I like a RAG [*Red, Amber, Green*] as well. And but again with the changes from 2016 to now from going from SWHMR [*Scottish Woman Held Maternity Records*] to xxxx, yes it would reading the whole, the whole case note and

Researcher: Episode of care?

Participant 1: And then completing it. But I find myself when we were testing it actually doing that, actually reading the whole, all the pages first before I then went back to that and then started

Participant 2: It's almost as if you would need to do, like if you did a labour episode of care. So you may be used it for one aspect of care like labour care and then post-natal care

Participant 1: So a separate one for each

Participant 2: A separate one for each to try.

Participant 2: Because actually to read a whole set of notes and then you maybe forget, did, did I say that, did I imagine her saying that?

Participant 3: I suppose the question then would be are we using the tool to assess full episodes of care or are we using it to assess an individual's standard of documentation. So that's the question. In which case you would only focus on that particular

Participant 2: Yeah. So it's what it's being used for at that moment in time.

Researcher: And that's a good point too because we are developing it as a tool to be used as a training or for peer review or sort of for multiple purposes. So it can be used as peer review or as, em yeah for training purposes or for just for audit you know, or improvement. So did you find anything particularly challenging when you were looking at it at the tool, to complete it. Was there anything that you found difficult to follow or?

Participant 3: I think the... I think the amber bit in the middle sometimes can be difficult to make your decision. I think if you simply use the tool and understand that's a standardised approach and that's what we want. But quite often if you are assessing one aspect of it and you think technically it would be amber but you know, my judgement would be, that's the highest that's a good standard I think the amber part is a wee bit of a challenge? I think, you know the black and white, it's really good. It fulfils everything. The red it's below standard but they are easy to do. But I also understand that you need that bit in the middle.

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Researcher: So you mentioned that you liked the RAG [*Red, Amber Green*] system. You mentioned the RAG [Red, Amber, Green] system. So you are quite comfortable having the Red and the Amber and the Green part of it. You think that's okay

Participants 1, 2, and 3: Yeah

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Participant 3: I think it is perfect for peer review. That's because that you have got your parameters and you know that it is a specific area of care.

Researcher: Okay. Thank you. Okay

Participant 1: Just it is easy to follow, it's not, so it doesn't have to be somebody that's looked at it before or seen it over a few years. It is a bit of instruction and it is easy to follow and as you say if you are using it for peer review then it is going to be a peer. So it's not going to be, as I imagine from peer review. It's not going to be somebody in the labour ward looking at somebody in day assessments documentation and care, so yeah your parameters are there. You know exactly

Researcher: And what if there is a problem now that supervisors of midwives are gone. What if there's a problem with somebody that peer documentation or probably self-review is not going to come up with but certainly peer or manager review of documentation using this tool maybe flag up. Managers not the problem probably just the peer review. What happens with the peer review If there is an issue with somebody's documentation.

Participant 2: I think that's down to the Individual midwife has got that responsibility to highlight that. Not only to the midwife but also through the line management structure if it is really bad. I think If it's something that's they've noticed that's in the black. Or the blacks good. Sorry. In the red. Here's me and in the RAG [*Red, Amber, Green*] I think, I think as midwives, we have that responsibility. Cause if its evidence its care, its well. That's my thoughts.

Participant 3: I think you might. Would we want instructions though for people in the back to say? You know

Participant 1: This is what to do.

Participant 3: In this instance, this is what you do. So actually a kind of step by step.

Participant 2: It might actually be that somebody in that situation might not feel quite comfortable doing that. So it's probably a wee bit about being supported in doing that. Instruction and maybe...

Participant 3: Yeah escalation

Participant 1: Okay

Participant 1: Who is asking for you to do the peer review? Is it, when we did it in the past? I know It was getting tested in the past and we sort of were under the umbrella of supervision at that point as well. So it's who is asking us to do it. Will it just be

something that every midwife would be asked to peer review five colleagues? So that we, so that it is something that everybody is doing or are there going to be certain people chosen to *(next participant starts talking)*

Participant 2: So it's whether then that everybody feels comfortable. Obviously there will be an element of training on it for people eh but there will be. But do they feel comfortable doing it. Is there an escalation plan but all over through are we escalated it in and getting support but also, oh I've lost my train of thought now. Em the purpose, and I can't remember actually what I was going to say.

Participant 1: The positive. A learning tool. Something we could learn from. It's not purely typical.

Participant 3: I could almost see it being part of like the revalidation process where an individual would, they maybe would self-review their own documentation and part of the revalidation, you would look at your own documentation and it would actually be better if you, they went and said XXXXX *[Name]*, would you peer, so it's coming from individuals rather than us putting it on them. Would you review mine and that's... Then that becomes part of your

Participant 2: That would actually be very good. And whether it's part of revalidation you have got somebody to do it and whatever then there's possibly a bit of reflection within it and that could form. So yeah. Good use for that.

Participant 1: Good.

Researcher: So that's us really sort of covered the peer element, the self-element of the and also the sort of management looking at the tool. Do you see it as a kind of ... Like when you are looking at the online, if it was something that could be added onto xxxx for instance. In not you know as a kind of check list almost at the end as an episode of care you mentioned about labour or before discharge or is that just putting the onus on the individual midwives.

Participant 2: I think you would lose a wee bit on it, within it because you've not got. Then xxxx would be electronically checking your notes. They would only be able to check for fundamental things like consent or you know... the quality then

Participant 1: Or if you are putting it on like that sometimes then it becomes a tick box exercise. Tick, tick, tick, tick, tick. Because it is very easy on an electronic system just to go yes, yes, yes, yes, yes. Yes I have done it correctly. I am sure that every unit that's using xxxx has the same. Where we all come across especially when we are reviewing notes as often as some of us do, where xxxx, it is just, it's only asking you to tick a box. It's not actually asking you for an explanation, where I think if that's in paper form and somebody's sitting down and actually that's my opinion.

Participant 2: The other side of it as well is the kind of that you would get feedback then, If you are doing it on paper and it's someone doing it from that side, then you will have feedback positive.

Participant 3: Maybe just further down the line maybe when it is well embedded and its part of everyday practice and it's used day in and day out. Then at that point it could be part of the electronic record. But my feeling is you would go through that process first.

Researcher: So far we have been looking at just some of the findings and sometimes there's quite a variety, a variation within the group, action learning group. There's been a bit of variation. Do you think the idea is to produce something that we could use as objectively as possible? How do you feel? You are all senior members of the organisation. How do you feel about that? The subjectivity amongst like people assessing the Documentation. How do you feel about that? Even using you know the tool.

Participant 3: I don't think you can remove it.

Participant 2: I don't think so. I think everyone has got different (participant

Participant 3: I don't think you can take that out no matter how good a tool is, Individuals have got their own viewpoint.

Participant 3: It's as good as we can be to give us standard set questions and parameters but XXXXX [Name] and I will always look at something differently. That's just how it is

Researcher: Yeah Okay. Em, that's great. Is there anything you would like to say about. Do you think it would be useful for yourselves as sort of senior people in the organisation as well as midwives.

Participant 1: For the amount of notes that just through, I know my job and I won't speak for anybody else in the room but yes I would. I think it would be.

Participant 2: We all, we are doing a form of documentation using a different tool at the moment. Em I think probably as time evolved it would be just nice to see that is the one we've got, is this better?

Researcher: Okay

Participant 3: Can I just ask you one thing? Just The score part at the bottom what would happen with that, or is that

Researcher: At the moment the score part is actually just about seeing how many. There are variations so every box has got a tick, so if for instance it was all this DOC tool was all green, em you would score sort of zero. You didn't get a mark off it for scoring. So then it's compared so it's more about for statistical analysis.

Participant 3: Because I don't remember scoring anybody.

Researcher: Sorry it is for me. Sorry, no it's actually alright. It is just for me. Research It's okay. It's only just for scoring. It's only just for me and the statistician to have a look at. But it's just to compare. So like you know looking at an all green one. It would be if all the ticks were in the right place. Then it would be sort of score zero. If there is one variation of that kind of thing. Okay?

Participant 3: Yes

Researcher: Thank you very much.

End of Focus Group 1

Appendix 28: Synopsis of comments from DOC Learning Tool

Synopsis of comments obtained from the free text box on the back of the DOC Learning Tool.

Comments	Number of times cited
Really like DOC Tool easy to use	16
Like the tool is on one page	11
RAG system easy to follow	9
Good to include NMC Standards in Tool	2
RAG system easy to follow	2
Difficult to use Tool with printed version of electronic notes	2
Chart section should not be included in Tool	2
Could be used as a learning tool for peer review	2
Good to reflect on documentation	1
Include observation section on Tool	1
Tool should be used in everyday practice	1

Appendix 29: Thematic analysis process: Stage 1

Researcher: Hi everybody and welcome to the DOC focus group. Thanks for coming along. I really appreciate your input. I have in front of me the DOC tool that you have all completed at least once. if you can remember back... So I would just really like to ask you a wee bit more about the DOC tool. So as I said you are free to say as much or as little as possible. I will ask a few wee questions along the way. And you know that it is being audio taped but just really just for my own transcription. So em we have the DOC tool in front of you and you did complete it. Can you say about how you felt about completing the DOC tool or how you felt?

Participant 1: Well I'll start. I actually I liked the DOC tool when we had hand written notes. I thought it was excellent and I found it very easy to use. But I struggled when we have moved onto the electronic notes. Em mainly through, a lot of it about consent and stuff because if you tick a box on the electronic notes and they then assume consent because you've ticked a box to say consent. But when we were testing it again with the print outs from electronic notes it looked as if there had never been consent. But In the back of my mind was well you can't actually open that until you've ticked a box to say you've given consent. So and I know that is just one little part of it. But I found it more difficult to use with electronic notes than I had with the when we used to do the handwritten notes.

Participant 2: So I would agree with that because again I think, obviously because when we did look at it we were using a print off copy for the electronic notes and sometimes the flow is. It happens kind of chronologically on the way XXXX works when you are printing it off. But sometimes you do find you are going backwards and forwards a fair bit. I don't know if that's more to do with possibly the system as opposed to the tool but it made it kind of difficult to look at. Whereas I suppose when we used it before, when we used it with hand held notes. Em It was... It was probably the flow was better. Again it might be just purely down to the fact of that we are still although we

are used to using a system, when we actually print it off and look at it, it's a collection of notes and documentation but we will be getting used to that

Researcher: Ok How do you feel, do you feel it would be useful, more useful as a live Document when you were looking on line to do it or...

Participant 3: That's what I am thinking actually, just to do it with a live electronic record. So em with a laptop so bring it up and use the tool there instead of what we did which was produce paper copies. So that mightI think part of the problem is this originated when we had paper notes. We have changed the systems completely In the middle of this process which is very, very difficult to then adapt.

Researcher: Yeah

Participant 2: Yeah Because I think when you're looking, when you actually look at it as a live record you can go in and out the area. You know. You will probably be able to find the areas a lot quicker because you can click into a particular area as opposed to it flowing off chronological. the way it has been printed off.

Participant 3: And I guess if we were, if we are using the tool, as it's designed to do then we would use a live record. Yeah.

Researcher: So that's a kind of sort of systems and processes sort of issue about how we can take forward at this stage. But what about the actual, the tool content? Would you say, If you can imagine yourself looking at live notes and not looking at the printed off version of the electronic notes. Can you think about what sort of good, bad ugly about that, what you would think of changing or to make it more useable, user friendly really?

Participant 3: What about what we really like. Like start with what we like about it.

Researcher: Yeah, whatever.

Participant 3: So I really like the headings and the categories. Just through the code I think that's really... because if we are, you know assessing someone's standard of documentation. It's against that. So I really like the fact that it is broken down. So I think that's really good.

Participant 2: I agree. I agree with that. I like a RAG [Red, Amber, Green] system. I like a RAG [Red, Amber, Green] system

Participant 1: You do.

Participant 2: I like it for lots of things. So yes, that appealed to me too so I really liked that about it. I don't think

Participant 3: And it's you know on one page it's on one A4 [Page size] so it's a manageable thing.

Participant 2: And it is quite, it's concise in the fact of that, you know, that you are making a comment on e.g. Evidence of the woman being involved in a care planning and so actual fact, you are reviewing the whole, the case notes as a whole to see then if that has actually happened throughout. That there has been lots of conversation and lots of discussion. And obviously evidence of consent and things like that throughout. So that I think probably to quote something that I maybe I won't say didn't like but is that you would probably for me, I think, you had to. You would need to read the whole set of case notes and then use the tool.

Researcher: Yeah

Participant 2: As opposed to Yes there's that and tick and things like that. So I suppose it's about different people and how they would approach it.

Researcher: Okay.

Participant 1: I would just say exactly the same actually. I do like the fact that it is in line with the code. And I like a RAG as well. And but again with the changes from 2016 to now from going from SWHMR [*Scottish Woman Held Maternity Records*] to xxx, yes it would reading the whole, the whole case note and

Researcher: Episode of care?

Participant 1: And then completing it. But I find myself when we were testing it actually doing that, actually reading the whole, all the pages first before I then went back to that and then started

Participant 2: It's almost as if you would need to do, like if you did a labour episode of care. So you maybe used it for one aspect of care like labour care and then post-natal care

Participant 1: So a separate one for each

Participant 2: A separate one for each to try.

Participant 2: Because actually to read a whole set of notes and then you maybe forget, did, did I say that, did I imagine her saying that?

Participant 3: I suppose the question then would be are we using the tool to assess full episodes of care or are we using it to assess an individual's standard of documentation. So that's the question. In which case you would only focus on that particular

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Then it would be sort of score zero. If there is one variation of that kind of thing. Okay?

Participant 3: Yes

Researcher: Thank you very much.

End of Focus Group

Appendix 30: Thematic analysis process: Stage 2

Appendix 32: Quantitative analysis method and key

Key

This is the questions from the left side of the DOC Learning Tool and is colour coded. The questions are related to the four pillars of the NMC Code (2018)

- Green: Prioritising people
- Amber: Practice effectively
- Blue: Preserve safety
- Red: Promotes professionalism and trust

- **Green, Amber and Red criteria** were ticked by participants.
- **Blank box or Black box** means that the participants did not complete this section completed or NA

Evidence that the woman is involved in her care planning

Changes to plan of care clearly documented including rationale and action plan

Evidence of consent noted throughout all documentation

Evidence of appropriate risk assessment

Evidence of referral and appropriate involvement of the multidisciplinary team

All records completed appropriately ("see record checklist)

Only NHS Board approved abbreviations used

CHI numbers on drug Kardex's: all records including electronic versions

Timely (as per NMC guidelines) and appropriate referral made and documented

Evidence of rationale for decision around further reviews and plan of care

Factual account only, no personal opinions

Key	
✓	YES
✓	Missing on 1 occasion
✓	NO or missing on ≥ 2 occasions
	N/A
	Not Completed

Appendix 33: Example of electronic case note: *Green Sample*

CHI 11111111

Personal details withheld.

ELECTRONIC RECORD

Risk Assessment	
Date and Time Risk Assessment Completed:	14 Dec 16 at 14:51
Period Completed:	Booking
All risk factors:	- Previous Caesarean Section
Medical Risk Factors:	None
Mental Health Risk Factors:	None
Gynaecological Risk Factors:	None
Obstetric Risk Factors:	Previous Caesarean Section
Previous Baby(ies) Risk Factors:	None
Family History Risk Factors:	None
Sensitive Risk Factors:	None
Current Pregnancy Risk Factors:	None
Anaesthetic Risk Factors:	None
Social Risk Factors:	None
Risk:	High
Antenatal Care Type:	Shared (Obstetrician + Midwife)
Referred To:	USS
Additional Notes:	Red pathway as per KCND due to X2 previous LUSCS. Will be referred to Dr ALLEN for review once booked 15/12/2016

Care Plan Update

Maternal Information	
Fundus Palpable:	Yes
Height of Fundus:	24 cm
Fetal Movements Felt:	Yes
Fetal Movements Discussed:	Yes
Fetal Movement Concerns:	No
Liquor Amount on Palpation:	Normal
Additional Concerns:	None
Notes:	Antenatal check within normal limits. some left sided hip pain. Using paracetamol when required. Aware to contact physiotherapist if worsens

Fetus 1	
Presentation:	Cephalic
Lie:	Longitudinal
Engagement:	Not Engaged
Fetal Heart Activity Checked Method:	Doppler
Fetal Heart Rate:	Heart Rate: 142

Observations

		Admin Data
Observations Performed:	29 Dec 16 at 09:30	
Consent Obtained:	Yes	
Location:	Antenatal Clinic	

		Observations
Abdominal Palpation Performed:	Yes	

Number of Fetuses: 1

		Maternal Information
Fundus Palpable:	Yes	
SFH (Symphis Fundal height):	24 cm	
Fetal Movements Felt:	Yes	
Fetal Movements Discussed:	Yes	
Fetal Movement Concerns:	No	
Liquor Amount on Palpation:	NAD	
Additional Concerns:	None	

		Fetus 1
Presentation:	Cephalic	
Lie:	Longitudinal	
Engagement:	Not Engaged	
Fetal Heart Activity Checked Method:	Doppler	

Specialist Review

		Specialist Review
Date and Time Recorded:	29 Dec 16 at 09:47	
Specialist Type;	Obstetric - Clinic	
Conducted By:		
Type of User:	Consultant DR Allen	
Location:	Antenatal Clinic	
History/Background Noted:	Yes	
Review:	Previous CS x 2	
	2012 Emergency LUSCS at 2 cm dilation. Long latent phase. labour - augmented. Baby unwell following birth HIE and had cooling. Normal progress and development. Live male *bs 4oz	
	2013 Emergency LUSCS at 2cms dilation for fetal distress - nuchal cord. IOL at 41 weeks with balloon catheter- had normal progress of labour. Live male 8lbs 3oz. Small stature 5 ft.	
	Really keen for VBAC. Aware risks 1/200 dehiscence, 1/2500 rupture with serious sequelae for baby and risk to mum.	
	Write to previous unit for further info. If no absolute contraindication would support VBAC. For serial growth in view of neonatal outcome first pregnancy.	
	See at 37 weeks after 2nd scan to discuss further.	

Management Plan

Completed:	Management Plan 29 Dec 16 at 09:54
Recommended Management Plan:	Ethnic Origin Complete family origin questionnaire at booking for both parents. VBAC - Discuss the risks and benefits unique to their need in the antenatal period from an obstetrician or consultant midwife - Document in her notes using proforma on topics discussed. - Discuss risks and benefits of vaginal delivery for mum and baby - Discuss risks and benefits of c section for mum and baby - Discuss risks associated with future pregnancies - increased risk of stillbirth after primary c section. - Women who present with a fear of birth issue should be referred to consultant midwife - Women who wish the opportunity to birth their baby in a midwife led environment, but does not fit criteria should have appropriate documented evidence of a discussion having taken place outlining any risks and Refer to management of labour guideline at; http://firstport2/staff-support/maternity/Documents/Clinical%20Guidelines/Induction%20of%20Labour%20%20ALL%20Guidelines%20June%202016v2.pdf
Actual Management Plan:	Await information from previous unit If no contraindications support VBAC Serial growth scans 32, 36, 38, 40 weeks. Cons review at 37 weeks. 31/01/17 [REDACTED] to attend consultant clinic on 14/02/17 to discuss IOL at term, care and level of monitoring during labour.
Management Plan Reviewed:	Yes
Do you want to change "actual management plan?":	No
Management:	Continue with Consultant Led Care

Referral

Time Ended:	14 Feb 17 at 11:28	On Leaving
New Pregnancy Problems:	None	
Booking Bloods Results	No	
Reviewed:		
Management Plan Reviewed:	Yes	
Additional Notes on Leaving:	I will discuss possibility of wireless monitoring and unit visit [REDACTED]	

Personal details withheld.

Antenatal Assessment

Personal details withheld.

Admin Data 14 Feb 17 at	
Time Started:	11:22
Reason for Assessment:	Antenatal Follow-up
User carrying out antenatal assessment:	[REDACTED]
Location:	Antenatal Clinic
Consent for Procedures:	Yes

Time Ended:	14 Feb 17 at 11:39	On Leaving
New Pregnancy Problems:	None	

Observations

Admin Data	
Observations Performed:	14 Feb 17 at 11:22
Consent Obtained:	Yes

Observations	
Type of Observations:	Antenatal Follow Up
General Condition:	Looks Well
Urinalysis Carried Out:	Yes
Urinalysis Outcome:	NAD
Height:	1.52 metre 5 Foot 0 Inch(es)
Booking BMI:	28.12
Blood Pressure: Systolic:	120 Diastolic 65 mmHg Arm
MAP:	83 mmHg
Oedema Present:	No
Additional Observations	Referral sent to USS dept for growth scans at 32 and 37wks.
Notes:	Long discussion today with Dr Allen - continued care confirmed Hb 11.8, Platelets 307 and MCV 95.2. A+, no antibodies. Clo thrush, LVS obtained today

Abdominal Palpation

General Information	
Date and Time:	14 Feb 17 at 11:35
Copied to Observation Note:	Yes
Consent Obtained:	Yes
Location:	Antenatal Clinic
Number of Fetuses:	1

Maternal Information	
Fundus Palpable:	Yes
Fetal Movements Felt:	Yes
Fetal Movements Discussed:	Yes
Fetal Movement Concerns:	No
Liquor Amount on Palpation:	NAD
Notes:	FMF/FHH 156 bpm. Fundus = 36cms

Observations

Admin Data	
Observations Performed:	14 Feb 17 at 11:35
Consent Obtained:	
Location:	Antenatal Clinic

Observations	
Abdominal Palpation Performed:	Yes

[Number of Fetuses: 1

Microbiological Tests and Results

Taken	
Date:	14 Feb 17 at 11:36
Location:	Antenatal Clinic
Offered and explained:	LVS Swab (complaining of thrush)
Test(s) Performed:	LVS Swab

END of Electronic Case Note GREEN Sample

Appendix 28: Example of Electronic Case Note *Red Sample*

CHI 33333333

ELECTRONIC RECORD

SBAR - Handover	
Date and Time of Handover:	20 Apr 17 at 08:44
Clinician Currently Responsible for Care: consultant Dr Allen	

Situation	
Situation:	Date/Time of Admission 20 Apr 17 at 00:05
	Reason for Admission: early labour

Background	
Background History Noted:	Yes
Additional Information:	Previous LUSCs x2 wishes VBAC Wishes pool delivery. Group B positive Was booked in for IOL today for Cooks balloon

Assessment Latest Obs Recorded	
Assessment:	20 Apr 17 at 08:05
	BP: 96/54 Temp: 36.6 VE : 0430hrs: Cx 1-2cms dilated 1-2cms long vertex-2 . Membranes intact
Additional Information:	contracting 2:10 moderate Diamorphine 10mgs ranitidine 150mgs 0440 hrs 0830 venflon sited

Recommendation	
Request Review:	No
Frequency of Observations:	4 hourly
Additional Actions:	For review by medical staff for plan. IV antibiotics administered

Clinical Note or Review

Clinical Note	
Date and Time:	20 Apr 17 at 09:17
Completed By:	[REDACTED]
Type of User:	Midwife
<p>[REDACTED] remains very sleepy with diamorphine and extremely nauseas. Contractions have become less frequent and shorter lasting around 2 in 10 minutes mild/moderate. Fetal movement felt. I feel that [REDACTED] is not coping well when having contractions. I told her that she would need to have a sleep just now as she was just in very early labour.</p>	

Personal details withheld.

Management Plan

Personal details withheld.

Clinical Note	
Date and Time:	21 Apr 17 at 10:16
Completed By:	[REDACTED]
Type of User:	Midwife
Notes and Care Plan:	Ante natal check performed with consent Looks well, experiencing some irregular but very uncomfortable contractions and is mobilizing around the room. On palpation of uterine activity contracting 1-2:10mins mild. O/P Fundus appropriate for dates Longitudinal lie Cephalic presentation 3/5ths palpable FHH 130bpm clear and regular over 1 min with doptone CTG commenced with consent, plenty fetal movement felt. Observations all within normal limits, see MEOWS chart. PLAN: For review on ward round by consultant

Observations

Admin Data	
Observations Performed :	21 Apr 17 at 10:26
Consent Obtained:	Yes

Antenatal Inpatient Assessment

Labour Progression	
Indication discussed and consent gained:	Yes
Vulva and Vagina:	NAD
Vaginal Condition:	Normal
Expected Dilatation:	1cm every 2 hours
Dilatation of Cervix:	3.0 cms dilated
Cervical Length:	Effaced
Position of Cervix:	Anterior
Station of PP above or below the Ischial Spines:	-3
Descent (fifths palpable):	4/5
Presenting Part:	Vertex
Position of PP:	other: unknown
Moulding:	Absent
Caput:	Absent
Membranes:	Intact
Fetus 1- Heart Rate Post-VE:	156 BPM method CTG - transducer

•

Drugs and Fluids

Drugs - Name: Dihydrocodeine, Other: Paracetamol
Drugs - Dose: 60mgs/1grm

Urine Output

Fluid Balance: Voiding spontaneously

Additional Notes

Dr's Review Required: No
Notes: for transfer to Labour Ward

Clinical Note or Review

Clinical Note

Date and Time: 21 Apr 17 at 18:15
Completed By: [REDACTED]
Type of User: Midwife
Notes and Care Plan: 16.15hrs In to check on [REDACTED] as she has requested analgesia
On all fours on the floor, sore
Contracting 1-2:10mins irregularly, but good moderate when they come

VE carried out-see notes
For transfer to LW now

Labour Progression

Expected Dilatation: 1cm every 2 hours
Membranes: ARM performed
Date/Time Membranes Ruptured: 21 Apr 17_ at 18:15
ARM: Induction
Current Liquor State: Clear

Urine Output

Fluid Balance: not measured

Additional Notes

Dr's Review Required: No
Notes: Contraction 3/10 Regular
CTG reassuring at present
Will observe -

Personal details withheld.

Labour Assessment

General Details	
Entry:	21 Apr 17 at 20:45
Type of Assessment (Clevermed Use Only):	
Completed By:	[REDACTED]
Type of User:	Midwife
All taken with consent:	Yes
Consent Gained:	Yes
Number of Babies on Scan:	Singleton
Mother Coping?	Yes
Posture:	Pool
Pool Temperature:	36.5 degree Celsius

Heart Rate	
Maternal Heart Rate:	84 BPM
Fetal Heart Monitored?:	Yes
Continuous or Intermittent?:	Continuous
Fetus 1 - Heart Rate:	120 BPM - Method CTG-transducer

Urine Output	
Fluid Balance:	250 mls of urine voided

Additional Notes	
Dr's Review Required:	No
Notes:	Contraction 3/10 Regular CTG reassuring at present Will observe

Personal details withheld.

Labour Assessment

General Details	
Entry:	21 Apr 17 at 21:15
Type of Assessment (Clevermed Use Only):	
Completed By:	
Type of User:	Midwife
All taken with consent:	Yes
Consent Gained:	Yes
Number of Babies on Scan:	Singleton
Mother Coping?:	Yes
Coping - Notes:	Distressed at height of contraction but overall coping well in pool.
Posture:	Pool
Pool Temperature:	37.0 degrees centigrade

Heart Rate	
Maternal Heart Rate:	84 BPM
Fetal Heart Monitored?:	Yes
continuous or Intermittent?:	Continuous
Fetus 1 - Heart Rate:	130bpm

Contractions	
Number of Contractions:	3
strength of Contractions:	Strong
Regularity of Contractions:	Regular
Duration of Contractions:	Greater than 50seconds

Clinical Note or Review

Clinical Note	
Date and Time:	21 Apr 17 at 21:31
Completed By:	
Type of User:	becoming unnecessarily distressed with contractions as felt mainly as felt mainly as backache. Support and encouragement given. Continues to be some loss of contact on CTG especially due to moving around a lot while contracting.

END of Electronic Case Note RED Sample

Personal details withheld.

Appendix 34: Quantitative Results from Cycle Two

	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4																
Evidence that the woman is involved in her care planning	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Changes to plan of care clearly documented including rationale and action plan	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Evidence of consent noted throughout all documentation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Evidence of appropriate risk assessment	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Evidence of referral and appropriate involvement of the multidisciplinary team	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
All records completed appropriately ("see record checklist")	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Only NHS Board approved abbreviations used	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
CHI numbers on drug Kardex's: all records including electronic versions	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Timely (as per NMC guidelines) and appropriate referral made and documented	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Evidence of rationale for decision around further reviews and plan of care	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Factual account only, no personal opinions	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
	11	11	11	11	11	11	5	4	11	10	8	3	11	10	9	9	10	10	6	6	10	10	7	7	9	9	4	8	10	10	7	8	10	8	2	8	11	10	8	8	11	9	9	9	11	9	10	7	11	9	8	3	11	9	4	2	11	10	5	6
	100.00				70.45				72.73				88.64				72.73				77.27				68.18				79.55				63.64				84.09				86.36				84.09				70.45				59.09				72.73			
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4				
	Expected				Participant																																																							
	Results				1				2				3				4				5				6				7				8				9				10				11				12				13				14			

Appendix 35: Interview schedule and amended prompt questions for focus group 2 and 3 (used in cycle 3 and cycle 4)

The sequence of questions for the focus group interviews was based on a schedule by Tod (2015).

Introduction

- The focus group took part in the participants clinical area of work.
- Ensured that participants were comfortable, and hospitality provided.
- The participants were welcomed by myself and introduced to the notetaker (they already knew me).
- The purpose of the focus group was explained to them.
- Written consent to take part in study was obtained.
- Verbal permission for digital audio recording was obtained.
- Purpose of focus group explained to group i.e., to elicit their views in the structure and content of the DOC Tool and any uses they think it may have in clinical practice.

Warm up

- A broad question was asked about how they found using the DOC Tool. A paper copy of the DOC Learning Tool was provided as a visual aid.
- Any general thoughts / observations about using the DOC Tool?

Main focus group questions (semi -structured)

- Any uses for using the DOC Tool?
- What do you think about the red, amber, green criteria used within the Tool?
- Any specific issues or concerns you had about using the Tool?
- Any improvements to the Tool?
- When participants were hesitant prompts were used such as that is an interesting point can you explain it further, can you please explain that more etc.

Close of focus group

- Asked if participants had any final remarks.
- Participants were reminded of the confidentiality of the discussion within the group.
- Participants were informed that one member would be sent transcript to check for accuracy.
- Participants reminded if they have any questions then they could contact myself or my supervisor (details available on participant information sheet).
- Participants thanked and focus group ended.

Appendix 36: Amended DOC Learning Tool for Cycle 3

The **DOC** Tool is a peer review tool to critically examine all forms of record keeping to assess if the practitioner has:

- Documented care accurately
- Ongoing risk assessed (patient safety)
- Communicated patient care effectively with all disciplines

Instructions: Please tick only one box for each Documentation Criteria

Documentation Number (please circle the set of notes you reviewed): SWHMR 1 / SWHMR 2 / SWHMR 3/ SWHMR 4

The NMC Standards	Documentation Criteria	N/A	YES	Missing on 1 occasion	NO or missing on ≥ 2 occasions
PRIORITISING PEOPLE	Evidence that the woman is involved in her care planning				
	Changes to plan of care clearly documented including rationale and action/ management plan				
	Evidence of consent noted throughout all documentation				
PRACTICE EFFECTIVELY	Evidence of appropriate risk assessment field completed				
	Evidence of referral and appropriate involvement of the multidisciplinary team				
	Only NHS Board approved abbreviations used				
	PLEASE IGNORE THIS QUESTION Correct CHI numbers / addressograph label on any paper documentation				
PRESERVE SAFETY	Appropriate and timely (as per NMC guidelines) recognition and escalation of concerns				
	Evidence of rationale for decision around further reviews and plan of care				
PROMOTES PROFESSIONALISM AND TRUST	Factual account only, no personal opinions				
Total Score (for use of researcher only)					

Comments on using the DOC tool (please leave any comments you wish about using the tool)

Appendix 37: Quantitative results from Cycle Three

	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4												
Evidence that the woman is involved in her care planning	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓												
Changes to plan of care clearly documented including rationale and action plan/management plan	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Evidence of consent noted throughout all documentation	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Evidence of appropriate risk assessment	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Evidence of referral and appropriate involvement of the multidisciplinary team	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Only NHS Board approved abbreviations used	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
CHI numbers on drug Kardex's: all records including electronic versions																																																												
Appropriate and Timely (as per NMC guidelines) and appropriate referral made and documented	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Evidence of rationale for decision around further reviews and plan of care	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
Factual account only, no personal opinions	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓																
	9	9	9	9	8	7	5	8	8	5	6	8	8	8	5	6	9	9	9	8	8	9	4	6	9	9	6	6	9	8	6	6	8	8	8	9	9	9	9	9	5	4	5	5	9	5	4	5	9	9	9	9	5	7	4	3	9	9	8	5
	100.00				77.78				75.00				75.00				97.22				75.00				83.33				80.56				91.67				100.00				52.78				63.89				100.00				52.78				86.11			
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4	S1	S2	S3	S4				
	Expected Results				Participant																																																							
					1				2				3				4				5				6				7				8				9				10				11				12				13				14			

Appendix 38: Amended DOC Learning Tool for Cycle Four

The **DOC** Tool is a peer review tool to critically examine all forms of record keeping to assess if the practitioner has:

- Documented care accurately
- Ongoing risk assessed (patient safety)
- Communicated patient care effectively with all disciplines

Instructions: Please tick only one box for each Documentation Criteria

Documentation Number (please circle the set of notes you reviewed): ELECTRONIC RECORD 1 / ELECTRONIC RECORD 2 / ELECTRONIC RECORD 3 / ELECTRONIC RECORD 4

The NMC Standards	Documentation Criteria	N/A	YES	Missing on 1 occasion	NO or missing on ≥ 2 occasions
PRIORITISING PEOPLE	Evidence that the woman is involved in her care planning				
	Management Plan clearly documented				
	Evidence of consent noted throughout all documentation				
PRACTICE EFFECTIVELY	Evidence of appropriate risk assessment field completed				
	Evidence of referral and appropriate involvement of the multidisciplinary team				
	Only NHS Board approved abbreviations used				
	All observations completed and documented appropriately				
PRESERVE SAFETY	Appropriate and timely (as per NMC guidelines) recognition and escalation of concerns				
	Evidence of rationale for decision around further reviews and plan of care				
PROMOTES PROFESSIONALISM AND TRUST	Factual account only, no personal opinions				
Total Score (for use of researcher only)					

